

THE PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

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The Journal

The Pastoral Counsellors (Journal of Nigerian Association of Pastoral Counsellors) is a peer-reviewed academic journal that advances research, theory and practice of pastoral care and counselling psychology. Essentially, it seeks to relate psychological science research with the work of ministry. It is a forum for the publication of original papers, irrespective of faith orientation. The thrust of this journal is the care for and interrogation of human beings as persons, in families, in small groups, and in community, to help them make the most of their lives. Theologians, spiritualists, researchers and academics are also encouraged to present various genres of writing, including book reviews and film reviews, committed to helping us gain a better understanding of humanity, to ensure more holistic and prosperous lives. The interface between the spiritual and psychotherapy remains a major issue in pastoral counselling. Religious and spiritual leaders, chaplains, social workers, counsellors, clinical psychologists, and psychiatrists are encouraged to present their peculiar perspectives here. The Journal expects contributors to examine and discuss pastoral care and counselling, pastoral theology, psychology of religion, and the multidimensional interface between psychology and spirituality. All theoretical perspectives are welcome from different schools of thought, including, but not limited to, social psychology, pastoral psychology, humanistic psychology, transpersonal psychology, and cultural psychology. Insights from existential perspectives, gender studies, phenomenology, sociology, anthropology, and Cultural studies are welcome. This journal is published twice every year (April and December, this volume is published in May).

This third edition is mainly the compilation of the published work of eminent scholars, academics and theologians who were keynote speakers, lead paper presenters and presenters at the third National Conference of Nigerian Association of Pastoral Counsellors, held at Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria in October 2023.

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Contents

Divine Mandate in Genesis 1:27 and LGBTQPLUS: Roles of Pastoral Counsellors <i>Isaiah O. ABOLARIN</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11230810	1-9
A Purview of Preaching and Teaching of Jesus Christ on Prayer, Forgiveness and Violence <i>Emmanuel O. MALOMO & Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11230606	10-17
Relevance of Marital Counseling in Some Selected Churches in the Context of 1 Corinthians 7:1-5 <i>The Very Rev'd Emmanuel ADETUNJI (Ph.D) & The Very Revd Adedotun Oluwasegu KILA</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11235877	18-28
Pastoral Response to Rising Mental Health Challenges in Nigeria in the Context of Pauline Mind Management Therapy in Philippians 4:4-9 <i>Oladele Olusola KOLADE, PhD & Ven. Ayodele ATOWOJU, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11237387	29-39
Ethical Issues in Pastoral Counselling of Widows: A Critical Review <i>Oluwakemi Bolatito BABARINDE, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11244634	40-46
Social Support Systems as a Correlate of Mental Health Disorders among Young Adults in Nasarawa State, Nigeria <i>Sholape Magaret OYEWALE</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11264270	47-56
Pastoral Counselling and Trauma-Responsive Healing for Managing Victims of Terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria <i>Inibong Isaac UBONG</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11284349	57-66
Roles of Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of a Marriage Partner and Its Impacts on Family Sustainability <i>James Olusegun KOLAWOLE & Atinuke Oludolapo KOLAWOLE</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11285816	67-76
Pastoral Counselling and Educational Development: Tools for Improving National Security in the 21st Century <i>K. Olubukola AJIBADE</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11297859	77-83
Impact of Pastoral Counselling in Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C) Oke-Anu in Ilorin Metropolis <i>Michael Oladele OLORUNNIMBE, PhD, Tosin Success ABOLAJI, & Elijah Olamidipupo AJIDE</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11299296	84-92
Child Upbringing Parental Styles and Personal Values of Adolescents in Pentecostal Churches in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria <i>Adeola Idowu OKE & Victoria Folake IYANDA, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11301501	93-106

Jethro's Counsels in Exodus 18:17-23: Lessons for Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis <i>Prof. Afolorunso Olalekan DAIRO & Tosin Success ABOLAJI</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11302341	107-115
Strategies for Promoting Marital Cohesion and National Security in Nigeria <i>Elizabeth Oluwaseyi OGUNDIPE & Atilola Dorcas ADERIBIGBE</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11305435	116-122
Religion, Culture, and Insecurity in Nigeria: Roles of State and Non-State Actors <i>Sulaiman Timilehin AYANKOJO</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11305699	123-135
A Pastoral Counselling Approach to the Challenges of Widowhood in Traditional Igbo Land <i>Samuel C. NWANKWO, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11320884	136-142
Intercultural Communication and Church Leadership Administration in Lagos Pluralistic Society, Lagos State, Nigeria <i>Regina Iyabode OBASA, PhD, Eyitayo Adewale ADELAKUN, PhD & Ayodele Adeyinka ATOWOJU, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11321325	143-152
Pastoral Counselling and Domestic Violence in Nigeria: The Way Forward <i>Olusegun Augustus HARMONA, PhD & Sarah Kehinde HENMAUGO</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11348726	153-160
An Appraisal of Intercultural Competence as a Predictor of Effective Pastoral Counselling <i>Ezekiel Olukayode OYINLADE & Oluwaseun O. AFOLABI, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11355904	161-168
The Book of Ruth on Widow's Challenges, and Pastoral Counselling for Effective Widow Empowerment among Nigerian Christians <i>Olawale O. PETER, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11365926	169-182
Pastoral Counselling: Panacea for the Divorce in the 21st Century Nigeria <i>Adebayo Oluwasegun BOLARINWA & Jacob Kehinde AYANTAYO, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11370938	183-190
Pastoral Counselling and Family Stability <i>Actor Emmanuel OYEWOLE, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11370783	191-196
Inculcating the Value of Integrity in Young Persons in Ibadan Local Government Areas, Oyo State, Nigeria <i>Linda Atuegbelo OGUNSHOLA</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11371596	197-205
Pastoral Counselling and National Development <i>Julius Olajide ADEMOLA, PhD</i> https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11371867	206-212

- Redemptive Excommunication in Matthew 18:15-20 and Its Implications for Pastoral Counselling in the Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria
Dr. Bukola OLUWAGBEMIGA & Prof. Afolorunso DAIRO 213-221
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11381558>
- Pastoral Counseling and Its Impacts on Selected Rehabilitation Centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State Nigeria
Rotimi Alaba OTI, PhD 222-227
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384864>
- Mentoring in Leadership: Appraising Samuel-Saul's Relationship
Olawale O. PETER, PhD 228-241
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11385370>
- Impacts and Benefits of Pastoral Counselling on Human Wellness in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria
Ismail Alabi MUIBUDEEN, Olawoyin Keji ENIOLA, & Seun W. AJAGBE 242-250
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11386471>
- Paul's Counsel in 1 Corinthians 7:1 & 8, Preferment of Celibacy: Its Authenticity and Effects among the Catholic Priests
Joseph Dayo MAKANJUOLA, PhD 251-261
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11391698>
- The Scope and Dynamics of Pastoral Counselling
Donald A. ODELEYE, PhD 262-269
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11394179>

Divine Mandate in Genesis 1:27 and LGBTQPLUS: Roles of Pastoral Counsellors

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Abstract

The world is going through rapid and drastic changes that question almost everything that has to do with security, morality, religion, education, economics, and the daily living of people everywhere. The changes are also questioning the origin of the world, the existence of God, and his standard for human existence. One of the changes that are spreading through the globe with human justification and, in some places, legal approval is LGBTQPLUS. Different methods are being employed to give orientation on this new way of life and to influence people, especially children and youth to imbibe and practice it. And this practice questions the injunction found in Genesis 1:27. Pastoral counsellors are individuals who are trained and equipped to guide people in living right according to the dictates of God. What are the roles of pastoral counsellors in this global phenomenon? The study is anchored on James Marcia's status theory. Adopting the phenomenology design of qualitative research, the study employed interviews using focus groups to collect data from 16 pastors with different pastoral experiences. The collected data were analysed thematically. The findings indicated that LGBTQPLUS is a way of attacking the divine mandate in Gen. 1:27 that God created humans male and female and in essence establishing atheistic philosophy. The study concluded with the recommendations that pastoral counsellors should engage people in understanding the phenomenon and guide them in living according to God's injunction.

Keywords: God's injunction, Human Existence, LGBTQPLUS, Morality and Religion, Pastoral Counsellors

Introduction

The world is going through a period when sexuality has become anything that anyone may think it is. Each person has the right to determine their sexuality differently from what is given from the creation of the world according to Genesis 1:27 which says, "So God created mankind in his own image, in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them" (NIV). This Bible passage is explicit that it is difficult for it to be misunderstood. With the passing of time and the entrance of sin, there came a muddling of sexuality from being male and female as created by God. This is indicated by God instructing the Israelites saying "Do not have sexual relations with a man as one does with a woman; that is detestable" (Leviticus 18:22, NIV). There is a further deterioration in the understanding and practices of sexuality among humans in this current dispensation beyond the command God gave in Leviticus. The known sexuality in the world now is LGBTQPLUS which is an acronym for Lesbian, Gay, bisexual, transgender, intersex, queer/questioning, asexual, and many other terms (such as non-binary and pansexual). Many have used the Bible to justify the new sexuality or sexual orientation. Markham (2023), justified that the Bible is in support of the new sexual orientation because it was unlikely that the biblical authors had any notion of sexual orientation in their time. A whole study has been carried out in Nigeria on sexual orientation which advocated

for the acceptance of LGBTQPLUS (Alimi, Boynton, Struharova & Wood, 2017). The study indicated that people of age groups 18–24 (36%) and 25–34 (51%) hold to and practice this new sexual orientation. The study is based on the personality identity theory by James Marcia.

The study reviewed relevant literature to bring about the understanding of some concepts. One of the important issues in the study is personality identity. The concept of sexuality identity is within the general understanding of personality identity. Identity according to Oyserman, Elmore, and Smith (2012), can be traits and characteristics, social relations, gender roles, and social group memberships that define who someone is. This can be focused on the past, present or future. Sometimes, what people have identified can change with time based on more understanding, exposure, or other factors. Personality identity, therefore, is what an individual perceives to be the characteristics, social relations or self-understanding possessed by the person. It is the answer a person gives to the question “who are you?” (Vignoles, 2017, p. 1). Sometimes, people can wish they are something different from what/who they are, and when a situation becomes favourable, the desired identity may be achieved. Identity is a personal orientation that provides meaning-making lens and focuses someone’s attention on some features of the immediate context. It is a personal awareness of one’s existence in the immediate context. Therefore, personality identity is what a person understands him/herself to be in the immediate context of existence.

James Marcia in his identity theory, presented “four stage progression through which individuals may achieve a strong sense of identity” (Kim, 2010, p. 107). Although he did not ascribe specific age group to each stage of identity but it is clear when someone may decide to switch identity. The identity stages according to James are adapted and summarized in the following table.

Table One: Identity Statuses (adapted from Kim, 2010)

Identity Status	Description	Crisis Level	Commitments to Ideal
Diffusion	Avoidance of responsibility; impulsive; low self-esteem; avoids commitments to parents, school, and work	Low because of avoidance of responsibility	Weak; subject to impulse, current situation, and positive/negative feedback
Foreclosure	Adopts the values and goals of others such as parents or significant other; very assured due to affiliation with others; authoritarian and sense of superiority over others	Low due to attaching identity to that of others, especially parents or guardians	Strong; having adopted and affirmed the commitments already made by their parents
Moratorium	Begins to have thoughts of uncertainty; rejection or weakening of parental commitments; begins to exhibit short-term commitments to relationships, school, task	Moderate; begin to ask identity-related questions to self	Weak; the previous answers from parents no longer respond to all of their life questions

Achievement	Make their commitments on their terms; determines their values, establishes commitments and relationships, and assumes responsibility for decision making	High due to complete engagement with identity crisis; has resolved it by assuming responsibility for making choices (with multiple alternatives)	Strong; committed individual choice	has by
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The diffusion stage indicates a critical stage that serves as the foundation for whatever identity someone will adopt in later years despite the avoidance of responsibility and other characteristics. It is on this stage that foreclosure is built upon when parental and significant others' values and goals are adopted. This stage is important because, even in the stage of moratorium when a person looks inward to determine identity, whatever has been imbibed during the first two stages can determine how a person will navigate through moratorium stage. Moratorium stage marks the period when things may go right or wrong afterward when the person reaches achievement stage. At the achievement stage, a person is ready to fight for whatever is already determined or established as a personal identity, especially in sexual identity which is the focus of this study.

Sexual-identity

Sexual orientation according to Hall (2019) is a multidimensional phenomenon that involves someone's sexual attraction, sexual behaviour, and sexual orientation identity. It is how a person is positioned in the three dimensions of sexuality — sexual attraction, sexual behaviour, and sexual orientation identity. These patterns according to him may be consistent or fluctuate over time. Hall (2019), acknowledged that the predominant sexual orientation and behaviour is heterosexual, but that there are other sexual expressions. It is important that Hall stated that sexuality is part of human development, which indicates that just as there can be developmental errors in development in any aspect of human life, there can also be sexual development leading to different orientations. This can be as a result of changes in hormone levels and anatomical characteristics that people personally pursue by personal choice (Teich, 2012). Sexuality orientation is closely associated with gender identity and expression. Identity has to do with the internal sense of being a man, woman, or another gender, while gender expression is how a person demonstrates their gender (clothing, hairstyle, speech, behaviour, and appearance). Despite all these, Hall (2019), recognised the dual sexual identity he called "assigned at birth" which is either male or female. The following table summarises the different sexuality orientations that resulted from factors—hormonal changes, social influence, personal choices, etc.

Intersex	A variety of biophysical manifestation where a person's genome or sexual anatomy do not fit the typical definitions of male or female
Transsexual	A subset of transgender people who pursue medical interventions to change their sex characteristics so that they match their gender identity
Gender Identity	
Cisgender	A person whose birth sex aligns with their gender identity (e.g. male and man, or female and woman)

Transgender	A person whose sex assigned at birth does not align with their gender identity; many gender identities fall under the umbrella term of transgender
Genderqueer	A person who has multiple genders (man and woman, bigender, and pangender), no gender (e. g. agender and gender free), or movement between genders (e. g. genderfluid)
Man	A person whose gender identity is connected to maleness and/or masculinity
Woman	A person whose gender identity is connected to femaleness and/or femininity
Sexual Orientation Identity	
Heterosexual	A person who is sexually attracted to people of the opposite sex or gender
Gay	A person who is sexually attracted to people of the same sex or gender
Lesbian	A female/woman who is sexually attracted to other female/woman
Bisexual	A person who is sexually attracted to males and females
Polysexual	A person who is sexually attracted to people of multiple sexes or genders
Pansexual or Omnisexual	A person who is sexually attracted to people of all sexes or genders
Asexual	A person with a lack or low level of sexual attraction to anyone
Questioning	A person who is uncertain who they are sexually attracted to
Queer	An umbrella term for people of diverse sexualities who are not heterosexual; an alternative identity to the traditional non-heterosexual identities such as gay, lesbian, or bisexual
Androsexual	A person who is sexually attracted to males, men, and/or masculine people
Gynesexual	A person who is sexually attracted to females, women, and/or feminine people
Skoliosexual	A person who is sexually attracted to people who are transgender or genderqueer

In a study conducted by National Survey of Family and Growth from 2011 –2013 according to Hall (2019) involving people of ages 18 to 44, it was indicated that 81% of the women in the study were attracted to only opposite sex, 92.1% of the men were attracted to only opposite sex. This implies that as of 2013, most of the people were still attracted to only opposite sex. When it comes to sexual behaviour, 95.3% of women and 93.5% of men had engaged in only opposite-sex sexual behaviour while 17.4% of women and 6.2% of men had engaged in same-sex sexual behaviour. In addition, 92.3% of women 95.1% of men identified themselves as heterosexual.

Hall (2019), stated that the etymology of heterosexuality is almost never questioned because it is the only way of ensuring survival of human species. Irrespective of many other orientations, the one that has always been is the one that can fulfil the purpose of continuity of life. Some of the factors responsible for different kind of sexuality orientations include, genetic, hormonal, and environmental (Cook, 2020).

LGBTQPLUS

LGBTQPLUS stands for different kinds of sexual orientations being practiced by people. This has been legalized in some nations like the United States, United Kingdom and Canada. The orientation and practices have not been publicly accepted in Africa and specifically in Nigeria. There are different write-ups on LGBTQPLUS and different more publications emerge each day with the name increasing in letters as a result of introduction of new orientation and practices each day. Nigeria is perceived as one of the most anti-gay nations in Africa and in the world. The laws in Nigeria (Same Sex Marriage Prohibition Acts of 2014) criminalised any sexual act different from heterosexual behaviour (Chimakonam & Agada, 2020). Some studies have been done on the issue of LGBTQPLUS in Nigeria (Alimi, 2017; Martins, 2022; Ogueji & Ogueji, 2022). Despite the promotions and quiet efforts to institutionalize it in Nigeria, it is still observed by scholars that the practices of LGBTQ will be difficult to have a widespread in Nigeria due to religion and culture (Martins, 2022).

In order to safeguard young people from this phenomenon, Martins (2022) suggested that the curriculum of primary and secondary schools and tertiary institutions be modified to include multiple sexual orientation in order to create awareness among students and enlighten them on the issues of LGBTQ. He also recommended that religious institutions should constantly preach against LGBTQ among their followers while traditional rulers should preach against it to safeguard Nigerian cultures.

Genesis 1:27

Before God instructed the Israelites not to “have sexual relationship with a man as one does with a woman” (Leviticus 18:22, NIV), there is an indication that such practices have been taking place in some nations, especially in Assyria and Egypt from where God brought them out (Thomas, 2006). In the beginning, at creation the Bible indicates what God created when it comes to sexual orientation as it is written in Genesis 1:27, “So God created mankind in his own image, in the image of God he created them; **male and female** he created them” (NIV). Scholars have explored this passage considering the original language which was Hebrew and they have given an insight into understanding the passage. The Hebrew word for male is *Zakar* (adjective, singular and absolute). This denotes the sex that can fertilize or inseminate female to produce offspring. The Hebrew word for female is *Neqebah* (adjective, feminine, singular and absolute). The word denotes the sex that can bear offspring or produce eggs (Soanes & Stevenson, 2011). These expressions clearly indicate the purpose of the existence of two the types of gender.

The creation of two different sexes by God presupposes his intention for them to “Be fruitful and increase in number, fill the earth and subdue it” (Genesis 1:28, NIV). It was in the creation of humans that the pronouncement “male and female he created them” to differentiate the gift of fertility from God to humans from that of other living creature who may not necessarily be aware of their existence as humans were given. Humans are to meet the requirement of the gift—fertility. It is only in human that the duality of sex finds its expression in the instruction of holy wedlock which is also called conjugal bond (Calvin, 1981; Nichol, 1953). It was God who identified that “It is not good for a man to be alone” (Genesis 2:18, NIV) and he was the one that gave the woman (female) to add to the man (male) to be one (complete). The pair was man (male) and woman (female) and there was no other sex or gender (Calvin, 1981). And

everything created by God from the beginning was “very good” (Genesis 1:31) including the “male and female.”

Nelson (2019), argued that no human is born differently from being either male or female. He made it clear that from scientific point of view there has not been evidence that people are born or could be born differently from being male or female. The current multiple sexual orientation is a complete deviation from biblical evidence in the creation account. Nelson gave some factors that may be considered as responsible for the multiple sexual orientation which are, a disrupted family life in early years, lack of unconditional love on the part of either parent, envy of the same or the opposite sex or a life controlled by various fears and feelings of isolation, incest or molestation, dominant mothers and weak fathers, and demonic oppression. From Nelson’s view, it could be said that dysfunctional home and early un-monitored relationship among children could be responsible for multiple sexual orientations and practices as they are in the 21st century.

Another biblical passage that brings some clarity to multiple orientation is Romans 1:18–32, specifically verses 24, 25–27 which reads,

There God gave them over in the sinful desires of their hearts to sexual impurity for the degrading of their bodies with one another.... their women exchange natural sexual relations for unnatural ones. In the same way the men also abandoned natural relations with women and were inflamed with lust for one another. Men committed shameful acts with other men, and received in themselves the due penalty for their error (NIV).

The above is a result of suppressing the truth about the knowledge of God as stated in verse 18–21. “For although they knew God, they neither glorified him as God nor gave thanks to him, but their thinking became futile and their foolish hearts were darkened” (Romans 1:21, NIV). From the passage it could be said that the multiple sexual orientation which is adding more nomenclature, is a result of suppressing the truth of God. It could be juxtaposed that the truth is accepting God as the Creator because it is his creative act that led to the creation of humans who he made male and female which has been changed from being that to LGBTQPLUS.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims at analysing Gen. 1:27 and relate it to the current sexual orientation (LGBTQPLUS) being promoted globally and to find out the role pastoral counsellors are to play in the phenomenon. The objectives are to:

1. Examine the validity of the divine injunction in Gen. 1:27
2. Understand the goal of the LGBTQPLUS as a sexual orientation
3. Explore the role of pastoral counsellors in the phenomenon

Research Questions

1. Does the injunction of “male and female he created them” still stand?
2. What is the goal of the LGBTQPLUS as a sexual orientation?
3. What are the roles of pastoral counsellors in this situation?

Methodology

This study adopted qualitative approach with interview as the means of data collection. Since the focus of the study was on the roles of pastoral counsellors, the study used a focus group

discussion. The group was made up of 16 pastors with one female pastor among them. The ages of the participants ranged from 26 years to 50 years, with diverse pastoral experiences. The group was met in a classroom where they received lectures. Permission was taken to conduct the interview which was granted by the entire group members. A background to study was given for proper understanding of the subject of study and for full attention and participation from the group members.

The participants responded to the following questions: What is your understanding of Genesis 1:27 in term of sexual orientation? What is your view of emerging sexual orientation (LGBTQPLUS)? How well established in Nigeria is the sexual orientation? What should be the roles of pastoral counsellors in the situation? What could be the factors responsible for such sexual orientations and practices? Could such practices have any effect on people's life? Could such have effect on the knowledge of God? What could be the implication on the knowledge of the Bible? What should be roles of pastoral counsellors in such situation? Responses were recorded using pen and paper. The data were analysed thematically. The collected data were analysed thematically and four themes emerged from the analysis.

Findings

Knowledge of LGBTQPLUS: Most of the respondents indicated their awareness of LGBTQPLUS but not all have deep knowledge of it. To those who have the knowledge, it is a community of people who are fighting for the freedom of multiple sexual orientation and practices. According to one of the respondents, it is a "deviation from biblical perspective of human sexuality." According to the group, LGBTQPLUS is a movement that is infiltrating every human society and endeavour. It has no respect for religion or anything of value. In Nigeria, according to the group, only few bishops are speaking against the orientation and practice because it has established itself even in Christian church. "Some pastors or men of God" according to a member of the group, "have promoted the orientation and engaged in the practices."

Effect of LGBTQPLUS: When it comes to the effect of LGBTQPLUS, the group argued that it is a movement that is bringing confusion about the knowledge of God, and is against God. The group specifically mentioned that it is a movement that works to contradict the creative work of God and especially Genesis 1:27 where it is written that "God created them male and female." In essence according to the group, LGBTQPLUS is to promote the removal of the law of God; "a strategy to further alienate humans from God and establish emptiness in humans." Looking at the movement critically, according to the group, it could be said that the goal is to attack the Bible, presenting it as outdated, irrelevant, and eventually to lead to a religion yet to be seen which will be a religion without God, moral, and holiness.

Factors responsible for the new sexual orientation: The group discussed some possible factors that could bring about such view as LGBTQPLUS. Some of such factors are, parenting negligence, lack of adequate help for teenagers to navigate a period of life when they become aware of their sexuality and orientation. The group also mentioned the desire for sexual relationships without commitment as a factor that can make someone to accept LGBTQPLUS. Given examples of such relationships, someone in the group narrated an experience of a group of men who molested another young man because they did not want to impregnate a lady. Brainwashing was mentioned as a factor that can also make young people enter into this orientation and practices without knowing.

Role of pastoral counsellors: Although, many pastors are not aware or do not understand LGBTQPLUS and how deep it has entered into human's society, according to the group, there are still some things that pastoral counsellors can do to save people from the "pandemic." Educating of members is one of the roles of the pastoral counsellors. Pastors are to understand what the movement is and its objective, and they should educate their members from falling into it. A member of the group suggested that it is important for pastors to be educated before they can educate members and that this is needed because many pastors are not knowledgeable in LGBTQPLUS phenomenon. Pastors, in essence are playing safe when in actuality many members have quietly and innocently imbibed multiple sexual orientations and practices. The group talked about working with children to understand and avoid the orientation and practices, not only in church and homes but also in schools because of "systematic desensitisation" which occurs through school curricula, test books, cartoon and different other programs on television and majorly on the Internet.

Discussion of Findings

The findings indicated that sexuality is part of human development which is according to Hall (2019) can be abused. As part of developmental process, there is a period in life when anatomy of people goes through changes (Teich, 2012), that lead to making choices which could be detrimental to not only sexuality of individual but also to other areas of the person's life if there is no proper guide. This makes the issue of adequate parenting, according to the findings, to be an essential factor to be considered as children grow up, to help them navigate through the critical or diffusion age period (Kim, 2010) in life when choices are made. The idea of educating young people, bring about the importance of the roles of parents and pastors. Proper education at the proper age period can make someone develop appropriate orientation about sexuality and life generally. Proper education is also needed to safeguard people from systematic desensitisation. Since the multiple sexual orientation is considered to be anti-Bible, anti-God, and something that can lead to a religion without God, moral and value, and that LGBTQPLUS is a deviation from God's original creation, pastoral counsellors should teach and preach about it in their congregations and talk about it in the society.

Conclusion

LGBTQPLUS, is a movement or a community of people fighting against laws that prohibit the acceptance of multiple sexual orientation and practices. The movement is real, although, without aggression or noise, it is already entrenched deep in the Nigerian society, not only among young people, but also among adults, pastors, teachers, rich and poor people, etc. It is a movement that leads people away from the knowledge of God and works to eliminate values in the society. The practice of multiple sexual orientation leads people to live a life without commitment to one another. Specifically, it goes contrary to God's original creation of male and female and the purpose (procreation) for it, thereby insinuating creation without God. Pastoral counsellors are to equip themselves to take proper position in making people to understand and maintain the dual sexual orientation—male and female—as created by God.

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A Purview of Preaching and Teaching of Jesus Christ on Prayer, Forgiveness and Violence

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Abstract

The overview of the teaching of Jesus Christ during His earthly ministry is a focus that cannot be trivialized in the practice of Christianity as a whole. This is because, the teaching of Jesus Christ is the bedrock on which principles, doctrines, and practices of the Christian faith are based and as a result, a consideration and reiteration of the major teachings of Jesus Christ is important to emphasize the expectation of Jesus Christ from His disciples and by extension to the contemporary Christians. This paper therefore examines some of the major teachings of Christ as discovered through the content of the Gospel, which contains the earthly preaching and teaching of Jesus Christ and as such, didactics are deduced and to be understood and inculcated by contemporary Christians. It is, therefore, recommended that if these teachings of Jesus Christ on love, forgiveness, and violence are followed religiously, there will likely be a peaceful society devoid of hatred, conflict, and violence. This will likely aid in the achievement of Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations which has to do with peaceful society by 2030.

Keywords: Forgiveness, Goal 16 of the SDGs, Prayer, Preaching of Jesus Christ, Teaching of Jesus Christ, Violence

Introduction

A cursory look in the study of world religions and religious leaders has obviously distinguished Jesus Christ, the lead figure for Christianity as a distinct personality with his mode and content of teachings. His miracles were great; His teachings were even greater. The things Jesus taught are more important than his methods. "He gave man a completely new way of life which is summed up in what has been called the golden rule of the Bible" (Kuo, 2002: 45): "Therefore, whatever you want men to do to you do also to them, for this is the Law and the Prophets" (Matthew 7:12). Therefore, "the golden rule is far above any other way of life" (Kuo, 2002: 45). The essence of the teachings of Jesus is in the Sermon on the Mount found in Matthew 5, 6, and 7. The sermon does not have a connected thought but is made up of sayings on different subjects. It begins with a group of "beatitudes" in which blessing is pronounced upon those who please God. For example, "Blessed are the merciful, for they shall obtain mercy. Blessed is the pure in heart, for they shall see God" (Matthew 5:7, 8).

One will note that Jesus gives His blessing, not to the rich or famous, but to those whose hearts are right and who strive to serve God by serving other people. In fact, He also said in one of His teachings, "Do not lay up for yourselves treasures on earth, where moth and rust destroy and where thieves break in and steal; but lay up for yourselves treasures in heaven..." (Matthew 6:19, 20), the Lord shows that true riches are to be found in spiritual, not material things. Therefore, this paper shall consider some of the teachings of Jesus to see their significance, especially in the peaceful coexistence of people in society.

Jesus, the Good Teacher

It is impossible to read the Gospels without getting a sense of the intensity and passion of Jesus' teachings. He spoke with great authority on spiritual matters, "often leaving his detractors tongue-tied and looking foolish" (Michael, 1996: 335). It means many of His teachings are disturbing and shake one out of comfort and contentment. He spoke of loving God above all other things, caring about all other people as much as we care about ourselves, the coming kingdom of God, and eternal life. Furthermore, Jesus Christ often spoke in parables, using common images of nature and agriculture, to deliver His spiritual messages. Many people, often including His disciples, were left baffled by the parables. But one about Him that is paramount is that He explained His parables to his disciples in private, but many of the explanations have not been recorded in the Gospels. With many similar parables, Jesus Christ spoke the word to them, as much as they could understand. He did not say anything to them without using a parable. But when he was alone with his own disciples, he explained everything (Mark 4:33-34).

The reason people do find it difficult to understand His parables is that, Jesus has also said it in His word that, "The secret of the kingdom of God has been given to you. But to those on the outside everything is said in parables so that, they may be ever seeing but never perceiving, and ever hearing but never understanding; otherwise, they might turn and be forgiven" (Mark 4:10-12). Therefore, with this statement of Jesus, one could draw out that Jesus constructed His parables so that only those who were pure of heart and receptive to His teachings could understand them. On the contrary, "Jesus' enemies and the merely curious were left baffled" (Flowers, 2001: 465). This 'harsh' attitude of Jesus may be the way of making His message available and inviting those who wish to understand and believe while never forcing anyone to know and accept His truths. Marshall (1997: 869) says, "If Jesus had spoken in plain language, the sheer power of His personality and message might have forced many to believe, even against their own will. By speaking in parables, Jesus made it possible to decline the invitation to understanding and commitment found in the parables."

The question one often asks about Jesus' parables is how can you explain to someone an experience they have never had? And how would you explain the beauty of a sunset to someone who had never seen one? The answer to this question is not far-fetched. Coleman (1990: 362) says, "Parables are skillfully painted mental pictures to help one to understand the kingdom of God and other spiritual things one has never experienced." This means that "the parables of Jesus are the appropriate form of communication for bringing to men the message of the kingdom, since their function is to shake them into seeing things in a new way" (Coleman, 1990: 362). These parables are a means of enlightenment and persuasion, intended to bring the hearers to the point of decision. Jesus, as it were, stands where his hearers stand, and uses imagery familiar to them to bring new and unfamiliar insights to them.

Some Selected Teachings of Jesus

In one of the synoptic gospels, Jesus says, "Do not think that I have come to abolish the Law or the Prophets; I have not come to abolish them, but to fulfill them" (Matthew 5:17). In this passage, which is part of the Sermon on the Mount, Jesus said that he didn't intend to abolish the old Jewish religious laws, such as the Ten Commandments and the various regulations on marriage, inheritance, property rights, diet, and similar matters. However, "he often did re-interpret these laws, or add to them, sometimes in very radical ways. As a result of this, it makes some of his teachings very controversial" (Hanna, 2002: 687). Moreover, even today, some of his teachings still seem very radical to many people. Here are some of the best-known examples:

Teaching On Violence

As Jesus Christ said on the mountain, "You have heard that it was said, 'eye for eye, and tooth for tooth.' But I tell you, do not resist an evil person. If someone strikes you on the right cheek, turn to him the other also." (Matthew 5:38-39). Looking at the world today, some Christians try to strictly adhere to this principle of non-resistance. Some of them have been put in prison, or even executed, for refusing to participate in wars. In Matthew 5:44 Jesus says "Love your enemies." Some people interpret this to mean that "you should try to help them rather than harm them" (Hanna, 2002: 687). Others also will say that "any needed punishments should be left to God" (Hanna, 2002: 687). However, there are many modern Christians who consider these ideas to be unrealistic. They believe that it is sometimes necessary to defend oneself or even to launch the initial attack. Many people also believe that evil-doers must be punished for their crimes, or at least locked up to prevent them from doing further harm.

Teaching On Wealth

In Mark 10:25, Jesus says, "It is easier for a camel to go through the eye of a needle than for a rich man to enter the Kingdom of God." Some scholars think that the word "camel" in this statement resulted from an accidental mis-copying of a very similar word which meant rope. Thus, Jesus may have actually said "It is easier for a rope to go through the eye of a needle..." (Hauge, 1995: 223) which is a more natural metaphor. Another tradition traces the "eye of a needle" as referring to the alternative route for a camel to pass through when it arrives late in the night and the big gate of the city has been locked. This is because, the alternate route is narrowly created and the camel must be willing and ready to surrender himself for pushing to enter through the narrow gate made through the fence (Buetel, n.d.). But whether he said camel or rope, his point was that it is very hard for a rich person to go to heaven. In fact, Mark 10:17-22 indicates that the only way a rich person can go to heaven is, in Jesus' words, to "sell everything you have and give to the poor." Some people try to avoid this conclusion by pointing to Mark 10:27, which says, "All things are possible with God". However, "God can make it possible for a rich man to go to heaven" (Buetel, n.d.). Certainly, this is true, but the context of the statement indicates that "God would accomplish this by inspiring the rich man to reform his life and willingly give his money to the poor" (Lucas, 1995: 456).

Jesus Christ also warned against the accumulation of wealth on several other occasions. In Matthew 6:19, He says, "Do not store up for yourselves treasures on earth", and a few verses later, in Matthew 6:24, he says "You cannot serve both God and Money". In Luke 6:24 he says "Woe to you who are rich." Jesus disapproved of wealth accumulation because he thought it was wrong for some people to live in wasteful luxury while others starved. According to the

Book of Acts, his original followers tried to live by these teachings after he left them. They formed a community in Jerusalem, known as the Nazarenes, in which everyone "had everything in common" (Acts 2:44), and any new member had to sell his or her possessions and give the proceeds to a common fund. However, many modern Christians disagree with these ideas. They see nothing wrong with acquiring money and wealth. People who do become wealthy are often admired by others.

Teaching on Compassion and Forgiveness

The teachings quoted above are examples of what is sometimes called the Difficult Teachings of Jesus because most people find them very hard to follow. "Their radical nature has led some people to call Jesus an extreme moralist. Others have called Him a utopian dreamer, a social or political reformer, or even a communist" (Amy, 2002: 115). However, whatever else He was, He was also a person of great compassion. He had very strong feelings for the poor, the downtrodden, the outcasts, and the persecuted, and he was keenly aware of the oppression and injustice that kept them in their place. This is why he condemned greedy people who live in opulence while so many others suffer in poverty. More so, Jesus also had a very strong willingness to forgive. He believed that everyone deserves another chance. A good example of this is his teaching about turning the other cheek: "Not only should you instantly forgive a man who strikes you on one cheek, but you should also turn your other cheek to give him a chance to see his error and realize the need to reform him" (Scolt, 1971: 445). From this point of view, one may draw that Jesus probably didn't mean it literally when he talked about gouging out eyes and cutting off hands. Most likely he was simply using hyperbole to emphasize his point. But the mere fact that he could talk in this way provides another example of just how strong his convictions were. Of course, most people can feel compassion, and most people have some willingness to forgive. Only few, if any, have ever felt these emotions as deeply as Jesus did, or had as strong convictions as he did. That difference may explain why some of his teachings seem so radical to us.

Teaching On Prayer

Prayer is a means of communication with God. Jesus' teaching on prayer was focused on training His disciples how to talk to God. One day Jesus was praying in a certain place. When he finished, one of his disciples said to him, Lord, teach us to pray, just as John taught his disciples. According to John Kant who made this assertion that,

It is therefore fitting to pray to the Father, to call upon him with all our mind, with all our will, not externally with the lips, but inwardly with the mind as it is drawn up from below, sighing, repenting for our unrighteousness, for the life we have been living, confessing our sins, perceiving the empty deceptions we have been living, weeping over how we have found ourselves in the darkness of ignorance, mourning for ourselves and asking the Father to have pity on us; hating ourselves for what we have become. For as Jesus says in Matthew 5:4, 6 "Blessed are they that mourn; for they shall be comforted (Kant, 1962: 114).

Blessed are they which do hunger and thirst after righteousness; for they shall be filled, Then Jesus says in Luke 14:26, "If any man come to me, and hate not his father, and mother, and wife, and children, and brethren, and sisters, yea, and his own life, he cannot be my disciple." In other words, you cannot serve God and mammon. The connection to the father is within, "mind connects with Mind" (Kant, 1962: 114). This is our father; approach him as a little child

would approach his father for help. It's our child-like faith in our Father's ability to make us whole again that opens our understanding of the teachings of Jesus. No man can open the door to understanding, only the father can do this. "Seek; Knock; Ask!" If you understand these teachings and do them. Your sins are forgiven, go and sin no more.

Furthermore, Jesus says; "When you pray, pray in private where no one can see you. Prayer is between you and your father. Do not use vain repetition. Do not ask for earthly things, for your father knows what things you need before you ask. While the soul can justify our thoughts, words, and deeds through rationalization, the Father cannot be deceived" (Matthew 6:5-8; Luke 16:15). Jesus Christ gives us an example of prayer in Matthew 6:9-13: this should be a prayer guide, an example of praying, not to become a "vain repetition" to be recited in public "with bowed heads." Jesus always raised his head, like a little child standing before his father and looking upwards, "Father be merciful to me a sinner." (Luke 18:13). Agahel (1998: 117) says,

Forgive others of their trespasses against you, forgive those who hate you, forgive those who use you, forgive those who steal from you, forgive those who hurt you, and so on. Do not return evil for evil; for if you do, what better are you than they? Whatsoever another does against you, remember Jesus words in Luke 2:34, "Father, forgive them, for they know not what they do.

God the Father is Spirit (Mind), and they that worship him must worship him in Spirit (Mind) and in truth (John 4:24). When you have lifted your mind, from being connected to the Soul below, and connect with the Father above, then shall you begin to experience revelation, the truth that shall eventually set you free from the Soul and this evil world.

The Teaching of Jesus About the Kingdom of God

The Kingdom of God is the place where Jesus is King. It is a spiritual, invisible kingdom that has made its presence felt to a degree in the affairs of this earth, but only to a limited extent. It is not confined to a particular geographical location, nor a particular religious organization. The Kingdom is truly present in a place to the extent Christ is honored as Lord and his will is done there. There are two types of kingdoms taught by Jesus, the kingdom of God and the kingdom of Satan. Firstly, some biblical scholars view the Kingdom of God as an alternative term for 'heaven', but Jesus taught that it could be in our midst on earth, and come to us now through his ministry – for example – the ministry of casting out demons by the Spirit of God (Matthew 12:28). When Jesus spoke of entering the Kingdom he was not merely saying 'going to heaven when you die'. He was talking about entering into the Kingdom life here and now. This includes heaven later on, and whatever plans God may have for us on the new earth, but it is far more than that. The Kingdom of Heaven is not about 'pie in the sky when you die' The second kingdom is the kingdom of Satan which stands as an opposing kingdom to the kingdom of God. Jesus spoke of Satan's kingdom (Matthew 12:26). The Scripture declares that 'the whole world lies under the sway of the evil one' (1 John 5:19). Satan is called 'the god of this age' (2 Corinthians 4:4), 'the prince of the power of the air' and 'the spirit who now works in the sons of disobedience' (Ephesians 2:2). "Satan, operating through a vast hierarchical network of fallen angels, evil spirits or demons as they are variously known, exercises a stupendous influence on the hearts and lives of men, women, boys and girls" (Borrel, 2004: 56). This means that the existence of Satan's kingdom accounts for the hatred, the wars, the stupidity and selfishness of mankind, the existence of false religions and philosophies and the presence of every kind of perversion and deception on the face of the earth. Satanic influence

is very effective because it operates in the background, and is generally not openly displayed. It is almost always covered under another name or philosophy. The kingdom of God is in perpetual conflict with the spiritual kingdom of Satan. These are the two spiritual kingdoms that dominate the affairs of mankind and influence the lives of multitudes. They are totally opposite in nature. There is no third kingdom. The kingdom of God only advances through the destruction of the works and influence of the devil.

Furthermore, in Jesus Christ's earthly ministry, Jesus taught much about the kingdom of God. Many of His parables compared the kingdom of God to such familiar things as leaven or mustard seed. Daniel had prophesied that "God would establish an indestructible kingdom" (Daniel 2:44). What the Jews were looking for was a temporal kingdom, "but the kingdom Christ came to establish was a spiritual one" (Borrel, ^{2004: 56}). He was to reign, not on the throne of David in Jerusalem, but in the hearts of men. Jesus did not teach that He would ever establish an earthly kingdom, but He did teach that His kingdom was the church (Matthew 16:18, 19) and that it soon was to be established.

Jesus Teaching on Love

Love is many things in our culture. For many it can be likened to an electric charge: either the zap of the feeling is there or it is not. For others, love is an arrangement, almost like a contract, sometimes voluntary, other times it is imposed by circumstances. Love for family members is not a given ordinance; instead, events have necessitated it. Marriages often proceed with this kind of arranged love. As long as the contract works and the zap is present, the arrangement is on. Often such love is managed by performance. "Love is to be demonstrated by what is done by an action: If you really cared, you would do this for someone" (Watterd, 1989: 121). This kind of love that Jesus teaches is a description of what love is for the child of God. "The love Jesus calls for is none of the things described above" (Watterd, 1989: 121). Jesus decries the contemporary culture's version of love. What is required to possess true love is an understanding of what it is to be loved by God and how God wishes one to love. At the center of Jesus' sermon "is a unique concept of love" (Tellar, ^{1998: 333}).

In the Old Testament, as Jesus' response pertaining to the direction to love God, Jesus was referencing the first commandment, recorded in Deuteronomy 6:4-5, "Hear, O Israel: The LORD our God is one LORD: And thou shalt love the LORD thy God with all thine heart, and with all thy soul, and with all thy might". These are the words that begin the '*Shema*' which is the primary declaration of faith of every practicing Jewish person. The first part, "Hear O Israel, the Lord our God, the Lord is One", is the most famous statement of all in Judaism and it is said, is the first statement Jewish teachers instruct their students to recite. The second commandment of Jesus is based on Leviticus 19:18 "Love your fellow as yourself"; it reflects the primary striving of every Jewish person; this particular statement is said to encompass all of the Spiritual Law of Judaism.

Furthermore, Jesus does not wait to make his point on the unusual character of such love. Although the righteous will be persecuted and rejected and God will judge the persecutors, Jesus issues a call to love the enemy. In fact, Jesus' call is specific: "Love your enemies, do good to those who hate you, bless those who curse you, and pray for those who mistreat you". Whether in attitude, action, word, or intercession, the enemy is to be loved. Jesus wants more than condemnation of the outside world. Jesus' call to disciples focuses not on our words to others, though John 11:37-54 does issue a stinging challenge regarding our words. Rather, Jesus zeroes in on our actions and attitudes toward others. He offers no platitudes about how

outsiders should be viewed. There is no abstract call to divide one's thought by "hating the sin, but loving the sinner." True as this saying is, Jesus is concerned that we follow through on it and show our love in concrete service for the sinner. Our model is God himself: "God so loved the world that he gave his only begotten Son" (John 3:16, 36). So, Jesus Christ calls for the performance of love in action, thought, and petition.

The significance of Jesus Christ's teaching is characterized by simplicity. That is, he used words the common people could understand and took his illustrations from those things with which they were familiar. Many of his principles were set forth by parables. "A parable is a true-to-life story with a lesson" (Williams, 1997: 321). For instance, in the story of the prodigal son in Luke 15:11-32, one will see that it is a wonderful story that could have happened, Christ did not tell it just to entertain His listeners. But He intended to show that a loving God will receive again His children when they stray. The number of Christ's parables is usually placed between 27 and 50, depending on what is classified as a parable. Of these, a majority deal with human beings while the others are built around animals, plants, or other objects with which the people were familiar. It is the wish of Jesus that men come to Him. But while He will compel no man to accept Him, He invites all. "Come to me, all you who labor and are heavy laden, and I will give you rest. Take my yoke upon you and learn from me, for I am gentle and lowly in heart, and you will find rest for your souls. For My yoke is easy and my burden is light" (Matthew 11:28-30). In other words, the significance of His teaching and what He wants His followers to learn is that they should put their entire minds to Him and seek the kingdom of God first.

Conclusion

An examination of the approach of Jesus Christ to people during His earthly ministry distinguishes Him from other teachers of the law, prophets, priests, and various religious and political leaders. His teachings were based on principles that were not intended to annul the existing law on the ground but were obviously different in approach to the existing mode of practice that is obtainable in the large society of the people. His teachings caused religious leaders to raise eyebrows since they contradicted their wrong interpretations that had been dominantly practiced of which they had selfishly benefitted in the status quo and the intended change and rectification of such anomalies did not settle well with the various leaders of the people and as such, they chose to wage war against Jesus from the beginning of his earthly ministry till the time he was crucified.

The persecutions, criticism, and opposition received by Jesus Christ from the people never made Him succumb or be mute in insisting on the validity of his teachings because, he was purposeful and He aimed at correcting the wrong that has become the norm of the days and also to make man realize that, it is possible to live like God. His teachings brought regard to human understanding of the mind of God and what God expects man to do by ultimately loving God and secondly loving fellow men which is the fulfillment of the entirety of the law. It is, therefore, recommended that if these teachings of Jesus Christ on love, forgiveness, and violence are followed religiously, there will likely be a peaceful society devoid of hatred, conflict, and violence. This will likely aid in the achievement of Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations which has to do with peaceful society by 2030.

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Relevance of Marital Counseling in Some Selected Churches in the Context of 1 Corinthians 7:1-5

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Abstract

Marriage counseling is as old as marriage itself. It is introduced to guide the couples how to have successful marriages and live happily yet the rate of divorce is increasing daily. This work considered the relevance of marriage counseling in some selected Churches in the context of 1 Corinthians 7: 1-7 the findings revealed that sexual incapability in marriage is still visible due to couple's noncompliance to biblical standard of marriage for peaceful homes, other factors are lack of continued love, pressure from the family, low income or economy situation, above all infidelity and marital bully from each side can lead to marital problem. The study adopted the descriptive and exegetical method of the survey type. simple percentage, while responses to the interview were qualitatively analyzed. Finding revealed that marriage crisis was all over the place and that Methodist Church Nigeria Diocese Mainland is not left out. The study concluded that adopting 1 Corinthians 7:1-7 as the basis for some selected Churches will enhance the peaceful co-existence among the couples in the Churches and society at large. The study recommended that Church should take cognizes of Paul' teaching in 1 Corinthians 7:1-7 in marriage for peaceful co-existence.

Keywords: Relevance, Marriage, Counseling, Church, 1 Corinthians 7:1-7

Introduction

The first letter of Paul to the Corinthians chapter seven addresses a number of issues that had come to the attention of Paul through reports from some of the members of the Church and apparently a letter from the Church in which they had asked the apostle certain questions. A cursive glance at the chapter reveals that in their prevailing circumstances, some Christians were concerned about whether or not it was good to have sexual relations with woman (1 Cor 7:1). Others had issues with whether to continue in marriage with an unbeliever (1 Cor 7:10-11) and perhaps, anxiety about the spiritual status with the children of unbelieving partners. There is almost a general consensus among scholars that 1 Corinthians 7 deals with questions and concerns the believers in Corinth had about marriage, sex and related issues. The background of the believers in Corinth lies in a variety of religious and philosophical beliefs and practices is established. This variety certainly influenced their concept of spirituality. No wonder, among the factors accounting for the differences within the Church was the concept of spirituality. Clearly, Paul's response to some of the questions having to do with marriage and related issues including sex. What made these issues matters of concern can be gleaned from Paul's response, which is believed to reflect the concerns of the Corinthians Christians (1 Cor 7:14).

The creator Himself declared that it was not good for the man be alone (Gen 2:18) yet no creature on earth could be found that was suitable partner for him (2:20b). Dogs, cats, parrots, horses, snakes, fish, etc., all these creatures of the animal world have become pets of mankind,

but a pampered pet is not an equal partner. So in the beginning God made a helper corresponding to the man, this new creature was perfectly suited to the man, for the woman was taken from the man, assuring the uniqueness, the ministry and the permanence of their relationship. The approval by God of this first relationship is vivified by the statement that the Lord himself brought the woman to the man, the detail narrative describing, the creation of the woman underscores her significance in God's purpose in creation.

Marriages a mystical and intimate union instituted and ordained by God with purpose of companionship and oneness. It is a sacred and permanent union that only death can dissolve. This is because as through marriage the man and the woman freely and willingly decide to spend the rest of their lives on earth together (Augustine, 1999).

Therefore, the covenant of marriage glues, unites and ties their hearts and live together. In respect of the filial duty, marriage is the merging of two different personalities, that is a man and a woman into an indissoluble union through covenant, as an ordained institution by God, marriage is the deepest corporeal and spiritual unity of a man and a woman.

Marriage is the foundation of human society because it is the first institution that was created by God. The stability of the human society depends on the stability of the marriage institution. An unstable marriage is capable of affecting every strata of life of an individual and his/her society, marriage was established by God before all other human institutions. This shows us that marriage is the foundation of human society. In God's plan, marriage is the basis for a morally and socially stable society. This is part of the reason why God hates adultery (Ex. 20:14), sexual immorality (1 Thes 4:3-6), incest (Lev. 18-6ft), and opined that "Marriage is not easy to define because of the diversities in the system of marriage throughout the world. Different scholars have defined marriage in different ways". Fagbeyibo (2005) stressed that marriage is "A relationship of one or more men, with one or more women, which is recognized by custom or law and which involves certain rights and duties, both in the case of parties entering the union and in the case of the children" One can deduce from the above definition that marriage recognized as such by society, according to its own rules, which could vary from place to place. However, such casual sexual relationships or even stable relationships as in the case of a man and a woman just living together are excluded. Certain obligations and requirements must be met especially as marriage involves the conceiving and bringing up children. And there are different types of marriage, such as customary or traditional marriage, religious marriage, ordinance or court marriage etc.

"Every culture in the world has its own set of customs and rules concerning marriage, sex and family. However, since it was God who created mankind as male and female and since it was God who joined the first man and woman together in marriage, it is very important for us to understand what God has to say about marriage, sex and the family" To Wright, "marriage is the state in which men and women can live together in sexual relationship with the approval of their social group"

The above definitions of marriage illustrate its dual nature as both a public institution and private personal relationship. On the other hand, marriage involves an emotional and sexual relationship between particular human beings. On the other hand, marriage is an institution that transcends the particular individual involved in it and unites two families.

Different people perceive marriage differently. "The customary belief is that marriage is primarily contracted to raise children. In-Laws, neighbours and friends are usually unkind to couples who have no child. The other dimension is the sex of the child. The clamour for male

Child in our society has affected even Christians. Mothers who have given birth to only female children are usually on edge whenever they are pregnant. Will it be a boy or a girl? Childlessness and having only female children contribute significant to the high rate of divorce and polygamy” (Timothy, 2010).

Who gives children, and who is responsible for the sex of the child? Often, it is the woman who is blamed for lack of children and giving birth only to females. Yet children are the heritage of the Lord (Ps 127:3). They cannot be bought in market. God gives them and determines their sex too. Although medically the male sperm that fertilizes the female egg determines the sex of the child. Christian knows that, God is at work, thus the woman is not the determinant of the child gender, is what the man deposited in her, she brings out.

In some subcultures, marriage connects two families in a complicated set of property exchanges involving land, labour and other resources. The extended family and society also share an interest in any children the couple may have. Furthermore, the legal and religious definitions of marriage and the laws that surround it usually represent the symbolic expression of core cultural norms (informal behavioral guidelines) and values. It is on this note that, Ubong E. Eyo, 2021 points out that “marriage is a complex affair with social, emotional and religious (though sometimes with economic and political) undertones with often overlap so firmly that each undertone cannot be separated from each other”.

Among Africans in particular, marriage is not only for the living, it is a union where the living, the dead and the yet unborn meet. Hence, John Mbiti says “It is the point where all members of the community meet; the departed, the living and those yet unborn”. Marriage is therefore, a duty, a requirement from the corporate society and a rhythm of life in which everyone must participate.

The Old Testament Theology of Sexuality

The first two chapters of the Bible deal directly with the question of human sexuality. Not only is human sexuality presented as a basic fact of Creation, but elucidating the nature of sexuality constitutes a central part of the Creation accounts.

A clear understanding of these basic statements is crucial, since here “the pattern is established and adjudged good. From then until the close of the biblical corpus it is the assumed norm.” In Genesis 1:26-28 “the highpoint and goal has been reached toward which all of God’s creativity from verse 1 on was directed.” Discussion among theologians over this passage has largely focused on the meaning of humans being created in the “image of God” and has almost entirely ignored the further affirmation that humankind is created male and female.” The fundamental insights into the theology of human sexuality from Genesis 1:1-24 come under seven subheadings.

- i. *Creation Order*: In the clause concerning the creation of humans as male and female (Genesis 1:27), sexual differentiation is presented as a creation by God, and not part of the divine order. Throughout the mythology of the ancient Near East, the sexual activities of the gods form a dominant motif. In the fertility cults, creation was often celebrated resulting from the union of male and female deities. In contrast, Genesis 1: with its emphasis upon the transcendent God (Elohim) and a cosmic view of creation, posits a radical separation of sexuality and divinity. God stands “absolutely beyond the polarity of sex.” The sexual distinctions are presented as created by God, not part of the divine order.

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- ii. *A duality from the beginning:* The sexual distinction between male and female is fundamental to what it means to be human. To be human is to live as a sexual person. The sexual distinction is presented in Genesis 1 as a basic component in the original creation of humankind.
 - iii. *Equality of the sexes:* A third insight into the theology of human sexuality stems from the equal pairing of male and female in parallel with Adam in Genesis 1:27. There is no hint of superiority or inferiority between male and female. Both are “equally immediate to the Creator and His act.” Both are given the same dominion over the earth and other living creatures (verses 26 and 28). Both are to share alike in the blessing and responsibility of procreation (verse 28). Both participate equally in the image of God.
 - iv. *Wholeness:* A fourth theological insight will serve to bridge our discussion from “male and female” to the image of God (imago Dei). In Genesis 1:27 the generic term for humankind (Adam) includes both male and female. The holistic picture of humankind is only complete when male and female are viewed together. Such a description points the individuality and complementarity of the sexes.
 - v. *Relationship:* The juxtaposition of male and female in Genesis 1:26 intimates what will become explicit in Genesis 2: the full meaning of human existence not in male or female in isolation, but in their mutual communion.
 - vi. *Procreation:* From Genesis 1:28, one of the primary purposes of sexuality is procreation, as indicated in the words, “Be fruitful and multiply”. Procreation is shown to be part of the divine design. This divine blessing or command is to be taken seriously and acted upon freely and responsibly in the power that attends God’s blessing. Nevertheless, sexuality cannot be wholly subordinated to the intent to propagate children. Sexual differentiation has meaning apart from the procreative purpose. The procreative blessing is also pronounced upon the birds and fish (verse 22), but only humans are made in the image of God. Genesis 1: emphasizes that sexual distinction in humankind is created by God, particularly for fellowship, for relationship, between male and female.
 - vii. *Wholeness and beauty:* When God saw everything that He made was good, including the sexuality of his crowning work of Creation (Genesis 1:31). Including the act of sexual intercourse which was part of God’s creation, part of his crowning act. Therefore, declares the first chapter of Genesis, sex is good, very good. It is not a mistake, a sinful aberration, a “regrettable necessity” a shameful experience, as it has so often been regarded in the history of Christian as well as pagan thought. Rather, human sexuality is divinely inaugurated; it was part of God’s perfect design from the beginning, a fundamental aspect of human existence.
 - viii. *Finding completeness:* Because man was created first, it has been asserted that “by this the priority and superiority of the man, and the dependence of the woman upon the man, are established as an ordinance of divine creation.” But the movement in Genesis 2 is not from superior to inferior, but from incompleteness to completeness. Woman is created as the climax to culminate of the story and she is the crowning work of creation.
 - ix. *Sexuality as wholeness:* The holistic view presented in Genesis 2:7 mean that human sexuality cannot be compartmentalized into “the things of the body” versus “the things of the spirit or soul.” Human beings are sexual creatures, and their sexuality

is manifested in every aspect of human existence. Genesis 2: opens with the creation of man. But creation is not finished for the man was alone and incomplete. But this was not good (Verse 18). Man needs a helper or benefactor who is his counterpart. Thus, begins man's quest to satisfy his God's installed "hunger for wholeness." Such hunger is not satisfied by his animal companions, but by the sexual being God has built or made to be alongside him as his complement. Adam in effect exclaims at his first sight of Eve, "At last. I am whole! Here is the complement of myself.

- x. *A multidimensional relationship:* Closely connected with "complementary wholeness" is the idea of relationship. If Genesis 1: whispers that human sexuality is for fellowship and for relationship, Genesis 2 orchestrates this act with a volume of double forte, and the melody and harmony of the narrative portray richness and beauty in the relational symphony of the sexes. In Genesis 2, the creation of Eve takes place in a context of loneliness. The keynote is struck in verse 18: "It is not good that the man should be alone..." This passage may be seen to affirm the various mutual social relationships that should take place between the sexes, but more specifically the Genesis account links the concept of sodality to the manage relationship.

Concept of Sex within Marriage

- i. *Sex Was Created by God and Is Good:* When he created human beings, God made us male and female and declared that his creation was good. He instructed the first husband and wife to "be fruitful and increase in number" instructions that clearly involved nakedness and sexual intercourse (Genesis 1:27-28; 2:24-25). This was not something considered shameful or at best tolerated by God, but rather sex is evidence of God's goodness. It is something for which we can express praise and gratitude.
- ii. *Sex Is for Propagation and Pleasure:* The first birth recorded in the Bible is described as a result of sexual intercourse plus "the help of the Lord" (Genesis 4:1). Obviously, sex is involved in the conception of children and in the divine command to multiply. In the New Testament, we read that a husband and wife are depriving one another when they refuse to give physical pleasure and satisfaction to each other. The only exception to this is when a married couple agrees to abstain from sex temporarily and for the purpose of retreating spiritually for a special time of prayer (Matthew 19:4-6; 1Corinthians 7:5).
- iii. *Sex Is for Marriage:* Whenever the Bible speaks approvingly about sex, it refers to married couples. Quoting Genesis, Jesus spoke with favor about the permanence and "one flesh" nature of marriage. Paul noted that marriage (not intercourse outside of marriage) is the desirable answer for a person who is struggling with sexual self-control. When marriage occurs, the husband and wife are to give their bodies freely to each other and not hold back sexually.
- iv. *Sexual Immorality Is Condemned Strongly:* Sexual looseness may be tolerated in our society, but it is condemned with vehemence in the Bible. God, who created sex, has commanded us to abstain from sexual immorality. This is not because God wants to take away our fun. It is because the Creator knows the dangers of sexual abuse and wants to protect us from the misery that comes when we give in to

lustful passions and accept the self-centered sexual values of people who neither know nor respect God's Word. Adultery is pictured in the Bible as something very attractive that ultimately is destructive and foolish.

Sexual Problems within Marriage

Probably most people approach marriage with enthusiasm about the sexual freedom that will follow. Many of these same people are disappointed when they discover (sometimes as early as the honeymoon) that sex within marriage is not as consistently exciting or pleasurable as they had hoped or expected. There are numerous causes for this.

- i. *Misinformation:* Despite the modern openness about sex, counselors often are amazed at the ignorance and lack of accurate knowledge that is characteristic of many couples. Sex researcher William Masters has concluded that "the greatest cause of sexual problems is misinformation, misconception, and taboo
- ii. *Cultural Attitudes:* The society in which one lives often molds sexual attitudes and behavior. In past decades sex was not discussed openly in our culture, and marital fidelity was the expected norm. Some people considered sex to be dirty, a taboo subject for polite society, something that interested men, but was of little concern to women who were assumed to be passive and lacking in sexual interest or arousal. Attitudes like these may have contributed to the relatively low frequency of intercourse apart from marriage, but they also must have created misunderstanding and sexual frustration.
- iii. *Stress:* Recently an experienced sex therapist was asked to list some sexual problems that have become more apparent during the past fifteen years. It is surprising perhaps that "lack of desire" came at the top of the list. One big cause of lack of desire today is stress, the counselor added. Many people invest so much energy and time into their jobs that they feel drained and want to be left alone. When work creates anxiety, concern over job security or fear of business reversals, interest in love making declines, partly because of physical reasons. In men, for example, prolonged stress sharply decreases the level of testosterone, the primary male hormone.
- iv. *Fatigue, Haste, and Lack of Opportunity:* Fatigue is a common cause of unsatisfactory sex. Mutually pleasurable sexual intercourse takes physical and mental energy. It also takes a relaxed, unhurried attitude that is not greatly concerned about time. When a young couple is first married, they can sleep late on weekends, and have no children to demand their attention, to interrupt their love making, or to interfere with sexual spontaneity. These couples often have a great deal of vigor and natural energy. As they grow older, the husband and wife may have an undiminished desire for sex, but they also have less energy, more responsibilities and demands on their time, increased mental or physical fatigue, and a need for more sleep.
- v. *Boredom:* After a couple has been married for a while, they get accustomed to each other. They run out of novel ways to have sex, foreplay becomes shorter, and coitus becomes routine. After several years, the sexual activities that once were so exciting have become monotonous. Partners spend little time stimulating each other sexually, and sometimes the husband and wife become less interested in their appearance. Sex under such circumstances is not very fulfilling to say the

least, and the stage has been set for an extramarital experience with someone who is more exciting and novel than one's mate (Familusi, 1976).

- vi. *Physical Causes:* Sometimes sexual problems have physical origins such as endocrine disturbances, obesity, diabetes, low energy level, or the weakening of vaginal muscles in women who have given birth. Sometimes a physical illness prevents sexual behavior, and at other times it may cause people to be afraid of intercourse. In one research study, for example, it was found that 80 percent of heart attack patients were afraid to resume sexual activity after their illness, and 42 percent of the men had difficulties attaining and maintaining an erection. Almost and always, when physiology creates sexual problems, psychological tensions come as well and a vicious circular develops, the physiological problem creates psychological tension that in turn hinders physical functioning. In some cases, physiological malfunctioning is used as an excuse for abstinence or sexual difficulties.

Effects of Sexual Problems within Marriage

When sexual problems appear, some couples simply give up and don't try to resolve their difficulties. There may be fear of discussing the frustrations or a belief that things will never get better. Others develop physical symptoms, such as headache, abdominal pain, fatigue, or emotional distress, all of which hide the sexual problem and provide an excuse for abstinence. In addition to the avoidance of intercourse, sexual difficulties in marriage can lead to several major effects:

- i. *Inability to Perform.* Numerous books and research reports have described the symptoms and causes of the more common sexual problems in marriage. These include orgasmic dysfunction (more often known as frigidity, a condition in which the female is unable or unwilling to experience full sexual pleasure including orgasm), vaginismus (a condition in which the vaginal entrance closes tightly when penetration is attempted), erectile dysfunction (also known as impotence, the inability of a male to achieve or maintain an erection), premature ejaculation (the ejaculation of semen, with a resulting loss of erection, immediately before, just at, or shortly after insertion of the penis into the vagina), retarded ejaculation (the opposite of premature ejaculation this occurs when the penis remains erect but ejaculation does not occur), and dyspareunia (painful intercourse). While each of these may have a physical basis, the cause can also be psychological (Ike, 2005).
- ii. *Lowered Self-Esteem.* Self-esteem and sexual capability often go together, especially in men. If intercourse is not mutually satisfying, the husband and wife may both have doubts about their sexual competence, doubts that sometimes are accentuated by the joking of one's mate. If a man cannot maintain an erection or arouse his wife, for example, he is likely to experience a loss of confidence about his sexual and manly capabilities. If his wife jokes about the fact that he may be losing his virility, this is an even greater blow to his self-esteem, and his ability to perform sexually is hindered further.
- iii. *Selection of Substitutes.* When sex within marriage is not satisfying, husbands and wives often turn to substitute activities. These include masturbation, or extramarital sex which often comes as a result of sexual problems within marriage,

but instead of the hoped-for fulfillment, affairs can often lead to guilt, concerns about secrecy, and further marital, sexual, and personal frustration.

New American standard Bible	Nestle Alland 27th Edition
But because of immoralities, each man is to have his own wife, and each woman is to have her own husband.	διὰ δὲ τὰς πορνείας ἕκαστος τὴν ἑαυτοῦ γυναῖκα ἔχέτω καὶ ἕκαστη τὸν ἴδιον ἄνδρα ἔχέτω

One is not surprised about the conclusion of the scholars who interpret “to touch as meaning’ to marry”, because it is only logical for them to conclude that ἔχέτω (have) would mean to get married. Consequently, it is not surprising that they concluded in this verse that Paul is saying that marriage is only permissible as a means of preventing sexual immorality. For example, Mare concludes that, “having said that it would be good under the present circumstances not to get married, Paul hastens to add that the general rule for marriage should apply. The reason, especially true at Corinth, is the prevalence of sexual immorality”. The correct interpretation is however as Saka,1980 also indicates that. “It is important to stress that the passage is not connected with any form of marriage but with celibacy and marriage threatened by sexual asceticism”. This assertion from Ukpong (2014) would fit in to the context as already indicated above, that if the word “touch” does not mean to marry, then it would be difficult to interpret verse two as taking about marriage, the understanding that ἔχέτω is also a euphemism for sex stands here also. So, the understanding of verse two would be that every man should have sexual intercourse with this wife and the woman is also to have sex with the husband. This interpretation fits the context more as it would also be revealed in the understanding of verse three to five.

Verse 3

New American standard Bible	Nestle Alland 27th Edition
The husband must fulfill his duty to his wife, and likewise also the wife to her husband.	τῇ γυναικὶ ὁ ἄνθρωπος τὴν ὀφειλὴν ἀποδίδωται, ὁμοίως δὲ καὶ ἡ γυνὴ τῷ ἀνδρὶ

The most important phrase in this verse is “*apodidoto*” which literally means “repay what is owed”. This again is another euphemism for sexual relationship between the husband and the wife. Samuel (2010) Greek Dictionary says that, figuratively the word means, obligation” or “duty” and that it is a euphemism for sexual intercourse that becomes a duty after a marriage and in this sense can also be translated conjugal duty”. A survey of various translations shows that various ways were used by the translators, but the meaning is still sexual relationship.

For example.

Bible Version	1 Corinthian 7:3
King James” Version	Let the husband render unto the wife due benevolence and likewise also the wife unto the husband
New International Version	The husband should fulfill his marital duty to his wife, and likewise the wife to her husband.

New American Standard Bible	The husband must fulfill his duty to his wife, and likewise also the wife to her husband.
Revised standard Version	The husband should give to his wife her conjugal rights, and likewise the wife to her husband.
The Bible in Basic English	Let the husband give to the wife what is right; and let the wife do the same to the husband.

Verse 4

New American standard Bible	Nestle Alland 27 th Edition
The wife does not have authority over her own body, but the husband does' and likewise also the husband does not have authority over his own body but the wife does.	ἡ γυνή του ἰδίου σωματος οὐκ ἐξουσιάζει ἀλλὰ ὁ ἀνὴρ, ὁμοίως δὲ καὶ ὁ ἀνὴρ τοῦ ἰδίου σώματος οὐκ ἐξουσιάζει ἀλλὰ ἡ γυνή

The key word in this verse ἐξουσιάζει which, as Paul 1975 and James 2011 indicate means having and exercising authority in its various senses; having the right or freedom to exercise authority over or having (independent) control of something. In this sense and context. Paul seems to emphasize that in a marriage situation, the independent control of one's body according to one's inclination ceases and it becomes a joint decision along with the partner.

The verse is the peak of one new teaching on sex and sexuality that Paul has introduced subtly to humanity. It is amazing that Paul did not give the man authority over the woman (neither did he give the woman authority over the man) in sexual matters. This teaching would greatly offend cultural sensibilities wherein the man is the lord of the jungle in sexual matters. For example, many people have in their subconscious minds that the woman has no right to ask for sex or imitate sex, and so women burn with passion rather than express it to their husbands. This point is also raised by Gerhard, 1961 who says that, "the sexual demands in the marriage were the same for both husband and wife. This represents a radical statement for the century-and for today's society as well".

A close examination of the build-up reveals that from verse 2, Paul had been balancing his statements in terms of gender. In verse 2 and 3, mentions the husband first, but in verse 4, he brings forth the woman to the first position knowing quite well that doing that places the emphasis on the woman. This could be interpreted for two angles first, it is the woman that is guilty of withdrawing her body from the man, usually as revenge tactics, second, it of importance in sexual matters

Building a Biblical View of Sex in Africa

Having arrived at what can be called the contextual message of 1 Corinthians 7:1-5, one can now on the basis of this postulate a biblical view of sex in African context.

- i. *Sexual Pleasure is not the Exclusive Preserve of Men:* It has to be understood and taught that sexual pleasure is not the exclusive preserve of men and so women too should be allowed to initiate and enjoy sex as much as men do. As such the practice of female genital mutilation and all attempts so discourage women from initiating and enjoying sex have to be stopped because it is unbiblical. It has to be understood

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- that even sexual passion is God created and every human being has the capacity and so none should be forced to suppress his or her feelings.
- ii. *Sexual Intercourse can take Place Daily:* Apart from the periods that women are under menstruation and when there is a mutual agreement, sex can be enjoyed by both male and female. There is need for a new orientation that would change the women perception about sex, arising from culture, in Africa in order to be able to have sex regularly. This is far too important because most people are running away from being polygamous, and so they have to fulfill their sexual desire outside marriage. We must note that non-satisfaction of sexual desires is one of the major causes of extramarital affairs, which is the alternative to the no more appealing polygamy.
 - iii. *Sex is not just for Procreation:* There is the need for Africans to realize that sex is not just for the purpose of rearing children. Sex is meant to be enjoyed both parties and not just for bringing children into the world. The emphasis on children should be played down. Rushing to get pregnant immediately after marriage is one of the things that destiny the intimacy a couple has to build together.
 - iv. *Sex is not Sin:* There is nothing in the Bible to suggest that sex is sinful. Sex is a God-given gift that has to be used within God's own prescribed boundaries and it is only when sex takes place outside God's instruction that it becomes a sin.
 - v. *Sex is not a tool for Vengeance:* Most often than not both the man and woman use sex a tool for vengeance so that the spouse can be taught a lesson There are times when people abstain from sex just because they want to deal with their spouse, as Wright (1973) opined For example, a woman may refuse to have sex with her husband because the husband has not provided her the money she has asked for or a man may refrain from sex just because the wife is nagging (Familusi, 2014).
 - vi. *Abstaining from sex for spiritual reasons is 'Pseudo-Spirituality':* Trying to avoid sex because one wants to be holy or draw closer to God is a form of pseudo-spirituality. It has to be noted that there are people who want to avoid their conjugal responsibility under the guise of serving God. These types of people have to be taught that taking care of one's conjugal responsibility is in itself a spiritual service and that neglecting it does not make one's service acceptable to God (Allan, 1969).

Conclusion and Recommendations

There is no doubt in the assertion that the family is the main source of security for individuals, however, families are faced with varying challenges and problems in the present modern societies which affects their marital relationships and satisfaction. Methodist church Nigeria, Diocese of Lagos Mainland which has been the focused of the work have shown strict adherence to biblical teachings on marriage through the culture of a robust family counseling. The paper based on the findings recommends that:

Counselors especially those trained by the church should focus on strengthening marital relationship through addressing role conflicts, enhancing life skills, and helping to foster wellness and resiliency to cope with factors leading to marital crises and divorce

In addition to that the spiritual leaders of Methodist Church Nigeria, Diocese of Lagos Mainland should regularly organize marriage counseling symposia, seminars, workshops for their married members to address career-related issues and them promote marital well-being.

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Pastoral Response to Rising Mental Health Challenges in Nigeria in the Context of Pauline Mind Management Therapy in Philippians 4:4-9

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Abstract

This paper discusses the significance of the pastoral response of priests, pastoral caregivers and other religious leaders to rising Mental Health Challenges in Nigeria. Focusing on the roles of pastoral care givers which involve looking after the people he or she has responsibilities, curative and pastoral oversight for, particularly by assisting them with their problems. This is a major assistance for other support systems, particularly psychiatrists, and other medical or *para-medical* health workers. With the multifaceted socio-political and economic problems faced in Nigeria comes an alarming increase in mental health-related challenges. These mental health problems manifest in depression, suicide, drug abuse, psychotic disorder, dementia, and several other mental health issues. Added to the challenges of the rise in mental health cases in Nigeria is the dearth of mental health specialists and inadequate infrastructures coupled with the problem of negative public perception of mental health problems. Pastoral counseling, through its tested and trusted spiritual capital resources, is a major hope in bridging the gap of a dearth of mental health experts and providing positive solutions to the mental health challenges faced in Nigeria including public misconceptions about mental health problems. The paper explores the scriptural recommendation in Philippians 4:4-9 as a mind management therapy towards ameliorating mental health challenges. The findings show that, although one may not be able to control the challenging events and circumstances of life, with the potent Pauline mind management therapy from Philippians 4:4-9, mental distress and ill health can better be managed especially given the inaccessibility of other biomedical models.

Keywords: Pastoral Response, Pastoral Care, Nigeria, Mental Health Challenges, Pauline Mind Management Therapy, Spiritual Capital Resources

Introduction

The world is grappling with complex issues across social, cultural, economic, political, and health domains, and one of the pressing global challenges is the increasing prevalence of mental health problems. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 450 million people grapple with mental illness, and an estimated 25% of the world's population will encounter mental health challenges at some point (Fadele, et al., 2024). Furthermore, mental disorders contribute to approximately 7% of the global health burden, impacting nearly 19% of individuals with disabilities. In Nigeria, it is apparent that mental health challenges and other illnesses are on the rise in contemporary times (World Health Organization, n.d.). The political climate, socio-economic and other bio-psychosocial factors have been implicated as factors contributing to the fast-rising burden of mental health (Lasebikan, et al., 2012). However, scholars from various fields and academic disciplines are making immense contributions at making efforts to match the demand for mental health care with supply of caregivers and professionals. In Nigeria, there is a dire need to draw people into the field of pastoral care, mental health and psychiatric support. To address these challenges, comprehensively, one proposes a holistic approach that involves cross-disciplinary collaboration, robust mental health education in all community-based awareness

initiatives, and trans-disciplinary teamwork among caregivers and mental health providers. This paper aims to identify and assess the escalating evil that plagues the society causing mental health challenges in Nigeria and proposes religious capital assistance, specifically applying Pauline mind management therapy derived from Philippians 4:4-9, as a viable solution to this issue. It employs the research method of Biblical Exegesis and Hermeneutics to explore the topic.

In Christianity, pastoral care and counseling is an approach to improve mental distress and has been practiced since the formation of the advent of the Church (Rizzuto, 1998). This is done by providing guidance and counsel; it is an easy and often preferred contact point for religious people seeking help with psychological problems or personal issues (Woldemichael, 2013). Pastoral care involves spiritual, emotional, and religious care for people of different backgrounds, faiths, statuses, sexes, races, and families.

It is indicated statistically that about 80% of people in Nigeria with severe mental health needs are unable to obtain care, which is primarily attributed to the country's stigma and negative social attitudes towards mental health issues as well as lack of facilities, resources, and mental health professionals (Demyttenaere, 2004).

Exegesis of Pauline Good Will Message and Mind Management Therapy to the Philippians (Phil. 4: 4-9)

One of Paul's purposes in writing this letter was to express gratitude for the affection and financial assistance the Saints in Philippi had extended to him during his second missionary journey and his imprisonment in Rome. The Philippian church had sent gifts through Epaphroditus (one of their members) to Paul (Phil. 4:18), who was in a Roman prison at the time. Paul wrote this letter to thank them for their gift and to encourage them in their faith and daily living (Phil. 1:3-11; 4: 4 - 9, 10-19).

Philippians 4:4-9:

⁴Rejoice in the Lord always. I will say it again: Rejoice ⁵Let your graciousness be known to everyone. The Lord is near. ⁶Do not worry about anything, but in everything, through prayer and petition with thanksgiving, present your requests to God. ⁷And the peace of God, which surpasses all understanding, will guard your hearts and your minds in Christ Jesus.

⁸Finally brothers and sisters, whatever is true, whatever is honourable, whatever is just, whatever is pure, whatever is lovely, whatever is commendable—if there is any moral excellence and if there is anything praiseworthy—dwell on these things. ⁹Do what you have learned and received and heard from me, and seen in me, and the God of peace will be with you.

4:4 – Rejoice in the Lord always

The church faces opposition within and without, yet here is Paul, writing a letter about joy and telling the Philippians to rejoice. From a human perspective, it sounds unrealistic and yet the path to joy is to actually choose to rejoice. Paul repeats the exhortation, because the honour of Christ, and the comfort of his followers, greatly depend on its being taken. **Let your moderation, that is,** the pursuit of the various enjoyments of life, and in the sense, you have of the injuries and indignities you may meet with: or **your gentleness** and sweetness of temper, as *επιεικεις υμων* may here be rendered, the result of your joy in the Lord. According to Macknight, moderation “means meekness under provocation, readiness to forgive injuries, equity in the management of business, candour in judging of the character and actions of

others, sweetness of disposition, and the entire government of the passions, Titus 3:2; James 3:17. Worldly happiness is not the same as godly happiness. In the Bible, the word joy is a celebration term, thus, Paul calls for celebration. The difference between joy and secular happiness is that the latter depends on what happens; it is circumstantially driven. So, if things are going in an upward direction in life, you feel up, but if things are going down, you feel down. This keeps you on an emotional roller coaster Biblical joy, by contrast, has to do with stability and celebration on the inside regardless of circumstances on the outside. The Philippian Christians must choose to rejoice in order to experience the joy God promises them (Macknight, 1987).

The Lord is at hand — God is the Judge, the rewarder, the revenger; he will put an end to all the temporal enjoyments of the wicked people, and put an end to all the sufferings from the enemies. **And in everything let your requests be made known unto God by prayer and supplication** — Paul used the Greek word, *προσευχη*, which is understood as petition for mercies, and by the latter, *δειςις*, deprecation of judgment; but it seems more probable that by the latter, properly enough rendered **supplication**, the apostle meant nothing more than enlarging upon and urging for petitions **with thanksgiving**. **This is a hope for blessings** already received, and for the general or particular goodness, forbearance, and long-suffering of God toward man (MacArthur, 2007).

And the peace of God, that is, not only peace with God, and peace of conscience, arising from the remission of past sin, and a consciousness of present power over sin; but **the peace of God**, that calm, heavenly repose, that tranquillity of Spirit, which God only can give; **which passes all understanding** — Which none can properly comprehend or appreciate, but those that receive it; **shall keep** — *Φρουρησει*, **shall guard**, as in a citadel or place of defence; **your hearts, that is**, your will and affections; **and minds** — your understandings, imaginations, intentions, determinations, and all the various workings of them in the knowledge and love of God; **through Christ Jesus** (MacArthur, 2007).

4:5 – Let your reasonableness be known to everyone

In other words, don't spread unhappiness to others. Being gracious means, we don't use our ministries to be vindictive or hateful when things aren't going well. Rather, we embrace a good attitude because we know **the Lord is near**. If we refuse to rejoice and instead complain, we can displease God.

4:6 – Do not be anxious about anything

Prayer is relational communication with God, it seeks to draw resources from the invisible spiritual realm into visible, physical reality. Every time one gives room to **worries is tantamount disbelief in Him**. **The community of faith** should see that as a call from God telling us that it's time to pray. The sobering truth is that the more you worry, the less you pray. But the more you pray, the less you worry. When you make a **petition**, be specific. A moment in which you are plagued by worry is not the time for one of those general prayers for God to bless the world. To deal with anxiety, make sure your petitions are precise. Get real with God (MacArthur, 2007).

Prayer can often feel frustrating—like when you go to a soda machine, put in your money, punch the button, and nothing comes out. But thinking of it in those terms causes us to miss how prayer works. God wants us to make requests **with thanksgiving**. Give thanks, not for the problem itself, but for the God you are inviting into your specific problem. Offering thanks is a demonstration of faith in God's goodness and provision despite what you see.

4:7 – The peace of God

When you pray as instructed in 4:6, **the peace of God, which surpasses all understanding, will guard [you] in Christ Jesus.** In other words, you'll experience calm amid chaos. You will know God heard your prayer, not necessarily because the problem is solved, but because of the peace that God gives you. It's as if God puts soldiers and sentries around your feelings and thoughts.

Kingdom Living: The Key to a Kingdom Mind

A kingdom mind is ultimately responsible for how you live out your life as a kingdom citizen. As you think, so you are. One of the most important things that you can do as a follower of Jesus Christ is to think about the true things. Far too often, Satan tries to place subtle lies within our thoughts. They aren't enough to attract our attention, but they are enough to get our line of thinking off of the truth. To remain focused on the truth, it is essential to commit the Word of God to memory.

Scripture tells us to think about the things that are lovely, pure, sensible, and true. We read in Paul's letter to the church at Philippi, "Brothers and sisters, whatever is true, whatever is honorable, whatever is just, whatever is pure, whatever is lovely, whatever is commendable – if there is any moral excellence and if there is anything praiseworthy – dwell on these things" (Phil 4:8) (MacArthur, 2007).

The reverse of that holds true as well. Whatever is untrue, dishonourable, unjust, impure, unlovely, and not commendable – we are to guard our minds against. Our minds are integral to how we live our lives: they steer what decisions we make, what words we choose to use, and even the level of faith we exhibit toward God. One of the most helpful things you can do is commit Philippians 4:8 to memory and make it your guiding force throughout your day. Do this and watch what God does both in and through you.

4:8 – Think about these things

We don't want to lose the peace God grants us in the next hour or the next day. So to prevent that, Paul says we're to dwell on **whatever is true, honourable, just, pure, lovely, and commendable, and if there is any moral excellence and . . . anything praiseworthy,** we're to focus our attention there. One of the reasons we don't keep our peace is that we tend to dwell on the things that are set in opposition to the peace we're asking for. If we continue to entertain messages that work against our peace, anxiety will soon return. The Philippians must, therefore, ask themselves if they can praise God for the things that they are dwelling on. If not, then they will soon lose the peace God has given to them.

4:9 – The God of peace

The Philippians were to handle things the way they had seen Paul handle things. He was in prison, but he was praising God instead of worrying. One of the purposes of the church is to connect believers with other kingdom-minded people. We need support, and we need good examples. When we're rejoicing and praying and dwelling on the right things and watching the right people, we don't just have the peace of God, we have **the God of peace.** We get his peace, and we get his presence (Wallace, 1999).

Finally – To λοιπον, as for what remains for me to say, it may be despatched in a few words. The apostle, says Bauer, "being anxious to make the Philippians virtuous, mentions, in this exhortation, all the different foundations on which virtue had been placed (Bauer,

2000), to show that it does not rest on any of these singly, but on them all jointly; and that its amiableness and obligation result from" **whatsoever things are true** — Conformable to truth; **honest** — Σεμνα, **grave**, or **venerable**; **just** — Equitable and righteous; **pure** — Chaste and holy; **lovely** — Προσφιλη, **amiable**, or, as the word may be rendered, friendly and kind; **of good report** — Ευφημα, **of good fame**, or reputable; **if there be any virtue** — Any real worth, or beneficial tendency, in any quality or action: in this place alone does St. Paul use the word αρετη, rendered **virtue: if there be any praise faithfully** resulting from anything (Atwoju, 2010). Bengelius gives a somewhat different view of the contents of this verse, thus: "Here are eight particulars placed in two four-fold rows; the former containing their duty, the latter the commendation of it. The first word in the former row answers the first in the latter; the second word the second; and so on: **true** — In speech; **honest** — In actions; **just** — With regard to others; **pure** — With regard to yourselves; **lovely** — And what more lovely than truth? **of good report** — As is honesty, even when it is not practised. **If there be any virtue** — And all virtues are contained in justice; **if there be any praise** — In those things which relate rather to ourselves than to our neighbour; **think on these things** — That ye may both practise them yourselves, and recommend them to others." **Those things which you have learned** — As catechumens; **and received** — By continual instructions; **and heard and seen** — In my life and conversation; these **do, and the God of peace shall be with you** — Not only the peace of God, but God himself, the fountain of peace (Atwoju, 2010).

Pauline Influence on Human Psychotherapy

Apostle Paul's teachings have been enormously influential on the psychological treatment of those dealing with guilt and suffering. A major part of therapy includes aiding the client in the restructuring of their self-image. Christian therapists use Paul's teachings to reach this goal, helping the client to see that "no one is any longer committed definitively to the flesh; the spirit dwells in every Christian. A positive self-image is thus maintained against the empirical reality of guilt and suffering" (Theissen, 1987).

Sigmund Freud is among the names often credited as having been influential in the professional field of psychology. Other prominent names include Carl Jung, Carl Rogers, B.F Skinner, Abraham Maslow, and many others who have come up with their own theory about studying the self. But long before the days when psychology began moving towards becoming its own profession, there existed biblical ideas that remain extremely influential in the field today. Paul's teachings on the self may be seen in both the theories about and in the treatments of many disorders and psychological problems seen in both secular and Christian counselling centres every day (Sande, 1991).

One can see evidence of Pauline influence on Gestalt theory. In the terms put forth by Gestalt theory, restructuring one's life may be looked at as a change in ground and background. By examining the text of 1 Corinthians 2:6-16, author Gerd Theissen concludes that "What otherwise is the hardly perceived or denied background of the everyday life-world emerges in religious experience as decisive reality. Foolishness appears as wisdom, weakness as power, a defeat as victory" (Theissen, 1987). As Paul teaches, reality may now be regarded in a different light, meaning freedom for the individual.

Paul's influence on Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic theory is one of the first psychological theories ever formulated, and Carl Jung's analytic theory become evident by studying 2 Corinthians 3:1-4:6. The goal of psychoanalysis is to allow the client to tap into their unconscious, thereby accessing the memories stored there and bringing them into the conscious. The aforementioned section by Paul "itself suggests a view 'from within'." Theissen

suggests that the veil discussed in 3:15 is representative of the boundary which separates the conscious from the unconscious, and Paul discusses how this veil may be eliminated in Christ. The author demonstrates this when he contrasts 2 Corinthians 3:13-15 ("the veil of Moses appears not only over the reading of the law but also over the hearts of the listeners") with 2 Corinthians 3:18 ("But we all, with unveiled face, beholding as in a mirror the glory of the Lord, are being transformed into the same image from glory to glory, just as by the Spirit of the Lord" (Theissen, 1987).

Psychologists often teach their clients that their negative behaviour can be reformed by choosing a behaviour model. That is, the client will focus on the positive behaviour exhibited by a certain individual, attempting to re-shape their own behaviour by modelling this individual. Paul discusses this idea by teaching his followers to imitate him just as he in turn imitates Christ (1 Corinthians 11:1). Various psychological themes such as Carl Jung's theory have emphasized the restructuring of the "inner man." After studying 1 Corinthians 2:6-16 one can conclude, "Christ is the cause of a radical restructuring of the internal and external world" (Theissen, 1987).

Author William Backus, in his book entitled *i*, uses Philippians 4:11-13 to describe the Pauline influence on truth therapy ("the practice of counselling based on the Christian belief that the truth can make you free") (Backus, 1985). As Paul taught throughout all of his writings, an important goal for Christians needs to be that they recognize what sins they struggle with, and thus an important goal for counsellors is to aid others in experiencing freedom from their sins. "The man or woman who would set others free must first experience freedom" (Backus, 1985). One can see evidence of this in Paul's life through his conversion on the road to Damascus. To convey the truth of the gospel to others, he had to first experience the truth of the Messiah for himself. This idea is prominent in the field of psychology today. A counsellor who knows nothing about the true reasons why many people suffer from eating disorders and insists that those who struggle with bingeing simply need to be placed on a diet will be of no use to the individual who comes to them for help (indeed, he will inflict more damage upon his client) (Allender, 1995). To provide adequate help, the counsellor must know the truth about what lies behind the many disorders plaguing society today.

Oftentimes when a client takes the step of coming to a psychologist for help, it is believed that such an individual is seeking repentance. "Repentance means, literally, 'getting a new mind, which the scripture calls living a new life.'" This can only take place by the work of the Holy Spirit, who works by "renewing and changing someone's old sinful, angry, unforgiving mind, and replacing it with a new mind like the mind of Christ." Paul's writings in Philippians 2 provide an explanation of a new mind in Christ. One of the steps involved in repentance, according to Backus, comes directly from Paul's letter to the Romans in chapter six. In therapy, the Christian psychologist often teaches the client to "Believe and tell yourself that the sin habit or root within you has no further power over you. Visualize it being nailed to the cross with Jesus and reckon yourself dead to it" (Backus, 1985).

Pauline influences on the treatment of anger is also imperative, not only does Paul teach that self-control is a fruit of the Holy Spirit and is something that then should be strived for, he provides advice on what to do when a person does experience anger at another by stating that it should be dealt with immediately as to avoid bitterness; "Be angry but do not sin; do not let the sun go down on your anger, and give no opportunity to the devil" (Ephesians 4:26,27). Paul also influenced the treatment of persistent anger by discussing the principle of thought practice: "repeatedly thinking the new thoughts you desire to install in place of others". Paul

discusses thought practice in Philippians 4:8: "Whatever is true, whatever is honourable, whatever is just, whatever is pure, whatever is lovely, whatever is gracious, if there is any excellence, if there is anything worthy of praise, think about these things."

A specific problem that Paul speaks to involves a common personality characteristic of those suffering from obsessive-compulsive disorder. Often these individuals will have an extremely difficult time in making decisions and will pressure their psychologist or others to literally make up their mind for them. Because these individuals often feel that they must come up with the perfect solution to everything, they will go back and forth in their decision-making process. "The apostle Paul specifically rejected this wavering stance toward decisions as one that is not appropriate for Christians to hang onto" (Backus, 1985). This rejection may be found in Paul's writings in 2 Corinthians 1:17-20:

When I planned this, did I do it lightly? Or do I make my plans in a worldly manner so that in the same breath I say, "Yes, yes" and "No, no"? But as surely as God is faithful, our message to you is not "Yes" and "No." For the Son of God, Jesus Christ, who was preached among you by me and Silas and Timothy, was not "Yes" and "No," but in him it has always been "Yes." For no matter how many promises God has made, they are "Yes" in Christ. And so through him the "Amen" is spoken by us to the glory of God.

Even those individuals whose hearts are closed to the word of God usually have a conscience, as Paul teaches in Romans 2:15. Sociopaths, however, seem to be absent of any conscience. As Backus states in his discussion on sociopathic personalities, sociopaths if they manage to live until middle age, often "settle down with a more conventional but burned-out pattern of behaviour....these people seem to live by the maxim that Paul rejects in 1 Corinthians 15, 'Let us eat and drink, for tomorrow we die'" (Backus, 1985).

Paul and Self-Evaluation

One significant concept to be remembered by a therapist must remember while counselling others, is that he must realize what his own sinful desires are, instead of deceiving himself into thinking that he is somehow above having lustful thoughts because he is a Christian. This idea originates from Paul's teachings in Romans 8:18: "I know that in me, that is, in my flesh, dwells no good thing." "The idea of trusting one's own organismic responsiveness, later to be taken as a primary indicator of psychological full-functioning, was clearly anticipated by ancient Christian writers who spoke of the journey of the soul and self-acquaintance with one's own soul" (Oden, 1992). Pauline influence on the treatment of sexual deviations may be seen in his writings on the "lusts of the flesh" in Galatians 5:17-20, and in 1 Corinthians 6:9-11). Empathy, as defined by Thomas C. Oden, is "a willingness to participate attentively and accurately with what another is experiencing here and now" (Oden, 1992). Empathy is a necessary quality for a good psychologist to possess. Paul discusses empathy in Romans 12:15 when he states "Rejoice with those who rejoice and weep with those who weep." Although resources on Pauline aspects in the field of psychology are few, there is no denying the apostle's tremendous influence upon the study of the self. This discussion has focused on only a few of the many ways in which Paul has influenced psychology in one form or another. Self-knowledge is related to the knowledge of God, for we were created in His image, thus Paul speaks on this matter abundantly (Imasuen and Atowoju, 2012).

The rising incidence of mental health challenges in Nigeria is evident in the daily news, and

research data, which frequently reports cases of mental health issues, including a disturbing increase in suicides. Common mental health problems in Nigeria encompass depression, drug abuse, psychotic disorders, and suicidal behaviours, affecting individuals across all social strata and lifespans (Oyetunji, et.al., 2021). Mental health issues are also prevalent in childhood, such as intellectual disability, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, and autism. Additionally, postpartum depression and pregnancy-related psychosis affect many women, while dementia is becoming a major concern among the elderly (Rai, 2015). Mental health, in its simplest terms, pertains to the overall well-being that enables individuals to cope with life's stresses, realize their potential, work effectively, and contribute positively to society (NIDirect, 2023). Factors that affect person's mental health can be social, biological, environmental, or psychological. Rapid social change, socio-economic pressure and hardships, stress, social exclusion, gender discrimination, and physical ill-health can equally affect a person's mental health condition.

Mental illness and behavioural disorders affect people regardless of where they come from, age, faith, gender, financial and social status. The rising level of mental illness and substance abuse-related behavioural disorders in Nigeria is partly attributed to economic hardship, rising cost of living, security, and environmental degradation. The outlandish declaration of the World Health Organization that over 450 million people globally are suffering from mental illness, and one in four individuals will experience mental health problems during their lifetime (World Health Organization, 2017) calls for proactive attention. Regrettably, awareness of mental health in Nigeria remains significantly low, as highlighted by a 2019 survey conducted by the Africa Polling Institute (API) and EPI AFRIC (Africa Polling Institute & EpiAFRIC, 2020). Nigeria's mental health infrastructure is also lacking, with only about 300 psychiatrists serving a population of over 200 million and a limited number of functional neuropsychiatric hospitals (Gureje, 2003). Pastoral counselors can play a vital role in bridging this gap and implementing Pauline mind management therapy to aid individuals with mental health challenges.

Some common types of mental illnesses include:

- Anxiety disorders involve more than normal temporary worry or fear one experiences before taking examinations when faced with occasional challenges at work place or before taking a crucial decision. Anxiety disorder is more pronounced and does not readily go away. Anxiety disorder can be panic-disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder or phobias.
- Depression is characterized by loss of interest or pleasure, sadness, feeling of guilt, poor concentration, low self-esteem etc. Depression can cause physical complaints without apparent physical cause.
- Bipolar disorder which is also referred to as maniac-depressive illness is a brain-related disorder that causes unusual changes in mood, activity level, and the energy required for day-to-day tasks. Bipolar disorder is essentially about mood swings.
- Schizophrenia is a chronic mental disorder that affects how a person feels, thinks and behaves. A schizophrenic person behaves like someone who has lost touch with reality. This condition distorts perception, thinking, emotion, and even sometimes language and sense of self.
- Dementia is a chronic, progressive deteriorating condition in the cognitive function/ability to analyze and process thought. Dementia affects memory, comprehension, calculation, orientation, and emotional control.

Analyzing the Need for Mind Management Therapy

The mind is the seat of thought, consciousness, and awareness, making it an essential element of our identity. Properly managing our minds is crucial for achieving mental peace, especially during challenging times. It has been said that a person can go without food for three weeks, without water for three days, and three minutes without oxygen but no one can go without thinking for three seconds (Adams, 1970). That you are your mind is scripturally supported (Proverbs 23:7). The world is beset with various problems, including climate change, diseases, pandemics, socioeconomic issues, and, most significantly, despair. Unfortunately, society tends to focus more on physical wellness, while mental and emotional well-being often takes a backseat. Modern information and communication technology have increased pressure and challenges, altering how people think and make decisions. This rush for data often sacrifices the processing of knowledge, leading to a decline in mental and emotional health (Bosamia, 2013). To address this issue, we need to learn the art of mind management to adapt to technological advancements effectively.

Mind Management Involves Several Aspects

- Programming and editing thoughts, actions, and reactions to avoid triggering toxic chain reactions that harm mental health.
- Directing the processes of cellular, molecular, genetic, chemical, and structural aspects of our being, putting the brain under the mind's control.
- Maximizing thought and brain performance for positive change.
- Teaching the brain how to learn in an organized, productive, and meaningful way.
- Regulating the intake of information, emotions, and physical sensations.

Conclusion

Pastoral counselors play a vital role in guiding those with mental health challenges toward mental health recovery through mind management therapy derived from Philippians 4:4-9. This approach enhances the connection between the mind and the body, promoting overall well-being and mental peace. It is a viable solution to address the rising mental health challenges in Nigeria and elsewhere. The scripture in Philippians 4:4-9 provides practical guidance on enhancing holistic mental health. Some key techniques and principles from this text include rejoicing, forbearance, appreciation, dependence on God, and godly dispositions. Therefore, Pastoral care and counseling as an approach to improving mental health should be encouraged because pastoral care involves spiritual, emotional, and religious care for people of different backgrounds, faiths, status, sex, race, and their families irrespective of their situations.

Recommendations

1. By employing Pauline Mind Management therapy, which has greatly influenced psychologists like Sigmund Freud, who believes that people learn to behave in certain ways because they have received positive reinforcement for their behaviour. Therefore, Nigerians should be encouraged to cultivate positive energy by rejoicing regardless of their circumstances. People should learn to exhume positive energies. One may not be able to control situations of things, but efforts should be made to react positively to challenging situations. Everyone should exhibit positive energy by learning to always REJOICE

(Philippians 4:4-5).

2. Combating anxiety through appreciation and recognition of the divine inundation in every aspect of life. Nigerians should be encouraged through Pastoral care and counselling to fight depression, distress, and bitterness, and eschew hatred and malice (Philippians 4:6).

3. Nigerians irrespective of their situation should learn to find inner peace by focusing on God's grace. Manage distractions around by activating inner peace. Anchor their heart and mind on the grace and inner peace given by God (Philippians 4:7).

4. Furthermore, Nigerians should cultivate their minds with virtuous values. Check and select what is allowed into their minds diligently based on: truthfulness, honesty, purity, justice, equity, praiseworthiness, and godliness (Philippians 4:8).

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Ethical Issues in Pastoral Counselling of Widows: A Critical Review

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Abstract

Widowhood is a reality and consists of grief situations. Often, widows seek help from pastors and the church during these unpleasant experiences. To aid holistic healing, pastoral counselling, a unique and integral facet of spiritual care, is vital. However, some pastors often use these counselling processes to exploit widows financially, sexually, and emotionally, amongst others. These exploitations have necessitated a careful review of the ethical issues during the counselling of widows. Secondary data sources were used to understand widows' grief situations, the impact of pastoral counselling, and the ethical dimensions surrounding the counselling process, with some ethical pastoral cases presented. It was found that theological institutions, pastoral, and the church have a role in addressing the ethical dilemma surrounding pastoral counselling. It was recommended that theological institutions develop modules on counselling widows, churches implement specialised training programmes for pastoral counsellors, and clear policies should be developed with regular evaluations. Likewise, pastors should integrate some secular counselling approaches and collaborate with professional therapists when needed. The review concludes that pastoral counsellors can establish a foundation of trust and support for widows in their journey toward healing by acknowledging and addressing the unique challenges they face through an ethical lens.

Keywords: Ethical Issues, Grief, Pastoral Counselling, Widows, Widowhood

Introduction

Grief describes a normal response to the loss of a loved one or anything dear to one's heart. The most common cause of this form of loss is death. Death is inevitable. It strikes at any time. To cope with such a loss, counselling may be required. Counselling assists individuals, such as widows, with their concerns to positively adjust to the reality of the loss (Mburugu, 2020). In most cases, widows seek counsel from their religious leaders. If they are Christians, they consult their pastors (Wolfelt, 2003). A pastor is the spiritual leader of a Christian congregation. According to Odeleye (2022), pastors can be referred to by several titles, usually based on their roles, such as shepherd, nurturer, watchman, and carer. Pastors need to be equipped with a unique blend of spiritual insight and psychological understanding to play a pivotal role in facilitating healing and inspiring resilience in widows, especially through counselling.

Pastoral Counselling involves a counsellor, in this case, a pastor, being receptive to exploring the inner psychological dynamics of individuals. Such assistance is given while recognising the shared spiritual values that can be crucial when navigating crises or existential challenges (Iwajomo, 2019). Hence, the significance of pastoral counselling in addressing the multifaceted needs of widows cannot be overstated, as widows often face challenges beyond conventional psychological counselling, involving issues of faith, existential questioning, and re-establishing purpose. Pastoral counselling integrates this unique space, intertwining

psychological principles with spiritual guidance to provide a holistic support system to people.

However, as with any form of counselling, pastoral counselling encounters ethical considerations that demand careful examination. The ethical dimensions of pastoral counselling have begun to gain increased attention in recent years, with pastors and theological scholars recognising the need for a nuanced understanding of how ethical principles apply in this context.

Consequently, this paper critically reviewed secondary data such as book, journals, and news articles to explore the ethical issues in pastoral counselling for widows. It aims to shed light on the ethical issues pastors delve into and the challenges they pose to the widows seeking their support and making contextual recommendations for pastors and churches.

The Widowhood Phase

A widow is a woman with or without children who has lost her husband through death and has not married again (Boaheng & Boahen, 2022). As a result, she enters into widowhood experiences. Widowhood is a phenomenon or condition a widow or widower undergoes after the death of a spouse. Widowhood experiences for a woman, irrespective of age at bereavement, has a wide array of destabilising effect on her emotional and psychological well-being that can lead to mental health issues, such as depression, anxiety, frustration and others (Nwaoba, Ajoku, & Uba, 2022).

The loss of a beloved is very draining emotionally. The person experiences shock, confusion, and disbelief from the day of loss. Hopes become shattered, aspirations dashed, and it appears the final end has come (Olateru-Olagbegi, 2012). Loneliness is also experienced, especially as a widow. Olateru-Olagbegi (2012: 29) mentions that “she usually sat on her balcony, gazing at nothing and expecting her husband to walk home and speak with her. She felt empty despite having family and loved ones around her.” This means that loss sometimes comes with the refusal to accept the new reality and status as a widow.

The death of a husband marks a new phase in a woman's life, and she is expected to undergo specific rights depending on her culture. According to Ayoola (2017), widows comprise about half of the adult female population in many African societies. For these African women, mourning rites are required; for some women, it involves shaving their hair, burning the clothes they wore at the time of the husband's demise, sleeping beside the deceased, or even drinking the water used to bath the deceased to prove their innocence regards their husband's death (Boaheng & Boahen, 2022). Widows often experience oppressive and dehumanising cultural practices (Damap, 2008). They grapple with numerous challenges, attempting to manage the responsibilities formerly shouldered by their deceased spouses, which frequently take a toll on them, particularly impacting their health.

The writer, from observations, discovers that the attitudes of the late husband's relations may not be satisfactory to the widow, particularly if she is still young and/or dependent on her spouse, who was very rich. The situation may be unpleasant if they are focused on acquiring the deceased's properties rather than the welfare of the widow and her children, if any (Olateru-Olagbegi, 2012). This makes financial problems rank highest in all the plights of many widows because survival needs must be attended to.

Widowhood represents a profound life transition often accompanied by grief, emotional turmoil, and various challenges that necessitate support. In this context, pastoral counselling emerges as a vital resource, providing spiritual and emotional guidance to widows navigating

the complexities of loss. One major aspect of pastoral care is pastoral counselling. It is a healing ministry of the religious community built on a connection between a family or individual and a pastor (or a pastoral team) with counselling skills (Lartey, 2003).

In a study by Mohammed (2022), all the interview respondents in the study identified multiple factors they relied on to cope and survive; one of the distinctive ways is Faith and Belief in God. All the widows identified their faith in God as the primary source of support in dealing with the loss of their spouse as well as enduring traumatic practices that some of them were put through.

Impact of Pastoral Counselling on Widows

Pastoral counselling has the potential to yield both positive and negative outcomes, profoundly influencing the well-being of widows. On the positive side, it serves as a transformative force, fostering emotional healing, offering invaluable support, and cultivating empowerment and resilience. However, the negative consequences of pastoral counselling may manifest when ethical lapses occur. These lapses can give rise to trust issues and, in more severe cases, contribute to psychological harm.

The ethical dimensions of counselling play a pivotal role in shaping the overall well-being of widows, underscoring the need for a conscientious and principled approach in pastoral care. It emphasises the responsibility of counsellors to uphold the highest ethical standards and to ensure that the therapeutic process is a source of positive transformation rather than unintended distress.

Ethical Frameworks and Challenges in Pastoral Counselling

From the foregoing, the great task of the church makes it more expedient for the church to have sound counselling strength for its members that would enable them to get adequate care as needed. However, as with any form of counselling, pastoral counselling encounters ethical considerations that demand careful examination. Ethics in counselling are concerned with human conduct and doing what is in the client's best interest. The most common ethical principles include confidentiality, informed consent, cultural sensitivity, and professional competence, which are the ethical concerns this paper hinges on.

Confidentiality and Consent Concerns

Christian counsellors must obtain and maintain client confidentiality to the fullest extent as allowed by the law, professional ethics and bodies, and the church (Babatunde, 2021). All personal information and the disclosures made during sessions must be kept secret and secure. Counsellors need to seek and get permission or consent from the clients before acting on their behalf (Babatunde, 2021). It should be documented for future purposes. However, it is important to balance confidentiality with mandatory reporting. This is usually done when the griever has done or is about to do something harmful to himself or a loved one.

Also, consent for biblical practices should be requested. Though the griever is a Christian, during the grieving process, they might be struggling with their faith in God and imposing faith-based counselling methods such as prayers and Bible reading might hinder the journey to recovery. However, communicating the purpose and scope of counselling can help to ensure the widow knows what to expect from the counselling sessions.

From the foregoing, pastors are discouraged from using the information shared confidently as a reference point during church services or sharing it with colleagues, church leaders or members during discussions. It amounts to betrayal. It is unethical.

Cultural Sensitivity

Counsellors need to recognise that widows come from varied cultural contexts, each with its own set of beliefs, practices, and norms regarding grief, loss, and coping mechanisms (Betancourt et al., 2003). For instance, different cultures may have distinct rituals, mourning periods, and expectations regarding expressing grief. A counsellor's ability to comprehend and respect these cultural nuances is crucial for establishing trust and rapport with widows. Also, cultural biases can inadvertently influence counselling approaches, potentially leading to misunderstandings or even exacerbating the emotional distress of widows (Sue & Sue, 2012). Counsellors should strive to be aware of their cultural biases and ensure their interventions are culturally sensitive and respectful.

Cultural sensitivity in pastoral counselling is a dynamic and evolving process that requires ongoing education and self-reflection. By understanding the diverse cultural backgrounds of widows and actively avoiding cultural biases, counsellors can create a therapeutic space that is affirming, respectful, and conducive to the well-being of widows during their grief journey. During the grieving period, pastors are usually contacted for assistance by the widows. However, some pastoral counsellors do not help resolve issues but worsen the situation as a result of ignoring cultural practices or not managing the conflict situation properly due to personal biases or incompetence which sometimes, they might be aware of.

Competence and Professional Boundaries

Christian counsellors should not aid or abet the practice of unlicensed, untrained, unqualified, or unethical counselling. Instead, they are to consult and/or refer to more competent superiors or colleagues when their counselling limits have been reached (Babatunde, 2021). This is because a referral is integral to the healing experiences of griever seeking wholeness (Abioye, 2021). It is important to note that referrals have a theological basis, which Abioye (2021) clearly expressed.

Usually, grievers, in this case, widows, need mature minds they can lean on for support and strength, and pastors fit in better to stand beside them. This type of service has been identified as ministry of presence. This usually provides succour and assurance of not being alone during grief, and widows can feel fulfilled, comforted and strengthened (Iwajomo, 2019). However, pastors need to maintain appropriate boundaries in the pastoral counselling relationship. In offering pastoral care and counselling, visitation, amongst many others, is a vital index because they need companionship and advice (Ayoola, 2017). If the visit is done, it should be with one's spouse or a partner or done in an open space to prevent suspicions or sexual temptations.

Professional boundaries can also be challenging, as avoiding such connections is crucial, especially when discussing sensitive topics that may lead to intense emotional bonds. This is why counsellors are advised to avoid providing therapy to family, friends, or individuals they have personal connections with, including relatives or acquaintances. These ethical boundaries aim to ensure impartial and confidential therapy for all clients, enabling them to express their issues freely. Because counselling means consultation, discussion, deliberation, exchange of ideas, advice or decision-making (Oyedele, 2017), some pastoral counsellors tend

to enforce decisions on widows due to the power dynamics in the pastor-widow relationship. This is because widows tend to go along with the pastor's decisions.

Cumulative Integrity

This implies soundness, adherence to principle, and completeness in the sense of being undivided. Babatunde (2021) further explains that integrity can be seen as faithfulness to the Lord, regard to the Scripture, integrity of role and with the congregation, and within the limits of pastoral training.

According to Ayandokun (2021), those who engage in pastoral counselling should be persons of integrity who can be trusted and dependable without any trait of deception and manipulation of the client. The scholar adds that those helping bring healing and restoration to the griever should not add to their calamities. Hence, the pastor's morality and the counselling process's integrity must be maintained.

Ethical Pastoral Cases

As background to recommendations being made, selected case studies are presented below: According to Ologbosere (2018), a 59-year-old man allegedly defrauded a widow of N3 million. The man conspired with a friend, an alleged international fraudster, who presented himself as a pastor and convinced the woman that she was dealing with a credible Nigerian. The widow then gave them the amount to help her purchase two fairly used jeeps, but they made away with the money and extorted more from the widow under the pretext of paying duties on the car they never bought.

Seiger (2020) reported that in North Carolina, a Concord pastor was found guilty of stealing more than \$120,000 from a widow who was his family friend in the months following her husband's death. This occurred over 13 months, beginning after her husband died in 2015. It was found that the pastor's suspicious activities were noticed by a relative of the victim and reported to law enforcement. Edem (2021) also reported a widow being sexually involved with the pastor who buried her husband. In Benin City, Edo State, a pastor allegedly turned a widow and her three daughters into his sex slaves, impregnating two of them (Oriental News, 2020). The pastor was also said to have collected every document and property left behind by the twins' late father and claimed that they were sowed to the Church as seed.

These examples represent only a portion of the unethical behaviours pastors may exhibit when caring for and counselling widows. They may subject widows to sexual exploitation, assert control over various aspects of their lives, and assume management of their resources, including finances and property.

Recommendations

According to Babatunde (2021), professionalism in pastoral counselling has gone beyond external qualifications such as training from a seminary or other theological institutions or belonging to one professional body. It involves getting a more comprehensive orientation on issues that border on the smooth and effective dispensation of counsellors' duties. Hence, the following are recommended:

1. Modules on grief dynamics, cultural sensitivity, and ethical considerations for counselling widows should be developed by theological institutions.

2. On different levels, Churches should implement specialised training programmes for pastoral counsellors that focus on the unique challenges widows face. In being proactive, churches should have programmes for married members with a focus on widowhood, ensuring they are prepared and protected after the demise of their partner.
3. Churches should develop clear policies, disseminate these policies, and regularly evaluate their ethical standards to guide pastoral counselling for widows. This will equip pastoral counsellors to perform their duties ethically despite any challenges.
4. There is also a need to advance research on ethical issues in pastoral counselling, as this will contribute significantly to developing guidelines, principles, and best practices to guide pastoral counsellors in navigating complex ethical dilemmas.
5. The pastors should integrate faith, ethics, and professional standards with secular counselling approaches. The pastors, leading the churches should collaborate with professional therapists to refer cases beyond pastoral competencies.
6. It is essential to have client education and empowerment by implementing educational programmes for widows to inform them about their rights, the counselling process and its importance, and the importance of ethical conduct.

Conclusion

Appraising ethical issues in pastoral counselling for widows emphasises the crucial importance of a nuanced and principled approach in supporting this group of people. The unique challenges widows face require a heightened awareness of ethical boundaries and a commitment to upholding the highest standards of care. By acknowledging and addressing these unique challenges through an ethical lens, pastoral counsellors can establish a foundation of trust and support that is essential for widows in their journey toward healing and living a fulfilled life.

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Social Support Systems as a Correlate of Mental Health Disorders among Young Adults in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated Social Support Systems as a Correlate of Mental Health Disorders among Young Adults in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. It emphasized the need to recognize and prioritize social support systems (such as family, friends, mental health services, online communities, and crisis helplines), as a vital tool to address mental health disorders (anxiety, depression, suicidal ideation) among young adults, which has become a global menace. A total of 674,861 young adults of both genders, aged 20-49 years from the 13 Local Governments in Nasarawa State made up the population of the study. A sample size of 400 young adults, consisting of 200 males and 200 females, was selected using the Slovin formula. A self-developed 4-point Likert scale instrument titled Social Support Systems and Mental Health Disorders (SSSMHD) was used for data collection. The study was premised on the Resilience Theory. At 0.05 level of significance and with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.906, the result shows a significant positive linear relationship between social support systems and the willingness of young adults to seek support which could reduce stress and help to prevent or manage mental health disorders such as anxiety, depression and suicidal ideation. Socio-economic factors such as income and employment, cultural beliefs, and stigmatization also contribute to young adults' decision to seek support. This study recommends that families, community, health practitioners, policymakers and government should work towards achieving mental health wellness and productivity of young adults in Nasarawa state.

Keywords: Social Support Systems, Social Support, Mental Health Disorders

Introduction

Mental health is a condition of mental wellness that enables people to manage life's stressors, develop their potential, study and work effectively, and give back to their communities. It is a crucial element of health and well-being that supports both our individual and societal capacities for decision-making, relationship-building, and world-shaping (WHO, 2022). Our emotional, psychological, and social well-being are all parts of our mental health. It influences our thoughts, emotions, and behaviors. Additionally, it influences how we respond to stress, interact with others, and make good decisions. A core human right is access to mental health. Every stage of life—from childhood and adolescence through adulthood—values it (CDC, 2023), and it is essential for socioeconomic, communal, and personal development.

The state of someone's mental health may alter throughout time depending on a variety of factors. A person's mental health may be affected if the demands placed on them are greater than their capacity for coping and resources. A person may have poor mental health, for instance, if they work long hours, provide care for a relative who is terminally sick, or are struggling financially. Sexual abuse, trauma, substance misuse, biological issues, social isolation, and feelings of loneliness are other elements that might have an effect on an individual's mental health (Amoah, Heck & Kim, 2022).

In particular, among young adults between the ages of eighteen and forty-nine, mental health issues are among the most prevalent medical illnesses worldwide. Anxiety, eating disorders including bulimia nervosa and anorexia nervosa, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), substance misuse, and depression which is the most prevalent of these diseases, are frequent mental health conditions affecting young adults (Martin, Dourish, Hook, Chamberlin & Higgs, 2020). These disorders might appear occasionally or persist for a long time in the lives of those who are affected. Lack of attention, severe mood swings, a lack of ambition, social isolation from family and friends, a significant change in eating habits, low self-esteem, and irregular sleep patterns are among the symptoms of mental health disorders in young adults that are frequently present. Mental health disorders can have environmental or genetic causes, such as poor living circumstances brought on by financial difficulty, a family history of mental health disorders, workplace or family disputes, traumatic experiences, and a lack of access to good support systems.

The mental health of young adults is influenced by life events. Social support has been revealed to have a cushion effect on the influence such events may have on mental health (Haugstvedt, 2022). Social support refers to the comfort given to people which could help them to overcome a set of social, economic, cultural, psychological, ethnic/racial and behavioral factors that can potentially impact their physical and mental health negatively (Adimora, Ogba, Omeje, Amaeze & Adene, 2021) and (Bello, Kinnawo, Akpunne & Onisile, 2022). Social support from family and close friends especially, is a vital protective factor (Bauer, Stevens, Purtscheller, Knapp, Fonagy, Evans-Lacko & Paul, 2021) which is very important for maintaining a positive mental health and for recovering from moderate to acute mental health disorders (Biorlykhaug, Karlsson, Hesook & Kleppe, 2021). Social support could come in various forms such as emotional, financial, tangible, appraisal, and informational support. These forms of support could be accessed physically or from support groups online from support systems such as the family, friends, school/work colleagues, online communities, crisis helplines, from government programs, and mental health professionals. However, a larger size of interpersonal interaction is said to be linked to a greater likelihood of receiving different types of social support, which in turn promote subjective mental health well-being (Han, 2023). In Nigeria's diverse society, social connections and relationships are highly prized but cost-push inflation and the current economic hardship has made it almost impossible for Nigerians to provide adequate social support for one another. Non-governmental organizations are crumbling under the weight of unfavorable government policies while anxiety, depression and suicidal ideation levels increase among young adults in the country.

It has long been known that stressful situations and unfavourable life events have the potential to cause mental health disorders. In the same vein, people have long been interested in the excellent outcomes that certain people achieve amid extremely unfavourable circumstances. Resilience in the context of psychology is the generic term used to describe these favourable reactions or results an individual exhibit in the face of severe danger to their physical and mental health (Vella & Pai, 2019). Various experts from diverse fields including psychology have studied Resilience theory over time and have related it to their study, therefore, the theory does not have a single proponent. However, from the field of psychology, there are notable persons who were considered pioneers of resilience theory based on their input. These people include Norman Garmezy and Ann Masten whose studies contributed to knowledge on resilience in children, child development and importance of social support

systems since 1970. Psychology's notion of resilience is a dynamic, multidisciplinary field of study that takes into account both environmental and personal elements that affect a person's capacity to adjust to and prosper in the face of hardship or intense challenge. Among young adults, certain positive traits like optimism, social and personal resourcefulness, optimism, and a sense of purpose in life may serve as buffers against anxiety, depression, and suicidal thoughts (Murphy & Allan, 2022)

Despite the increase in mental health disorders among young adults globally and in Nigeria, individuals still refuse to access the help which social support systems provide due to some factors. Socio-economic factors such as income and employment (Hazell, Thornton, Haghparast-Bidgoli & Patalay, 2022), cultural beliefs and stigmatization due to mental health disorders (Rodwin, Shimizu, Banya, Moore, Bessaha, Pahwa, Yanos & Munson, 2023) are all significant barriers to young adults' willingness to seek mental health service use and recovery.

This study investigated the relationship between social support systems and mental health disorders (anxiety, depression, suicidal ideation) among young adults between the ages of twenty and forty-nine years old in the thirteen local government areas of Nasarawa state. Ethical considerations including acquisition of informed consent from respondents, confidentiality, and protection of the respondents' data were strictly carried out during the course of this study.

Statement of the Problem

The growing prevalence of mental health disorders such as anxiety, depression, to mention a few, among young adults between the ages of twenty and forty-nine years has become a major public health concern in Nigeria. Socio-economic factors (especially in the face of the current economic hardship due to a hike in petroleum prices), cultural beliefs, stigmatization attached to mental health issues and traditional healing practices which are unique to Nigeria and to Nasarawa state all contribute to the willingness of these young adults to seek out available social support systems which could help lift their burdens and also prevent or reduce the effect of mental health disorders on their lives. Due to the limited number of literature on the role of social support systems in preventing or eradicating mental health disorders, this study seeks to address this gap in literature by exploring the relationship between social support systems and mental health disorders among young adults in Nasarawa state, Nigeria

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to determine the relationship between social support systems and mental health disorders among young adults in Nasarawa state, Nigeria. The study's objectives were to:

1. examine the level and patterns of mental health disorders (anxiety, depression) among young adults in Nasarawa state
2. examine the level of social support systems available to young adults in Nasarawa state
3. examine the influence of social support systems on the prevention of mental health disorders among young adults in Nasarawa state
4. identify the combined influence of socio-economic factors (income, employment), cultural beliefs, stigmatization due to mental health disorders on young adults' willingness to seek social support.

Research Questions

1. What is the level and patterns of mental health disorders (anxiety, depression) among young adults in Nasarawa state?
2. What is the level of social support systems available to young adults in Nasarawa state?

Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant influence of social support systems on the prevention of mental health disorders among young adults in Nasarawa state

HO₂: There is no significant combined influence of socio-economic factors (such as income, employment), cultural beliefs, or stigmatization due to mental health disorders on the willingness of young adults of Nasarawa state to seek social support

Methodology

The population of the study consists of a total of 674,861 male and female young adults between the ages of 20 and 49 years from the 13 Local Governments in Nasarawa State. The respondents at this level were specifically chosen for this study because they are in the transitional period of life; moving from the completion of their education to building careers and families. This age group is presumed to be able to provide pertinent information that could aid in achieving the study's goals. In order to construct a statistically meaningful sample for the study, the researcher created precise criteria for sampling both male and female residents of the 13 Local Government Areas in Nasarawa State. The sample size for the study; a total of 400 respondents which includes 200 male and 200 female respondents, was determined using Slovin's formula $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$. Thirty respondents were chosen from each of the three smallest local governments while thirty-one respondents were chosen from each of the ten larger sized local government areas in the state. The sample for the study was chosen using simple random sampling technique.

A self-developed instrument tagged Social Support Systems and Mental Health Disorders (SSSMHD) was designed for the study to gather the required data from the respondents. The instrument is segmented into three sections A, B and C. The demographic information of the respondents, including age and gender, is gathered in Section A. Section B contain items to determine the types of social support, social support systems, the levels of availability of the support systems and the perceived influence of social support systems on mental health prevention among young adults in Nasarawa state. Section C contain items to determine the types and prevalence of mental health disorders among young adults in Nasarawa state and the influence of factors such as socio-economic, cultural beliefs and stigmatization due to mental health disorders on the willingness of young adults to seek help from social support systems. The instrument was scrutinized and vetted by experts in research items generation at Lead City University before it was administered to the respondents. A pilot study was carried out by administering the instrument to fifty (50) respondents who were exempted from the actual study. With a Cronbach alpha coefficient $r = 0.87$, the instrument was deemed reliable. Data analysis for the stated research questions and hypotheses was done using the IBM SPSS 25 statistical package.

Data Analysis

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level and patterns of mental health disorders (anxiety, depression) among young adults in Nasarawa state?

Table 4.2.1: Mental Health Disorders

S/N	Types and Prevalence of Mental Health Disorders	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	I am aware of the types of mental health disorders such as depression, anxiety and suicidal ideation among young adults in Nasarawa state	2.04	1.111
2	I understand that mental health disorders such as depression, anxiety and suicidal ideation are prevalent among young adults in Nasarawa state	1.92	1.101
Total		1.98	1.106

Table 4.2.1 show a moderate level of awareness of the types of mental health disorders among young adults in Nasarawa state. However, the respondents have varying degrees of the level of awareness of these mental health disorders among young adults in Nasarawa state. Also, the respondents' understanding of the prevalence of these mental health disorders appears to be slightly lower compared to the level of awareness of the mental health disorders. This answers the first research question of this study.

Research Question 2: What is the level of social support systems available to young adults in Nasarawa state?

Table 4.2.2: Types of Social Support Received by Respondents

S/N	Social Support Types	Frequency	Percentage
1	Emotional Support	70	17.5
2	Financial Support	48	12.0
3	Informational Support	91	22.8
4	Tangible Support	65	16.3
5	Instrumental Support	45	11.3
6	Appraisal Support	16	4.0
7	Companionship	48	12.0
8	Support	17	4.3

Network Support		
Total	400	100

Table 4.2.2 show the different types of social support received by young adults in Nasarawa state. Informational support is the highest social support type which young adults in Nasarawa state receives while Appraisal support is the least type of social support received by the young adults in Nasarawa state. This answers the second research question of this study.

Table 4.2.3: Levels of Social Support Received from Support Systems

S/N	Social Support Systems	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	I receive emotional, financial, tangible and informational support from my family members	2.74	1.022
2	I am currently in a committed relationship	1.54	1.073
3	My spouse is supportive of my emotional, and financial well-being	1.50	.782
4	Besides family and friends, I turn to other sources for support during times of stress and difficulty	2.96	1.094
5	I have close friends whom I can confide in or seek support from	2.21	1.256
5	I have close friends whom I can confide in or seek support from	2.46	.988
6	I am actively involved in community or social groups within Nasarawa state	1.26	.460
7	I attend religious gatherings (church or mosque) where I interact with others and potentially receive support	3.51	.596
8	I participate in online social networks or support groups that provide	2.45	.871

9	emotional or/and informational support	3.20	.816
	I am satisfied with the support I currently receive from my social network		
10	I take advantage of mental health services available in my school/work/environment	2.00	1.084
11	and crisis hotlines when I undergo stress or need someone to talk to.	2.40	1.071
	I take advantage of government programs and financial aids to ease financial or emotional constraints		
	I am satisfied with my overall perceived social support		
Total		2.57	1.010

The results on Table 4.2.3 show that the respondents seem satisfied with the level of support that they receive from their family members. The respondents agree to being in committed relationships with supportive spouses, and they seek varying levels of support from support systems besides their family and friends. The respondents are involved in community and religious activities, online social networks, and are moderately satisfied with their current social support. The respondents reported taking advantage of mental health services and programs provided by the government to ease emotional and financial constraints of young adults. A total mean score of 2.57 and standard deviation of 1.010 indicates that the respondents have an overall moderate level of social support, at different degrees. Therefore, the first hypothesis (H_{01}) of the study which states that there is no significant influence of social support systems on the prevention of mental health disorders among young adults in Nasarawa state is rejected.

Regression Analysis

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant combined influence of socio-economic factors (such as income, employment), cultural beliefs, or stigmatization due to mental health disorders on the willingness of young adults of Nasarawa state to seek social support

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.906 ^a	.821	.820	1.36893	.056

a. Predictors: (Constant), SoCulStig

b. Dependent Variable: Willingness

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3412.003	1	3412.003	1820.742	.000 ^b
	Residual	745.837	398	1.874		
Total		4157.840	399			

a. Dependent Variable: Willingness

b. Predictors: (Constant), SoCulStig

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	.213	.194		1.095	.274
	SoCulStig	.528	.012	.906	42.670	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Willingness

With a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.906, the result of the regression analysis shows a significant positive linear relationship between social support systems and the willingness of young adults in Nasarawa state to seek social support from support systems due to socio-economic factors, cultural beliefs and stigmatization due to mental health disorders. Therefore, the second hypothesis (HO₂) of the study which states that there is no significant combined influence of socio-economic factors, cultural beliefs, or stigmatization due to mental health disorders on the willingness of young adults of Nasarawa state to seek social support is rejected.

Summary of Findings

At 0.05 level of significance and with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.906, the result shows a significant positive linear relationship between social support systems and the willingness of young adults to seek support which could reduce stress and help to prevent or manage mental health disorders such as anxiety, depression and suicidal ideation

Conclusion

The ability to recover from hardship, such as stress, pain, trauma, and other life experiences, is known as resilience. It is vital to teach young people how to set long-term goals and a

successful approach, as well as good coping mechanisms, adaptation, and perseverance, in spite of life's challenges. Reliable and efficient social support networks will help young adults prevent and manage anxiety, depression, and suicidal ideation in addition to helping them develop resilience.

Recommendations

The researcher made the following recommendations based on the findings of the study;

1. Promotion of community-based initiatives to raise awareness of mental health issues and to provide support services in Nasarawa state that are especially geared towards young adults. The goals of these efforts ought to be to raise awareness of symptoms, lessen the stigma associated with mental health illnesses, and advertise options that may be used to get assistance.
2. The growth and development of young adults' social support systems in the state of Nasarawa should be encouraged. This can entail setting up online forums, community centres, and peer support groups where people can get in touch with others going through comparable struggles. It can also be helpful to teach volunteers and community leaders in providing sympathetic support and making appropriate referrals to mental health services.
3. In Nasarawa state, mental health education and awareness initiatives ought to be part of the curricula of educational institutions and career centres. Likewise, workplaces must to offer training courses and workshops on coping mechanisms, stress management, and identifying symptoms of mental health issues. Promoting mental wellbeing at a young age and in the workplace helps people find better coping strategies and get help when they need it.
4. Adoption of laws in the state of Nasarawa with the goal of closing socioeconomic gaps, and removing societal stigmas related to mental health issues. This could entail making improvements to underprivileged young adults' access to healthcare, work opportunities, and education. Community-based interventions should also emphasise dispelling damaging cultural stereotypes about mental health and fostering understanding and acceptance in families and communities.

These recommendations seek to establish a conducive atmosphere in which young adults in the state of Nasarawa feel empowered to seek out mental health services, obtain sufficient assistance, and get over obstacles arising from cultural and socioeconomic considerations.

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Pastoral Counselling and Trauma-Responsive Healing for Managing Victims of Terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the pivotal role of pastoral counseling in facilitating trauma resolution and fostering healing within Nigerian communities, particularly in the northeastern region profoundly impacted by terrorism. Employing a mixed-methods research design, questionnaires were distributed to 200 representative individuals, and in-depth interviews were conducted with pastoral caregivers and community leaders, selected through stratified random sampling. With 93% of the respondents responding with a no to existing resources/initiatives, 7 % agreed that there existed few resources and initiatives from NGOs in their affected localities. The research highlights the dearth of initiatives and resources for trauma-responsive healing in affected communities, with 93% of respondents indicating a lack thereof. Findings also reveal varying perceptions regarding the effectiveness of pastoral counseling, with only 44% strongly agreeing with its efficacy, while 53.5% expressed moderate agreement. The questionnaire utilized in the study was self-structured and underwent rigorous psychometric evaluation, including assessments of reliability and validity. In light of these findings, the study emphasizes the critical need for trauma-informed interventions administered by pastoral caregivers, informed by the Traumatic Growth Theory, to address the multifaceted challenges faced by Nigerian communities post-terrorism. This paper underscores the potency of pastoral counseling as an indispensable tool in nurturing the healing process and fostering resilience amidst adversity.

Keywords: Healing, Pastoral Counseling, Trauma, Terrorism and Trauma-responsive

Introduction

Over a prolonged duration, Nigerian communities, with a specific focus on the northeastern region, have grappled with the formidable challenge of terrorism. The principal perpetrator of these attacks has been the extremist organization known as Boko Haram, which espouses the ideology that "Western Education is forbidden." The terrorism problem in Nigerian communities has had far-reaching consequences, including loss of life, displacement, economic disruption, and a climate of fear, insecurity, and traumatic experiences. Corroborating this, Onuoha (2014) records that "since July 2009 when Boko Haram engaged Nigerian forces in a short-lived anti-government uprising, the group has grown to become a serious national, regional, and international concern". From the bombing of the United Nations Building in Abuja, which resulted in the tragic loss of 23 lives, to the infamous kidnapping of more than 200 schoolgirls in 2014, an event that sparked the global campaign known as Bring Back Our Girls, the impact of these actions by Boko Haram has instilled deep-seated fear and trauma within the Nigerian nation.

In the face of adversity, human resilience often emerges, guiding the path towards healing and restoration. However, for Nigerian communities deeply affected by the venomous grip

of terrorism, the wounds inflicted extend far beyond the physical realm, reaching into the depths of the human psyche. The psychological and emotional traumas wrought by acts of violence, loss, and displacement have left indelible imprints on individuals, families, and entire communities. In these troubled times, the role of pastoral counseling emerges as a beacon of hope, offering solace and support to those grappling with the aftermath of terrorism.

Grounded in the principles of spirituality, compassion, and cultural understanding, pastoral counseling possesses the potential to address the unique psychological and emotional needs of individuals affected by terrorism. Drawing upon Traumatic Growth Theory, developed by Richard Tedeschi and Lawrence Calhoun, we can understand how trauma can lead to positive psychological changes and personal growth. This theory suggests that traumatic events like terrorism can cause vulnerability and distress, prompting the need for pastoral counseling to help individuals build resilience, facilitate meaning, and foster spiritual growth (Bassel, 2015). Relating this theory to the Nigerian context, it becomes evident that traumatic events such as terrorism often leave individuals and communities in a state of vulnerability and distress. It is in such states that pastoral counseling emerges to assist individuals in building resilience, finding meaning in the aftermath of trauma, and fostering spiritual growth.

This study seeks to explore the frontiers of pastoral counseling in the Nigerian context, particularly in the northeastern regions deeply scarred by terrorism. The paper aims to examine the unique challenges faced by pastoral counselors working in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism, delving into the delicate balance required between providing spiritual guidance and psychological support for the victims.

Trauma and its State among Nigerian Communities in Related Literatures

Trauma is an emotional, psychological, or physical response to shocking, distressing, or harmful events, which can significantly impact an individual's mental health. In line with this school of thought, Bessel in his book "The Body Keeps the Score" explores how trauma impacts the body and offers insights into various therapeutic approaches. The author opined that individuals can get through the difficulties that arise from their traumatic experience through participation in his therapeutic approaches (Bassel, 2015). Herman in her work "Trauma and Recovery" discusses the long-term effects of trauma and the process of recovery, emphasizing the importance of validation. She explained the concept of trauma as the process of recovery and emphasized the need for empowerment and validation in the recovery process (Herman, 1992). Correlating Bessel's opinion, Friedman (2000) also in his work "Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder" delved into the clinical aspects of PTSD, including its diagnosis and treatment. The scholar did well by highlighting some of the experiences such as rape, sexual abuse, and domestic violence as possible causes of trauma. In the same vein, Goodman and Espstein (2007) in their work "The Impact of Trauma on Communities" examined on a broader scale how trauma affects communities as a whole, including social and cultural aspects.

On the effects of Trauma on individuals and communities, scholars have acknowledged the profound impact of trauma on mental health often leading to conditions like anxiety and depression. Chronic health issues and heightened stress responses have been noted as consequences of trauma. Friedman (2000) opines that sometimes trauma can destabilize communities, leading to crime, substance abuse, and a breakdown of social structures.

However, there have been other opinions from recent scholars that trauma destabilizes relationships and social functioning, contributing to feelings of isolation.

On the state of Trauma Counseling in Nigerian Communities, scholars such as Haldun & Opeyemi (2016) and Abdul (2017) noted that scarcity of mental health resources has been a major challenge in Nigerian communities. These scholars also stressed the importance of culturally sensitive approaches to trauma counseling in Nigeria, incorporating traditional healing practices. Sheikh, et al. (2014) highlighted community-based organizations and NGOs as vital in providing trauma support where formal services are lacking. As of 2021, there were nascent efforts by the Nigerian government to improve mental health services, but challenges persisted.

It must, however, be taken into consideration that the literature on trauma and pastoral counseling approaches is limited, particularly in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism. While scholars have identified trauma as a challenging phenomenon, there is a lack of comprehensive research on the specific needs and experiences of individuals in these communities, making it crucial to address this gap.

Understanding Trauma and its Challenge in Nigerian Context

Trauma is a deeply distressing experience that can have long-lasting psychological and emotional effects on individuals. Understanding trauma in the Nigerian context involves considering the cultural, religious, and spiritual dimensions that influence how individuals experience and cope with traumatic events. In Nigeria, religion plays a significant role in people's lives, and it often shapes their understanding of trauma and healing processes.

Trauma counseling in Nigeria encounters obstacles due to scarce resources, cultural beliefs, and social stigma. Traditional values and cultural norms frequently shape the perception of trauma, resulting in a shortage of trained trauma counselors and insufficient facilities. This stigma deters individuals from seeking treatment, while a lack of awareness about the benefits of trauma counseling impedes early intervention. Religious beliefs, including prayer, meditation, and attending religious services, offer a framework for comprehending traumatic events and providing coping strategies. The religious and spiritual dimensions of trauma in Nigeria are influenced by individual beliefs, cultural practices, and affiliations, making it crucial to consider this diversity.

Nigerian Christianity tackles trauma by incorporating its distinct religious beliefs and practices. Traumatic experiences, such as violence, loss, or natural disasters, impact individuals irrespective of their religious affiliation. To combat this crisis, Nigerian Christians employ spiritual activities like prayer, fasting, and seeking counsel from religious authorities. The supportive nature of the Christian community contributes to the process of healing.

Hence, understanding trauma in the Nigerian Christian context requires acknowledging the religious and spiritual dimensions that influence the healing process. By recognizing the specific beliefs and practices of Nigerian Christianity, individuals can find solace, hope, and meaning in their traumatic experiences. Religious leaders and mental health professionals need to work collaboratively in providing support and guidance to those affected by trauma within this context.

Methodology/Data Collection on Advancing Pastoral Counselling Approaches for Trauma-Responsive Healing in Northeastern Nigerian Communities Affected by Terrorism

Employing a mixed-methods research design, this study investigates Pastoral Counselling and Trauma-Responsive Healing for Managing Victims of Terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria. Quantitatively, 200 individuals affected by terrorism were surveyed using the "Pastoral Counselling and Trauma-Responsive Healing Assessment Questionnaire," employing a random sampling technique to ensure diversity. Concurrently, qualitative insights were garnered through in-depth interviews with pastoral caregivers and community leaders, selected via a stratified random sampling method to represent various affected demographics and regions.

Data analysis involved quantitative assessment through percentages and statistical methods to discern trends, while qualitative data from interviews was thematically analyzed to identify recurring patterns and perspectives. This mixed-methods approach provides a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in addressing trauma among victims of terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria, offering valuable insights for the development of effective interventions and support programs.

Data Analysis

Chart I

Section: Demographic Information Gender
 200 responses

The chart 1 above represents the demographic information showing that females responded more to the questionnaire than the male gender.

Chart II

Occupation
 200 responses

Chart II represents the occupation of the participants.

Chart III

Age
 200 responses

Chart III shows the age categories of the respondents indicating that majority of the respondents were between the youthful ages of 18-25

Chart IV

Have you or someone you know experienced trauma as a result of terrorism?
 200 responses

Findings showed that 11.5% of the total respondents never experienced trauma as a result of terrorism in the study location. However, 88.5% of the total respondents agreed that they knew someone and may have experienced trauma as result of terrorism.

Chart V

Are you familiar with pastoral counseling approaches for trauma responsive healing?
 200 responses

Chart V revealed that 51% of the respondents in the study locale were somewhat familiar with pastoral counseling approaches; 15.5% were not familiar with the approaches at all; 33.5% claimed to be familiar with the approaches in pastoral counseling regarding the subject matter. The level of awareness according to the findings seems very low and needs to be addressed.

Chart VI

How effective do you think pastoral counseling approaches are in promoting trauma responsive healing in affected communities?
 200 responses

The findings from this chart shows that majority of the respondents were not really certain with the effectiveness of pastoral counseling approaches in promoting trauma responsive healing in affected communities. With only 44% agreeing to pastoral counseling approaches as very effective in trauma responsive healing, 53.5% agreed to a moderate level thereby leaving 2.5 % disagreeing totally.

Chart VII

Which of the following pastoral counseling approaches do you think would be most beneficial for trauma responsive healing in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism?(Select all that apply)
 200 responses

The chart above represents the opinion of the respondents regarding what they would think is most beneficial pastoral counseling approach for trauma-responsive healing in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism. Majority of the respondents opted for individual counseling; expressive therapies and trauma focused cognitive behavioral approaches as the best approaches in ensuring quick healing process.

Chart VIII

In your opinion, what types of community support are essential trauma responsive healing in affected communities?(Select all that apply)
 200 responses

Chart VIII expressly shows the opinions of the respondents on the type of community support they consider to be essential for trauma healing in affected communities. With access to mental health professionals being the most accepted community support, financial assistance and reintegration programs were also highlighted in significant percentages.

Chart IX

Are there any existing community resources or initiatives in your area that provide support for trauma responsive healing?
 200 responses

On the issue of existing community initiatives and resources, it was observed that in most affected communities of the respondents, there were no initiatives or resources to provide support for trauma responsive healing. From the findings, 93% of the entire respondents responded with a no to existing resources. However 7 % agreed that there were few resources and initiatives from government and NGOs.

Chart X

Do you have access to pastoral counseling services in your community?
 199 responses

Chart X shows that 62.8 % of the total respondents in the study location do not have access to pastoral counseling; 31.2% claimed to have access but their services are not easily accessible, and 6% of the respondents agreed to have easy access to pastoral counseling. This needs to be addressed.

Chart XI

If pastoral counseling services were more accessible, would you be more likely to seek help for trauma-related issues?

199 responses

Chart XI shows that majority of the respondents would likely seek out help for trauma related issues if pastoral counseling were more accessible. The idea projected here is that accessibility is much keyed in enhancing trauma responsive healing for individual and even communities at large.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the provided charts offer valuable insights into the landscape of pastoral counseling and trauma-responsive healing in communities affected by terrorism in Northeastern Nigeria. Firstly, the demographic breakdown illustrates a higher response rate from females, indicating a potential gender disparity in engagement with trauma-related research or experiences. Additionally, the majority of respondents fell within the youthful age bracket of 18-25, highlighting the significant impact of terrorism on younger generations in the region. This demographic composition underscores the urgent need for tailored interventions to address the specific needs and vulnerabilities of youth affected by trauma. Secondly, the data reveals several key perceptions and challenges regarding pastoral counseling and trauma-responsive healing. While a significant portion of respondents acknowledged familiarity with pastoral counseling approaches, a substantial proportion expressed uncertainty regarding their effectiveness in promoting trauma healing. Moreover, the lack of accessibility to pastoral counseling services emerged as a prominent issue, with a considerable majority reporting either no access or limited accessibility. However, there is a clear indication that improved accessibility to pastoral counseling could significantly enhance the likelihood of individuals seeking help for trauma-related issues, underscoring the critical role of accessibility in facilitating trauma-responsive healing within affected communities. These findings collectively emphasize the importance of addressing both awareness gaps and accessibility barriers to enhance the effectiveness of pastoral counseling interventions for trauma healing in Northeastern Nigeria.

Advancing Pastoral Counseling Principles for Trauma-Responsive Healing in Nigeria

Terrorism in Nigeria has caused significant trauma, especially in the northeast. To address these issues, trauma-responsive healing approaches, including pastoral counseling, are crucial. Christian-based counseling, rooted in Christian principles, offers emotional and spiritual support, integrating faith-based perspectives into the healing process. This holistic approach to trauma recovery is essential for Nigeria's affected communities. Some of the basic Pastoral Counseling Principles for Trauma-Responsive Healing may include:

1. **Culturally Sensitive Approach:** Pastoral counselors need to be aware of and respect the cultural beliefs and practices of the affected communities. Understanding the specific religious and spiritual traditions of Nigerian Christianity is essential for effectively addressing trauma. This includes acknowledging the role of prayer, scripture, and communal support in the healing process.
2. **Creating Safe Spaces:** Trauma survivors require safe spaces where they can express their emotions, share their experiences and feel heard and understood. Pastoral counselors can establish safe environments within churches, community centers, or other gathering places, where individuals can openly discuss their trauma and receive support without judgment.
3. **Trauma-Informed Care:** Pastoral counselors should receive training in trauma-informed care to understand the impact of trauma on individuals' mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being. This knowledge enables counselors to provide appropriate support and interventions, considering the specific needs and vulnerabilities of trauma survivors.
4. **Collaborative Approach:** Collaboration between pastoral counselors and mental health professionals is crucial in addressing trauma in Nigerian communities affected by terrorism. By working together, these professionals can combine their expertise to provide a comprehensive and integrated approach to healing. This collaboration can involve referrals, joint training programs, and shared resources.

Conclusion

Owing to what we have observed, the terrorist issue in Nigerian communities has had far-reaching effects, including fatalities, evictions, economic disruption, and an atmosphere of dread, insecurity, and traumatic events. The injuries sustained go much beyond mere physical harm; they penetrate the core of the human psyche. Violence, loss, and displacement have all caused psychological and emotional traumas that have permanently altered the life of certain people, entire families, and entire communities. As a result, there is a need for pastoral care providers as well as professional counselors to intervene and offer hope to these afflicted victims. These care providers should make an effort to adopt a culturally sensitive approach, create safe spaces, implement trauma-informed care, and foster collaboration with mental health professionals when conducting counseling sessions.

Recommendations

This study therefore recommends that;

1. That collaborative approach which would involve community leaders, religious organizations and mental health professionals should be encouraged to foster innovative interventions and best practices in counseling communities affected by terrorism in Nigeria.
2. Access to Pastoral services must be made easy and accessible to trauma survivors in the affected Nigerian communities.
3. Resources and initiatives should be mobilized and encouraged by both the pastoral care-givers and the government so as to pave way for sustainable trauma-responsive healing.

4. Training and Capacity building must be taken into consideration. Professional development for pastoral caregivers in trauma-informed care must be encouraged and trauma-focused education must be integrated into theological institutions.

Policy recommendations for supporting trauma survivors and affected communities should be issued by the Nigerian government at the three-tier levels.

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Roles of Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of a Marriage Partner and Its Impacts on Family Sustainability

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Abstract

The need to ensure that people seek pastoral counseling before choosing a marriage partner is of paramount importance in this complex society, inability to seek pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner has constituted some setbacks to marriage sustainability. The paper identifies the concept of pastoral counseling, the biblical foundation in the choice of a marriage partner, the roles or importance of pastoral counseling, the impacts of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner for sustainable family life, the consequences of avoiding pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner, pastoral counseling prerequisite for choosing a marriage partner and encouragement to singles in embracing pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner. This paper reveals that pastoral counseling helps in making the right decision in the choice of marriage partner, and builds healthy relationships in courtship and marriage. The consequences for not embracing pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partners are confusion in the choice of a marriage partner, missing God's will, regret, or disappointment in courtship and marriage. However, the paper stresses the need for improvements in the pastor's relationship and availability with the youths who are still singles, in the same manner pastor's wife should be someone whom singles can easily relate with. Orientation for singles about the difference between pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner and premarital counseling is also important for singles to take pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner seriously.

Keywords: Roles, Pastoral counseling, Choice, Marriage partner, Family sustainability

Introduction

The issue of marriage is very important in Christendom and society at large; knowing the choice of a marriage partner before entering into any relationship is of great importance. The role of Pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner can never be underestimated. Many people would have been enjoying their marriages if they had sought proper pastoral counseling in their choice of a marriage partner. However, it is expedient for intending couples to submit his/her totality to pastoral counseling before entering into a relationship. This brings boldness and assurance to come to God in the times of trouble and challenges in the home. Therefore, entering into a relationship without the right pastoral counsel is not ideal because seeking counsel for the choice of a marriage partner has a great impact on sustaining the family life. Furthermore, many families are going through serious pain which can never be discussed by anybody, because of the costly mistake they have made in the choice of a marriage partner this has inadvertently stolen their joy in the home, sometimes some couple

looks healthy outside but inside they are unhealthy in their relationship, due to time-to-time bully on each other. Many Christian brothers and sisters today reject counseling and enter into relationships without knowing the effect such a decision will have on them. Today many youths and even married couples are regretting the relationship they had entered into because they refuse to have proper pastoral counseling. The majority of the singles out there do not know that there are certain steps and guidelines to be followed in choosing a marriage partner which pastoral counseling will open one's mind to, that is why many homes lack divine and ordained beauty because they marry outside their divine purpose, timing, and will of God for their life (Oladapo, 2008, p. 22-23). The motivation for this paper is to emphasize the importance and impacts of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner and the challenges befalling singles in courtship and marriage for lack of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner in this present society.

Concept of Pastoral Counseling

"Pastoral Counseling is the utilization of a variety of healing (therapeutic) methods to help people handle their problems and crisis more growth fully and thus experience healing of their brokenness" (Clinebell, 1984, p. 26). The overview of counseling comes from God's interest in caring for the church, to ensure that He puts things in place for them. He sends Jesus Christ; the great shepherd/Pastor into the world, to love and care for His people. Jesus deals with people such as sinners, outcasts, and many others and associates with them, Jesus did not discard anyone who comes to Him. The same ministry He commits to the pastors, to care and counsel the people of God. Macdonald (2016) stated that "Pastoral care and counseling is a ministry of evangelism, teaching, discipleship, and encouragement" (p. 6). This is a clear picture that Pastoral counseling models the lives of counselees into the purpose of God for their lives, and also leads the people by the word of God into eternity. The world is full of ups and downs, Challenges, and crises, which left many people with doubt about what to do. "Pastoral Counseling then comes as ease or relief to the people, since counseling deals with the behavior, attitudes, thought, and beliefs of the counselee; this does not rule the facts that counseling must be placed on the leading of the Holy Spirit and Biblical standard in attending to the problems of the counselee" (Benner, 2015, p. 56). The researcher agrees that the Pastoral counselor should follow the leading of the Holy Spirit in addressing the major issues of life in the counseling process. He must always depend on God in leading the counselee to know the will and mind of God in choosing a life partner; as human beings, despite all creatures certified good by God. In Genesis 2:20, Adam finds it difficult to get suitable help among the creatures until Eve is created. According to Olaniyi (2004), "God originated marriage for the well being of humans and it must be centered on the Godly counsel in order to locate the missing ribs" (p. 45)

Biblical Foundation for Choice of a Marriage Partner

Marriage, a journey of no return was established by God; marriage institution was the original plan, all about marriage began in the commencement of creation in the Garden of Eden. Therefore, every foundation of marriage must be on the solid rock (God). "God in marriage aims to establish His plan on earth through marriage; this means there is no home that must be without having her foundation being laid on God" (Adediran, 2017, p. 1-2). In Genesis 2:18 (The Lord God said it is not good for the man to be alone. I will make a helper suitable for him" Also in verses 23-25 'the man says this is now the bone of my bones and flesh of my

flesh; she shall be called woman for she was taken out of a man. For this reason, a man will leave his father and mother and be united to his wife, and they will become one flesh. The man and his wife were both naked, and they felt no shame. From the above Bible passage, it is understood that Adam was a lucky man, God discovered that he was lonely and needed a companion, so as a lucky man he was he did not need to convince a woman to accept him in marriage, God has perfectly done the work for him. "In verse 23 God does not compel Adam to accept Eve, It was through a willing heart he accepted the woman, this means that God can never force a woman or man on anybody though He would surely give direction in ordering one's steps" (p.1).

Nakedness, as seen in Genesis 2:25, implies that they were not ashamed to behold the nakedness of each other. Ogheneakpobo (2015) opined that "both Adam and Eve do not have anything to hide from each other again, the kind of marriage God wants for everyone is an excellent and unique one that is devoid of hidden secrets whether good or bad, palatable or unpalatable, pleasant or unpleasant" (pp. 19-20). Nakedness in marriage brought trust between the spouses. It also determined the wellness, happiness, and blessedness of every marriage. Furthermore, Jesus continues the image of the scripture in the New Testament where He speaks of Himself as the bridegroom (Luke 5:33-35). Jesus provided comparatively little instructions on marriage. "He affirmed the permanent nature of marriage in no uncertain terms; comparing Bible Passages. Genesis 1:27 and Matthew 19:6 give the understanding that Jesus knows the implications of marriage to be a sacred bond between a man and a woman which is established by God Himself" (Kostenderger, 2010, p. 52).

Also, the teaching of Paul from Ephesians 5:21-33. Paul gave the details of marriage to be set within the larger context of God's end-time restoration all things under the headship of Christ, thus Christ's relationship with the Church provides the pattern for Christian marriage. Meanwhile, the writer of Hebrews indicates that marriage still has an ethical place in the life of the redeemed fellowship (Hebrew 13:4) from (Romans 7:1-3), marriage is seen as a lifetime covenant, it is a sacred agreement between a man and a woman, "It is also a permanent indissoluble union which must not be subjected to man's interpretation but a divine truth because of its deep interpretation that is beyond any human imagination" (Olayoku, 2005, p. 23). Adams (1983) also reiterated "that the church has ignorantly assumed of having the full understanding of the teaching and has not taught the biblical facts and this has made many couples build their homes on worldly standard" (p. 9). Therefore, the marriage relationship is held as God's ordained institution, an institution to bring a love of God and salvation to humankind under the headship of Christ the Lord.

Roles of Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of a Marriage Partner

Seeking counsel in all situations of one's life is a very important decision in the life of a believer, especially in the area of choosing a life partner because no one knows where, when, under what circumstances, and how God will lead one to the right person, Ecclesiastes 4:9-10 says two are better than one.

1. Pastoral counseling helps in the areas where one is confused concerning the issue of choice of life partner, that is "consulting a person who is known to be a strong committed Christian who may be praying along and talk issues over will help to shed light on the confused area and lead one to get the right conviction" (Omojola, 1994, pp. 47-48).

2. It helps to set the priority right in the choice of life partner, some youth today believe that asking and seeking God's face for a life partner comes first but knowing the source and foundation of every good partner which is God is the first priority; after the issues on the salvation of souls have been settled, then comes the prayers on choosing a life partner
3. Another truth on the roles of pastoral counseling is that, "it helps spinsters and bachelors to understand that it is only in Christ that a woman can be free to fulfill her potential when married unlike other religion of philosophy that treat women as inferior" (Osinowo, 2011, pp. 104-105).
4. It guides a spinster or bachelor on how to pray on his/her marital matters; with interaction with a counselor, counseling may lead one to know how God speaks because there are diverse ways through which God speaks to His own children.
5. Another role counseling play in the life of single is that, it helps on how to make right choice of spouse and also liberates singles from all forms of physiological, emotional, spiritual, physical and social trauma and problems.
6. It helps singles to prepare for the task in marriage, since proper understanding of what marriage is and what marriage is not will be discussed during counseling and also liberate singles on how to live during courtship and to understand better the "dos' and don't" in courtship.
7. Pastoral counseling also helps singles to trash out issues that could cause or become problems in their marital life (Oladeni, 2004, pp. 76-78).
8. Collins (2007), submits that "pastoral counseling, helps singles to build stable marriages and healthy families, this means that singles at times are afraid of marriage and as result be reluctant to enter into marriage relationship because of the experience he /she might have seen in the relationship of their relatives but counseling play a very good vital role in helping the unmarried to have stable home and healthy family" (p. 501).

Impacts of Pastoral Counseling for the choice of marriage partner for Sustainable Family Life

Ukarke (2006) stated that "pastoral counseling is important venture in life and it is always good for believers to start all ventures with God, Prov. 3:5-6 says "Trust in the Lord with all your heart and lean not into your own understanding in all your ways acknowledge Him and he will direct your path". Therefore, getting God involved in plans to get married is a step towards success" (p. 34)

1. Field (1986) opined that "counseling helps couple to have healthy relationship and no one, even the marriage therapist will be able to understand the magnetism such a couple are like giant electromagnets drawing each other into their own magnetic field as a result of unhindered time spent together" (p.16).
2. Sylvester Ogbeneakpobo (2015) in his own opinion discussed that "one of the impacts of counseling on family sustainability is to open couple's eye and enlightened them that sensitive decision should be made together by the spouses bearing in mind that the man ought to play a guiding role that will lead to making right decision for the good of the home" (p. 19). The researcher agreed with Sylvester on this point so as to eradicate making the same mistake Eve made in Genesis 3:6

3. Counseling also helps couples to understand that the blame game will not help matters, it can only complicate issues. Human beings are bound to make mistakes (p. 19). As for marriage, to free one mind is to accept one's fault and see how to find solution together in order to move forward and enjoy peace and progress.
4. Furthermore, counseling helps couples to demonstrate true and unconditional love. True love usually ushering home into an atmosphere of ever-increasing conjugal bliss, with the help counseling couple will understand that it is only true love that can glue them together in bearing consequences together (p. 20).

Consequences of Avoiding Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of Marriage Partner

Avoidance or neglects of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage has led to the followings

1. Wrong Choice of Marriage partner: The inability of singles to seek for pastoral counsel has led many singles to choose wrongly, because they did not consent to the leadership of the Holy Spirit to seek for right pastoral counseling guidance
2. Confusion in the choice of marriage partner: Lack of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner has resulted to destabilized mind whereby choosing of a marriage partner is like a child play without a serious commitment from both sides. Sometime both parties might be subjecting their courtship to test whether it will work or not because they are not that sure.
3. Missing of God's will: It is easy to miss the choice of God for one's life if care is not taken by seeking proper pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner. Some couples' homes has been destabilized, some are just managing themselves they do not really enjoy the peace of God in their home because they choose by their own understanding, not allowing proper pastoral counseling in the choice a marriage partner.
4. Disappointment in Courtship: Many singles have disappointed God by not being sincere and faithful God in luring themselves to sin of fornication, and through these some impregnate each other because their choice of a marriage partner was not really guided by pastoral counseling, consequently removing the fear of God in their courtship.
5. Marriage Crises: "Some of the reasons why there a lot of divorce, infidelity, adultery in marriages today starts from not seeking proper pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner" (Oladapo, 2016, p. 59). Many so-called Christian homes have crashed landed, many wives have become single mothers likewise the husband. The children are not enjoying their parenthood and some children are now hanging out with bad friends to keep their company since their homes are in disarray.

Pastoral Counseling Prerequisite for Choosing a Marriage Partner

The issue of choosing a marriage partner is so crucial that knowing God's will about it is of great importance that entails one to be really sure that a person one intends to share his/her life with is the one that God has in mind for one life. The reason is that, no one can fully understand the details of the life of another person except God, therefore involvements in pastoral counseling before making a choice of marriage partner is crucial matter that must not be handled with levity hand. The followings are pastoral counseling pre-requisite a spinster or bachelor must follow in choosing a life partner.

1. "A brother/sister who is seeking God's face in choosing a life partner must be connected to the source of all good partners that is "God", this means that such a

person must be a child of God, a disciple of Christ, someone who has cordial relationship with Christ and must be sincerely busy with kingdom business” (Shoremi, 2002, p. 23).

2. He/she must be ready to submit to the order, leading and the will of God because it is only God who knows the right and best marriage partner for His people. “The Bible says look not on his countenance or the height of his stature: because I have refused him; for the Lord sees as not the man sees, for man looks on the outward appearance, but the Lord looks on the heart, anyone who submits himself/herself to God’s will, shall never err; he/she will enjoy the guidance of God” (Ogunlade, 2005, pp. 5-6).
3. He/she must be matured: Such a person must be matured in the following major aspects of life
 - a) Physical Maturity: A person who is physically matured in such that he/ she is not a kid or a child, he must be of right mind who knows right from left, be able to think well and have good plan for marriage sustainability.
 - b) Spiritual Maturity: The person must have grown and still growing spiritually. He must know the methods and how God deals with him/her.
 - c) Intellectual Maturity: This is the ability to know and understand people, problems and situations without relying on other.
 - d) Social Maturity: This has to do with the ability to relate well with people and interact well
 - e) Financial Maturity: A brother or sister must be economically and financially stable; he/she must have stable income and able to solve the problem in the family. 1 Timothy 5:8 says. If any one does not provide for his relatives and especially for his immediate family, he has denied the faith and his worse than unbeliever (Oladapo, 2008, pp. 23-24)
4. The brother or sister must Know how God speaks to him/her; God speaks in diverse way to His children, a spiritually inclined person must be able to discern because God deals with individuals based on their level of understanding of God’s knowledge such as the, Bible: Psalm 119:105; Still voice; 1 king 19:11-12, Dream, visions and Revelation; Genesis 37: 5-9, Discerning spirit/ Prophecy; Act 16:16-18, Circumstances; Jonah 2:1-10, Heart conviction; Mathew 4: 18-22, Audible voice; Number 12: 18-22, and Message/Preaching’ 1 Corinthians 2:4-5.
5. Prayer: Waiting on God through prayers is another pre-requisite for choosing a life partner; hence prayer is the key to obtaining the gifts from God.
6. The word of God: He/she must key himself/herself into study the word of God and understand well the standard of God for choosing a life partner.
7. Avoid setting standard or idol in heart; Ezekiel 4:1-4 says some of the elders of Israel came to me and sat down in front of me, then the word of the Lord came to me “Son of man, these men have set up idols in their hearts and put wicket stumbling blocks before their faces, should I let them, this is what the sovereign Lord says; when any Israelite set up idols sin his heart and put a wicked stumbling block before his face and then goes to a prophet, I the Lord will answer him myself in keeping with great idolatry. Whatever a person cherishes in an individual whether physical or spiritual could become idol that would gain all the attention of such person and this could eventually influence the choice of life partner. Every one seeking for God’s will in

marriage must be of clear mind, and must be ready to submit to His leading in discernment.

8. The person must avoid match-making and writing of names for prophet to choose God's choice.
9. "Pride and self confidence should be avoided instead he/she should be humbled and fear God" (Ogunlade, 2005, pp. 5-6)

Pastoral Counseling towards Conviction in the Choice of a Marriage Partner

Omojola (1994) suggests some fundamental principle that can help in getting confirmation and to test conviction.

"According to him in looking for conviction, the devil or personal ego can interfere and cause confusion or pass wrong message. The following will be directions for conviction.

1. Consistency: What are revealed by God must follow in sequence and in uniformity, not zigzag, when there is confusion, one need to continue to wait on God until there must be correlation in any message, vision, dream and revelation that are revealed by the Lord.
2. Compatibility: Since marriage is a spiritual relationship, spiritual compatibility must influence the quality of one's choice and relationship.
3. A deep sense of contentment: In getting God's conviction, the divine contentment will fill the heart of the fellow if indeed it is God who is speaking, when it is revealed and received, there will a deep satisfaction in such hear; it is this contentment that keep the spouse to be loyal to each other after wedding,
4. A deep sense of gratitude and thankfulness towards the giver: Human experience has proved that when something desperately needed is given; such heart will be filled with gratitude and thankfulness, which finally accomplish with the peace of God" (pp. 49-54).

Encouraging Singles to embrace Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of a Marriage Partner

Bad experiences/ encounters some singles have had with some pastors may have caused avoidance of pastoral counseling in the choice a marriage partner; however, the singles can be encouraged through the following ways:

1. Prayer: Prayer as it says is the master key. Since marriage is the institution created by God, devils as it is known is the greatest enemy and antagonist to every good thing which includes marriage relationship because as Gods is interested in marriage relationship, so also is the devil, "therefore pastors should always intercede for bachelors and spinsters so that their minds will be opened and release themselves for counseling" (Adams, 1983, p. 1).
2. Availability of the counselors (Pastors): Adams noted that marriage relationship and counseling is often the catalyst for individual growth (p. 1). "Many pastors today do not have time to counsel the youth, they are pre-occupied with church activities and meetings, and they do not have counseling hour. Biblical counseling is all about discovering the people's problem and solving it. If then a pastor/counselor is not available, and sensitive, how then can the problem be solved" (MaCarthur, 2005, p. 101).

3. Pastor and his wife relationship with the youth in the church: Everybody needs friends who can care and cherish them. Bachelors and Spinsters also need care and good relationship from pastors and their wife, "this serves as source of encouragement to them and give them a sense of belonging, but many ministers instead of relating with them will desert and live them uncared for like sheep without shepherd. Therefore, pastor should always build good godly relationship with their members because this will enable the singles to see them as their spiritual and caring father" (p. 101).
4. Pastors should organize seminars and program on the important of counseling in the choice of a life partner.
5. There should be teachings on danger of self confidence and choosing a life partner without the proper seeking of counseling.
6. Parents also should always encourage their children to seek proper counsel before embarking on journey of marital relationship.
7. Minister/ Pastors should have good approach: manners of approach are very important in every relationship, minister of God should curtail kind of approach that will make members to always come to them and not be judgmental because it may serve as source of discouragement.
8. Churches should establish marriage committee that will see to the affairs of youth especially in the area of choosing life partners and this should consist of church members who are spiritually inclined and whose home are of good model to the youth

Conclusion

The paper discussed the concepts of pastoral counseling, biblical foundation in the choice of marriage partner, roles of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner and its impacts for family sustainability, it has looked at importance or perception of people about pastoral counseling in choice of a marriage partner, the impacts and consequences of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner and pastoral counseling for the choice of marriage partner. However concerted efforts of pastors are needed to encourage the singles to embrace pastoral counseling before they choose the person to marry, and singles should know the different between seeking pastoral counseling for the choice of marriage partner and premarital counseling.

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Pastoral Counselling and Educational Development: Tools for Improving National Security in the 21st Century

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Abstract

This study investigates ways by which Pastoral Counseling and Educational development can improve national security. Pastoral counselling helps theological institutions grow and improve in ways to care for students and staff in a rather supportive way and this brings about the growth of the country. Pastoral counselling and educational development teach the counselling skills needed to improve national security skills to help churches and church leaders such as pastors and counsellors, to serve others better in different ways. Pastoral counseling develops counseling skills designed to enhance the ministry of the pastor in his relationship with the perceived counselee people to live in humility and obedience to the law of Nigeria. Survey research technique of data analysis was used in this study because of its effectiveness in attitudinal and behavioural studies. One hundred copies of the questionnaire were administered and recovered. The data was analyzed using frequency tables and simple percentages. The purpose, challenges, and importance of improving the performance of pastoral counsellors were discussed as well as recommendations. This article explores ways in which pastoral counselling reflects educational preferences and references to the Nigerian context. The theoretical framework used for this paper is "Reality Therapy". This study recommends that there is an urgent need for pastoral counseling to be introduced to the theological seminaries to help pastors in training to enable them to counsel their members very well because being a pastor is different from being a good counselor. This study concluded by saying, that when the pastor is equipped with pastoral counseling techniques, the counselee will get his/her desired answers which in turn foster peace in his life and vice-versa national development.

Keywords: Counsellor, Pastoral Counsellor, Development, Education

Introduction

Winkel (2005), defined counselling as a relationship between a professionally trained and competent officer and an individual seeking help in gaining greater self-understanding, improved decision making, and acquiring behavioural changing skills for problem resolution and development. Counselling unlike other professions, provides a safe place for clients or students to talk and process their thoughts feelings and needs.

It has been observed that most ethno-religious conflict broke out as a result of inciting statements either through religious sermons or publication by different religious groups (Ayinla, 2010). Counselling is a process in which the counsellor facilitates the expansion of students' view of life enlarges the repertoire of coping resources and enables them to make appropriate choices (Yeo,1993)

In the Nigerian educational system, a Pastoral Counselling degree is to be designed for those who plan to pursue vocations in congregation-based ministry. It is to improve the student to serve a diverse community by facilitating healing and growth through reflectively integrating Christian values, principles, and resources of pastoral counselling practices with theological tenets and experience.

According to Abiri (1996), a society can only be considered desirable if it provides adequate guidance and counselling to help individuals, especially pastors, set realistic goals and reach their full potential, leading to effective ministerial development. Pastoral counseling is a unique form of psychotherapy that uses spiritual resources as well as psychological understanding for healing and growth. The educational industry is the bedrock of sustainable human capital development and progress in any nation. It is also globally recognized as an agent of positive change in all spheres of national endeavor. The success of the education industry depends largely on the level of professionalism, integrity, competency, and dedication of teachers who are the prime movers of the industry (Okesina, 2012).

Pastors can professionally discharge their task of facilitating meaningful learning by maintaining a very high level of academic development. Academic development is also an advancement in the educational pursuit of a pastoral counselor to help in moral uprightness, honesty, soundness, and unimpaired or uncorrupted condition (Barber, 1998).

Consequently, man as a social animal is a unit of sociological and spiritual studies, where he acquires his learning experience that sharpens his personality and aids in the process of physical and spiritual adjustments which pastoral counsellor suggests. Humans encounter multi-dimensional problems within living, ranging from social, environmental relational, mental, emotional, psychological, medical, educational, cultural, humanitarian, and personal. This shows how the educational development of pastoral counsellors affects these counselling practices because it enhances the affective, cognitive, and psychomotive domains of individuals in the past, present, and future life experiences.

Meanwhile, there are four phases of counselling *vis*; clarification, formulation, intervention, and termination. In this field, some principles are significant in bringing improvement, insight, effectiveness, exposure, growth, and changes that impact lives for good.

Purpose of the study

This study investigates the impact of pastoral counseling on national security, educational pursuit, development, and the perception of pastoral counsellors. It further aims to help pastors restore wholeness into people's lives, systems, relationships, and existence. Hence, intended pastors need pastoral counseling training in their programme in the seminaries.

Significance of the Study

For development to be achieved by counsellors, Gary Collins enumerated, the process of relationship that can be result-oriented between the pastoral counsellor and the counsellee, the process *i.e.*: attending, listening, responding, teaching and filtering. This will help counsellors to be effective in bringing changes in peoples' lives using psychological and biblical-based counselling for future reasons.

In counselling relationships, the counsellor being cautious might incorporate theological facts to identify a problem, guide, educate, motivate, encourage and advise the counsellee towards living responsibly. Some of the theological facts include sin and salvation, guilt and forgiveness, despair and hope, love and hatred, anger, grace and redemption, and judgement

and grace. There are stages of life that need the assistance of pastoral counsellors before one can make positive headway in life. the apostles took an assignment of counselling the converts in the bible.

Statement of the problem

Over the years, there have been developmental crises, most pastors have mixed up pastoring with pastoral counselling. Pastoral counselling is quite different from pastoring a congregation because it has its own techniques or skills of practices. Other root causes of pastoral emotional problems due to lack of educational-counselling development include over-reaction to events, conflict over inner expectation, over-identification, unresolved issues, sensitivity to failure, and the like.

Therefore, in the previous research reviewed, the Author elaborates on some importance that can help pastoral counsellors improve their performance in carrying out their duties (Owoade, 2022). Here, this study investigates pastoral counsellor perception of educational development and its impact on counsellors.

The pastor framed or equipped with pastoral counselling skills or techniques is best equipped to meet the immediate emotional, social, environmental relational, mental, emotional, psychological, medical, educational, cultural, humanitarian needs of his members or people around, unlike the pastors without the knowledge. This works with the scriptures and pastoral counselling theories, not leaving out pastoral matters. So, a pastoral counselling course should be introduced to seminaries, and theological and mission training institutions to enable pastors and missionaries to farewell in ministry.

Scope of the study

This study covers both the staff and pastors-in-training of the Redeemed Christian Bible College, main campus, Mowe, Ogun State, and as required the administration of the questionnaire.

Research questions

This study attempted to provide answers to the under-listed questions as a pathway to achieve the stated purpose of the study.

1. Does Pastoral Counselling improve the security of the nation?
2. Is there any relationship between educational development and Pastoral Counselling?
3. Does the intended Pastors need pastoral counseling in their theological training?

Methodology

The Redeemed Christian Bible College students were used for the study, this set of students have been workers in the church for years so they will be able to give adequate information in response to the questionnaire. The inability to expose student/pastors to pastoral counseling programme can be attributed to the teething problems of insecurity in churches today caused by pseudo-pastors. The survey research technique of data gathering and analysis was used because of its effectiveness in getting the current facts, opinions, motivations, and behavior of people.

The population of this study is limited to the ministers and pastors in training in the college's main campus because of the diversified nature brought to bear positively on the survey conducted. The qualitative and quantitative sampling method is the procedure adopted by

the researcher in arriving at her sample size of 100 respondents given 100 questionnaires respectively in their various offices and classrooms.

Analysis

Subject responses were then subjected to descriptive statistical analysis using frequency tables and percentages to analyze the data.

Table 1-3 Gender, Age and Designation Distribution of the Respondents

Table 1 As represented in the table below, most respondents are males, 90 in number, accounting for 90% of the total while the remaining 10% are females. It is safe perhaps to deduct from this simple frequency table that more males than females are ministers or pastors in the redeem Christian Bible College.

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
MALE	90	90%
FEMALE	10	10%
TOTAL	100	100%

Table 2 Age Distribution of Respondents

From the frequency table below, it is apparent that majority of the respondents are those in their thirties and forties, 10 people making 10% have their ages ranging between 19 and 29 respondents, which make 10% of the total, are aged between 51 and above. The age range with the most number of respondents is 30 to forty with 50 people making 50% half of the total, while those above the age of 41 and 50 are 30, amounting to 30%. It is clear from this analysis that not many people below 30years of age are ministers or pastors in the pastor.

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
19 ~29	10	10%
30~40	50	50%
41~50	30	30%
51~ABOVE	10	10%
TOTAL	100	100%

Table 3 Designation and Distribution of Respondents

From the table below, it is clear that majority of respondents are pastors, 70 in all making 70% of the total, while the remaining 30, accounting for 30% are ministers.

DESIGNATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
MINISTER	30	30%
PASTORS IN TRAINING	70	70%
TOTAL	100	100%

FIELD SURVEY 2023

Results on Evaluation of the Study

Table 1: For the purpose of this study, three research questions were formulated. These were further broken down to contingency nine items to further probe the respondents in proving

answers to the formulated research questions based on rank or score-position of their responses YES or NO.

Item 1: The impact of Pastoral Counselling and Educational Development on cohesion and national security

Item 2: There is a relationship between educational development and pastoral counseling

Item 3: Intending pastors and ministers need pastoral counseling in their theological training

Item 4: There are differences between pastors and pastoral counselors prior to their educational development

Item 5: The national security and cohesion is dependence on the pastoral counseling training of ministers.

Item 6: Pastoral counseling training should be an effective capacity development tool for church in this nation.

Item 7: Ministers and lecturers in seminaries benefit from the pastoral counseling

Item 8: The educational development of pastoral counselors have effect on their performance

Item 9: The spiritual healthiness of the church is dependence on the pastoral counseling training of the minister.

Item 1: The impact of Pastoral Counselling and Educational Development on cohesion and national security

Table 2 Distribution of respondents on pastoral counselling

DESIGNATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
YES	90	90%
NO	10	10%
TOTAL	100	100%

This study result on table2, 90% of the respondents were of the affirmative response.

Meaning that majority of the pastors and ministers accept that pastoral counseling helps the nation in peace and security, as presented in the table above.

Item 3: Impact of Pastoral Counselling techniques on National Security

Table 3 Distribution of respondents rating the relationship responses in yes and no

Relationship	Frequency	Percent
Yes	80	80%
No	20	20%

There is relationship between educational development and pastoral counseling, from the data generated from the table above. Out of the total of 100 respondent 80 agreed that there is relationship between the training which is an affirmative response which means those 20 pastors who said no have not attended the training and as not rated it to be fair.

Item 3 There is a Need for Intending Pastors in Nigeria to have pastoral counseling in theological training to help Nigerians growth

Table 4 Distribution of respondent's appreciation of the pastoral counseling training

COUNSELLOR TRAINING	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
YES	88	88%

NO	12	12%
TOTAL	100	100%

From the data presented in the table above, 88 respondents in RCBC that has undergone the pastoral course appreciated it and others that are yet look forward to the experience. While 12 respondents says no because they have not attended the training and are still ignorant.

Discussion on the Result Findings and Implication

It is obvious that there is relationship in the pastoral counseling and educational development, the majority of the respondents indicated that pastoral training has effect on their performances as it was rated above average.

Pastoral training to a large extent has impact on the performance of pastors and ministers.so as to get prepared for the work ahead with necessary information and knowledge needed in their duty post.

Conclusion

Across the nation, more than 3000 pastoral counsellors provide a variety of services including treatment for persons with mental disorder; counselling for adults, adolescents, children, families and couples: substance abuse treatment, wellness programs, religious retreats, spiritual direction, clinical training, and consultations to corporations and outreach preventive services in prisons, community settings and schools. There is urgent need for educational development of pastors in training on pastoral counselling by including it into their course of programme in the Institution. If all Pastors or Missionaries undergo the pastoral counselling training in the context of principles and practices of guidance counsellor they will be fit to render their duties as a trained therapist not pseudo counsellor lacking the in-depth knowledge of counselling and people will not blame them on any result of counselling sessions.

Nigeria at large will be peaceful, when the pastors and counsellors are well equipped to help the people with emotional, physical, social, environmental, relational, mental, emotional, psychological, medical, educational, cultural, humanitarian and spiritual concerns. Here vital issues that are interconnected with pastoral counsellors who have vast knowledge in doing eclectic method of counselling their various members as discussed and should be put into workable practices. As Solomon said in Ecclesiastes chapter 12; 13-14. ``Let us hear the conclusion of the whole matter; fear God and keep His Commandments for this is the whole duty of man. For God will bring every work into judgement, including, every secret thing, whether good or evil''.

Recommendation

1. Tertiary institutions should formulate curriculum inculcating the pastoral counselling trainings on biblical basis and theories of counselling.
2. Government should approve the establishment of pastoral counsellor offices outside the church settings to help people in need of professional pastoral counsellors.
3. Pastoral counsellors should improve themselves by attending refresher courses and trainings regularly for their own educational development.
4. There must be caring and counselling for marital relationship, caring and counselling during grief period, burnout and sustainable nature because the empirical view of the

planet earth revealed that something dramatic need to be done quickly to redeem the collapsing status of nature and the environment.

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Impact of Pastoral Counselling in Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C) Oke-Anu in Ilorin Metropolis

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Abstract

Pastoral counselling uniquely merges spiritual guidance with psychological support to address intricate family dynamics. It helps to synergies pastoral care and family counselling, integrating faith and therapy to heal emotions and enrich familial bonds. The church is a spiritual space where people meet for the purpose of worship. However, the church has been seen not only as a place of worship but also a place for spiritual healing which finds expression in prayer, psalmody, fasting and as well the talk-therapy by proffering solutions to family related issues. The paper therefore examines the impact of pastoral counselling in Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C) Oke-Anu in Ilorin Metropolis. Data were harvested through interviews from pastors and members of the congregation, historical and descriptive methods were adopted as secondary sources. It was discovered that there is huge impacts of pastoral counselling on families in the church and through various pastoral engagements in the light of talk therapy many families have been saved at the verge of divorce and marital failure. It also shows that interactions between pastors and members have helped to identify problems and provide solutions in the church and homes. The paper concluded that talk therapy is a viable tool to reduce the issue of conflict in homes and church as seen in C.A.C Oke-Anu, Ilorin. Therefore, the study recommended that the pastoral counselling should be embraced by all pastors and also pastors should be well-informed and trained about ethics of counselling.

Keywords: Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu, Family Counselling, Spiritual Therapy
Pastoral Counselling, Ilorin Metropolis

Introduction

One of the common imprints about Christ Apostolic Church is the spontaneous saying of prayers in their gatherings and prayers have always been the basis of their regular meetings. Due to their prayer life, it is given a nomenclature known as "praying church", to indicate a church that is known for no other business than prayer. The place of the church in keeping the prayer life of members which can be seen as its legacy and heritage cannot be contested but rather view with an eagle eye as a panacea to spiritual and physical challenges. At the centre of spirituality and physicality lies the root of counselling as another diversified medium to combat against spiritual and physical maladies. Aldridge (2014) cited *Royal College of Psychiatrists'* on counselling that counselling is a general term for exploring emotional problems by talking them through with a trained counsellor or therapist. The view of

Aldridge is aptly to the current situation in Christ Apostolic Church where Pastors are not only concerned about praying for deliverance but by incorporating talk session into solving spiritual problems, and problems caused as a result of contraction in social relations.

Pastoral counselling involves the steps –proactive and active steps taken to combat against and integrate psychological, family and spiritual differences in the life of congregants through the use of scriptural passages that are relevant and appropriate to the situation of the counsees. Pastoral counselling involves talking with people one-on-one, in relationships, and in families to help them better understand emotional and religious challenges and to find solutions utilizing both religious and secular resources (Encyclopedia.com, n.d.). Counselling on its own is a scope that cannot be limited to faith-based institution such as Christianity but rather by extension is a conscious and unconscious practice in the traditional African society. At the family level, counselling can be seen as an advice, while in the religious level (African Religion), it can be viewed as consultation. At an administrative level, counselling can be seen as directives, instructions, seminars, workshop amongst others. However, in the medical sphere, it can be viewed as a healing measure where the therapist converse with the counselee to acquire the information needed in order to proffer the adequate solution needed.

The essence of counselling has necessitated the development of counselling as a course in tertiary institutions. In secondary schools, the guidance and counselling unit is put in place with a professional counsellor who guides the efforts and choice of learners to fruition. Hence, counselling is not limited to a particular sector rather it is an encompassing act in every human endeavours with variance in the level of expertise. It is no gainsay to accentuate that the level of counselling in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu is of a great commendation to the growth and application of counselling to solving disputes in the church and families thus providing vitality for the sustainability of the family and the church at large thereby creating a safe society where spirituality and physicality converse to ameliorate man's challenges.

The thrust of this paper is to reveal the impacts of pastoral counselling in Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C) Oke-Anu. The paper is thus subdivided into; the concept of pastoral counselling forms of pastoral counselling, brief history of Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu in Ilorin, District Coordinating Council (DCC) headquarters, Ilorin, strategies adopted for pastoral counselling in C.A.C Oke-Anu, impact of pastoral counselling on the Church and conclusion.

The Concept of Pastoral Counselling

The term "Pastoral Counselling" can be derived from two independent words –Pastoral from Pastor and Counselling from Counsel. A Pastor is an oracle of God who teaches and preaches the good news and oversees the Church. The role of the Pastor is usually narrowed to the role of a shepherd. The word translated "Pastors" here is the Greek word *Poimen*, meaning "a herdsman, especially a shepherd" (Carter, n.d.). Durojaiye (1987) opines that counselling involves the development of interaction through the relationship between a trained therapist (counsellor) and a troubled person in a perceived temporary state of indecision, confusion, malfunction, habit disorder, distress or despair. Akinade (2012) corroborated Durojaiye's view on counselling. He defined counselling as a number of procedures used in assisting an individual in solving problems which arise in various aspects of a counselee's life.

The significant similarity between the definitions of Durojaiye and Akinade is the formative factor that led to counselling – a problem. Hansen, Stevic, and Warner (1982) affirmed that the purpose of counselling is to provide for the individual functions in a social context and not in

isolation. To understand the position of Hansen et al, McLeod (2007) buttressed further that counselling is an activity which takes place when someone who is troubled invites and allows another person to enter into a particular relationship with them. Hence, the “social context” which Hansen portrayed found expression in the “invitation into a relationship” of McLeod. This implies that counselling as act is not or cannot be achieved in isolation rather in a social context where relationship is ignited.

Pastoral Counselling is the “relationship or talk relationship” established between a counsellor, who is a pastor or uses pastoral methods and approach such as using biblical quotations, references, pastoral care and a counselee, who is either a member of the congregation or an outsider. McLeod (2007) cited Vance and Volsky (1962) that counselling deals with so-called individuals whose problems are developmental in nature. It can be deduced that problems are of stages and the need to approach these diversities made counselling to continue to be relevant. Murry (2005) cited Clinbell that Pastoral Counselling as “the application of a range of healing techniques to assist individuals in handling their issues and crises more fully and, as a result, experiencing healing of their brokenness”.

The human society has been characterized with several issues which often lead to misunderstanding and conflict, thus, the need to engage the existential realities through a talk therapy is important. The church space is not indispensable since it is a society where people relate, relationship is established and communication is enhanced. The Pastor is one who is saddled with the responsibilities to feed God’s people with His word.

In the biblical accounts, pastoral counselling is made evident from both testaments. In the Old Testament there are several allusions to pastoral counselling such as Jethro counselled Moses (Exo. 18:17-23), Isaiah counselled Hezekiah (2 Kgs 19), Rebecca counselled Jacob (Gen. 27:57), Samuel ministry also provides an insight to pastoral counselling. Furthermore, in the New Testament pastoral counselling was evidence through Jesus’ teachings and ministry, and in several Pauline epistles such as Rom. 12:15 and 1 Thess. 2:11-12. Pastoral counselling is the conscious and intentional use of divine provisions through the scriptural passages to heal, bring calmness and proffer solutions to problems. Asamoah opines that “Pastoral counselling is a psychotherapeutic approach to counselling that employs biblically spiritual and ethical principles to decode and address client problems that may be of emotional, spiritual, psychological, physical and material or socio-cultural nature”.

Counselling is an enlightened process whereby counsellors help counselees by facilitating growth and positive adjustment through self-understanding (Akinade, 2012). One of the ways to be emancipated is through self-understanding. It is pertinent for the counselees to understand the situation not only through their views but through the views of the counsellor. Gail (2010) remarks that counselling developed from the psychoanalytic theory of Sigmund Freud and was first introduced as such to Britain in the 1950s via the National Marriage Guidance Council, now called “Relate”. Pastoral counselling started as a separate discipline in the North America as far back as the 12th century (Wikipedia, n.d.). GoodTherapy (2021) writes:

Ministers of all religions usually offer counselling to members of their religious communities. For support, direction, and solutions relating to *mental* health difficulties, people have long looked to religious leaders. Pastoral counselling was developed with the understanding that, while this form of support is beneficial, other problems can call for a higher calibre of assistance.

From the foregoing, pastoral counselling emerged to provide support, direction and solutions to members with mental health and marital challenges. Counselling is timeless. It is not time framed or bound. It can be planned and unplanned. Thus, a pastor's word(s) of advice at any time and at any given place can also be regarded as pastoral counselling. McLeod (2007) corroborated this view by saying that counselling can be a brief conversation of only a few minutes, within a "window of opportunity" that arises during involvement in other helping, caring or clinical activities. Pastoral counselling can also be called "divine counselling" since pastors are looked upon as God's representative to His people.

Forms of Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral counselling has engaged both spiritual and physical issues emerging within the faith-based i.e the church through teaching, sermonizing and instructing an individual or group of individuals. Pastoral counselling can be **individual and group** in nature. Akinade (2012) cited McLeod that an **individual counselling** is a professional assistance in which the counsellor works on a one-to-one basis with the clients to help them resolve their mental and social problems. It connotes a session whereby the counsellor has a direct "talk" with the counselee without hindrance. This is one of the commonest ways used in churches today to address families intricate matters arising in the spiritual domains.

The need for individual counselling is to afford and assure the confidentiality of the counselee who wants to divulge the truth behind the identified problems. In Nigerian Churches, ministers like Pastor E.A. Adeboye, Pastor W.F. Kumuyi amongst others, allow their wives to handle some individual counselling among members and those who are non-members but come for counselling. It is pertinent to say that individual counselling can also be necessitated based on the trust of the assumed counsellor. This finds expression in the fixed mindset of some counselees who conceived that a problem can be fully addressed by a "particular" pastor, or so to say that one can only abide by what such individual counsellor has to say about the problem.

Pastoral Counselling entails sessions with individuals such as family, friends, couples and other close relatives and friends may be included in pastoral therapy. Pastoral counsellors can provide both family and couple counselling; but, in some instances, they may concentrate primarily on these relationships (Zencare, n.d.). Individual counselling is a concentrated and narrow-centred approach that is believed to address a particular counselee or specific individual at a given time. In this situation, the counsellor only listens to a particular counselee and suggests a panacea that can alleviate the problem. Patterson (1971) asserted that counselling is a relationship in which the counsellor must understand the client. Thus, the counsellor needs to comprehend the counselee's situation to proffer a suitable solution.

Group counselling implies the collectiveness, commonness, and generality of counsellor to counsel diverse counselees with the same or similar problems. Akinade (2012) opined that a group counselling is an interpersonal process in which a professionally trained counsellor helps more than one person or individuals who are having similar problems. He went further to assert that it is a process of using group interaction to facilitate the understanding and self-acceptance of individuals in the group. Group counselling is also a common form of pastoral counselling found mostly among Nigerian Church leaders. Pastors tend to collate and address issues with specific similarities to proffer a solution that can be applied to the problem. Counselling Centre of the University of Illinois (n.d.) writes:

Group counselling is a form of psychotherapy that usually involves four to ten participants and one or two group therapists. Most groups meet regularly at the same time for one to two hours. During that time, the members of the group discuss the issues that are concerning them and offer each other support and feedback. Interpersonal interaction is highly valued and encouraged.

From the definition above, group counselling involves a range of number of counsellors and counselees within a particular range of time for a specific purpose. In other to settle family disputes, both individual and group counselling may be adopted. It is individual when the pastor seeks the audience of either the husband or wife, but, it becomes a group counselling when the spouses are on seat for the session.

Brief History of Christ Apostolic Church, Oke-Anu, DCC Headquarters, Ilorin

Generally, the history of Christ Apostolic Church in Ilorin metropolis can be traced back to July 1947 by the leading of the Holy Spirit when one Prophet P. A. Olagbami came from Offa to Ilorin for a revival programme. The church started in a very small way in the house of one Elder Ikuforiji, the acting chief sanitary, who was then staying at Opo-Maaluu quarters. They started with morning and evening prayer meetings. People brought their different problems and challenges to God like diseases, barrenness, and demonic attacks etc., and there were records of supernatural interventions in answer to prayers (Abolaji, 2022).

However, the history of Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu began in the year 1978 after a great revival service held by a group of other Christ Apostolic Church (C.A.C.) members around Ilorin province in the same year. Its first service was held by Evangelist R.A. Fasoyin and Pastor Michael Agbedde from Oke-Isegun (Mountain of Victory) and other fathers from Sabo-Oke and Agbo-Oba areas on August 14, 1978 where about forty-three people attended the service exclusive the children and representatives from other C.A.C branches in Ilorin (C.A.C Oke-Anu, 2023).

The revival was birthed from a vision given to the then Pastor –Pastor Michael Agbedde (late), who also chaired the revival team. He was given a vision by the Lord that he should start another branch of the C.A.C. around Gaa-Akanbi area of Ilorin to make it the fourth branch within the major part of the town. The revival service itself, led by Prophet- Evangelist Michael O. Adio was so mighty, crucial and effective that it made awareness to C.A.C. members living around the area. It also gradually brought about the attendance of other non-C.A.C members as well. Initially, service was been held at a land space which was borrowed from one of the church members – Elder D.A. Dada who also laboured hard in aiding the church to purchase and acquire a four plot of land –where the church is currently situated (C.A.C Oke-Anu, 2023).

C.A.C. Oke-Anu continued to grow through the help of the Lord and through prayers, commitments and dedication from members and other faithful. It became a District in 1993 during the tenure of Pastor Akinyele. December 2008, under the leadership of Pastor Adeolu Bokode it aroused the status of a Zonal Headquarter, then in the year 2015 the church became a Districts Coordinating Council (DCC). C.A.C. Oke-Anu now has many branches such as C.A.C. Oke-Ibukun, C.A.C. Temidire, C.A.C. Oke-irapada in Asa-dam area of Ilorin, C.A.C. Tanke-Iledu, C.A.C. Chapel of Mercy (English Assembly), C.A.C. Oke-anu II (in Amoyo area Ilorin), C.A.C. Oke-anu III (Atere/Agah area), with four among them rising to District levels (C.A.C Oke-Anu, 2023).

Strategies Adopted for Pastoral Counselling in CAC Oke-Anu

Pastoral counselling in C.A.C Oke-Anu is paramount and it has been viewed as an important tool for church growth and transformation since the inception of the Church (Pastor Jaiyeola, personal communication, September 17, 2023). Dicks (1963) seeks to make a distinction between the approaches of the psychologist and of the pastor. He went to further to states:

Psychology studies the behaviour of people, whereas religion provides the hope for these same people regardless of their behaviour. Psychology focuses upon human relationships as they are while religion inspires and motivates people to change and improve their condition. Supported by psychology and religion the pastor moves into the arena of relationships and becomes an active participant.

From the excerpt above, Dicks provides a distinction between the approaches of the psychologist and of the pastor in a precise summary using behaviour of people and hope of people to explain the meaning of pastoral counselling. Thus, it is important to state that Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu resonate Dicks views on Pastor's approach in counselling. The church counselling unit is headed by the curate pastor, Pastor T.O. Ogunleye. The unit meets regularly to ensure love and unity are maintained and restored in the church. The normal protocol before engaging the services of the unit is to be scheduled after proper dissemination of information either through verbal communication or a counselling leaflet that is given to the counselee which contains the required details. There several strategies of pastoral counselling adopted by the church. These strategies are:

- 1. Face-to-Face:** This method affords the unit to meet personally with a counsellor and have a therapeutic session where the counselee enjoys maximum privacy for whatever issues discussed. The counsellors are well-trained to keep matters discussed away from the public. For family issues, in cases where both parties are members, sometimes each party is scheduled for a personal session before inviting both parties for group counselling.
- 2. Special visitations:** Another method embarked on by the team for effective counselling is through visitation. This is usually done by persistently visiting members of the church to know about their welfare and engage them in discussions about the scriptures, life and pray for them.
- 3. Special Seminars/programs for families:** The inclusion of special programmes dedicated to questions on family issues is evident in the church. This is usually accompanied with rigorous prayers. The church is also observing a seven-month family concert seminar especially during Sunday school sessions and sometimes in the main service. There is also a prayer retreat between 9:00 am and 12:00 pm of every Mondays for families (Pastor Ogunleye, personal communication, September 17, 2023)

Impact of Pastoral Counselling in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu

There are several traceable impacts of pastoral counselling on individuals, families and the church. The interviewees are Pastor D. O. Ajaiyeoba (DCC Pastor), Pastor T. O. Ogunleye (Curate Pastor and Counselling Head), and Elder Jaiyeola Victor (Choir Master) who are key members of the church with relevant information that aided the study. From the interviewees in C.A.C Oke-Anu the impacts of pastoral counselling are not limited to the below:

- a. It fosters relationship between individuals, families and the church leaders:**
Pastoral counselling has assisted the church in relationship building through the establishment of a communication network among members and the pastor.

Counselling has disclosed several issues which were initially concealed and that have the potential to cause damages to the family.

- b. Restoration of broken homes:** C.A.C. Oke-Anu has been able to intervene and mend shattered homes and some nearly collapsing relationships through successful counselling. According to Pastor Ogunleye (personal communication, September 17, 2023) there are several cases where members come back to testify how their homes that have been hot and almost scattering have been restored to their first love”.
- c. It aids the spiritual growth of the church:** On the other hand, pastoral counselling has thus far helped the church to preserve the high spirituality for which it is renowned. Counselling has kept the leaders abreast of the spiritual challenges of the church members and also proffers solutions to them through prayers and divine leading. As a result, the church can claim to have experienced significant spiritual growth and maturity.
- d. Increase in Number:** Elder Jaiyeola (personal communication, September 17, 2023) submits that effective counselling has added to the number of worshipers and their commitment to the church. Many members and families who happen to be satisfied with the counselling aspect of the church and those regular follow-up services give back total commitment and dedication to the church. To him “it has really encouraged a high number of attendance and dedication to the church more especially during hard and discouraging times like this”.
- e. Unity within homes and the church:** Many houses have experienced the establishment of true love, peace, and unity through fervent counselling and prayers, which has become a significant reflection inside the church of God. According to Pastor Ogunleye (personal communication, September 17, 2023) when the home is settled in peace and love, the church would march forward in progress and faith.
- f. Progress from all spheres:** Adequate counselling has fostered progress from all spheres within and outside the church. It was discovered that pastoral counselling has impacted the spiritual progress of all committed and dedicated members, to the fatherly advice for the youths on chosen fields, to the effective maintenance of a balanced life of a believer (Rom. 12:11; not slothful in business, fervent in Spirit and serving the Lord).
- g. Changes from Luke-warmness:** Pastor Ogunleye (personal communication, September 17, 2023) confirms that not all humans are the same, neither do people enjoy same upbringing, there have been some members who had initially had negative thoughts about life and have thus reflected such in their relationship with others” pastoral counselling has been cognizant so far in making positive changes in view of such people and have created a better environment for them. These positive changes have really brought out great potentials in such people.

Conclusion

The impacts of pastoral counselling in C.A.C Oke-Anu cannot be overemphasized. Pastoral counsellors often incorporate modern psychological thought and method with traditional religious training in a determination to address psycho-spiritual issues in addition to the traditional spectrum of counselling services (Stephanie, Douglas, & Donna, 2005). It is noted that pastoral counselling in Christ Apostolic Church Oke-Anu serves as a therapeutic measure

to physical and spiritual laxity thereby facilitating cure to family related issues within the ambit of the church. The Pastor, Elders and the counselling unit of the church have been of great help in balancing spiritual and physical issues to maintain peace, promote love and restore broken homes within the church. It is therefore safe to say that, counselling is a measure that is needed to be embraced by sundry of Christian denominations in the 21st-century Nigerian society to enhance the level of Church growth and development not only through “prayers” but also through the effective use of the talk therapy.

Recommendations

1. Pastoral counselling should be embraced by all pastors and also pastors should be well-informed and trained about ethics of counselling.
2. Trainings such as seminars, workshops and conferences should be organised for pastoral counsellors to ensure they are up-to-date with the latest counselling techniques and theological insights.
3. Church foster relationship with specialise health institutions or workers to provide therapy for those who require special treatment.
4. Pastoral counselling should be included in outreach endeavours to further extend it beyond the church scope and to enhance evangelism method.
5. It is not enough to have Pastoral counsellor if there is no proper funding and emotional support from the church. Pastoral counsellors should be encouraged with financial resources and emotional support.

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Child Upbringing Parental Styles and Personal Values of Adolescents in Pentecostal Churches in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Adolescence is a challenging time that entails self-discovery and social connection with others. Parental styles are patterns of behaviors, attitudes, and approaches that a parent uses when interacting with and raising their child. Personal values are a set of guiding principles and beliefs that help differentiate between “good” and “bad.” These are concepts like integrity versus dishonesty or hard work versus cutting corners. Personal values influence people’s behaviors, relationships, and everyday life. This study child upbringing, parental styles, and the personal values of adolescents attending selected Pentecostal churches in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria. It aims to identify prevalent parental styles in child upbringing, understand the personal values exhibited by adolescents, examine the influence of child upbringing parental styles on personal values developed by Adolescents, and assess the impact of the religious environment in Pentecostal churches on the personal values of Adolescents. The study employs a descriptive survey design method, using a questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 200 adolescents. Findings reveal that parents in these religious communities significantly exhibit the four types of parental styles. The religious environment plays a substantial role in shaping personal values, both positively and negatively, impacting adolescents' moral development, resilience, and social responsibility. Parents and guardians are encouraged to actively engage with their adolescents in navigating religious diversity. The recommendation aims to create a more informed, inclusive, and tolerant environment for adolescents within Pentecostal churches in Ede South Local Government Area.

Keywords: Child Upbringing, Parental Styles, Adolescents, Personal Values, Ede South Local Government, Pentecostal Churches.

Introduction

In contemporary times, the phase of adolescence has gained recognition as a distinctive phase of life that comes with unique requisites. It is recognized as a phase, rather than a singular moment, in an individual's life. Along with physical and mental changes, societal perceptions and expectations also undergo a shift during this period. As a part of the process of crafting an identity, they may experiment with diverse roles, behaviours, and philosophies. This recognition of adolescence as a unique phase of life, coupled with the researchers' experiences

on various behavioural pattern among adolescents while reaching out to secondary school students in Ede and its environments, has prompted researchers and scholars to delve deeper into understanding its intricacies, particularly concerning the influence of child upbringing parental styles on the development of personal values among adolescents in Ede.

Exploring the dynamics between parental guidance and adolescent autonomy sheds light on how adolescents navigate the complexities of identity formation and value acquisition within the context of their familial and social environments. This exploration becomes especially pertinent within the framework of religious communities, such as Pentecostal churches, where familial values often intersect with spiritual teachings and community norms.

Understanding the interplay between parental styles and personal values among adolescents attending Pentecostal churches in Ede, Osun State, Nigeria, holds implications for individual development and individual development, community cohesion, and cultural preservation. By examining the influence child upbringing parental styles have on Adolescent personal values, researchers aim to uncover patterns that may contribute to a more nuanced understanding of adolescent development within religious contexts. Additionally, assessing the influence of the spiritual environment in Pentecostal churches on personal values provides insights into the role of faith-based institutions in shaping moral frameworks and ethical decision-making processes among youths. The study of child upbringing parental styles is based on the idea that parents differ in their parenting patterns, and that these patterns can significantly impact their children's personal value development and well-being. Scholars said that parenting styles are distinct from specific parenting practices since they represent broader patterns of practices and attitudes that create an emotional climate for the child (Hong,2021). Parenting styles also encompass how parents respond to and make demands on their children.

To effectively explore the influence of child upbringing Parental style on the personal values of Adolescents, it must be well understood that there are several types of parental styles in child upbringing such as Authoritarian, Authoritative, Permissive, and Uninvolved parental styles as classified by a psychologist (Vijay, Christy; Gonsalves, Kavita Peter, Ramesh, and Naveen, 2022) and various values adolescents can develop. Hence, the researcher focuses on the four types of parental styles mentioned above and personal values such as cultural, ethical and spiritual values.

Statement of the Problem

Adolescence is a critical developmental period when individuals form their identities and personal values. Parental styles are the totality of approaches and behaviour of parents in raising their adolescents (Bak-Coleman, 2021). This method has a significant influence on adolescents' value systems and behaviours. Furthermore, religious institutions, such as Pentecostal churches, play an important role in shaping the moral and ethical beliefs of their adolescents. (Mamarasulovich,2022)

The influence of parental styles on the personal values of adolescents in Pentecostal churches in the Ede South Local Government (L. G.), Area is not well understood. This is because there is limited research on this topic, and the existing research is often limited in scope. Additionally, the cultural context of Nigeria is complex, and it is important to consider this context when studying the influence of parental styles on the personal values of adolescents (Bak-Coleman, 2021). While studies on parental styles and adolescent development exist (Bak-Coleman, 2021). There is limited research specifically examining the influence of child

upbringing parental styles on the personal values of adolescents attending Pentecostal churches in Ede South L.G. Area, Osun State, Nigeria. This is the gap the researchers worked on. The unique cultural and religious context of Ede, with a strong presence of Pentecostal churches, also calls for an investigation into how parental styles in these religious communities influence the formation of personal values in adolescents.

Literature Review

Concept of Personal Values

Fundamentally, the concept of personal values mirrors internalized beliefs concerning what is deemed right, significant, or fulfilling in life. Individuals frequently construct a hierarchy of values, with certain principles considered fundamental and non-negotiable. These values not only shape behaviour but also play a pivotal role in aligning life goals and aspirations, providing a framework for decision-making. (Shelton and Elliot, 2018)

Personal values are the principles and beliefs that guide our decision-making and behaviour. They help us to differentiate between what is good and bad, and they shape how we move through the world. According to a Scholar, we can learn personal values from the people around us (the first example is our parents), or we can develop them on our own through personal growth (Tascherrau-Dumouchel, Mathias, Stefan, 2022). Adolescents often adopt most of their values from their family members (parents especially), but they start to build their own value systems as they age. Your personal values are the principles that you hold most dear. They are the foundation of your ethical compass and guide your thoughts, words, and actions. When we live by our values, we feel a sense of purpose and fulfillment (Lilach and Shalom, 2022). Scholar K.M Sheldon & A. J Elliot. made it known that "Our personal values can change over time, but our core values tend to remain relatively stable." (K.M Sheldon & A. J Elliot, 2018) It is very important to take time to identify our personal values, as this can help us to clarify our goals and priorities and also help us make better decisions in life. The notion of personal values constitutes a deep and intricate facet of human identity, encompassing the firmly rooted principles and beliefs that steer an individual's decision-making and conduct. These values are inherently subjective, influenced by factors such as cultural nuances, upbringing, education, and personal experiences. Serving as a moral guide, personal values establish the bedrock of one's identity, molding priorities and contributing to a sense of purpose (Lilach and Shalom, 2022).

Cultural and societal influences exert substantial impacts on the formulation and expression of personal values. Yet, individuals may also foster values that challenge established norms, emphasizing the intricate interplay between personal values and the broader social context. Negotiating situations where values clash necessitates careful consideration, as individuals may be compelled to make decisions involving trade-offs between competing values (Bak-Coleman, 2021).

Effective communication of personal values is pivotal in forging meaningful relationships, given that shared values often contribute to stronger connections. Simultaneously, comprehending and respecting divergent values is vital for navigating potential conflicts. Regular introspection and self-awareness are integral to elucidating and conveying personal values, ensuring harmony with an individual's evolving sense of self. Personal value is a broad goal, varying in importance and underlying and guiding attitudes and behaviour. 'Personal value is divided into two major components: the content of values and the commitment to those values' as stated by Tascherrau-Dumouchel, Mathias, and Stefan (2022).

The content of values is the things people value, such as power, achievement, hedonism, stimulation, self-direction, universalism, benevolence, tradition, conformity, and security. Living under one's core principles provides a sense of contentment, authenticity, and purpose. An individual who prioritizes and behaves by their values report higher levels of pleasure and inner peace. Personal values impact relationships and interactions with others because they shape one's views toward empathy, collaboration, justice, and understanding (Xiong, Hao, Mengmeng, Chengfu, Xin, Congshu & Yifan). Personal values must be defined via introspection and contemplation. It entails recognizing and defining the values and ideals that are truly important to a person. This self-awareness enables people to make deliberate choices and decisions that are consistent with their beliefs, resulting in a more rewarding and purpose-driven existence. It must be noted that everyone has values, but each individual has a unique set of values. These distinctions, as said by an author, are influenced by a person's culture, personal upbringing, life experiences, and a variety of other factors. The simplest method to define personal values is to consider the individual's personality and habits. Values eventually intertwine into people's personalities and become a part of them (Weber, 2017).

Religious Values

Religious values are typically derived from the values expressed in religious texts or from the influence of the lives of religious figures. Religious values can vary from religion to religion, but some common values are shared by many religions. Such values include love, compassion, forgiveness, justice, and mercy (Lilach and Shalom, 2022). These values can play an important role in people's lives, providing guidance and inspiration, and helping people to make better choices. The beliefs of an individual are often centered around religion, so religion can be the origin of that individual's values. When religion is defined heuristically, it can be used by individuals, communities, or societies to answer their existential questions with the beliefs that their religion teaches. According to a scholar, Religions offer answers to life's ultimate questions, which can influence our values and the answers that religions provide to these questions can have a profound impact on our values. For example, if a religion teaches that the meaning of life is to love and serve others, then we may develop values of compassion and kindness. Or, if a religion teaches that suffering is a test of our faith, then we may develop values of perseverance and resilience (Lilach and Shalom, 2022).

Ultimately, the values that we hold dear are a reflection of our individual beliefs and experiences. However, the answers that religions provide to existential questions can play an important role in shaping our values. This research was conducted in a way that is consistent with Christian beliefs.

Cultural Values

The values of a particular culture can have a significant impact on how adolescence is experienced. For example, adolescents may be given more freedom and autonomy in cultures that value independence and self-reliance than in cultures that value obedience and conformity (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, and Sapana, 2023).

Economic Factors

Economic factors can also play a role in shaping the experience of adolescence. In cultures where there are limited economic opportunities, adolescents may be expected to start working

and contributing to the family income at a younger age (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, and Sapana, 2023). This can limit their opportunities for education and self-exploration.

Social Norms

Social norms can also influence the experience of adolescence. In cultures where there are strong expectations about how adolescents should behave, they may feel pressured to conform to these expectations, even if they do not agree with them (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020). This can make it difficult for adolescents to develop their own identities and make their own choices.

The different experiences of adolescents across cultures can have a significant impact on the lives of adolescents. In cultures where adolescence is a time of great freedom and exploration, adolescents may have more opportunities to develop their own identities and make their own choices. In cultures where adolescence is a time of greater restriction and control, adolescents may feel more constrained and may have fewer opportunities to express themselves (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, Sapana, 2023).

It is important to be aware of the different experiences of adolescents across cultures in order to understand the challenges and opportunities that adolescents face. By understanding the cultural context in which adolescents are growing up, we can better support them as they navigate this important stage of development.

Parents and other adults who care for and work with adolescents need to stay up-to-date on adolescent development and the realities of adolescent life. Adolescents face a variety of complex and ever-changing challenges, including social media and mental health disorders. By understanding these challenges, adults can provide more effective support and encouragement to young people (Pearce, Uecker, Melinda, 2019).

Adolescent Development

Adolescence is a transitional phase of growth and development between childhood and adulthood. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines an adolescent as any person between the ages of 10 and 19. This age range falls within WHO's definition of young people, which refers to individuals between the ages of 10 and 24.

However, the definition of adolescence varies across cultures. In some societies, adolescence is narrowly equated with puberty and the physical changes that lead to reproductive maturity (Yeo-eun, Yu, Wolters and Eric, 2023). In other societies, adolescence is understood in broader terms that encompass psychological, social, and moral development, as well as physical maturation. In these societies, adolescence typically refers to the period between the ages of 12 and 20 and is roughly equivalent to the word teens.

Bard, a large language model from Google AI, has pointed out that adolescence is a universal stage of development, but the way it is experienced and understood varies greatly across cultures. In some cultures, adolescence is a time of great freedom and exploration. Adolescents are encouraged to experiment with different identities and roles, and they are given a great deal of autonomy. In other cultures, adolescence is a time of greater restriction and control. Adolescents are expected to conform to traditional norms and expectations, and they may have limited opportunities for self-expression (Luitse, Wiebke, and Eric, 2023).

The duration of adolescence also varies across cultures. In some cultures, adolescence is a relatively short period, lasting from the onset of puberty to the early twenties. In other

cultures, adolescence can last much longer, extending into the mid-twenties or even thirties (Luitse, Wiebke, and Eric, 2023).

The different experiences of adolescence across cultures can be attributed to several factors, including:

Influence of Parental Styles on Adolescent Personal Values

Parental styles are categorized under three major forms: authoritarian, authoritative or democratic, permissive or laissez-faire, and self-indulgence or un-involving. The authoritarian parental style consists of parents who are often strict, and harsh. Authoritative parents are flexible and responsive to their children's needs but still enforce reasonable standards of conduct (Oyebode, 2020). At the same time, permissive or laissez-faire parents are those who impose few restrictions, rules, or limits on their children. Reports have shown that authoritarian parental styles have a negative connotation in literature because of the negative behaviour outcomes of adolescents and children. However, on the same, note outcome of some research revealed that authoritarian parents yield positive effects on adolescents. Some found that authoritative parental style has more positive effects on adolescents' behavior (Lilach and Shalom, 2022). Permissive or laissez-faire parents without well-defined or clear-cut goals and such parents play a passive role in the rearing of children. Authoritarian parents enforce their beliefs and opinions as laws of the mind (nature). They believe that what they know is the reality and facts can be imposed from outside. There is no need for the child to work on his way. Raising a child like this is simple, easy, and fast like raising hormone-injected tomatoes. No questioning, inquiring just accepting without proof. Even though the facts that are presented by the authority are valid and real because children have to accept them, the children would not own them (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020). Children would not own them because there is no self-effort involved in the process. They have to prove these facts to their minds to make them their own. Authoritarian parents set strict rules and standards and expect their children to obey them. Everything is thought and predetermined by parents, the only thing that children have to do is follow the instructions. The children of authoritarian parents actualize the wills and orders of their parents; therefore, they often either cannot or will not take responsibility for their own actions (Lilach and Shalom, 2022). If children do not feel responsible for their actions, they may find themselves engaging in a variety of actions that could cause harm both to themselves and to others. Such a situation provides the appropriate conditions for delinquent behaviour. It has been found that children of authoritarian parents have higher rates of delinquency than children of non-authoritative parents (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, Sapana, 2023).

Children of authoritarian parents have difficulty in differentiating between right and wrong because in their case right and wrong depends on the authority. Therefore, morality is conditional, with conditions determined by external forces. Again, because children are not raised as independent individuals, they cannot express a need for and/or develop independently a set of humanistic moral values. Dependent people cannot develop moral values. Authoritarian parents seek to ensure that their children obey rules and standards; their relationship with their children is basically based on a power conflict. As adolescent grows, older authoritarian disciplinary styles decline.

The connection between parental approaches and individual values stands as a crucial element in human development, molding the convictions and actions of individuals over their lifetimes. Parenting styles, encompassing the emotional atmosphere and behavioral methods employed by parents, wield a considerable influence over the internalization of personal

values in their children. Through the processes of modeling and observation, parents assume primary roles as exemplars, with children often absorbing the values demonstrated by their caregivers, thus shaping their own set of personal values (Yeo, Yu, Wolter, and Eric, 2023). Authoritative parenting, characterized by a harmonious blend of warmth and clear expectations, correlates with positive outcomes, and nurturing values like responsibility and empathy. In contrast, authoritarian parenting may foster the internalization of values stressing conformity and obedience, while permissive parenting may contribute to values associated with autonomy and self-expression. Inconsistencies in parenting styles may generate confusion for children, affecting the establishment of a cohesive set of personal values. Communication styles, cultural and religious influences, and negative experiences further contribute to the intricate relationship between parental styles and personal values. While parental approaches exert significant influence over values, individuals also retain the capacity for independent thought, enabling the development of values that may diverge from those imparted by their parents (Luitse, Wiebke, 2021). The interplay among these factors highlights the nuanced and dynamic nature of the association between parental styles and personal values.

Role of Personal Values in Adolescent Development

The role of personal values in adolescent development is significant and multifaceted. Personal values encompass an individual's core beliefs, principles, and ethical standards, which guide their thoughts, behaviour, and decision-making processes (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, Sapana, 2023). During adolescence, a period marked by self-discovery and identity formation, personal values play a crucial role in shaping a young person's sense of self and their place in the world. Adolescents often begin to question and explore their values as they navigate through various life experiences and interactions. These values can stem from cultural, familial, religious, and societal influences, as well as personal reflections (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020). As adolescents strive to establish their identities, their personal values serve as a foundation for understanding their priorities, aspirations, and the kind of person they want to become.

Moreover, personal values influence the choices adolescents make, impacting their relationships, academic pursuits, and involvement in their communities. For instance, an adolescent who values honesty and integrity may prioritize academic integrity and transparent communication in their interactions. On the other hand, an adolescent with a strong value for social justice might become actively engaged in advocacy and community service. It's important to note that personal values are not static; they can evolve and change over time as adolescents gain new experiences and insights (Sheldon and Elliot, 2018). These values also play a role in moral development, as adolescents grapple with complex ethical dilemmas and gradually refine their sense of right and wrong.

Personal values are integral to adolescent development as they contribute to the formation of identity, guide decision-making, and shape the path to adulthood. Understanding the interplay between personal values and development can provide valuable insights into the motivations and behaviour of adolescents (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020).

Personal values are a broad goal, varying in importance and underlying and guiding attitudes and behaviour. Personal values are formed in adolescence, which may affect long-term cognitions and behaviour. A previous study reported that universalistic values, which were classified as self-transcendence, were related to the creation of meaningfulness.

Religious Influence on Adolescent Values

Religious influence on adolescent values is a substantial and intricate aspect of their development. Adolescents often look to their religious beliefs and practices as a source of guidance and meaning, which can profoundly shape their values, attitudes, and behaviour (Yue, Shihong, Wenjuan, Yanfeng, Pingping & Y. Qingqiang, 2019).

Religious teachings provide a framework for understanding moral and ethical principles. Adolescents who are actively engaged in a religious community often absorb values that align with their faith's teachings (Juuso, 2021). For example, religions may emphasize compassion, kindness, honesty, and respect for others. These values can become integral to an adolescent's sense of right and wrong, influencing their interactions with peers, family, and society.

Religious rituals, such as prayer, meditation, or attending worship services, can foster a sense of connection to a higher purpose and a broader community. This connection can instill values related to humility, gratitude, and a sense of responsibility to contribute positively to society. At the same time, adolescents may also engage in a process of questioning and reinterpreting religious teachings as they develop their understanding of the world. This critical examination can lead to a more nuanced and personalized set of values. Some adolescents might align closely with their religious teachings, while others may integrate aspects of multiple belief systems or develop values that are more secular in nature (Francois & Rossetti, 2020).

Religious influence on adolescent values can extend to various domains of life, including decisions about friendships, relationships, career choices, and social justice advocacy. For instance, an adolescent influenced by their religion's emphasis on service to others might be drawn to volunteer work or community service projects (Juuso, 2021). It's important to recognize that the impact of religious influence on values varies from person to person and depends on factors such as the strength of religious upbringing, exposure to diverse perspectives, and personal introspection. Open communication between adolescents, their families, and their religious communities can provide a space for exploring and discussing how religious values intersect with their developing sense of self and values. Religious influence on adolescent values is a complex interplay between faith, personal reflection, and societal norms. It can play a significant role in shaping adolescents' moral compass, guiding their decisions, and contributing to their overall sense of purpose and identity (Bak-Coleman, 2021).

Adolescents' religious and spiritual development is influenced by many factors, including their parents, peers, institutions, and culture. These social influences can provide examples and feedback that shape how adolescence thinks about, practice, and experience religion and spirituality (Lilach and Shalom, 2022).

Religious influence on adolescent values plays a significant role in shaping the moral and ethical compass of young individuals. Pentecostal Churches, a subset of Christian denominations, are known for their strong emphasis on the Holy Spirit, spiritual gifts, and charismatic expressions of faith (Bak-Coleman, 2021). In these churches, the Holy Spirit is central to the believer's experience, with practices such as speaking in tongues and the manifestation of spiritual gifts being integral to their worship services. Pentecostal worship is characterized by its lively and expressive nature, often involving energetic music, clapping, dancing, and the use of spiritual gifts. Charismatic leadership within these churches guides congregants and is seen as essential for facilitating a deeper connection with God.

In addition to their charismatic worship, Pentecostal Churches (such as RCCG, DLBC, MFM, and Winners Chapel) are part of the broader evangelical movement, emphasizing evangelism and the spreading of the Gospel message. These churches vary in beliefs and practices, and they are often actively engaged in community outreach and social programs (Juuso, 2021). The eschatological beliefs within Pentecostalism, such as the expectation of the Second Coming of Christ and the rapture, are also important aspects of their theological framework. With millions of adherents worldwide, Pentecostalism has become a global movement, contributing to the diversity of religious influences on the values and beliefs of adolescents within their congregations. The impact of Pentecostalism on adolescents is profound, as it introduces them to a dynamic religious environment that fosters strong spiritual experiences, emphasizes the role of the Holy Spirit, and encourages active participation in charismatic worship and evangelical efforts. This influence can have a lasting impact on the values and worldviews of young individuals, shaping their understanding of faith and morality during the critical stage of adolescence (Bak-Coleman, Mark, Wolfram, Carl, Miquel, 2021).

Adolescent Development in Pentecostal Contexts

Adolescent development within Pentecostal contexts is a subject that reveals the interplay between religious beliefs and the psychosocial growth of young individuals. Pentecostalism, characterized by its emphasis on spiritual experiences, gifts of the Holy Spirit, and vibrant worship practices, contributes to a unique environment that shapes adolescents' cognitive, emotional, and social development (Lilach and Shalom, 2022).

Pentecostal beliefs often emphasize the transformative power of personal conversion experiences and the Holy Spirit's role in guiding one's life. These theological foundations can influence how adolescents perceive their identity, purpose, and moral compass. Adolescents within Pentecostal communities may experience a heightened sense of community and belonging, as well as opportunities for leadership and service within the church (Xiong, Hao, Mengmeng, Chengfu, Xin, Congshu & Yifan, 2021). These experiences can contribute to their self-esteem and identity formation.

At the same time, the distinct practices of Pentecostal worship and spiritual engagement might also introduce challenges related to the balance between religious commitments and the secular demands of adolescence. Negotiating these tensions can impact adolescents' psychological well-being and the development of their autonomy (Weber, 2017). The spiritual guidance and mentorship often available within Pentecostal contexts can play a significant role in shaping adolescents' values, relationships, and aspirations.

Adolescence development in Pentecostal contexts is a multifaceted process influenced by the unique religious dynamics and beliefs of Pentecostal Churches. Within these contexts, adolescents experience a distinct blend of spiritual and social influences that impact their growth and values. Pentecostalism, known for its emphasis on the Holy Spirit and spiritual gifts, shapes the religious landscape in which adolescents navigate their journey from childhood to adulthood (Syamsul, Sutama, Sekar, Prayitno &Waston, 2023).

In Pentecostal contexts, the evangelical mission is paramount, with a focus on spreading the message of the Gospel. Adolescents are actively involved in evangelism and community outreaches, which not only strengthens their faith but also nurtures a sense of purpose and responsibility towards others. This engagement provides opportunities for adolescents to apply their values in practical ways, contributing to their moral and ethical development (Lilach and Shallom, 2022).

Principles of Christian Values

Christian values are the principles that Christians believe are important in life. They are based on the teachings of Jesus Christ and the Bible. The term "Christian values" has a variety of meanings, and specific definitions can vary widely between denominations, geographical locations, and different schools of thought (Chloe, Sommerfield, Britta, 2020). However, some common Christian values include:

Love: Love is the foundation of all Christian values. It is expressed in many ways, including compassion, kindness, forgiveness, and mercy.

Justice: Justice is the belief that everyone deserves to be treated fairly, regardless of their race, gender, sexual orientation, or social status.

Peace: Peace is the absence of war and conflict. It is a goal that Christians strive for in their personal lives and in the world at large.

Hope: Hope is the belief that things will get better. It is a source of strength and resilience for Christians facing difficult times (Tascherrau-Dumouchel, Mathias, Stefan, 2022)

Forgiveness: Forgiveness is the ability to let go of anger and resentment towards someone who has wronged us. It is a way to heal ourselves and create a more peaceful world.

Honesty: Honesty is the practice of being truthful and forthright. It is a value that is essential for building trust and relationships.

Integrity: Integrity is the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles. It is a value that is essential for living a life of virtue.

Courage: Courage is the ability to face fear and danger. It is a value that is essential for standing up for what we believe in, even when it is difficult.

Perseverance: Perseverance is the ability to keep going in the face of challenges. It is a value that is essential for achieving our goals.

The Bible has long described Christian values as the Fruit of the Spirit, a list of nine attributes written by the Apostle Paul in his letter to the Galatians. These nine attributes are not exhaustive, but they are a good summary of the Christian values that are important to many Christians. These values can guide our thoughts, words, and actions, and they can help us to make better choices in our lives (Sheldon, Elliot, 2018).

"But the fruit of the Spirit is love, joy, peace, longsuffering, gentleness, goodness, faith, meekness, temperance: against such there is no law" (Galatians 5:22-23 KJV).

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory

Social learning theory explains the process of acquiring social behavior through observation and imitation of others. This theory posits that learning is a cognitive activity that happens within a social setting and can transpire simply through watching or receiving direct guidance, even when motor reproduction or direct rewards are absent.

Social Learning Theory, developed by psychologists, offers a comprehensive framework for understanding how individuals learn and shape their behaviour through observation and interaction. At its core, this theory asserts that people acquire new knowledge and behaviours not only through direct experiences but also by observing and imitating the actions and attitudes of others in their social environment (Lilach and Shallom, 2022). Role models, whether they are parents, peers, teachers, or influential figures from the media, play a pivotal role in molding behaviour, as individuals are more likely to emulate the actions of those they

admire. The first people children learn from in their social environments are their parents, so much knowledge and behaviours can be learned through the development of their personal values. As stated by Lilach and Shalom, (2022), this theory has found application in fields such as education, psychology, and criminology, offering insights into skill acquisition, behaviour change, and the development of personality traits through observation and interaction with others. Social learning theory is a psychological theory that states that people learn new behaviour by observing and imitating others. This theory was developed in the 1960s. The three main principles of social learning theory are:

Observational Learning: People learn new behaviour by observing others and then imitating what they see. This can happen even if the observer does not intend to learn the behaviour.

Reinforcement: People are more likely to imitate behaviour that is rewarded or reinforced.

Motivation: People are more likely to imitate behaviour that they are motivated to do. This motivation can come from internal factors, such as a desire to learn something new, or from external factors, such as a desire to be liked or accepted by others (Pearce, Uecker, Melinder, 2019).

Social learning theory is a powerful tool for understanding how people learn new behaviour. It can be used to explain a wide range of behaviour, from simple everyday activities to complex social behavior (Lilach and Shalom, 2023). Social learning theory can be applied to real-life situations:

- A child who sees their parents arguing may learn to argue themselves.
- A student who sees their teacher being rewarded for good behaviour may be more likely to behave ways similarly.
- A person who is motivated to lose weight may imitate the behaviour of someone who is already thin.

Social learning theory can be a helpful tool for parents, teachers, and other professionals who work with children and adolescents. By understanding how social learning works, they can create environments that encourage positive behaviour and discourage negative behavior (Lilach and Shalom, 2023).

Development Theory/ Modelling Behaviour

This concept involves the initial step of observation, where individuals closely watch the behaviour or skills displayed by others in different contexts, ranging from family and school to the workplace and media (Weber, 2017). Crucially, people tend to identify with the individuals they observe, particularly if these role models possess qualities or characteristics that the observer admires. The context in which the behaviour is observed and cultural and social factors also contribute to the decision of whether to model a particular behaviour. Role models, which can be parents, teachers, peers, or public figures, are pivotal in shaping an individual's behaviours and values. Modeling behaviour is a pervasive and influential process that occurs throughout an individual's life, impacting their development, learning, and adaptation of new behaviours within various settings and social contexts (Priti, Shilpa, Shagufta, and Sapan, 2023). Understanding these principles is essential for educators, parents, and individuals seeking to guide and influence the behaviours and values of others.

Methodology

The study employs a descriptive survey design method, using a questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 200 adolescents. The study design involves the random selection of a sample

of 50 Adolescents from each selected Pentecostal church in Ede and collecting data on their parental styles, personal values, and how the parental styles and religious environment influence them. The population of this study consists of 950 **adolescents aged between 12 and 21 years** in the selected Pentecostal Churches in Ede (namely, Redeemed Christian Church of God, Osun Province 9; Deeper Christian Life Ministries, aka Deeper Life Bible Church; Winners Chapel; And Mountain of Fire and Miracle Ministries aka MFM).

Findings

Findings reveal that each parent of the respondents exhibits parenting styles within the four styles focused on by the researchers but with significant diversity in the perceived parenting approaches within these religious communities. Each denomination exhibits distinct patterns of parenting styles among its members.

One striking observation is the prevalence of uninvolved parenting, particularly prominent within the Deeper Life Bible Church (DLBC) denomination, where most respondents perceive their parents as adopting this style. This finding raises concerns about the level of parental engagement and involvement within DLBC families. What could have been the cause? Could it be that they are occupied with too many religious activities, or could it be they believe that the children are getting enough training/teaching from the church, and so on and so forth? This highlights a potential area for further exploration and intervention.

The findings from responses to open-ended questions about the influence of the religious environment in Pentecostal churches on the development of personal values in adolescents reveal several key insights. First and foremost, the majority of respondents concur that the religious environment in Pentecostal churches holds a significant influence on their personal values, extending its impact beyond that of parental styles. Several factors contribute to this influence, encompassing doctrinal teachings, peer interactions, participation in youth programs, engagement in religious practices, the presence of role models, involvement in community service, a sense of purpose, encouragement of personal faith, and the establishment of a strong moral foundation.

The advantages of this influence are numerous, as adolescents exposed to the religious environment often develop strong moral and ethical values. They also experience spiritual growth, which can provide them with a profound sense of solace, purpose, and belonging. Furthermore, these adolescents tend to develop resilience in the face of adversity and engage in social responsibility, along with finding support and guidance from peer groups formed within the religious community.

Conclusion

Based on the findings drawn from responses to open-ended questions regarding the influence of the religious environment in Pentecostal churches on the development of personal values in adolescents, this study arrives at a conclusion that reflects the nuanced nature of this process (K. Edwards & M. Edwards. 2022). These findings have provided valuable insights into the multifaceted influence of religious environments and adolescent values, shedding light on both the advantages and drawbacks of such influences.

It is evident from the responses that the majority of adolescents in Pentecostal churches acknowledge the significant role the religious environment plays in shaping their personal values, extending its impact beyond the sphere of parental guidance (May & Robbins 2017). This influence is achieved through a combination of factors, including the church's doctrinal

teachings, the peer interactions fostered within the religious community, participation in youth programs, engagement in religious practices, the guidance of role models and mentors, involvement in community service, a sense of purpose, encouragement of personal faith, and the establishment of a strong moral foundation. The advantages of this influence are manifold, as it often leads adolescents to develop strong moral and ethical values, experience spiritual growth, find solace and purpose, and build resilience in the face of adversity (Yasuma, Watanabe, Iida, Nishi, & Kawakami, 2019). Moreover, it encourages social responsibility, offers a support network, and provides moral guidance, empowering adolescents with a sense of self-confidence and personal agency.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Young parents should take time to study various child upbringing and parental styles and be conscious of the ones they imbibe in nurturing their children and adolescents because they play vital roles in the development of their personal values.
2. Religious leaders and institutions in Pentecostal churches should consider promoting inclusivity and diversity within their congregations. This includes embracing individuals with varying beliefs, backgrounds, and lifestyles. Such an approach can mitigate potential drawbacks associated with religious rigidity and intolerance, as identified in the study (Juuso, 2021). Religious communities should continue to invest in youth empowerment programs that encourage adolescents to develop a strong sense of personal agency and self-confidence. These programs can play a significant role in nurturing adolescents' personal values in a positive and empowering manner (Juuso, 2021).
3. Encourage interfaith and interdenominational dialogues and events to facilitate a broader understanding of diverse religious beliefs and values. This may help reduce social isolation and promote tolerance and respect among adolescents with different religious backgrounds (Bak-Coleman, Mark, Wolfram, Carl, Miquel, 2021).
4. Religious institutions should recognize the importance of mental health and emotional well-being among their members, including adolescents. They can provide resources and support for individuals who may be dealing with mental health challenges and ensure that their congregations are places where individuals feel safe seeking help and guidance (Juuso, 2021).

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Jethro's Counsels in Exodus 18:17-23: Lessons for Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis

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Abstract

Counselling is a therapeutic measure through the use of communication skills. In the Old Testament, counselling is used as a medium to helping someone in distress, proffer solutions and give necessary insights to solving problems. Moses led the children of Israel out of Egypt without an administrative plan of overseeing the large congregation of the Israelites community. The study examined Jethro's counsel to Moses in Exodus 18:17-23 and lessons for Nigerian Pentecostal Church Leaders in. The workloads on Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis are enormous, and as a result pose threat to their health, effective church administration and wellbeing as Church Leaders. The study adopted exegetical, historical and participatory observation methods. It was discovered that Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis engage in several activities such as the Church weekly services and the Sunday services. They also chair and oversee virtually all units in the Church, and hold important leadership position among other Christian fellowship in their neighbourhoods. Therefore, the study recommended that the Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church leaders in Ilorin Metropolis should engage in division of labour among members for effective church administration and reduction in health hazard.

Keywords: Exodus 18:17-23, Ilorin Metropolis, Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders, Jethro's Counsel, Moses

Introduction

The history of the children of Israel remains at the core viewpoint of biblical history and the world at large. This owes to the premises that the Israelites were God's chosen people through whom God's divine purpose (the redemptive plan) was brought to fulfilment thus affording the biblical Israel the pride of place in biblical times and the history of the modern Christianity. The Pentateuch which was the Greek version of the Torah (Law) becomes a reference since many centuries till now. These books also pictured the origin of human leadership and the loopholes in the supposed perfect man's administration. It can be said that, leadership trait and tendency was an in-built capacity since man's creation. This finds expression in the use of the word *radah* in Genesis 1:26-28 account and which according to Brown-Driver-Briggs (n.d.) means to rule or have dominion.

The narrative of Israelites history continues in the land of slavery, Egypt. Moses was introduced as God's deliverer of his people from the Egyptian bondage. Traces of his selection can be seen from the time of his birth as he was miraculously saved from the great massacre of the bloody Pharaoh (Exodus 1:22-2:1-8) and by adoption became an Egyptian prince down to

the time of his first Sinaitic experience (Exo. 3). Moses elopement to Midian was to save his life from the looming destruction and at there he met the priest, Jethro, through his daughters. He was later engaged with Zipporah in marriage (Exo. 2:20-21). Jethro's involvement in Moses' life began from the marriage with his daughter thus creating an unending relationship with the potential deliverer and leader of the Israelites.

It is important to recall that seventy people of the household of Jacob entered the land of Egypt (Gen. 46:27; Exo. 1:5). At their exodus, there were about six hundred men on foot excluding the women and the children (Exo. 12:37). Though biblical scholars such as Jeff after his mathematical approach summarized that, approximately 6,000 individuals travelled from Egypt to Mt. Sinai (Jeff, n.d.). Redford (1992) opined that since the 600,000 men were accounted for in the Exodus account, he added that the 600,000 plus wives, children, the elderly, and the "mixed multitude" of non-Israelites would have numbered some 2 to 2.5 million. The thrust of this paper is not to argue the particular number of departed Israelites but to point out a drastic shift in their number from the time of Jacob to Moses which calls for adoption of a broader pattern of administration different from the small patriarchal system used during the time of Abraham, Isaac and Jacob to a wider administrative pattern.

Moses was relatively a novice in the governance of the people, thus the observation and conclusion of Jethro which ultimately led to his counsel. Counselling according to Francis (1993) is a relationship between a professionally trained, competent counsellor and an individual seeking help in gaining greater self-understanding and improved decision making and behaviour changing skills for problem resolution and developmental growth. The view of Francis is apt to the role of Jethro's in Mosaic administration, paving way for understanding an administrative process through engaging others, in order to ensure safety of the leader and peace in the wider community. Moses embraced Jethro's counsels as identified in Exodus 18:17-23 and as he continues in his voyage to the promise land, he ensured equal representation and division of labour among the people. Church activities today are enormous and cannot be executed by a single person (pastor), thus, the need to diversify roles among members of the congregation. It is important to state that as counselling is a key to development and progress (Psalm 1:1), it can also be a tool to destruction (1 Kg. 13:18-19). Therefore, is it right to say that Nigerian Pentecostal Indigenous Church Leaders must oversee every department in the church? Is Jethro's counsel to Moses applicable to the Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis? Should church administration be monopolised? All these are buttressed under, historical background of Exodus 18, Pentecostalism in Nigeria: The Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Churches, exegetical analysis of Exodus 18:17-23, lessons for Nigerian indigenous Pentecostal church leaders in Ilorin Metropolis and conclusion.

Historical Background of Exodus 18

Exodus literarily means 'going out' or departure. The word itself was adopted into English (via Latin) from Greek ἐξοδος, which literally means a way out, a going out; a going out, departure, the exodus, Hebrew 11:22; met. a departure from life, decease, death, Luke 9:31; 2 Peter 1:15 (Bill Mounce, n.d.). The Greek word was formed by combining the prefix *ex-* (meaning 'out of') and *hodos*, 'road' or 'way' (*Merriam Webster Dictionary*, n.d.) Jamieson et al (1871) commented that Exodus derives its name from its being occupied principally with a relation of the exit of the Children of Israel from Egypt and the unfolding events succeeding their escape. Umaru (2023) writes:

Exodus was written down historically to preserve the stories of how the Israelites became enslaved in Egypt, their liberation, and their preservation in the Sinai desert. Theologically, the book's primary goal is divine self-disclosure because God has revealed Himself to Israel as Yahweh (Exo. 6:2-3), a name that means that Yahweh, the God of the Hebrews, will take Israel for His people and will be their God. God has not only remembered His 240 covenant promises to the Hebrew Patriarch (Exo. 6:7).

The above excerpt resonates the importance of Exodus account. Thus, it is crucial to state that the book of Exodus was a compendium that gives a link to the Israelites who lived in Egypt and the Israelites who lived in Canaan. This is not to say that there are two Israelites rather it is affirmed that the history of the Canaanite' Israelites can be traced to the Egyptian bondage, therefore, establishing the salvific work of God through the Exodus account (Boaheng, 2021).

The chapter clearly expressed a moment of succeeding their deliverance from Egypt. Meyer (2005) quoted Carpenter that the Chapter 18 introduces the problem of community organization and adjudication. At the same time, it is a transitional chapter; as an epilogue to chapters 1-17 and a prologue to chapters 19-40, it is thus a bridge between the exodus story and the Sinai event. *Enduring word* (n.d.) writes:

Jethro, the priest of Midian, Moses' father-in-law, heard of all that God had done for Moses and for Israel His people: The greatness of God's work through Moses and for the people of Israel became known to surrounding peoples, especially those with an interest in Moses as Jethro. Jethro was the priest of Midian – likely a descendant of one of Abraham's other children through Keturah named Midian (Genesis 25:1-2). Because of this connection with Abraham, we have good reason to believe he was a true priest and worshipped the true God.

The foregoing shows a connection of Moses with the priest of Midian and also went further to trace the origin of the Midianites to Abraham, establishing an ancestral origin with people of Israel. It is important to state that, Moses first elopement from Egypt to Midian (Exo. 2:15) serves as a bedrock for the continuity of the relationship seen in Exodus 18. The initial was an escape from death while the later was mark of total deliverance and success of Moses and the entire congregation of Israelites from Egypt, therefore, this call for celebration. Henry (2010) commented that Jethro came to rejoice with Moses in happiness of Israel, and to bring his wife and children to him. Moses must have his family with him (Exo. 18:1-6), that while he ruled the church of God, he might set a good example in family (1 Tim 3:5).

The conversion between Moses and Jethro does not only show that they were in-laws but it also established the cordiality between both personalities. Verse 7-12 showcased the conversion concerning God's wondrous works. Henry (2010) sharply noted that Jethro not only rejoiced in the honour done to his son-in-law, but in all the goodness done to Israel. Non-Israelites were more affected with the favours God had showed to Israel, than many were who received them. The initial government collapsed (Pharaoh's government) and the New Government (Theocracy) was established under the leadership of Moses.

Pentecostalism in Nigeria: The Indigenous Pentecostal Churches

Adesayan noted that the term "Pentecostal" is from the Greek word which may refer to the modern charismatic reformation movement with a distinctive theology of the Spirit that gives doctrinal priority to the practice of spiritual gifts of tongues. Ogidiolu (2019) remarked that the term Pentecost grammatically is a word from Greek language. The word according to him

is a compound word of two words: *pente* and *cost* which means fifth or fifty and celebration respectively. He further buttressed that, it is a feast of the Jews slated for fiftieth day after the Passover feast. O' Connor proposed a definition for the term Pentecostalism. The term Pentecostalism according to him means:

A movement of Christian renewal typified by the first Christian Pentecost when the Holy Spirit descending upon the fearful Apostles, transformed them into bold, ardent and convincing evangelists. It is characterized by the reappearance of the charisma of glossolalia, healing, miracles etc. (O' Connor, 1993).

From the submission of O' Connor, it can be deduced that the Holy Spirit enables, transforms and strengthens the feeble minded and wearied soul into a powerful, Spirit-filled, energized and determined personality of the apostles. Many Pentecostal Churches such as Living Faith, the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Powerful Bible Church, Mountain of Fire, Deeper Life Bible Church just a mention a few attested to the manifestation of the Holy Spirit before the eventual launching out of the evangelistic works carried out by the founders of these aforementioned church and their members. Hence the place of Holy in the founding of Pentecostal Churches is incontestable.

The Indigenous Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria such as Christ Apostolic Church, Cherubim and Seraphim, Celestial Church of Christ, and Church of the Lord believes in the Holy Spirit origin. Thus, Ayegboyin and Ishola (2013) referred these Churches as *Ijo Emi* (spiritual churches), where Holy Spirit is believed to feature prominently in their worship as he manifests through visions, interpretation of dreams, ecstatic behaviour and prophetic utterances. Oshitelu (2007) asserted that the rise of indigenous churches that could be regarded as forerunners of African Pentecostalism also arose from a number of other factors among which are the mode of organization in the mission churches –Anglican, Methodist and Baptist by foreign leaders who were imposed on the Africans. This was dictatorial attitude. The Africans were not allowed to lead organize the affairs of their churches. The Europeans treated the Africans as if they had no ability whatsoever to rule. They undermined their integrity.

The earliest origin of indigenous churches in Nigeria can be traced as far back as the 1918 in the St. Anglican Saviour Church, Ijebu-Ode with a group of prayer warriors called 'Diamond Stone'. This group eventually metamorphose into Christ Apostolic Church in 1943 (Oshun, 1981). Ayegboyin and Ishola (2013) provided a historical background of the origin of other indigenous churches such as Cherubim and Seraphim founded in 1925 as a prayer group which started in Lagos; Church of the Lord started with only ten people who attended its inauguration at Ogere in 1930; and Celestial Church of Christ founded in 1947.

It was observed that among these indigenous Churches in Ilorin Metropolis, Church leaders are usually occupied with different activities which include mid-week services and Sunday services. These churches are also fond of organising constant revivals which may tarry for weeks and possibly months. Due to this, the health conditions of these church leaders are not usually put into consideration. The results of these numerous church activities often lead to health challenges, sudden breakdown, ineffective church administration and mass movement of the youths from these churches to other neo-Pentecostal churches where youth are prioritised in the church administration.

Exegetical Analysis of Exodus 18:17-23

Verses 17-18: Moses' father-in-law replied, "What you are doing is not good." Jethro first comment after he had observed Mosaic leadership style was to make a remark that may seem negative to the audience but on the critical look of his statement, it portrayed good intention rather than the negative tone. Gill (n.d.) buttressed that the statement "what you are doing is not good". The Hebrew expression טוב לא (lo tob) which literally translated to mean "not good" does not mean that it was not morally good, or that it was morally evil; for it was certainly a good thing to inquire of the mind and will of God for the people, and to hear and decide matters in controversy between them, and do justice to both parties; but it was not good for the health of Moses; it was not commodious and convenient for him; it was not for his bodily welfare; it was too much for him, as he explains himself in the next verse. Ellicot (n.d.) further buttressed on the verse 17 that Moses practice was unadvisable, both on his own account and on theirs. To keep suitors waiting all day, and perhaps finally dismiss them without their turn having come, was not fair upon them. The **verse 18** shows clearly Jethro's intention on the use of טוב לא in the verse 17. The **verse 18** shows a parallelism which is a common characteristic of Hebrew Poetry. תִּבּוֹל (*tibbol*) which is translated as 'will wear yourselves out' was expatiated in the parallel lines "the work is too heavy for you; you cannot handle it alone." This, however, portrays a coherent in the verses. According to Meyers (2005) the line of **verse 18** is a threefold declaration that portrayed that Moses caseload is too large.

Verse 19-21: The verse opens with the counselling session of Jethro. "Listen now to me and I will give you some advice (NIV)," indicate the tone of a counsellor and his counselee, which is common among in Israelites community; between God and man and vice versa (Prov. 8:32; Eze. 3:10; Job 37:14; Mt. 11:15). The first attention of the verse is a call to attention and consideration that is mostly needed between a father and his son, like the children of Israel is to God. Henry (2010) noted that Jethro thought the task was too much for Moses to undertake alone; also, it would make the administration of justice tiresome to the people. There may be over-doing even in well-doing. According to Ryken and Hughes (2005) the initial of the verse shows that Jethro was preserving the role of the prophet. "...may God be with you" according to Matthew (n.d.), shows that a certain level of assurance which alleviate fears and doubt from His concept about God. He further went on to say that God is a God of order, and loves order; and he is a God of mercy, and would not have you destroy yourself in his work. Or it may be taken for a prayer, and God be with you, i.e. bless and assist thee therein.

Barnes (n.d) noted that **verse 20** "and you shall teach them the statutes and the decisions, and make them know the way in which they must walk and what they must do" (Revised Standard Version). The Hebrew word is emphatic, and signifies "enlightenment." The text gives four distinct points: the "ordinances," or specific enactments; "the laws," or general regulations," the way," the general course of duty; "the works," each specific act. **Verse 21** Keil and Delitzsch (n.d.) also went further to affirm that Moses was to select able men (לְיָדָי אַנְשֵׁי חַיִּיל) 'anšê hayil –men of moral strength, 1 Kings 1:52). The characters of the able men are, God-fearing, truthful and unselfish (gain-hating). The word rulers or overseers used in this passage is same as the one used in Deuteronomy 1:15 rendered 'captains' and not to be seen as the word rendered 'ruler' in Exodus 16:22. The word שָׂר (*sar*), when followed by 'of thousands', 'hundreds' is used only in connection with the army, being then rendered 'captain' (1 Samuel 8:12, 2 Kings 1:9: 'captains of tens,' however, occurs only here and Deuteronomy 1:15) (Cambridge Bible for Schools, n.d.).

Verse 22-23: The keywords of **verse 22** can be found in the expressions of *הַדָּבָר הַקָּטָן וְהַגָּדוֹל* (*haqqaton haggadol haddabar*). The word *קָטָן* (*qaton*) means “small” or “minor” (Brown-Driver-Briggs, n.d.). Jethro suggests (*qaton dabar*) can be settled by appointed able men. It will also afford Moses the avenue to focus on (*haggadol dabar*) that require his urgent attention and wisdom. The Hebrew word *דָּבָר* (*dabar*) can mean both “thing” and “matter,” and it is used here to refer to legal matters or disputes. Jethro’s advice shows that not all matters require Moses’ direct attention (Gary, n.d.). **Verse 23** Jethro ended his counseling thus, *שְׁלוֹמֵךָ אֵינִי מְקַמֵּן עַל-הַיְהוָה מִהֵנָּה כָּל-יָגַם עָמְדוֹ וַיִּכְלַתְתָּ בְּאֵלֹהֵי וְצִוְיָהּ תַעֲשֶׂה הַזֶּה הַדָּבָר אֶת-אֵם אֱלֹהִים: אֵינִי מְקַמֵּן עַל-הַיְהוָה מִהֵנָּה כָּל-יָגַם עָמְדוֹ וַיִּכְלַתְתָּ בְּאֵלֹהֵי וְצִוְיָהּ תַעֲשֶׂה הַזֶּה הַדָּבָר אֶת-אֵם אֱלֹהִים* (*im et- haddabar hazzeh ta’she wesiweka elohim weyakalit amod wegam kal- haam hazzeh ‘al- meqomow yabo besaliwm*). The phrase, (*im elohim wesiweka*) indicates Jethro’s counsel is subjected to God’s commands. Although Jethro is a priest to God, he did not fully appreciate or understand all the God was able to do. So, he is trying not to be arrogant here, and saying, “Listen, this is your only solution” (Gary, n.d.).

Lessons for Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis

There are lessons to be learnt by the Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church leaders in Ilorin Metropolis from the episode of Jethro and Moses in Exodus 18:17-23. Jethro was a good observer, listener and presenter. He observed the situation (Exo. 18:14a), listened to Moses’ explanations (verse 15) and presented his counsel in a godly way (verses 19-23). These three attributes are highly commendable for Church leaders who would want to give counsel to counselees. In applying the lessons from Exodus 18:17-23, Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church leaders can create an environment where the Gospel is effectively shared, individuals are nurtured and empowered, and the church contributes positively to the spiritual and social landscape of the nation. By embracing these principles, the Nigerian church can play a transformative role and serve as a beacon of light and hope in a diverse and dynamic society. Division of roles and tasks-sharing is identified in the passage. Jethro’s counsel to Moses on task-sharing became a new form of Israelites policy even as they continue under the theocratic governance. The church today is made up of different people and functions that cannot be executed by an individual thus the need for concerted efforts by the make-up of the church. The pastor cannot be alone by himself the choir, usher, elder, Sunday school teacher, keyboardist and congregation. Therefore, it is pertinent to say that, church leaders must designate these functions to various members of their churches in order to ensure smooth service running. Jethro gave a prudent counsel as to the division of labour (verse 21-22) and universal experience in the Church and State has attested the soundness and advantages of the principle (Jameison et al., 1871).

Excessive tasks are hazardous to the health. Jethro’s counsel showcases one with great concern about health issue. As a priest of Midian who must have served in that capacity for many years even before Moses’ call, must have been aware of the health danger involve in Moses administrative policy hence call his attention to it. Church leaders must know and accept the fact that no one is indispensable. This means that, there is always a replacement for a person who is no longer active hence the need to be health conscious while in the service to God.

Appointment criteria must be defined and re-defined. The way church appointments are characterized by favouritism, nepotism, tribalism and affluence. Less emphasis is placed righteousness, infill of the Holy Spirit, wisdom and good ambassador of God through obedience to His words. Jethro’s criteria for selection are godly approach which will enable continuity between God and the Israelites communities. Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal church leaders should teach God’s decrees and instructions, way to congregation and how

they are to behave. In addition, selected appointees should fear God, be trustworthy and hate dishonest gain. In a society often contending with issues of corruption and ethical challenges, the church has the responsibility to model the values it preaches.

Another important lesson to learn for the Jethro's counsel to Moses is the encouragement of mentoring. Tunji (2018) opines that mentoring produces leaders that ensure steadiness and preserve the culture and values of the institution because such leaders have not only been taught but also groomed and nurtured. They rise on the shoulders of their predecessors, and therefore are far more effective and visionary in administration. Thus, he further warned against godfatherism which is one of the menaces hindering church progress and effective leadership. Uroko (2020) lamented that the issue of capturing in Nigerian church has deteriorated. He stated that "unfortunately, mentorship has really gone sour amongst the pastoral ministry in Nigeria. Mentorship among Christian ministers in Nigeria is marred by many accusations and counter accusations". It is important to note that Nigeria Indigenous church leaders should encourage building capacities through raising mentees who will be useful in church administration.

Jethro's counsel is suitable for progress positioning, change desiring and goal-oriented venture. Nigerian church leaders can benefit from engaging in cross-cultural and interdenominational dialogue, gaining insights from other leaders, both within and beyond their nation's borders. Also, every counsel must be godly and God's command. Jethro started with '...listen now to me' (verse 19) which shows that the counsel he was about to give is from his own perspective, perhaps an experience and concluded in verse 23 'if you do this and **God so commands...**' Moses needs to understand that what is superior to his counsel is God's instruction. Leaders of different capacities in Church must be cautious of counsel they receive and apply. All counsel must be godly and not contradict God's instruction hence the need to consult God before every act is taken.

Conclusion

Jethro's contribution to Mosaic leadership as revealed in Exo. 18:17-23 is relevant to Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal church leaders in Ilorin Metropolis for effective health and wellbeing, encouragement of participation of Church members in church services and assignments, Church administration, and indeed for leaders in different segments in the society. These verses underscore the importance of effective leadership, job sharing, and the establishment of a structured and accountable system. In Jethro's suggestion, Moses cannot be the burden bearer alone as the Journey ahead is far and the assignment is tedious thus carrying the responsibilities alone will not only affect the health of Moses but also makes him to be ineffective. In a multi-church enterprise society like Nigeria where mega Churches are growing rapidly, the need for delegation of responsibility will not only create more chances for their successes but will also guarantee long life and foster unity within the church.

Recommendations

1. Division of responsibilities should be encouraged in among the Nigerian Pentecostal churches in Osun State in order to avert health hazard and promote church development
2. Mechanics such as organized system of leadership should be put in place in order to ensure good decision-making and conflict resolution within the ambit of the Church.

3. Selection for criteria into Church positions such as Deacon/Deaconess, Choir master, Sunday school teacher, Church secretary, Heads of Units amongst others should be defined and adhered. Pentecostal Church leaders must avoid all means of manipulation and favouritism in selection. This may jeopardise church growth and development.
4. The study also recommends that elites in the church should carefully encourage their Church leaders in order to avoid misunderstanding. For instance, in a situation where a church leader is illiterate, members should encourage such leader to enrol into a seminary for basic theological studies and administration. This may be enhanced by giving full or partial sponsorship to the leader with the aim that upon the completion of the programme, such leader would be able to apply the knowledge and administrative skills learnt in during the course of the programme.
5. In correcting an autocratic leader, a person giving such leader a counsel must first be humbled and ask for God's wisdom in what to say and how to present the case before the leader.
6. Godly elders in the church should be consulted before approaching any administrative issue. From a godly counsel, a proper recommendation may be given.
7. Pentecostal Church leaders must also acknowledge that a church is a civil society yet having Christ as its head. Therefore, leaders should also seek God like Solomon did in 1 Kg, 3:1-4 and got a blank cheque which enabled him to ask God for wisdom.

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Strategies for Promoting Marital Cohesion and National Security in Nigeria

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Abstract

Challenges are inevitable either in micro or macro environments. Marriage is the foundational relationship for all of society, therefore, all other relationships in society stem from the father-mother relationship, and these other relationships thrive most if that father-mother relationship is simultaneously a close and closed husband- wife relationship. Good marriages are the bedrock of strong societies, for they are the foundations of strong families. Marriage contains the five basic institutions, all the basic tasks of society: family, church, school, marketplace and government. These fundamental tasks, if well done in unity between father and mother, make for a very good marriage and peaceful co-existence in the society and nation at large. Within a family built on such a marriage, the child gradually learns to value and perform these five fundamental tasks of every competent adult and of every functional society. Marital cohesion refers to the degree of connectedness, togetherness, and emotional bonding between marital partners. Cohesion in marriages is related to positive relationship qualities, including greater relationship satisfaction and lower hostility between partners. Also, marital cohesion is positively related to individual well-being, such as higher levels of self-esteem. Moreover, national security is commonly used to mean safety from danger and protection from internal, external attack or infiltration. This usage is tied on the apron string of defense and security forces. The cold war era gave the highest currency to the conventional security doctrine that rested on the assumption that only a strong military can effectively deter attacks and threats of force (Chris, 1997). On the contrary, (John, 1991) conceives security in terms of arms, armaments, and military personnel. He posits that security is the relative freedom from harmful threats. In the post-cold war period, the concept of security has attracted a new thinking by contemporary scholars who condemned the militaristic thought of security insisting on the concepts of rehabilitation, transformation and expansion. This study focused on providing strategies to promote marital cohesion and national security.

Keywords: Strategies, marital cohesion, national security, Nigeria

Introduction

Marriage is a globally accepted practice and it means different things to different people even among the scholars. Its understanding varies in every context based on the social and religious practices of the society. Historically marriage is God's idea and an institution established by Him. Marriage is seen as a social institution as there are rules, rights and

responsibilities surrounding marriage because it is seen as the stabilizing force within the societies (Seccombe, 2008). Marriage is one of the most important institutions affecting people's life and well-being. Marital institutions regulate sexual relations and encourage commitment among spouses. This commitment has positive effects, for instance on spouses' health and their earnings on the labor market (Stutxer & Frey, 2005). Marriage and family sociologically signify the stage of greater social advancement. It is indicative of man's entry into the world of emotion and feeling, harmony and culture (Mondal, 2014). Hence, marriage provides an adventure playground for couples and their ability to adjust paves the way for a successful marriage. Marriage has been defined as an institution which creates new social relationships and reciprocal rights among the spouses. As a personal relationship, marriage is deeply meaningful to the individuals involved although "meaningful" is conceptualized differently within social, historical and cultural contexts.

Marriage is not the outcome of a human pervert; it is the outcome of a divine arrangement. God has specifications for the marriage correlation. To attempt to build a marriage without following God's mandate is to invite failure. However, man today is interfering with God's intention and purpose for marriage in so many ways. Until marriage is understood from God's point of view, many marriages will not fulfill its purpose and will eventually experience break-down. If the factors responsible for the rapid and high rate of break-down of marriage and its effects on society are understood by couples, many marriages will be saved.

Challenges in marriage have been perceived as misunderstanding between a man and a woman that can lead to separation, dissolution or divorce of their marriage. Different factors that vary from threat from in-laws, sexual intercourse, delay in child bearing, environmental factors, finance, infidelity and the like are responsible for marital challenges. The reasons for marrying are threefold: fidelity, procreation, and the fulfilling of a sacred obligation. If one did not have the spiritual strength or the economic resources to commit oneself to a fully devout life of celibacy, one could still choose faithfulness and a contained concupiscence. This was the next best thing to celibacy, and a proper and fitting gift of one's self to God. Good marriages are the bedrock of strong societies, for they are the foundations of strong families. The general social survey showed that adults who grew up living with both biological parents experience higher levels of marital happiness. As life expectancy of married persons has increased significantly, divorce rates have skyrocketed since the Victorian era to a new plateau, where almost half of all marriages are expected to end in divorce (Gregorio, 2013: 48-50). Hence, this paper proffers different strategies to curb marital challenges/concerns for cohesion and national security.

Meaning of Marital Challenges

Challenges are a natural phenomenon and it is inevitable in human relationships. It occurs in marriage, family, ministry, communities and organizations. From the Bible point of view, marriage has been grappling with this problem of conflict. The present state of homes depends on the number of challenges it had experienced in the past. In recent times we have witnessed the greatest proliferation of marriages in challenges. It is not possible to rule out conflict in human relationships and the family being an organization where people of different backgrounds, cultures and languages come together as husband and wife. The two most common responses to challenges are to ignore it and let it go away or handle it badly. All managed challenges on the other hand are good for our marriages (Imobighe, 2003: 17-19).

Marital challenges are perceived as disagreement between couples from the fact that they differ in status, goals or perception. In other words, it is argued that challenges are the opposite of cooperation. This is so because marital challenges imply a process whereby couples see their interests as mutually incompatible, whereas in co-operative processes the parties see their interest as mutually supportive. "Conflict" could replace "Challenges" because a family in conflict is also a family facing challenges. Challenges connotes to "strike together" whenever two or more people pursue mutually exclusive goods or whenever one person's needs collide with another, challenges result (Odukoya, 2012: 105-107). Challenges are indispensable in human society, it occurs between two or more persons, families, marriages and communities, church, government and organization. Marital challenges have the strength to retard progress, growth, development and unity in the society. Marital challenges also mean deep disagreement between husband and wife that could lead to dissolution, separation or collapse of marriage. It is recognized as a struggle or contest between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values or goals. Incompatibility in marital challenges could bring about individual needs, interests, values, objectives and aims (Amadi-Nche, 2018: 1, 3).

Causes of Marital Challenges in Nigeria

Marital concerns could originate from different sources, some of which could be psychological or psychosomatic in nature. It is retorted that more and more marriages run into marital challenges and eventually pack up because one partner has a borderline personality disorder such as narcissist, antisocial, psychopathic personality disorders (Edward, 1974: 80-82). The underlisted are some of the most prominent causes of marital challenges in Nigeria:

Couple's Incompatibility: Incompatibility has been one of the major causes of marital challenges amidst husband and wife, and this has been generating a lot of issues in the public. To solve this problem, husband and wife should ensure their compatibility before engaging or involving themselves in any marital matters or unending marital journey. This will help to reduce the high rate of divorce caused by this factor and also a tool for cohesion in our society.

Sexual Dissatisfaction: Poor sexual-satisfaction on the part of a married partner may spice up marital challenges in the union if not properly and timely detected and managed. It could lead to extramarital sexual affairs, a situation that on its own leads to disaffection and distrust among couples. When either of the parties is not sexually satisfied, there is the tendency for such to lead to marital challenges among the couple. Oftentimes such predicament tends to be difficult to overcome and manage among the couple and escalate to become unresolved marital challenges that could lead to dissolution or breakage of the home (Wheeler-Reed 50, 51). Sexual dissatisfaction may be as a result of couple mis-orientation about sex, hatred for sex, weak erection by the husband, lack of sexual interest by the wife, stress from both partners or due to fatigue or strenuous office work. If the aforementioned factors are not well managed by the couple, it will lead to marital dishonesty, insecurity, dissatisfactions at all levels and disunity among the couple. In essence, husband and wife are expected to find a solution to their sexual dissatisfaction which may demand medical attention or special treatment or special counselling.

Problems Emanating from In-Laws, Friends and Relatives: Some men/women often quarrel with spouses whose interests are only on the betterment of their own relations. Trends bordering on in-laws, friends, and relatives constitute a point that never seems to get out of style. Experiences over years and across many cultures and climes have shown that mothers-

in-law are culprits for many family challenges. Couples should learn how to put in-laws, relatives and friends in their proper place, outside the sanity of their homes.

Disrespect among Couples: Mutual respect for one's spouse is critical for marital union sustenance and lack of it is a challenging factor capable of rocking even the strongest marital foundation of hitherto blissful homes. Respect and love are reciprocal variables in every marital union and as such, a spouse owes it an obligation to respect and love his/her marriage partner, failure which fans the embers of marital discord and discontent (Keil 45, 46).

Financial Difficulties: Money is one area where marriages are tested today without exception. Whether you are rich or poor, educated or uneducated, you will have to deal with the financial demon that is out to break the home. For the man that refuses to work or that is finding it difficult to get a well-paying job, to the wife that earns much more than the husband, to a spouse that won't cut coat according to pocket size, to a family carrying too much financial responsibilities from relatives and the ones that have poor financial planning skills. Men turn to crime to satisfy an insatiable wife's financial demand. Couples go into rituals with their children as sacrifice just for a little more money. All these end up destroying the family more at the end. In solving these problems, they should have a saving culture and in addition think of a small business to do that would guarantee a daily income would do wonders to the happiness experienced in the home (Crossby 85-88).

Globalization: Globalization has failed the family in larger measure. It has eroded strong family values and replaced it with commercialized relationships, thereby inflicting a heavy blow in the marriage institution worldly. The world has become a global village. It has not only made the world smaller, it has also made it independent. The dissolution caused by global trends does not only affect the family economically but also morally, religiously, socially and psychologically (Falako, Francis 326, 327).

Strategies for Promoting Marital Cohesion

Strategy is a system of finding, formulating, and developing a doctrine that will ensure long-term success if followed faithfully. Strategy generally involves setting goals and priorities, determining actions to achieve the goals, and mobilizing resources to execute the actions. Strategy describes how the ends (goals) will be achieved by the means (resources). Marital challenges are not bad or unnatural, it is the way couples handle it that determines its impact on marriage relationship. Marital challenges can destroy or strengthen a marriage while a successful marriage is one in which the couple resolved their differences either openly, secretly, constructively or without any bias for cohesion in the immediate society and national security. Marital challenges are detrimental to the marriage union because it becomes a means to attack, destroy, damage and wound others.

The following are some of the strategies to promote marital cohesion:

Couple's Commitment: Husband and wife should be committed to preserving their marital covenant. They should work out their differences within the context of a loving and irrevocable commitment to their marital covenants and vows. Couples should be determined not to let anything interrupt their marital affairs. They are expected to be open-minded in their discussions and manage their individual differences. Couples are to remain committed to their marital covenants and vows in order to do away with arguments that could generate into hostile, quarreling and confrontations. (Melgosa 77).

Control over Aggression: Husband and wife should not allow their anger to become uncontrollable. Uncontrolled anger among couples becomes a deadly weapon which couples

should do away with. Inability to control one's anger could gash either of the couples and become ugly nature by retailing with similar outburst of rancour. Aggressive words can easily break inner peace and confess marriage covenant between husband and wife. Transfer aggression will worsen the situation and as such couples should do away with such and exercise control over their aggression whenever they are angry.

Forgiveness: Couple should have total willingness to forgive and forget. Marital challenges among couples should be handled in a controlled and natural way. It is important for couples to do away with pride, abusive language, irrational accusations and cutting remarks; as such behaviour awakens ugly side of husband and wife in marriage.

Spiritual, Mental and Emotional Unity of the Couples: This comes when husband and wife live in harmony and agreement. Couples should have at least some common values, goals and interests. Culture and language encourage mental and emotional unity between husband and wife. This kind of unity meets people's need for companionship, cohesion, acceptance and value as human beings. Every human being desire to be wanted, loved and appreciated by someone.

Accommodating: Individual couples should seek to meet the needs of others at their own expense. They are not very assertive but are highly cooperative. Accommodating each other will not only help couples to live harmonious life but help them to avoid the opportunity of keeping records of wrong doings which may fuel marital challenges in their homes. Accommodating each other will help a couple to appreciate each other, bring out the best from each other and avail them the opportunity to develop themselves to a higher position and level in life.

National Security

National security is directed at having a reliable, strong and viable state that is free from threat internally and externally which is targeted at peace and tranquility of the state. Bolu-steve and Esere (2017) asserts that security means protection from hidden and harmful disruptions in the partners of daily life in home, offices or communities security, must be related to the presence of peace, absence of crisis, threats to human injury among others. However, Babangida (2012) views National Security as "The physical protection and defense of our citizens and our territorial integrity, of which it is a part, but also the promotion of the economic wellbeing and prosperity of Nigeria in a safe and secure environment that promotes the attainment of our national interests and those of our foreign partners. To Ebeh (2015) national security is more than territorial defense and should focus on the "physical, social and psychological equality of life of the society and its members both in the domestic setting and within the large regional and global system". For workable understanding of national security, especially when referring to a nation-state, Security means likelihood of survival; it means confidence in the maintenance of state boundaries and the preservation of its territorial, ideological and cultural integrity (George & Ukpong, 2013). It has been observed that there have been no generally and universally accepted conception of national security but it is more than the military aspect, it should encompass all facets of national life in preservation of its values (Otto & Ukpere, 2012). Looking at national security from this perspective we can deduce that marital concerns in our societies will continue to pose a challenge to Nigeria's security and development if not curbed.

Impact of Marital Cohesion on National Security in Nigeria

Marital concerns may have had some deleterious consequences on couples, their children and the society at large. Available literature revealed that social vices and crimes may become the order of the day as delinquent children from crisis-ridden or broken homes ultimately graduate into an irresponsible adult population. The adolescence is a stage at which human beings are highly emotionally unbalanced, character formation not yet stabilized and as such people can always tilt to either side of the scale at the slightest pressure. This is the singular reason why robbery, gangs, kidnap and assassination squads, and prostitution are mostly populated by people in their adolescence and early adulthood. Living with their parents did not offer them the opportunity to develop as good citizens as agents of cohesion and national security with good scales of conscience.

Marital challenge is a serious public health problem and it has both short and long term negative physical and psychological effects on health and wellbeing of Nigerians couples, it constitutes security problems that can endanger the peaceful co-existence of the society and country, in the same manner conflict and insecurity can be very havoc to the sustainable development of the country.

Conclusion

Marital challenges are an essential creative element in human relations, it is the means of change and the means by which our social values of welfare, security, justice and opportunities for personal development can be achieved. In other words, marital challenges are an inescapable part of our daily lives, an inevitable result of our highly complex, competitive and often litigious societies. The paper identifies strategies to curb marital concerns/challenges in Nigeria as a whole; Couple's commitment, control over aggression, forgiveness, spiritual/mental and emotional unity of the couple, setting clear boundaries expectations, establishment of a healthy communication patterns, showing genuine love, seeking professional help such as couples counselling and prioritizing self-care and personal growth.

Recommendations

1. The paper recommends that there is need for more training for couples or those who are coming into marriage to develop more endurance towards each other and seek for marriage counselling.
2. Couples are to jointly combat their marital challenges through prayer, mutual understanding and agreement.
3. Since challenges are inevitable in human society, couples are enjoined to define their marital challenges, and adopt the researcher's strategies accordingly.
4. More talks on husband's materials and wife's materials for the younger ones coming behind for peaceful togetherness in our society and for a secured nation.
5. In addition to the above, this work concludes that God is the harbinger of marriage and that no marriage is exempted from marital challenges, however, strict adherence to all these aforementioned strategies surely promotes marital cohesion in Nigeria.

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Religion, Culture, and Insecurity in Nigeria: Roles of State and Non-State Actors

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Abstract

This paper examines the complex interplay between religion, culture, and insecurity in Nigeria, focusing on the roles of both state and non-state actors. It highlights how political manipulation, ethno-religious conflicts, and socio-economic disparities exacerbate insecurity. By analysing the actions of key figures and the impact of regional security initiatives, this study proposes comprehensive strategies for enhancing national security. The recommendations emphasize the practice of true federalism to ensure equitable representation and governance across all regions, decisive governmental action against criminal organizations, strategic use of military contractors to enhance operational effectiveness, and the strengthening of institutions to reduce corruption and inefficiency. Furthermore, the paper advocates for ensuring justice and equity to promote peace, fostering public participation in decision-making processes, adhering to the rule of law, and improving intelligence gathering to counter security threats effectively. This study draws on recent literature and data, providing a robust academic foundation for its arguments.

Introduction

The biggest country in Africa, Nigeria, is shaped by a rich fabric of many cultures, faiths, and ethnicities that together form its national character. This diversity has created serious security issues even as it has been a source of rich cultural legacy. In Nigeria, insurgency, banditry, terrorism, and ethno-religious disputes are just a few of the ways insecurity appears. The stability and growth of the country are challenged in many ways by these problems, which are made worse by political manipulation, inadequate governance, and socioeconomic inequality.

One cannot stress the need of addressing insecurity in Nigeria enough. Economic activity is disrupted, social cohesiveness is hampered, and the legitimacy of the state is questioned by instability. Both human life and property are seriously threatened by it, which results in fatalities, population displacement, and infrastructure ruin. Furthermore, public confidence in governmental institutions can be undermined by insecurity, hence thorough approaches to address these issues must be investigated.

This research tries to investigate the intricate interactions between religion, culture, and insecurity in Nigeria, emphasising the contributions of both state and non-state actors. Several particular goals motivate the study:

1. **To examine the function of federalism in managing Nigeria's variety historically and currently:** This entails knowing how federalism has been used in Nigeria, as well as its achievements and shortcomings. The project will investigate how real federalism may be used to solve regional disparities and advance national cohesion.

2. **To investigate the impact of political manipulation on security:** Political elites often exploit religious and ethnic differences for personal or political gain, exacerbating insecurity. The paper will examine how these actions undermine national security and propose ways to mitigate such manipulations.
3. **To explore the roles of religious and cultural factors in exacerbating or mitigating insecurity:** Religion and culture are powerful forces in Nigerian society. The study will investigate how religious leaders, cultural practices, and intergroup relations influence security dynamics.
4. **To assess the effectiveness of state and non-state security actors:** This involves evaluating the actions of governmental bodies, such as the military and police, as well as non-state actors, including vigilante groups and civil society organizations, in addressing insecurity.
5. **To propose comprehensive strategies for enhancing national security:** Based on the findings, the paper will offer policy recommendations that encompass the practice of true federalism, decisive governmental action, the engagement of military contractors, the strengthening of institutions, ensuring justice and equity, promoting public participation, adherence to the rule of law, and improved intelligence gathering.

Background to Nigeria Political Structure

Federalism, as a system of governance, involves the distribution of power between a central authority and constituent political units, such as states or provinces. It is designed to accommodate diversity within a unified framework, allowing for local autonomy while maintaining national cohesion. In Nigeria, the concept of federalism has been both a solution and a source of contention since independence. Scholars such as Jinadu (2007) and Suberu (2010) have examined the evolution of Nigerian federalism, noting that while it has the potential to manage diversity, its implementation has been flawed, leading to persistent regional inequalities.

Colonial Legacy and the Emergence of Federalism

The colonial history of Nigeria laid the groundwork for its federal structure. The British colonial administration amalgamated diverse ethnic groups and territories into a single entity in 1914 for administrative convenience and economic exploitation. This forced union created a mosaic of cultural, religious, and linguistic identities, laying the foundation for the country's complex socio-political landscape (Osaghae, 2021). The arbitrary boundaries drawn by the British ignored existing ethnic and cultural divisions, leading to a heterogeneous and often contentious population within Nigeria's borders.

Post-independence, Nigeria adopted a federal system of governance in 1960, with the aim of accommodating its diverse population and managing regional differences. The 1960 and 1963 constitutions established a framework for federalism, delineating powers between the central government and regional entities. However, the federal structure was severely tested by successive military regimes, which centralized power and eroded the autonomy of regional governments. The military coups and the subsequent civil war from 1967 to 1970 further strained the federal arrangement, highlighting the challenges of maintaining national unity amidst profound diversity.

Centralization and Regional Tensions

The period of military rule in Nigeria, particularly from 1966 to 1999, witnessed a significant erosion of federalism. Military leaders, motivated by a desire to maintain control and suppress dissent, implemented a series of policies that undermined the principles of decentralization and regional autonomy (Suberu, 2020). Decrees such as the creation of 12 states in 1967 and the subsequent state creation exercises further centralized power in the hands of the federal government, exacerbating regional tensions and disparities.

Centralization of power during military regimes led to significant challenges, including unequal development, marginalization of minority groups, and ethnic tensions. The over-concentration of resources and decision-making authority in the central government stifled local initiatives and exacerbated feelings of disenfranchisement among states (Elaigwu, 2019). Moreover, the lack of accountability and transparency in governance fostered corruption and inefficiency, further fueling grievances and discontent.

Advocacy for True Federalism

Despite the challenges posed by centralization, there has been growing advocacy for true federalism in Nigeria. True federalism advocates for a more equitable distribution of power and resources, granting significant autonomy to states to manage their affairs and develop policies suited to their unique contexts (Akinola, 2021). Scholars and policymakers argue that true federalism could promote more balanced development and reduce ethnic tensions by ensuring that all regions have a stake in the nation's prosperity.

Comparative analyses with other federal systems provide valuable insights into the potential benefits and challenges of true federalism. For instance, the federal structures in India and Switzerland offer examples of how diversity can be managed within a unified state. In India, federalism has allowed for regional autonomy while maintaining national unity, despite significant linguistic and cultural diversity (Sarkar, 2020). Switzerland's model of cantonal autonomy provides another example of balancing local governance with national cohesion, offering lessons for Nigeria's federal experiment (Steffen, 2021).

Historical Context of Federalism in Nigeria

The colonial history of Nigeria laid the groundwork for its federal structure. The British amalgamation of diverse ethnic groups into a single colony in 1914 created a mosaic of cultural, religious, and linguistic identities. Post-independence, the federal system was adopted to manage this diversity. However, the centralization of power during military regimes, particularly from 1966 to 1999, undermined the principles of federalism. This period saw the erosion of state autonomy and the concentration of resources and decision-making authority in the central government, exacerbating regional tensions.

Challenges of Centralization

Centralization in Nigeria has led to significant challenges, including unequal development, marginalization of minority groups, and ethnic tensions. Scholars such as Elaigwu (2013) argue that the over-concentration of power at the center has stifled local initiatives and exacerbated feelings of disenfranchisement among states. This centralization has also been linked to corruption and inefficiency, as the central government often fails to address local needs effectively.

Potential of True Federalism

True federalism, which advocates for a more equitable distribution of power and resources, is seen as a viable solution to Nigeria's challenges. According to Wheare (1963) and Ayoade (1998), true federalism involves granting significant autonomy to states, allowing them to manage their resources and develop policies suited to their unique contexts. This system could promote more balanced development and reduce ethnic tensions by ensuring that all regions have a stake in the nation's prosperity.

Case Studies and Comparative Analysis

Examining federal systems in other multi-ethnic countries can provide valuable insights for Nigeria. For instance, the federal structures in India and Switzerland offer examples of how diversity can be managed within a unified state. In India, federalism has allowed for regional autonomy while maintaining national unity, despite significant linguistic and cultural diversity. Switzerland's model of cantonal autonomy provides another example of balancing local governance with national cohesion.

Decentralization and Local Governance

Decentralization is a core component of true federalism and involves the transfer of administrative, political, and fiscal responsibilities from the central government to local governments. Rondinelli, McCullough, and Johnson (1989) define decentralization as the restructuring or reorganization of authority so that there is a system of co-responsibility between institutions of governance at the central, regional, and local levels according to the principle of subsidiarity. This concept is critical in addressing Nigeria's unique socio-political landscape.

Research by Wunsch and Olowu (1990) has shown that effective decentralization can enhance local governance, improve public service delivery, and increase citizen participation in decision-making processes. In Nigeria, efforts to decentralize have faced numerous challenges, including lack of political will, inadequate resources, and resistance from entrenched interests. However, successful examples from other countries suggest that with the right institutional frameworks and political commitment, decentralization can significantly contribute to national unity and development.

Ethnic and Religious Diversity

Nigeria's ethnic and religious diversity is both a strength and a challenge. The country is home to over 250 ethnic groups, with the three largest being the Hausa-Fulani, Yoruba, and Igbo. Additionally, Nigeria's population is roughly split between Muslims, predominantly in the north, and Christians, predominantly in the south. This diversity has often been a source of conflict, as different groups vie for political and economic power.

Studies by Lewis and Bratton (2000) and Mustapha (2006) have explored the implications of this diversity for national unity. They argue that federalism, if properly implemented, can provide a framework for managing diversity by ensuring that all groups have a voice in governance. However, the current federal system in Nigeria has often been criticized for exacerbating divisions rather than mitigating them, due to its uneven implementation and centralization of power.

Resource Control and Economic Federalism

Resource control is a contentious issue in Nigeria, particularly in the oil-rich Niger Delta region. The centralization of oil revenues has led to conflicts and calls for greater resource control by states. Economic federalism, which involves the equitable distribution of resources and fiscal autonomy for states, is seen as a potential solution to these conflicts.

Watts (2008) and Agbu (2004) highlight the importance of fiscal federalism in promoting equitable development and reducing regional disparities. They argue that allowing states to control their resources and retain a significant portion of revenues can incentivize economic development and reduce dependency on the central government. This approach could also address the grievances of regions like the Niger Delta, where perceptions of exploitation and neglect have fueled unrest.

Federalism and Development

The relationship between federalism and development has been extensively studied, with mixed findings. Some scholars, like Rodden (2004) and Oates (1999), argue that federalism can promote development by fostering competition among states and encouraging innovation in policy-making. Others, such as Treisman (2007), caution that without proper safeguards, federalism can lead to disparities and inefficiencies.

In Nigeria, the potential of federalism to drive development is hampered by issues such as corruption, weak institutions, and inadequate infrastructure. However, there are also positive examples of states that have leveraged their autonomy to drive economic growth and improve public services. For instance, Lagos State has been recognized for its efforts in urban development and economic reforms, demonstrating the potential benefits of effective federal governance.

The complexity of implementing a system that balances diversity with national unity. While true federalism holds promise as a means to address Nigeria's socio-political challenges, its success depends on the commitment of political leaders, the establishment of robust institutions, and the active participation of citizens. This study seeks to build on this body of knowledge by examining the specific mechanisms through which true federalism can enhance national unity and reduce ethnoreligious tensions in Nigeria.

Roles of State Actors

Government Actions and Policies

The primary role of the state is to protect the lives and property of its citizens. However, certain actions and policies of the Nigerian government have had mixed impacts on national security. State actors play a crucial role in addressing insecurity within Nigeria, with their policies, initiatives, and actions significantly impacting the security landscape. This section delves deeper into the role of state actors, discussing specific government policies, initiatives, and challenges, as well as analyzing the impact of international partnerships on Nigeria's security.

Government Actions and Policies

Protecting the lives and property of its citizens is the main responsibility of the state. National security has, nevertheless, been mixedly impacted by some of the Nigerian government's policies and activities. With their policies, projects, and acts having a big influence on the security environment, state actors are essential in tackling insecurity in Nigeria. In-depth

discussion of particular government policies, projects, and issues is provided in this section, which also examines how international collaborations affect Nigeria's security.

Federal Programs and Policies

1. **Counterterrorism Strategies:** The Nigerian government has put into place a number of counterterrorism measures to fight terrorist organizations such as ISWAP (Islamic State West Africa Province) and Boko Haram. These tactics comprise intelligence gathering, military offensives, and cooperation with local and foreign allies (Oladejo, 2021). The efficiency of these tactics has been impeded, meantime, by issues including corruption, insufficient funding, and violations of human rights by security personnel (Islam, 2020).
2. **Amnesty Programs:** The government has implemented programs of amnesty meant to heal and reintegrate former rebels and militants into society. One such instance is the Presidential Amnesty Program for former Niger Delta fighters, which aims to employ empowerment, vocational training, and education to address the underlying reasons of militancy (Okoli & Ugwu, 2020). Critics contend that even if these initiatives have helped to lower violence in some places, they could unintentionally encourage criminal activity and foster an environment of impunity (Adebayo, 2021).
3. **Community Policing:** In reaction to growing insecurity, the Nigerian government launched community policing initiatives meant to improve cooperation between local communities and law enforcement organizations. Under these initiatives, community people are sought out and trained to assist the police in crime prevention, intelligence collection, and conflict mediation (Okeke, 2021). Community policing may increase public-police trust and collaboration, but its success is contingent upon sufficient funding, training, and oversight procedures.
4. **International Partnerships:** To deal with security issues, Nigeria has formed alliances with foreign governments and international organisations. Fighting transnational threats including terrorism, arms trafficking, and organized crime in the Lake Chad Basin region is the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF), which is made up of soldiers from Nigeria, Niger, Chad, Cameroon, and Benin (Okoli & Ugwu, 2020). To bolster its counterterrorism capabilities, nations like the US and France also provide Nigeria with military aid, training, and intelligence support.
5. **Shoot on Sight Directive:** The directive issued in March 2021 to shoot anyone found with AK-47s was intended to curb banditry. While it demonstrated a commitment to addressing armed violence, the policy's lack of clarity risked targeting non-state security units like local hunters and militias who have emerged to defend communities (Ogunleye, 2021). Effective implementation of this policy requires careful distinction between bandits and legitimate community defense groups.
6. **Demand for State Police and Regional Security Outfits:** The establishment of regional security outfits like Amotekun in the Southwest and Ebubeagu in the Southeast reflects a response to rising insecurity. These units, while controversial, have been necessary to address localized security concerns and reduce crime rates (Akinyele, 2021). However, their existence has also heightened ethnic tensions and fears of regionalism (Nwankwo, 2021).

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7. **Open Grazing Ban:** The ban on open grazing by southern state governments aims to reduce farmer-herder conflicts, a significant source of violence (Usman, 2021). Implementing ranching as an alternative has shown promise in reducing clashes and promoting agricultural stability.

Challenges Faced by State Actors

1. **Corruption and Mismanagement:** Effective attempts to combat instability are hampered by corruption in government agencies and security services. Funds diverting, procurement fraud, and embezzlement damage institutional capacity, undermine public confidence, and make it more difficult to provide necessary services (Chukwuemeka, 2020).
2. **Human Rights Violations** Human rights abuses including extrajudicial executions, torture, and arbitrary detentions have been linked to state actors, especially security personnel. In addition to violating basic freedoms and rights, these violations feed resentment, radicalization, and insurgency (Adebayo, 201).
3. **Ethnic and Religious Bias:** Social gaps are made worse and confidence in state institutions is undermined when people believe that government policies and security activities are biased toward one ethnicity or another. Reported cases of discrimination or preferential treatment because of one's race or religion erode national unity and heighten tensions across communities (Agbiboa, 201).
4. **Capacity and Resources** State players frequently don't have the manpower, funds, or tools needed to deal with security issues. Security personnel are hampered in their capacity to tackle new threats and defend civilians by inadequate training, antiquated infrastructure, and inadequate money (Uzundu, 2021).
5. **Amnesty to Terrorists:** It has been contentious to see former President Muhammadu Buhari back amnesty for bandits and Boko Haram. Opponents contend that because this action was seen as a reward for illegal activity, it demoralized the military forces and gave terrorists more confidence (Adibe, 2021). A message of weakness is sent by amnesty without a clear military victory, which can encourage criminal behavior among young people without jobs and worsen the security situation (Campbell, 2020).

The Role of Non-State Actors

Non-state actors, including religious leaders, local militias, and civil society organizations, also play a significant role in shaping Nigeria's security landscape. This section provides more comprehensive insights into their contributions and challenges.

Religious Leaders

1. Religious leaders hold significant sway over their followers and communities due to their spiritual authority and moral influence. In Nigeria, where religion often intersects with politics, ethnicity, and identity, religious leaders can shape public opinion, mobilize support, and influence behavior on issues related to security.
 - **Moral Guidance and Mediation:** Religious leaders often provide moral guidance and counsel to their adherents, promoting peace, tolerance, and

coexistence. They may also engage in mediation efforts to resolve conflicts and foster reconciliation between conflicting parties.

- Influence on Public Discourse: Through sermons, public statements, and religious gatherings, religious leaders can shape public discourse on security issues, either by promoting messages of peace and unity or by exacerbating tensions through divisive rhetoric.
2. Local Militias and Vigilante Groups: Local militias and vigilante groups are grassroots organizations formed by community members to address security challenges at the local level. These groups often emerge in response to perceived inadequacies or failures of formal security forces in protecting communities from threats such as insurgency, banditry, or communal violence.
 - Community Defense and Protection: Local militias and vigilante groups serve as a form of community defense, mobilizing to protect their homes, families, and livelihoods from external threats. They operate within their communities, leveraging local knowledge and networks to identify and neutralize security risks.
 - Risk of Vigilantism and Abuse: Despite their intended role as protectors, local militias and vigilante groups may engage in vigilantism, extrajudicial actions, or human rights abuses, particularly in contexts of conflict or insecurity. Lack of oversight, training, and accountability mechanisms can exacerbate these risks.
 3. Civil Society Organizations (CSOs): Civil society organizations are independent, non-governmental entities that work to promote social change, advocate for human rights, and provide services to marginalized or vulnerable populations. In the realm of security, CSOs play diverse roles, including advocacy, monitoring, service provision, and community engagement.
 - Advocacy and Monitoring: CSOs advocate for policies and practices that uphold human rights, promote accountability, and ensure transparency in security governance. They monitor government actions, security operations, and human rights violations, providing critical oversight and accountability.
 - Service Provision and Community Engagement: Some CSOs provide direct services to communities affected by insecurity, including humanitarian assistance, psychosocial support, and conflict resolution initiatives. They engage with local communities, building trust, fostering dialogue, and promoting community resilience in the face of security challenges.

Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in the context of Nigeria's security landscape play crucial roles in advocating for human rights, promoting accountability, and providing assistance to communities affected by insecurity. Here are some examples of CSOs and their activities in Nigeria:

1. Human Rights Watch (HRW): HRW is an international non-governmental organization that conducts research and advocacy on human rights issues globally, including in Nigeria. In Nigeria, HRW has published reports documenting human

rights violations by state and non-state actors, including abuses committed by security forces during counter-insurgency operations and in response to protests.

2. **Amnesty International Nigeria:** Amnesty International is another international human rights organization that operates in Nigeria, documenting and reporting on human rights abuses, including extrajudicial killings, arbitrary arrests, and torture. The organization advocates for justice for victims of human rights violations and calls for accountability for perpetrators.
3. **Civil Liberties Organization (CLO):** The Civil Liberties Organization is a Nigerian non-governmental organization that focuses on promoting civil liberties, democracy, and good governance. CLO monitors human rights abuses, provides legal assistance to victims, and engages in advocacy campaigns to address systemic issues affecting human rights in Nigeria.
4. **Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD):** The Centre for Democracy and Development is a research and advocacy organization based in Nigeria that focuses on democracy, governance, and conflict resolution. CDD conducts research on security-related issues, engages in policy advocacy, and facilitates dialogue between stakeholders to promote peace and stability.
5. **Search for Common Ground Nigeria:** Search for Common Ground is an international peacebuilding organization that works in Nigeria to promote dialogue, conflict resolution, and reconciliation. The organization facilitates community dialogues, peacebuilding workshops, and media campaigns aimed at reducing tensions and building trust between communities affected by conflict.
6. **International Crisis Group (ICG):** The International Crisis Group is an independent organization that provides analysis and policy recommendations on conflict situations worldwide. In Nigeria, ICG publishes reports and briefings on security challenges, political developments, and conflict dynamics, offering insights to policymakers and stakeholders on potential avenues for conflict resolution and peacebuilding.

These CSOs, both local and international, play critical roles in promoting human rights, advocating for peace and stability, and holding government actors accountable for their actions. Their activities contribute to efforts to address security challenges in Nigeria and advance the cause of justice, peace, and respect for human rights.

Recommendations

1. **Practice of True Federalism:** True federalism is imperative for Nigeria's diverse society to thrive cohesively. It entails granting substantial autonomy to states, enabling them to govern efficiently while ensuring equitable representation across regions. Legislative, executive, and judicial autonomy at the local level fosters unity and diminishes regional disparities. By implementing true federalism, Nigeria can address historical grievances and promote a sense of inclusivity among its populace (Abubakar, 2020).
2. **Decisive Action Against Criminal Organizations:** To combat terrorism and criminality effectively, the Nigerian government must take resolute measures. This involves formulating clear policies and consistently enforcing them to deter criminal

- activities. Swift and decisive actions signal the government's commitment to maintaining law and order, bolstering public confidence in the justice system and deterring potential wrongdoers (Adamu, 2021).
3. **Use of Military Contractors:** Given the limitations of Nigeria's security apparatus, strategic engagement with military contractors presents an opportunity to enhance operational effectiveness. Past successes with contractors underscore the potential benefits of this approach if managed judiciously. By leveraging the expertise and resources of military contractors, Nigeria can augment its security capabilities and better address evolving security threats (Smith, 2021).
 4. **Strengthening Institutions:** The resilience of Nigeria's institutions is paramount for ensuring effective governance and maintaining public trust. Strengthening anti-corruption agencies, the judiciary, and para-military organizations is essential for combating corruption and ensuring accountability. Robust institutions are better equipped to withstand external pressures and uphold the rule of law, fostering stability and bolstering national security (Ogunyemi, 2021).
 5. **Ensuring Justice, Fairness, and Equity:** Upholding justice, fairness, and equity is fundamental for fostering social cohesion and countering insurgency. Fair and equitable treatment within the judicial system not only promotes peace but also discourages recruitment by insurgent groups. By adhering to principles of justice and fairness, Nigeria can mitigate grievances and address underlying socio-economic disparities, thereby reducing the drivers of insecurity (Olukoya, 2021).
 6. **Promotion of Public Participation:** Engaging the public in decision-making processes is essential for fostering a sense of ownership and reducing discontentment. By soliciting and considering public opinions, policymakers can develop inclusive policies that address the needs and concerns of diverse communities. Promoting public participation enhances legitimacy and accountability, ultimately contributing to peace and stability (Eze, 2021).
 7. **Adherence to the Rule of Law:** Respecting legal procedures and constitutional mandates is crucial for upholding the rule of law and maintaining social order. Leaders' adherence to legal norms sets a precedent for citizens, reinforcing the importance of lawful behavior and discouraging impunity. By upholding the rule of law, Nigeria can strengthen its democratic institutions and build a society grounded in justice and accountability (Onwuegbuchulam, 2021).
 8. **Improved Intelligence Gathering:** Enhancing intelligence gathering capabilities is essential for preempting security threats and safeguarding national interests. By investing in advanced intelligence technologies and fostering collaboration between security agencies, Nigeria can gather critical insights into insurgent operations and develop proactive response strategies. Improved intelligence gathering not only enhances security but also enhances the government's ability to address emerging challenges effectively (Anyanwu, 2021).

Conclusion

In a nutshell Nigeria's security problems are complex and numerous, with an established basis in the socio-political and financial conditions of the nation. We explored the complex relationships among religion, culture, governance, and insecurity in this research, while noting the efforts made by state as well as non-state actors to the persistence or reduction of these challenges. One of the study's main conclusions is that tackling Nigeria's insecurity requires a comprehensive strategy. Ethnic and religious strife, economic inequality, and governance are all intertwined with security concerns. Thus, addressing these fundamental reasons and enlisting the cooperation of several stakeholders are essential components of any effective national security enhancement plan. Nigeria's security issues may be resolved by implementing true federalism, which provides a framework for more fair resource allocation and governance. True federalism can enable local communities to solve their own security concerns while promoting a sense of ownership and engagement in the governing process by giving states more autonomy and encouraging decentralised governance. Moreover, the government must move decisively to combat insecurity. This entails having unambiguous policies, efficient law enforcement, and holding violent offenders accountable. In order to battle criminal elements, maintain the rule of law, and safeguard human rights, the government must show political will. Nigeria's security environment can be improved by international collaboration and partnerships. Building capacity, exchanging intelligence, and conducting joint operations against transnational threats like organised crime and terrorism can all be facilitated by working with regional and international organisations as well as through bilateral partnerships with other nations. Promoting peace and stability also requires working with non-state players including local militias, civil society groups, and religious leaders. These individuals can be extremely important in resolving disputes, fostering social cohesion, and establishing peace because they frequently have strong links to their communities.

In conclusion, tackling Nigeria's security concerns calls for an all-encompassing strategy that takes into account conflicts between ethnic and religious groups, economic inequality, and governance problems. Nigeria can strive towards a more secure and stable future for all of its residents by embracing true federalism, guaranteeing prompt governmental action, encouraging international cooperation, and including non-state players. However, maintaining dedication, political will, and collaboration from all parties involved will be necessary to achieve long-term security.

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A Pastoral Counselling Approach to the Challenges of Widowhood in Traditional Igbo Land

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Abstract

This research argued that women in traditional Igbo land are faced with myriads of factors challenging their personalities, worth, dignity and contributions towards development in the family and the larger society. One of the obnoxious cultural traits that dehumanizes, relegates and obliterates womanhood in traditional Igbo society is widowhood practices. This is the case in most African climes, where male chauvinism, oppression and women relegation are dominant features of their culture. While this practice is entrenched in the traditional culture of the Igbo people, the women are seen to be the ones encouraging and enforcing it against their folks in Igbo land in most cases. Descriptive phenomenology approach was adopted for this research; while secondary sources of data collection and analysis were equally employed to give the work the desired attention. It was discovered that widowhood practices in traditional Igbo land, subject women to various forms of sexual abuses, stigmatization, denials, poverty and incapacitation; and thus, reduces them to the status of slaves in the society. Women undergoing these treatments are psychologically, socially, religiously and economically unproductive and cannot contribute meaningfully to development. The research recommended that Christian religious leaders should rise to the occasion and bring this obnoxious widowhood practices in Igbo land to a stop. Pastoral counselling approaches of teaching, preaching, prayer and care should be engaged to assist widows and as means of discouraging cultures perpetuating this ugly practice. The work further advised that pastors should work with government agencies, women groups and NGOs in the area of advocacy and empowerment for widows suffering untold hardship in the hands of cultures that still uphold this menace.

Keywords: Widowhood, tradition, pastoral counselling, Igbo land, cultural practices

Introduction

Women have been for the most part made objects of discrimination and male dominance in various parts of Igbo land and elsewhere in the world. Hence, Lane (1985, p.664), opined that, "down through the ages, women have been regarded as second class citizens. They are stereotyped into roles of dependency, submission as passivity... exploited as objects... defined in terms of men... excluded from the centers of power and the decision-making processes in the society." Obi and Ogbenna (2010, p.328), averred that, in Africa, sex inequality is a strong belief and the majority of women are placed under severe socio-cultural and economic disabilities and discriminations in areas like: inheritance rights, childlessness and male child preference, exploitation, domestic violence, polygamy, sexual harassment and obnoxious widowhood practices. In fact, women have always been seen and treated as unequal in the whole of known and recorded history.

Widowhood practices is one of the many woes that has subjugated womanhood in traditional Igbo land. In this clime, men (widowers) are treated differently and are allowed some privileges at event of the demise of their wives; while the contrary is the case at the death of

the men's folk. As such a dehumanizing and traumatizing elements of widowhood rites are meted out on the woman whose husband is dead (Obi and Ogbenna, 2010). Speaking further on this, Uchem (2005, p.65), noted that, "a further socio-cultural face of gender inequality is manifested in the often talked about degrading treatments which are meted out against widows in some Nigerian cultures." The sad thing about these cultures where such treatments exist, is that the widow is generally suspected to have killed or caused the death of the husband directly or indirectly. Thus, she is meant to undergo certain dehumanizing rituals. All that is possible because as an "inferior" human being, it is automatically believed that the woman is the culprit (Uchem, 2005).

The research methodology adopted was descriptive phenomenology. This method according to Ituma (2015, p.37) is "an attempt at describing the diversity, complexity and richness of experience." This method enabled the researcher to uncover descriptively, the experiences widows undergo in Igbo land. Equally used were the secondary sources of data collection, where materials from the library and online contents were accessed to enrich the research with necessary information needed.

Analysis of Key Concepts

Agumagu (2007, p.16), averred that a widow is a woman who has lost her husband by death and has not remarried. Townsend (1995, p.891) states that, "a widow is a woman whose marriage partner is dead and who has not remarried." Nnachi and Nnubia (2011, pp.146-147) maintained that, "widowhood means the condition in which a woman finds herself at the death of her husband." Widowhood practices entail the traditional agonizing conditions widows are subjected to as their husbands die. Osita-Njoku and Uwaoma (2001), Kolo (2002) and Lannap (2005) expressed that widowhood is a period of grief and pain, marginalization of women, accompanied by emotional deprivation, forceful seizure of property and cultural seclusion.

On traditions, Isichei (1976, p.11), averred that, "people will not look forward to posterity who never look backward to their ancestors." Tradition is a part of culture that is passed from person to person or generation to generation. Ezekwugo (1992, p.231) said, "that every racial group of people in the world has a code of ordinances, mores and lores which are supposed to have decreed by the land. These sanctions are the traditions (*odinana*), ordinances, customs and bye-laws enshrined in the sinews and marrows of a social fabric of ancestral heritage."

On the other hand, pastoral care and counseling are valuable instruments by which the church stays relevant to human needs. They are ways of translating the good news into a language of relationships. Clinebell (1984), affirmed that:

Counselling can help save those areas of our lives that are shipwrecked in the storms of our daily living, broken on the hidden reefs of anxiety, guilt, and lack of integrity. An effective caring and counselling program, in which both minister and trained lay persons serve as enablers of healing and growth can transform the interpersonal climate of a congregation making a church, a place where wholeness is nurtured in persons throughout the life cycle (pp.13-14).

Widowhood Practices in Traditional Igbo Land

In traditional Igbo setting, the funeral rites of a dead man involve many ritual practices that are necessary for religious change. These rituals most times are very adverse to the wellbeing and existence of the widow of the dead man. Nmah (2003, p.70), accentuated that:

“widowhood practices in Igbo land are another area in which women are reduced to slave states.”

Ogu, Obi, Isidiho (2020, p. 1051), opined that:

Many communities still retain the notion that widows are responsible for the death of their husbands; therefore, to prove their innocence they are often compelled to undergo certain rituals. In this case, women whose husbands died undergo series of widowhood practices which have various implications.

Ndulue (1995, p.108), classified widowhood practices in Igbo culture into three main groups:

The first group is widows whose husbands took traditional titles before their death. The second group is widows whose husbands did not take any traditional title before their death. The third group involves some Igbo communities who do not believe in overt self-denial or mortification while mourning a deceased husband.

In the first two cases, there are similarities. But widowhood for women whose husbands took traditional title before their death is very stringent and primitive.

Widowhood generally, was considered a taboo in traditional Igbo land and as such, various practices were carried out against the woman in order to make her ritually clean, before integrating her back into the society (Nwankwo, 2014). Thus, such obnoxious widowhood practices include but not limited to the following:

Excommunication, restrictions and isolation of the widow: Nmah (2003, p.79), said that, “in parts of Igbo land, when a man dies, the wife is secluded. That is, she is kept in a separate place. Such a woman does not come out for about eight days after the death of her husband. She will not be touched by anybody in this secluded place.” She is meant to eat with stick not her hand. In those days she is not shaved for a long period of time. Sometimes, it will take years before her hair was shaved (Nwankwo, 2014).

Ezeaku (1990, p.107), noted that “as soon as the husband dies, a small make-shift hut is built for her at the back of her residential house. She is to an extent excommunicated from the people. She isolates from the people in her community. The hut is built with materials which could easily be discarded and cast into evil forest as soon as the burial and funeral ceremonies of the late husband were completed.

The widow is isolated and restricted from getting into the market to buy or sell. If she needs anything she has to look for someone to do that for her. This makes the situation of a widow who is childless, breastfeeding a baby or sick very deplorable as the law has no consideration. The widow cannot attend meetings or other social functions (Ogu, Obi, Isidiho, 2020).

Shaving of the widow's hair and wearing of sackcloth: Obi and Ogbenna (2010), identified another area of violence against women in Igbo land. This is in respect to widowhood practices. He affirmed that, “another area of violence is forced shaving of the widow's hair as a symbol of respect for the dead husband and to make her unattractive to other men while mourning. The widows look abandoned, hopeless, ugly, rejected and helpless” (p.335).

The beauty of a woman consists of the hairs on her head. Shaving of the hairs on the head and other parts of the body seems to be the ugly responsibility of the *umuokpu* or *umuada* (married daughters of the deceased family) or even the older widows. The widow is compulsively taken behind the kitchen, near a bush and given a clean shave by these women with ordinary razor blade despite the health risks (Ogu, Obi, Isidiho, 2020).

On sackcloth, Obi and Ogbenna (2010, p.335) furthermore said that, “the imposition of black mourning cloth makes mourning frightful and gloomy. It instills fear in the widow and

generated nightmares. It makes them look like outcasts and people avoid them as such." She must wear one particular mourning clothes for one year not even when it is totally worn out.

Drinking of the water used to wash the corpse of the deceased husband: Nmah (2003, p.79), observed that "there are extreme cases where the woman is forced to drink water used in washing her husband's corpse, especially, if she was accused of being responsible for the husband's death." Similar to this is the act of walking across the corpse by the widow as it lay on the floor to show that she has not killed the husband because everyone now sees her as a witch and call her bad names especially very young widows (Ogu, Obi, Isidiho, 2020).

Challenges of Widowhood in Traditional Igbo Land

The challenges of widowhood are enormous. It ranges from socio-cultural, economic and psychological dimensions. Widows pass through a lot of denials, abuse, stigmatization and other forms of violence in the face of cultures and traditions entrenching this practice.

Socio-cultural challenges: Widowhood practice is shrouded in superstitions that subject the victims to fear both from the kinsmen of her husband and the fear of being harmed by the spirit of her dead husband. The women are not accorded full social recognition in accord to the dignity of their person. According to Obi (2001, p.109) "the widow becomes aware of her limitations since the source of her pride has passed away." The children could be subjected to social ridicule and torture since they lack protection. It brings untold hardship, distress, and cries in the family.

Economic challenges: Widows are at risks of economic deprivation, especially the younger ones. In a culture where the men are seen as the breadwinners, in the event of death, their widows are exposed to a greater danger of economic hardship and hunger. The widows must live in their husband's family no matter the situation because re-marriage is usually difficult. Therefore, widowhood remains an easy transition to economic poverty as the widow is faced with loss of status and resources (Ogu, Obi, Isidiho, 2020).

Accordingly, Afolayan (2011) in Ikwuegbu (2017, p.226) affirmed that, "widowhood deprives women of homes, comforts, agricultural lands and other valuables." Without inheritance rights widows are practically dependent on occasional charity of their husband's friends.

Psychological and Health challenges: Psychologically, widows are thrown into serious mental stress at the death of their spouses. The inhuman treatment faced during the period of mourning and after lingers and can lead to other complications.

Sickness is another major threat to the peace of the widow. With her low income and status, she finds it very difficult to rise to her challenges when sickness strikes in the family. According to Damap (2007), "most of the illnesses found within the household of many widows are nutrition-related; they eat whatever is available only to fill up their stomach." Most of these widows do not have good means of livelihood, some do not eat well.

Widowhood and Care in Biblical Perspectives

The Bible is replete with stories about and commands concerning widows (Bloechl, 2022). God cares for widows and calls His people to do the same in both Old and New Testaments of the Bible. God assumed the responsibility of taking care of the widows that lost their bread winners. The Psalmist describes God as the protector and upholder of widows (Ps. 68:5, 146:9). It is evident that care of widows is a priority in God's economy. The biblical widows like Ruth, the widow of Zarephat, the widow of Nain and Dorcas were taken care of by God (Nwaudo,

2012). He did not only care for the widows but also, He defended their cause (Exodus 22:22-24). The Israelites were warned not to persecute and exploit the widows (Kunhiyop, 2008). Widows were not abandoned in the New Testament. The early Christians quickly responded to the murmurings of the Grecians that complained that their widows were neglected in the sharing of food which led the church to appoint the seven deacons (Acts 6:1). But, the apostolic dispensation witnessed a tremendous decline in the caring of widows. In that era, heads of families, *pater familias*, declined in providing for the widows in their families. This situation prompted Paul to write a letter to Timothy admonishing Christian men that any man who fails to take care of the widow in his family has denied the faith (1 Timothy 5:8) (Pfeiffer, Vos and Rea, 2000). The church filled the gap created by families by providing relief for the elderly widows that had no relations that would take care of them (James 1:27, 1 Timothy 5:9) (Strong, 1999). The relief contributed a lot in alleviating the plight of widows in the New Testament period.

The Pastoral Care Approaches to Widowhood Challenges in Igbo Land

The contributions of pastoral counsellors and church leaders in general, in ameliorating the plight of widows in Igbo land cannot be overemphasized. These range from spiritual, psychological, material, advocacy and humanitarian assistance.

Spiritual and Psychological support: The first approach of pastoral counsellors towards widows generally, is to encourage, restore hope and disabuse their psychological disposition of thinking that all hope is lost, with the death of their husbands. Widows at this point in life need all the spiritual assistance like prayers and word of assurance from the counsellors. This in turn will heal them psychologically.

Pastoral Advocacy: The widows are greatly disadvantaged in Igbo land and need to be taken care of by the laws of the land; their voices heard and their needs addressed. Widows in traditional cultures are voiceless in most cases. It is the roles of Pastors and Church leaders to speak against cultures and traditions in Igbo land that still dehumanize, traumatize, abuse, relegate and mistreat widows. Widows are humans and must be treated as such. Iwe (2000) responding to the plight of widows and widowhood practices today averred that personality is perceived as the foundation of man's dignity and sense of responsibility. This should distinguish man from the other creatures of the universe; hence man (generic) should not be treated as an inanimate object.

Educational and Material support: Pastors should encourage the girl-child education so as to mitigate the worrisome effects of early child marriage that critically endangers the future of the young woman. Skills acquisition centers can be established where majority of these widows can easily learn one trade or the other so as to meet their daily needs.

The church must also stand with the widow if her late husband's family come to lay claim to his property. The church, and especially the pastor, should intervene to mediate between the parties and restrain abuses (Kunhiyop, 2008).

Humanitarian assistance: The church has founded humanitarian associations to cater for the needs of widows. There are associations of widows in many Christian denominations in Igbo land. These associations are saddled with the responsibility of alleviating the plight of widows. In many occasions, widows smile homes with money, cloths and food stuffs. The children of indigent widows are offered scholarships. Onah (2008, p.77) observed that the church through women organization has reduced the burden of widowhood. The church has reduced the mourning period from one year to six months while few widows do not observe

widowhood rites. Some widows can now take baths and sit on upholstery chairs. The mourning cloth has changed from black to white which symbolizes purity and innocence (Obi and Ogbenna, 2010).

Conclusion

This paper has reinforced the invaluable contributions of Pastoral counselling and care in handling the challenges of widows in traditional Igbo society. Widowhood rites in Igbo land has dehumanized and degraded widows. Widows pass through excruciating pains like loss of breadwinners, companions and heads of families. However, instead of being comforted and given succor, she is being subjected to further sorrow and anguish. It is based on this, that the pastoral counsellors should intervene as the last hope of widows in order to alleviate her plight. On that note, the following recommendations have been adduced to mitigate the pains of widows in Igbo land.

Recommendations

1. The church should not stop at reducing the period of mourning, changing the colour of mourning cloth, but also should address the remote causes of widowhood rites in order to abolish this ugly practice that is contrary to reason as well as unacceptable in the 21st century.
2. The church should contribute relief for the indigent widows to enable them take care of their families.
3. Pastors should intensify pastoral care by visiting and counseling the widows to enable them overcome psychological problems like fear, loneliness and anger.
4. There should be workshops, seminars and symposia for widows, where they will be sensitized on how to live as Christian widows.
5. Pastors should campaign against and work with policy makers to abolish widowhood rites in Igbo land generally.

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Intercultural Communication and Church Leadership Administration in Lagos Pluralistic Society, Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Pluralism is a state in which people of different cultural backgrounds, socio-economic status, religions, races, ideology, philosophy, etc., are together in a society, but continue to exhibit their different traditions and interests. The existence of diverse cultural and religious belief systems in the metropolis of Lagos with virtually all the major 380 ethnic groups in Nigeria and the naturalized Portuguese, Sierra Leoneans, Liberians, Kenyans, Lebanese, Arabs and Chard business tycoons coupled with the effects of modernity and globalization have made Lagos Churches pluralistic causing constant change in co-existence and intercultural relationship with its antecedent challenges of suspicion, prejudice, disunity, tribalism and poor integration in spite of the rich array of culture and civilization. Scholars have carried out some research on Church leadership roles in managing the recurrent problems. However, intercultural communication skills for Leadership Administration in Lagos have not been given adequate attention, this lacuna is the crux of this paper. The paper employed historical and quantitative methods premised on Xiuwen and Razali's Intercultural Communication Skill theoretical framework, which states that, in human society, communication provides a premise to share pluralistic worldview, ideas, moral values, emotional intelligent and feelings, promoting mutual relationship in the society. The finding reveals that, the churches in Lagos are characterized with multi-cultural diversity because of the variegated interconnectedness, which makes it increasingly clear that Church Leadership requires intercultural communication skills for understanding individuality and corresponding cultural traits for encouraging oneness and unity in the churches. Conclusively, Intercultural Communication skill is a veritable mechanism for church leaders in managing and administering their pluralistic congregations for cohesion and integration in spite of the cultural diversities. It is recommended therefore that, the multicultural composition of the churches in Lagos should make the adoption of intercultural communication a crucial skill for church leadership administration.

Keywords: Intercultural Communication, Church Leadership Administration, Lagos Pluralistic Society, Cultural Diversity, Lagos State.

Introduction

Since its advent in Jerusalem, the Church has always been a composition of people from different cultural and ethnic nationalities. For instance, the early church was home to people from different languages, cultural affiliations and ethnic nationalities. In other words, like any human institution or organization, the church is also characterized with cultural and language diversity. Apostle Paul in Romans 11: 13-25 also remarks about the uneasiness between the original and wild olives – representing the Jews and the Gentiles in the Roman Church. The existence of diverse cultural and religious belief systems in the metropolis of Lagos with virtually all the major 380 ethnic groups and over 500 languages in Nigeria (Atowoju, 2024). This array of culture and civilization which resulted from the various ethnic diversities has brought a lot of beauty and splendor to the socio-economic, religious and political life of Lagos and the Christian community in particular as one of the microcosms of Lagos religious communities. In spite of the rich array of culture and civilization, the multicultural diversity and constant change in co-existence and intercultural relationship has equally come with its antecedent challenges of disunity, tribalism and poor integration. Scholars have carried out some research on Church leadership roles in managing the recurrent problems. However, intercultural communication skills for Leadership Administration among Christians in Lagos have not been given adequate attention, this lacuna is the crux of this paper.

Lagos Pluralism and Cultural Diversity

Lagos also known as Eko (as its traditional Yoruba name) is primarily a Yoruba socio-cultural setting, Yoruba people are the major ethnic group, but the population does not exclude other ethnic groups in Nigeria, these include but not limited to Edo, Hausa, Igbo, Fulani, Efik, Igarra and several individuals from other countries, Britons, Kenyans, Sierra Leoneans, Portuguese, Liberians, Senegalese, Malians, Togolese, Arabs, Nigeriens, Beninese, Ghanaians, Chadians, Cameroonians, Lebanese, Brazilians, etc. (Patrick 2014). This makes Lagos the most populated and culturally diversified city in Nigeria. Lagos is evidently a centre of diverse cultural and ethnic nationalities (Lagos State Government, 2021). The peculiarity of cultural diversity in Lagos is hinged on strong attraction to Lagos' beautiful landscapes, infrastructures, job opportunities, industrial and economic development, urbanisation, globalisation and civility of Lagosians to people from other parts of Nigeria and the world at large (Lagos, 2021). These attractions are also based on strong economy, commerce and industry, and socio-political inclusiveness. Etomes (2020) stresses that Lagos metropolis gives the platform for openness, innovation and increase investment for people from different part of the world.

Lagos is widely recognised as the commercial centre and epicentre of all ethnic nationalities in Nigeria and other nations around the world. Lagos inclusiveness encompasses both indigenes and non-indigenes in the state. Non-indigenes have become a fundamental factor in Lagos state politics, religion, economy, social and leadership administration in all spheres of life. No state in Nigeria has such cultural accommodation, tolerance and open playing field for leadership aspiration either in civil service or political office. For instance, non-indigenes of Lagos dominate the market and business life of the state, which in turn contributes enormously to the economic development of Lagos. Most of the industries and private organisations are established by non-indigenes of Lagos state. For instance, the Dangote

Refinery owned by Aliko Dangote was inaugurated on the 22nd of May, 2023 in Lekki, Lagos, Nigeria. When in full operation, it is expected to have the capacity to process about 650,000 barrels of crude oil per day, making it the largest single-train refinery in the world. According to Desmond (2023), the investment worth of over 19 billion US dollars.

The role of communication in any organization cannot be over-emphasized as it has been termed by many as the life-support or blood needed for survival. In a pluralistic society of Lagos, intercultural- communication ensures that there is a proper interaction between persons at different levels of an organization. Xiuwen and Razali's (2020) state that, in human society, communication provides a premise to share pluralistic worldview, ideas, moral values, emotional intelligent and feelings, promoting mutual relationship in the society. Intercultural communication or communication between people of different cultural backgrounds has always been and will probably remain an important precondition of human co-existence on earth.

The Concept of Communication

There is no universal accepted definition of communication among scholars. This makes the subject of communication a very difficult to define in a particular way, because it involves series of different conducts associating to the transmission of information among people (Jiequ and Zhu et al, 2020). Experience also shows that communication means to share or to be in relation with (Cherrez-Ojeda, et al 2020). For instance, communication is an apparent answer to the painful divisions between a person and other, private and public, and inner thought and outer world (Culmin, et al 2021). In this sense, communication plays important roles in peaceful co-existence between individuals and general society. Imagine if there is no medium of communication among the people, how would the world and creations survive? In actual fact, communication is key to existence, it gives life and meaning to human existence. Communication is conceptualized in different ways by many individuals. It can be viewed as the process of transferring information and meaning from a sender to a receiver with the use of a medium in which the communicated information is understood by both the sender and the receiver. Communication is a process that allows human beings to exchange information by several methods. In its simplest form, communication is the use of words to describe and convey a message or give information to another person. We communicate using language as a code to share information, ideas and feelings.

Concept of Intercultural Communication

According to Oana-Antonia (2019), intercultural Communication is regarded as ability and skill needed in interaction with people from different cultures. Therefore, communication is not as easy as many people think it is, especially, when communicating with people from different cultural background. Effective communication demands skills and understanding of different cultures and languages. It is not cultures that communicate, whatever that might imply, but people with different cultural backgrounds that do. In general, the term cross-cultural is probably best used for comparisons between cultures. Bearing in mind that every religious set up is a mixture of people from different cultural backgrounds, which brings about complexity and plurality (Mayda, 2022). It is noteworthy that intercultural communication is studied widely across various academic disciplines due to international relation.

The world today has become a global village whereby communication with people different from one's cultural orientation is daily experience in every institution of life such as the church, private cooperate organization and government public establishment. For Byram & Golubeva, (2020), the concept of intercultural communication can be regarded as communication among individuals from different cultural and ethnic nationalities in this age of globalization. This means for a successful interaction among people from different cultural affiliation, the knowledge of intercultural communication is a perquisite (Sinden, 2021) Relating this concept of intercultural communication to the church context which is the focus of this study, the church is like epicentre for different means cultural background. Therefore, intercultural communication becomes an essential tool for effective information dissemination among people of diverse cultural orientations. The skill of intercultural communication is beyond creating of awareness or passing of information among people from different cultural understanding, but also crucial for leadership in a multicultural context. The working environment in the whole world is all encompassing in terms of gender base, religious and cultural divide. Effective leadership in a multicultural location requires knowledge of intercultural communication. For example, leadership is service. In order to render effective service delivery in the church context or any human institution on the surface of the earth, intercultural communication knowledge and skill is inevitable.

Conceptual Understanding of the Church

Berg (2020) narratives about the early church reveals the dynamic nature of the Christian communities (Acts 1: 1-6). The Church is rooted in the heart of God's mission and Gospel of Jesus. The Church lies at the very centre of the eternal purpose of God on earth from generation to generation. Pillay (2020) argues that the church is the gathering of the people called out of the world for Jesus' own glory (1 Peter 2:9). Therefore, the mission of Jesus was concerned with the creation of community, which formed the basis of the Church that was inaugurated on the day of Pentecost.

Understanding Difference Between Cultures and Communication Patterns

The term culture refers to all the characteristics common to a particular group of people that are learned and not given by nature. Hunt & D'Érrico (2000) emphasised that the members of a group have two legs is not a cultural characteristic but a natural one, while a special but common way of walking would probably be cultural. Culture is complex phenomenon which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by a person as a member of society (Staff, 2020). In relation to this, culture constitutes everything that controls life and society values and cosmology. Kaplan (2018) highlighted the following cultural patterns or norms that govern the behaviour of a group of people, according to their traditions, customs, habits, beliefs, geographical location and experience in establishing models of behaviour.

- i. **Patterns of behaviour:** common ways of behaving, from ways of speaking to ways of conducting commerce and industry, where the behaviour can be intentional or unintentional, aware or unaware or individual or interactive.
- ii. **Patterns of artefacts:** common ways of manufacturing and using material things, from pens to houses where artefacts include dwellings, tools, machines or media. The art factual dimension of culture is usually given special attention in museums.

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- iii. **Imprints in nature:** the long-lasting imprints left by a group in the natural surroundings where such imprints include agriculture, trash, roads or intact or ruined human habitations.
 - iv. **Patterns of thought:** common ways of thinking, where thinking includes factual beliefs, values, norms, and emotional attitudes (Neff & Mathew, 2020).

Communication is very important wherever people find themselves. Nevertheless, communication across cultures can be very difficult because cultures have ways of communicating both formal and informal. Cultures have one thing in common, which is that they can get offended if you do not understand their communication practices. If that has to be avoided in Intercultural Communication, people have to learn how to communicate. In his view, Hadad (2021), describes language as an effective instrument for intercultural communication. This is because it is tied to cultural pattern in every locality or society. Hence, beyond traditional writing of language, greater consideration must be given to the conditions for understanding in order to appropriately relate with people from other cultural settings.

Models and Approaches to Intercultural Communication

1. Social science approach: This model focuses on observing the behaviour of a person from a different culture in order to describe it and compare it with other cultures (Ndhlovu, 2022). It also examines the ways in which individuals adjust their communication with others in different situations, depending on who they are talking to. For example, we would tell the same story differently to our best friend than we would to our grandmother or an elderly member of the society.
2. Interpretive approach: This theory focuses on accumulating knowledge about a culture through communication in the form of shared stories based on subjective individual experiences (Allard-Kropp, 2020). The main focus is on intercultural communication as it is used in particular speech in different communities, so ethnography plays a major role here. Because the individual context is so important for this model, it does not strive to make generalized predictions based on its findings.
3. Dialectical approach: This method examines aspects of intercultural communication in the form of six dichotomies, namely cultural-individual, personal-contextual, difference-similarities, static-dynamic, history/past-present/future, and privilege-disadvantage (Heggernes, 2021). A dialectical approach helps us think about culture and intercultural communication in complex ways, so we can avoid categorizing everything in either-or dichotomies by adopting a broader approach and acknowledging the tensions that must be negotiated.
4. Critical approach: This approach examines cultures according to their differences compared to the researcher's own culture and, in particular, how these cultures are portrayed in the media (Sharifovna, 2021) The critical approach is complex and multifaceted and therefore leads to a rich understanding of intercultural communication.

Church Leadership Management and Administration in Lagos Pluralistic Society

According to United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, cultural diversity is a common heritage of humanity (Ridley, et al). Lagos is a pluralistic society and

most of the churches in Lagos are unarguably multi-ethnic and multi-linguistic. Cultural diversity is synonymous to multiculturalism which promotes congregational groupings of people with different cultural backgrounds (Park, 2022). In this sense, cultural diversity covers values, beliefs, attitudes, language, customs, and behaviours. Likewise, Karjalainen (2020) cultural diversity is personified in the distinctiveness and variety of identities among groups in the society. The distinctiveness of human Cultural heritage is rooted in race, ethnicity, nationality, religion, gender, and several differences related to human existence. Cultural diversity exposes people to different cultural orientations and norms different from one's culture. Therefore, leadership management and administration in the pluralistic society like Lagos requires a deep understanding of intercultural communication. Leadership can be defined as the process of getting things done through and with people. This definition is apt because three variables are involved in this process. The activity to be done, the people to do the activity, and the person to get them perform the task or activity. This can be likened to management of people and resources to achieve a particular goal. Definitely, management has three dimensions which are management of people, management of work and management of operation (Tyari, 2023) In other words, there is overlapping function between leadership and management. In explicit way, Mohta (2022) describes management as the integral process of planning, organizing, staffing, direction, controlling and coordinating all activities in as established organisations. In another way, Herrity (2023) conceptualised management as coordination and administration of operation to achieve organizational desired goals per time. Furthermore, some scholars conceptualized management as the act of bringing people together to attain stated aims and objectives efficiently and effectively through available resources (Kaehler and Grundei, 2019).

However, beyond managing of physical resources, church management encompasses managing the spiritual life and growth of members. Church leadership management is also conceived as ministry, stewardship and managing of God's resources (Boaheng, 2021). From business orientation, Kwabena, et al (2021) conceived church management as business function that provides leadership support to organizations' resources to achieve vision and planned goals of the organisation. These scholars argued that, though the church is not a business organisation, but management of church members and resources required provision of leadership and management structure. In Church management leaders are not passive persons, but they are also workers because they have to initiate the activities to be done and also see to it that they are done well. In actual fact, the multicultural combination of the church demands development of management skills in pastoral training that can adequately manage inter-relational activities within the multicultural milieu (Chatira and Mwenje, 2018).

The Conversational Constraint Theory

The theory focuses mode of conversation that individual exhibits at one time or the other. This theory tries to investigate how and why people choose to communicate in a certain manner. Conversational constraint theory provides some common conversational constraint which are clarity, minimizing imposition, consideration for other's feelings, risking negative evaluation by the hearer; and effectiveness (Min-Sun,1994) However, people respond to some of these constraints in different ways. The reason is that there is

individual difference, and several factors such as family background and upbringing, environment and cultural orientation contribute to it.

The church is the body of Christ and community of believers from diverse cultural backgrounds and ethnic nationalities. It is expected that the church should manifest the love of Christ, and live in peace and harmony with one another. The church should be a healthy and loving community regardless of cultural or ethnic background of members. This will only be possible if the leaders and members care about others and are careful about their manner of communication. Some of the indicators highlighted by this theory are so crucial for healthy church management. Management of people demands effective communication. Hence, effective communication requires clarity, and consideration for others' feelings.

Ruben's Behavioural Theory of Intercultural Competence

This theory explored a behavioural approach to examining the gap between knowing and doing, that is, between what people know to be intercultural competence and what they do in intercultural situations (Sinicrope, et al, 2007). The theory constitutes several dimensions that are essential in determining and measuring individual intercultural communicative competence. These dimensions are display of respect, interaction posture, orientation to knowledge, empathy, self-oriented role behaviour, interaction management, and tolerance for ambiguity. The leaders and church members are expected to manifest Christ-like character, respect for people regardless of their cultural affiliation, showing empathy for others and tolerate every member in the congregation no matter social class, sexual orientation and level of service in the church.

Conclusion

The paper reveals that attitude and perception of some leaders towards people from different languages and cultures usually caused conflict in the church. Essentially, wrong attitude and negative perception about people from different language and culture always result to superiority complex and undue segregation in the church. The reality of cultural diversity, uniqueness and importance of every culture should not be neglected or ignored in the church for efficient pastoral ministry, leadership administration and effective service delivery to the congregation without cultural or language discrimination and disparity. This is in tandem with the view of Xiuwen and Razali's concept of intercultural communication skill, which states that, in human society, communication provides a premise to share pluralistic worldview, ideas, moral values, emotional intelligence and feelings, promoting mutual relationship in the society. Intercultural communication or communication between people of different cultural backgrounds has always been and will probably remain an important precondition of human co-existence on earth.

In providing good leadership in the church, the leaders should apply their intercultural communication skills and abilities such as beliefs, values, ethics, character and knowledge as well as selfless service to the Church. Church management is combining the spiritual and the organizational work. In this wise, the Church is both the body of Christ and a human institution. Whilst there are Biblical standards and terms or definitions, philosophies of management are also embedded into Christian Organizations like Churches, and ministries. Most importantly, the purpose of management in Churches is to create a peaceful environment for spiritual service, a sense of shared mission, stewardship of resources and mutual supportiveness.

Recommendations

The purpose of a Christian ministry is not excellent management per se but a means of serving God. Leadership, management and administration of the Church is to be people oriented and participative. The leadership places high value on cooperation and teamwork. Team members are motivated by a shared sense of vision and mission which is more important to them than personal gain. Goals are pursued selflessly and sacrificially. A key concept of leadership, management and administration is to help the team members become more Christ like. Management in Churches is ultimately a partnership with God built on prayer, faith and obedience.

The Bible unveils that right from the period of early church that the first set of Jesus' disciples presided over, identity discrimination was a major conflict. The writer of the Acts of the Apostles explicitly narrated the bias of Hebraic Jews against Hellenistic Jews. In those days when the numbers of disciples were increasing, the Hellenistic Jews among them complained against the Hebraic Jews because their widows were being overlooked in the daily distribution of food. In contemporary time, experiences also show that self-worth and face service are parts of the reasons for several conflict in the church. Identity or Face Negotiation theory deals with people's reaction and identity management during intercultural engagement.

The leadership and member of the church should be able to understand, accept and tolerate the culture of every other people group for the purpose of accommodating one another and fulfilling the purpose of existence of the church. In actual fact, multi-ethnic reality of the church is a basis for the relevance of communication adaptation theory. Experience shows that no church is mono cultural or ethnic. Unfortunately, the contemporary church is characterized with difference social status, disparity, ethnic and cultural discrimination. Members are seen themselves as member of the same cultural background instead of one body of Christ. Accommodation theory sets antidote to ethnocentric and all forms of attitude that are contrary to what the church represents without losing one's original identity and cultural value. This theory is equally relevant in promoting unity, fellowship and mutual love among members of the Church.

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Pastoral Counselling and Domestic Violence in Nigeria: The Way Forward

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Abstract

Pastoral counselling plays a pivotal role in addressing various challenges confronting human beings in the society; be it social, economic, religious and political. There is no gainsaying the fact that in the midst of problems, man needs counselling to serve as succor to the challenges of life. Pastoral counselling is a unique form of psychotherapy that uses spiritual and psychological resources in providing services for people. A close look at the Nigerian society today reveals that the family institution has lost its sacrosanctity as the foundation of the society. An average Nigerian family is faced with various forms of domestic violence that have led to severe injury, deformity and sometimes death. The focus of this paper is to unravel the roles of Pastoral Counseling in curbing domestic violence in the family. Analytical, historical and exegetical methodologies are employed. The findings revealed that domestic violence is caused by factors such as poverty, transfer of aggression and other related factors. The paper recommends effective and proper counseling for families in order to reduce the frequency of domestic violence.

Keywords: Pastoral Counseling, Domestic Violence, Family, Psychotherapy

Introduction

Domestic violence has become a common occurrence in Nigeria contemporary time. A critical look at the society reveals that cases of domestic violence are on the high side and has cut across all facets of the Nigerian society, regardless of age, tribe, religion and social status. Domestic violence takes many forms which include physical, sexual, emotional and mental. In Nigeria, domestic violence is traditionally committed against females. Common forms of violence against women include; rape, acid attacks, molestation, beating and verbal abuse. It is estimated that approximately one in every three women in Nigerian family suffers domestic violence and intimate partner violence from the hands of those who claim to love them. This is not to say that men do not also suffer domestic violence from women (Adekoya,2020). However, there are stories and videos on social media indicating that women are predominantly impacted by domestic violence. A good example is the case of the popular Gospel singer, late Mrs Osinachi Nwachukwu amongst others.

It is important to point out that domestic violence becomes rampant in our society because most victims still shy away from reporting cases of domestic violence to appropriate authorities, due to cultural factors and fear of stigmatization (Afolabi,2022). It is against this background that the researchers intend to examine the role of pastoral counselling in curbing domestic violence in Nigerian family.

The Concept of Pastoral Counselling

Pam (2013) describes pastoral counselling as a type of counselling or psychotherapy where in knowledge and standards stemming from the disciplines of theology and the behavioural sciences are utilized in working with people, couples, families, other sets of people, and cultural systems to reach a place of healing and development. Also, Odeleye (2017) sees pastoral counselling as a helping relationship in which a trained therapist (pastor or minister) assists individuals, couples and families resolve their emotional, relational and psychosocial issues, utilizing the Bible as primary manual. Pastoral counselling is a unique form of counselling which utilizes spiritual and psychological capital to help individuals to understand possible options to attain the balanced life. Odeleye (2022) pointed out that pastoral counseling is a therapeutic relationship between a congruent, stable and coordinated pastoral counselor and an incongruent, disturbed and confused counselee.

The American Association of pastoral counselling (1988) defines pastoral counseling as a unique form of psychotherapy which uses spiritual resources as well as psychological understanding for healing and growth. It is provided by certified pastoral counselors, who are not only mental health professionals but who have also had in-depth religious and theological training. It is imperative to point out that pastoral counseling is a specialized type of "pastoral care". Pastoral care is derived from the biblical image of a shepherd who expresses concern for persons in trouble or distress. The word 'pastor' literally means shepherd, nurturer, watchman, carer. In this sense, pastors have a divine mandate to watch over spirit, soul and body of individuals and families committed to their care.

From the above conception of pastoral counseling, it is obvious that pastoral counselling is a humanitarian service/services rendered by trained pastors to people that are faced with challenges of life ranging from bereavement, trauma, personality disorder, spiritual depression, marital issues, mental health and so on.

Some Principles of Pastoral Counselling

Odeleye (2022) identifies some principles which every pastoral counselor needs to master in order to ensure optimal performance in his ministry. They are as follows:

- **Indepth Knowledge of the Bible:** The Bible is the inspired words of God. It is God's revelation to guide the effective functioning of the human race. The counsellor needs to take the Bible as an integral part of his life before he can function effectively as a pastoral counselor.
- **Prayer and Meditation:** A lifestyle of prayer and communion with the Holy Spirit should be the hallmark of a pastoral counsellor. A prayerful life will enable the counsellor to grow in grace and in the knowledge of His Lord and savior Jesus Christ. In addition to this, the counsellor should be able to meditate on the word of God. One of the keys to making success in therapy is the ability to meditate on the word of God for spiritual guidance.
- **Pragmatic Preaching and Teaching:** The pastoral counsellor should make the pulpit the starting point of his work. The pastor or counselor should make his/her preaching relevant to the needs of the people. It is assumed that not all issues will be addressed in a one-to-one situation, therefore the pastor should be able to proffer solutions to human problems in the course of preaching and teaching.
- **Maintaining Confidentiality:** The counselor should be careful to keep all information the client gives to them in confidence. By this, the counselor earns the

respect of the clients. Some information about the counselee are “classified information”. It therefore behoves the counsellor to treat the information as such. This demands some degree of maturity.

- **Empathy:** Empathy is the ability to place oneself in the shoes of others. It is the ability to share the feelings of others. The counsellor needs to demonstrate Christ love in the course of helping people to solve their problems. In this wise, the counsellor shares the burden of the counselee.
- **Experiencing the New Birth:** Pastoral counselling is not only based on the knowledge of psychology or academic qualifications. The pastoral counselor must be a firm believer in Christ and must be born again. The counsellor needs to have experience the salvation of God through our Lord Jesus Christ. He needs to be energized by the power of the word of God and the Holy Spirit.
- **Fruit of the Spirit:** The counselor should exhibit the fruit of the Holy Spirit as enunciated in Galatians 5: 22-23. Love, Joy, peace, long suffering, gentleness, goodness, faith, meekness, temperance etc. lack of the fruit of spirit will dissuade the pastor from performing his duties as a counselor. It will be difficult for him to have compassion towards others.
- **Attentive Listening:** The counsellor should be a good listener. It is fundamental for a spiritual counselor to possess the ability to listen to others with rapt attention. The counsellor should be a lover of humanity. Active listening conveys to clients that they are valued. However, listening involves every part of the body.

Biblical Foundation to Pastoral Counselling

There are no direct sayings on pastoral counselling in the Bible. However, there are allusions to counselling in the Old and New Testaments. The Christian’s basis for counselling is nothing other than the scriptures. The bible makes it clear that God is in search of bringing healing, a holistic healing to the groaning creation (Ezammo, 2005).

Pastoral Counselling in the Old Testament

The care of God towards His creatures is visible in the creation story as presented in the Book of Genesis. The presence of a God who is active in the affairs of man is everywhere assumed. He demonstrates his act of love and kindness to all creatures. Genesis 1:27 asserts that man is made in the image and likeness of God. This is corroborated in Psalm 8:5 where man is described as “little less than God”. In the anthropology of the Jewish scripture, all aspects of persons, not just their minds or spirits, are perceived as created in the divine image (Howard, 1984).

In the book of Exodus, when Moses was leading the Israelites through the wilderness, he was advised by Jethro his father-in-law, who himself was a priest to appoint helpers to share the work of counseling the people (Exodus 18:1-2). This underscores the importance of counselling in the Old Testament scriptures. Also, the prophets performed the role of counsellors. Aside from interceding and calling the people to repentance, their fundamental role was to proclaim the word of God to the people. They reveal God’s plan to the people who came for help. The prophets stood as mediators between God and the people by intervening in their personal problems. A good example is the case of Isaiah and Hezekiah where the prophet demonstrated personal empathy towards the king.

The Psalms are also reflections of human emotional experiences that are valuable for pastoral counselling. Feelings such as resentment, anxiety, despair on one hand and gratitude, serenity, confidence and joy on the other. The Psalms is therefore meant to encourage the development of positive feelings in the midst of life challenges. Psalms 23 for example emphasize the ‘shepherding role’ of the counselor.

Pastoral Counselling in the New Testament

There are lots of allusions to pastoral care and counseling in the New Testament especially in the life and ministry of Jesus. The New Testament writers used different Greek words to describe the various aspects of counselling. The words “Nouthesia” (giving advice or instruction), “paraklese” (to exhort, comfort, encourage, strengthen), “paramutheomai” (to cheer up, to encourage) and so on. From these Greek words, one can deduce that the word “counselling” contains many ideas depending upon the sort of help needed, and the aim of the counselor (Harold, 1989).

The Gospel of John describes Jesus’ purpose of coming as being so that people could have “life in all its fullness” (John 10:10). The fullness here referred to “wholeness”. Despite human limitations and brokenness, Jesus is a sure guarantor of our wholeness. Jesus as a model counselor had a deep psychic insight to read human mind. His conversation with the Samaritan woman is a good example. All through his ministry, he had compassion and showed love and care for people.

In the Book of Acts, the deacons were anointed to provide social support and care for widows in the early church. Also, in Acts 20:28 Paul admonishes the church elders to keep watch over themselves and all the flocks which the Holy Spirit has made them overseer. “Be shepherds of the Church of God, which he bought with his own blood”. Also, in 1 Peter 5:2, Apostle Peter encouraged the elders to be shepherds of God’s flock that is under their care, watching them not because they must, but because they are willing, as God wants them to be; not pursuing dishonest gain, but eager to serve. In the Epistles, Pastors are listed among other ministers (apostles, prophets, teachers and evangelist), for which Christ gave the gifts “to equip the saints for the work of ministry, for building up the body of Christ” (Ephesians 4:12)”. From the above analysis, it is evident that pastoral care and counseling has its root from the Bible.

The Family

The family is a group of persons united by the ties of marriage, blood, or adoption, constituting a single household and interacting with each other in their respective social position usually those of spouses, parents, children and siblings (Alan, 2023). Basically, the family consists of two married adults, usually a man and a woman along with their offspring. This is known as the nuclear family. It is the basic social unit of the society. The family performs various roles for its members. Some of the roles are; the provision of emotional and psychological security, rearing and socialization of children, provision of food, shelter, clothing, education and physical security for its members.

In most cultures, the family is patriarchal or male-dominated. However, the modern family that emerged after the Industrial Revolution is different from the earlier mode. The patriarchal posture of the family gave way to equality between the sexes. Family responsibility became a shared activity between the husband and the wife. The emancipation of women in the 19th and 20th centuries changed married dramatically, particularly in connection with prosperity and economic status. By the mid-20th century, most western countries had enacted laws

establishing the equality between spouses. However, at the beginning of the 21st century, family notion has become complicated by calls for the acceptance of same-sex marriages and non-traditional family settings.

The average Nigerian family is made up of the father, mother and the children (nuclear family). In addition, the extended family system is still rampant in Nigeria like any other African countries. Despite the fact that the western lifestyle is slowly sipping into the Nigerian community, the issue of marriage or even the family system at large is not a private one, these two institutions are rarely established without the interference of the extended family members (Caldwell & Orubuloye, 1991). It is important to point out that in Nigeria (like other African countries), men are still dominant in private and public life. According to Ogundipe-Leslie (1994) 'the ideology that men are naturally superior to women In all areas, affects the modern-day organization of societal structures'.

Emphasis has always been placed on the male especially in the family system; mainly because the families in Nigeria are patrilineal, the males are seen as continuity of both family names and lineage. Women are generally seen as playing a second fiddle, with limited freedom. She is mostly restricted to child bearing and household duties.

Domestic Violence in Nigeria

The average Nigerian family is beset with so many problems ranging from poverty, infidelity, alcoholism, barrenness, pressure at workplace, financial problem and so on (Monday, 2010). The focus of this paper is the issue of domestic violence among Nigerian families. There is no gain saying the fact that domestic violence is a pervasive issue that affects the societies worldwide, with Nigeria being no exception. This silent pandemic has continued to erode the social fabric of Nigeria, leaving countless individuals, particularly women and children traumatized.

United Nations (1993) defines domestic violence as a pattern of behaviours in any relationship that is used to gain or maintain power and control over an intimate partner which could be physical, sexual, emotional, economic or psychological actions or threat of actions that influence another person. Also, section 18(g) of Lagos State domestic violence law defines domestic violence to include physical abuse, sexual abuse, exploitation including but not limited to rape, incest, and sexual assault, starvation, emotional, verbal and psychological abuse, economic abuse and exploitation; intimidation, harassment, hazardous attack... etc (Morohunfolo, 2021).

Recent studies reveal that domestic violence is on the increase in Nigeria. According to a study commissioned by the Ministry of Women's Affairs and Social Development and the United Nation's Population Fund (UNPA), 28% of Nigerian women aged 25-29 have experienced some form of physical violence since age 15. Also, according to the National Bureau of Statistics (2019), 30% of Nigerian women aged 15-49 have experienced physical violence, while 68% have encountered emotional, economic or sexual abuse. However, it is important to note that it is not only women that suffer domestic violence in Nigeria. Researches have also shown that men are also subjected to domestic violence. It is recorded that out of a total of 48 victims of domestic violence in Nigeria, 10.4% were males. However, these figures are undoubtedly underreported, as victims are faced with the barriers of cultural stigmas, fear of retribution and lack of trust in the legal system.

The causes of domestic violence in Nigeria include factors such as; gender inequality, harmful cultural practices, poverty, lack of education etc. The persistent adherence to patriarchal

norms and beliefs contribute significantly to domestic violence against women. Moreover, harmful practices such as child marriage, female genital mutilation enhance these nefarious acts. Coupled with the above is the fact that the Nigerian judicial system is not robust enough to combat the menace of domestic violence.

Some Cases of Domestic Violence

There are numerous cases of domestic violence in recent times. According to the Lagos State Domestic and Sexual Violence Agency (DSVA, 2022), the agency received over 4,800 cases of domestic violence from September, 2021 to July, 2022. A strong case of domestic violence in Nigeria is that of a popular gospel singer, Osinachi Nwachukwu who died after suffering from alleged domestic violence from her husband, Peter Nwachukwu. Similarly, a man named David Idibie was arrested for allegedly beating his wife Julianah Idibie to death at the Ajah area of Lagos State. In April, 2022, one Anulika Aguru, a mother of seven died in Ebonyi State following alleged domestic violence by her husband. These are few cases of reported domestic violence that has led to the death of the victims. It is pertinent to say that women are majorly the victims of domestic violence.

Impact of domestic violence

There are many negative impacts of domestic violence on individuals and the society. Firstly, domestic violence may cause serious injury and sometimes *death to the victim*. *Even if it does not lead to death, it causes some psychological distress or trauma to the victim. It reduces the personality of the victim, and may also lead the victim to a state of depression.* Secondly, domestic violence affects the emotional state of the children in the affected family. *The children of the victims of domestic violence might become exposed to violence and other ungodly behaviours. In the aspect of education, such children may experience low academic performance because of lack of concentration.* Thirdly, domestic violence is a dishonor to the family and the marriage institution. God instituted marriage as a means of companionship and togetherness. The man and the woman leave their parents to become one flesh. It is therefore pertinent to say that domestic violence is a crime against humanity

Pastoral Counselling and Domestic Violence

It should be noted that domestic violence and abuse can cause emotional disturbances such as self-hatred, guilt, despair, psychological trauma and self-annihilation. One should understand that a common symptom of mental disturbance is the loss of a sense of reality (Davies, 2014). In situations like that, pastoral counseling becomes necessary. The pastoral counsellor needs the knowledge of the spiritual and the emotional aspects of health as well as the socio-cultural structures, individual's psychological structures and social context. The pastoral counselor should understand the distress of the victim of domestic violence and should be eager to lead the victims out of the situation into right relationship with themselves, the world and God (Collin, 2003). An image from the Old Testament poetically describes this process: "For in the wilderness shall waters break out, and streams in the desert" (Isaiah, 35:7-10). In this passage, healing from emotional wounds is compared to the streams of water breaking out in the wilderness or desert to revive, bring relief and quench the thirst of a person going through emotional dryness, loneliness or pain (Davies 2014).

A pastoral counsellor is looked upon as a person of faith who is committed and trustworthy (Vanghan, 1987:17). He understands the value of God's power as a result, he needs the

instrument of prayer to counsel the victim of domestic violence. Prayer can provide spiritual support for people suffering from anxiety and depression, by giving them a sense of belonging and comfort. Pastoral care and counseling should provide emotional support for survivors of domestic violence. According to Bay (2008), individuals who received pastoral care are better equipped both emotionally and spiritually. Pastoral counseling includes listening, understanding and building a trusting relationship, as well as treating the person with compassion, dignity and respect (Newett, 2009).

Amongst the various therapeutic methods used by pastoral counsellors in solving the problems of domestic violence, narrative counselling and logotherapy are identified as appropriate methods (Bigear, 2010). These two methods are compatible with religious themes such as 'hope' and 'new life'. In narrative method, the aim is for people to find hope. The stories of the past and memories are searched to discover meaning in life and the individual is guided to develop a new future story (Muller, 2010). In narrative pastoral counseling, the narrative of the individual is merged with the story of Christ. Logotherapy method is a model of psychotherapy which focuses on the meaning of life. It allows the counselor to enter the counsellee's emotional sphere and then bring about a new meaning in life (Frank, 2004).

The point of departure between psychologists and pastoral counsellors is that psychologists assist people with troubled lives and dysfunctional relationships to move to a healthier, functioning life and relationships while pastoral counselors for instance make use of biblical themes and spiritual devices such as prayer. Survivors of domestic violence need the services of pastoral counselors to handle the trauma caused by domestic violence.

Conclusion

This paper examines the relevance of pastoral counseling in addressing the menace of domestic violence in Nigeria. The researchers observed that domestic violence is one of the major social vices in the contemporary Nigeria society that has led to distress, emotional and psychological trauma, despair, annihilation, hatred and loss of self-dignity in the lives of survivors. It was also discovered that women and children are majorly the victims of domestic violence when compared to the number of men. The paper therefore submits that pastoral counseling has a major role to play in helping the survivors to come out of the trauma of domestic abuse.

Recommendations

- i. Pastors and other church ministers should embark on effective marriage counseling for their members and those who approach them for marriage counseling.
- ii. Premarital seminars should be organized for youths in the church in order to take precautions before going into marriage.
- iii. The church should educate the people to seek for "safety" whenever they observe any form of domestic abuse in their marriages.
- iv. Pastoral counselors should adopt an effective, biblical base method of counseling the victims of domestic violence.
- v. Pastoral counselors should show the feeling of 'empathy' for survivors of domestic violence, in the process of counseling.
- vi. Pastoral counselors should be well equipped with the Bible and also be prayerful in their work of counseling the people.

- vii. Pastoral counselors should understand the principles of human psychology in order to make their job easier.
- viii. The pastoral counselor should endeavour to develop the skills of bringing hope to people that are experiencing the trauma of domestic violence.
- ix. Government should establish a strong judiciary system to address cases of domestic violence.
- x. Lastly, people should be educated on the need to cry out whenever they are being abused.

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An Appraisal of Intercultural Competence as a Predictor of Effective Pastoral Counselling

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Abstract

One vital quality which a pastoral counsellor should possess is intercultural competence. Intercultural competence refers to the ability to understand, appreciate, and adapt to different cultural norms, values, and communication styles. This paper looks into the place of intercultural competence in effective pastoral counseling. Intercultural competence is very vital because the counselling profession is relational and because all counselling is cross-cultural—the counsellor deals with clients who are culturally varied in terms of race, ethnicity, social economic status, educational background, family background, age and gender. This means that pastoral counselling cannot be done the same way with every client. The ability of the counsellor to cross to the culture of the client, while still retaining his own culture, requires intercultural competence. The author adopted the Fantini's model to describe the four dimensions in which intercultural competence can be measured. They are: intercultural knowledge, intercultural attitude, intercultural skill and intercultural awareness. Intercultural competence enables effective intercultural communication, which in turn results in effective pastoral counselling. This work reveals that this competence can be developed through conscious efforts. An interculturally competent counsellor is more likely to address the client's major problems more effectively due to the counsellor's ability to approach counselling within the context of the client's world. It is recommended in this paper that pastoral counsellors should undergo periodic assessment tests on intercultural competence so that areas of needed adjustment could be identified and proper adjustments made.

Keywords: Intercultural Competence, Pastoral Counsellor, Counselling, Effective, Culture

Introduction

Many scholars in the field of Counselling have highlighted the essential qualities which a pastoral counsellor needs to possess. For instance, Adams mentions spiritual knowledge of the will of God, divine wisdom in one's relationship to others and good will and concern for other members of the body of Christ as requisite qualities of a good pastoral counsellor (Adams, 1986). Collins lists seven qualities of effective counselors which are: psychological health, a genuine interest in people, empathy, personal warmth, self-awareness, awareness of values and tolerance of ambiguity (Collins, 2007). In the opinion of Odeleye, a pastoral counselor should possess the following characteristics: adept knowledge of the Bible, a lifestyle of prayer and meditation, pragmatic preaching and teaching skill, maintaining confidentiality, empathy, new birth experience, a personal life of purity, fruit of the spirit, attentive listening and referral (Odeleye, 2022). Yet, there is a vital quality which a pastoral counselor should possess and which has not been so much emphasized—that is intercultural competence. Thus, the focus of this paper is to look into the place of intercultural competence in doing an effective pastoral counseling. For the purpose of this study, "culture" encompasses ethnicity, race, gender, social and economic status, educational background and the like and "pastoral counsellor" refers to a Christian or biblical counsellor.

Effective Pastoral Counselling

According to Sohn (1951), pastoral counseling is such "a personal and dynamic relationship between two or more people, one of whom is a pastor, who approach a problem for the purpose of finding a solution to it on the proper basis." It should be noted from the above definition that counselling work is relationship between two or more people who may be coming from different cultural orientations. Collins defines pastoral counselling as a "more specialized part of pastoral care that involves helping individuals, families, or groups as they cope with the pressures and crises of life (Adams, 1986)." These "individuals" usually are culturally varied in terms of race, ethnicity, social economic status, educational background, family background, age, etc. Odeleye submits that "pastoral counselling is a therapeutic relationship between a congruent, stable and coordinated pastoral counsellor and an incongruent, disturbed and confused counsellee (church member, congregant)." He, however, notes that there are times when the counsellee is not exactly disturbed or confused but will just like to seek more information or clarification on certain issues of interest (Odeleye, 2022).

One common denominator in all these definitions is that counselling is essentially relational and because the counsellor and his client are often culturally varied, the counsellor will be crossing from his own culture to the culture of the counsellee. This suggests that, in addition to other qualities earlier mentioned, the pastoral counsellor must be interculturally competent in order to have an effective pastoral counselling.

Intercultural Competence

Intercultural competence is generally understood to be someone's ability to interact appropriately and effectively with others in possession of different cognitive, affective, and behavioural orientations towards the world in intercultural situations (Hang & Zhang, 2023). According to Zelenková and Hanesová, an intercultural competent person can be described as a person "not only with some acquired knowledge on culture and its cognitive comprehension, but also competent to demonstrate intercultural empathy, respect, tolerance, sensitivity and flexibility, as well as the openness to negotiate, the ability to argue, the good will to understand others, discuss with them, and reach consensus (Zelenková & Hanesová, 2019)."

Thus, interculturality penetrates into all three dimensions of personality and relationships. For instance, it penetrates into the cognitive domain because a person should be aware of his own culture and other people's cultures before he could be deemed to be intercultural competent. It also penetrates into the affective domain because such a person is expected to be empathetic, tolerant and appreciative of cultural diversities. Lastly, intercultural competence penetrates into the behavioural domain because such a person is expected to possess good interaction and cooperation skills. Therefore, intercultural competence refers to the ability to understand, appreciate, and adapt to different cultural norms, values, and communication styles. The concept of intercultural competence was first muted by Bennett, who proposed a developmental approach to training for intercultural sensitivity. He suggests that individuals with intercultural sensitivity tend to transform themselves from the ethnocentric stage to the ethno-relative stage. By ethnocentrism he refers to the experience of looking at one's own culture as central to reality. Beliefs, values and behaviours acquired through primary socialization are seen as adequate descriptors of the way things are. By ethnorelativism he refers to the experience of viewing one's own culture as just one organization of reality amongst many legitimate possibilities. This developmental model is a conceptual framework that describes the stages individuals go through as they develop intercultural competence. Bennett identifies six distinct types of experience across the continuum from ethnocentrism to ethno-relativism: denial, defense, minimization, acceptance, adaptation and integration. Each stage represents a different level of intercultural sensitivity and competence. These stages provide a good framework for determining how to improve the capacity for intercultural competence (Bennett, 1986).

Another influential scholar is Michael Byram. Byram makes a significant contribution to the field of intercultural competence in the context of language education. He emphasizes the importance of developing intercultural communicative competence, stressing that this competence goes beyond language proficiency to include one's ability to appreciate and navigate cultural diversity (Byram, 2020).

Several other scholars have subsequently contributed by applying the concept of intercultural competence to several areas of human endeavour: from education, business, economy and politics to religion and military work. For instance, Han calls

for adult education and Human Resource Development professionals to acquire intercultural competence by applying adult learning theories in cross-cultural learning, in order to help various people from diverse cultural backgrounds. He believes this will help them to become successful in their international assignments (Han, 2010). Hang and Zhang are of the opinion that the rate of worldwide mobility of students and increasing globalization and internationalization of university and college campuses call for the cultivation of students' intercultural competence. They believe that this will enable them to communicate effectively on campus and even in campuses outside their home countries (Hang & Zhang, 2023).

Olagbaju discusses how education, with Literature-in-English as a tool, can be used to teach intercultural communicative competence in multicultural classrooms in Nigeria, thereby facilitating cross-cultural competence. He identifies cultural diversity as one of the major factors responsible for incessant civil unrest, hate speeches and insecurity in different parts of the country (Olagbaju, 2020).

Bradford and Bradford apply the concept to the U.S Navy. They stress that the Sea Services must reinforce their relationship with global maritime partners and in order for this to be possible the force has to embrace international organizations, local mariners and commercial operators. The diversity of partners and their cultural backgrounds would necessitate the mariners' intercultural competence to be built over time (Bradford & Bradford, 2008). Tucker and others look at intercultural competence with respect to its importance in global leadership. According to them, for business organizations to be successful, they need leaders who can drive business on a global scale. In these days of globalization and high competitiveness, no major company can be satisfied with being successful in the home market, or even in one or two cross-border markets. Even if a major company chooses not to expand globally, international competitors will enter its favorite markets. These scholars therefore submit that leading across cultures is a critical element in driving a business enterprise to a great success (Tucker, Bonial, Vanhove & Kedhamath, 2014).

Cross-cultural Nature of Counselling

According to Collins, "all counselling is cross-cultural." He believes that cross-cultural issue in counselling does not have to do with tribal, racial or ethnic affiliations alone. "You are counselling cross-culturally if you work with someone of an age, background, gender, level of education, set of values, socio-economic status, belief system and sexual orientation that differs from yours (Collins, 2007)." Of course, all of the above elements combine to form an individual's worldview. This implies that pastoral counselling cannot be applied the same way to every client. The counsellor should be able to cross to the culture of the counsellee. This may account for why the biblical Paul says:

And unto the Jews I became as a Jew, that I might gain the Jews; to them that are under the law, as under the law, that I might gain them that are under the law; To them that are without law, as without law, (being not without law to God, but under the law to

Christ,) that I might gain them that are without law. To the weak became I as weak, that I might gain the weak: I am made all things to all men, that I might by all means save some (1Corinthians 9.20-22).

During His earthly ministry, Jesus was always aware of cultural differences. His counselling, preaching and one-on-one contacts revealed His awareness of cultural differences. The way He talked with the Samaritan woman was quite different from the way He approached Jewish leaders, fishermen, or Roman officers like Pilate or Herod (Collins, 2007).

Augsburger, one of the pioneers of cross-cultural pastoral counselling, once argued for the need for a culturally capable (or competent) pastoral counsellor who possesses the ability to join another in their culture while fully retaining his own culture. His objective was to assist in training culturally able counsellors who will be able to cross over effectively into another culture while still retaining their own (Augsburger, 1986). This means that for pastoral counsellors to be effective, they should be able to cross over to the culture of the client, without losing their own cultural values.

Dimensions of Intercultural Competence (Fantini's Model)

One popular categorization of intercultural competence is the one given by Fantini in his assessment scale. He divides intercultural competence into four dimensions which are: intercultural knowledge, intercultural attitude, intercultural skill and intercultural awareness. These four dimensions can be used for self assessment.

Intercultural Knowledge: This dimension is also considered as the conceptual aspect of intercultural competence. Intercultural knowledge is taken into consideration as an individual's skills to have relevant information which would help the individual to interact with people from the other culture personally. This includes knowledge of the essential norms and taboos of the host culture; knowledge of the history of the host community; ability to cite important historical and socio-political factors that shape one's culture and the host culture and the ability to contrast important aspects of the host language and culture with one's own in a cross-cultural setting.

Intercultural Attitude: This dimension includes being curious about different cultures, being empathic, open-minded and having respect for differences. Therefore, the following are some of the variables under intercultural attitude: ability to interact with people of other cultures, learn from them, eat local foods, feel safe and use the native dress in a cross-cultural setting. It also includes showing interest in new cultural aspects and dealing with emotions and frustrations with other cultures.

Intercultural Skill: The ability to listen to people from other cultures, observe other cultures, interpret, analyse, evaluate and relate them. Besides, skills to learn a second or third language, skills to stand up to the difficulties faced during the process of learning a second or third language, skills to interrelate languages with each other, listening skills, information gathering skills and problem-solving skills are among the intercultural skills.

Intercultural Awareness: This refers to individual's ability to see the similarities and differences between their own culture and the other culture with a criticising point of view. The following are some of the variables under intercultural awareness: being aware of differences and similarities across one's own culture and another culture; being aware of diversity in the host culture and being aware of one's personal values affecting one's approach to ethical dilemmas in a cross-cultural setting (Fantini, 2007). Therefore, a person can be said to be interculturally competent having possessed the skills mentioned above.

Impact of Intercultural Competence on Pastoral Counselling

Intercultural competence enables effective intercultural communication, which in turn results in effective pastoral counselling. Intercultural competence involves much more than mastering a foreign language or understanding non-verbal communication. Gleaning from the opinion of scholars above, it is the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately with others having different cultural backgrounds, and because counselling is communication and cross-cultural, lack of intercultural competence leads to misunderstanding and the breaking of relationships. Cultural stereotypes have been found to be among the most important barriers to effective intercultural communication. Intercultural competence eliminates communication obstacles such as misunderstandings because of cultural differences, cultural stereotypes, and language barriers (Szóke, 2018).

Pastoral Counsellor's Intercultural Competence Development

The American Psychological Association has published a list of terms for counselling ethics when engaging with clients of linguistic and culturally diverse populations. The list includes:

- Counsellors should educate their clients on the goals, expectations and scope of counseling as well as the counselor's own orientation.
- Counsellors should acknowledge ethnicity and culture as important parameters in understanding psychological processes.
- Counsellors should respect the roles of family and community values and beliefs in the client's culture.
- Counsellors should try to communicate in the language requested by the client. If this is not possible, the client can be referred to another counsellor.
- Counsellors should try to eliminate biases and prejudices (Khoo, Abu-Rasain & Hornby, 2002).

Collins' opinion goes in line with the foregoing. He provides five multicultural competencies which a Christian counsellor needs to learn and practice:

- The counsellor should develop awareness of his/her own cultural values and biases.

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- This could happen through personal assessment of one's biases which could negatively affect the counselling process. External assistance could be sought for a proper assessment to be done.
 - The counsellor should try and become aware of the cultural background of each counsellee. This implies a deliberate search for facts about the different groups the counsellor encounters.
 - The counsellor should seek to understand the ways in which culturally diverse counsellees see the world.

This could be made possible through a deliberate effort to make friends or relate with people who are culturally different.

- The counsellor could benefit from an understanding of cultural adaptation.
- This means that he should be ready to walk through the acculturation process.
- The counsellor should develop and use appropriate counselling strategies and techniques (Collins, 2007). For instance, counsellors should respect their client's religious views, values, beliefs, indigenous practices, and languages.

Conclusion and Recommendation

It has been established through this paper that pastoral counsellors have an obligation to grow in intercultural competence in order to be effective. The counselling relationship becomes strengthened when a counsellor is interculturally competent. An interculturally competent counsellor is more likely to address the client's major problems more effectively due to the counsellor's ability to approach counselling within the context of the client's world. Therefore, counsellor's own cultural values or bias must not take precedence over that of the client. It is recommended that pastoral counsellors undergo periodic assessment tests on intercultural competence so that areas of needed adjustment could be identified and proper adjustments made. The counsellor can make use of Fantini's dimensions of intercultural competence mentioned above for self-assessment (Fantini, 2007).

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The Book of Ruth on Widow's Challenges, and Pastoral Counselling for Effective Widow Empowerment among Nigerian Christians

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Abstract

Pastoral counseling as a practice of ministry and discipline, serves as a theological bridge discipline connecting ministry, marriage and family therapy. Among the points in Theopsychology of Pastoral Counseling is the fact that the Bible presents God's recipe for wholesome living. Many tragic and traumatising circumstances in life befall people and Christians are not exempted. Widowhood is one of such traumas. Widowhood is an inevitable tragic human phenomenon which nearly every married person experiences. While the degree of pain varies according to age and other socio-economic factors, the gravity of its trauma is evident in the usual immediate sympathetic response to widows or widowers. Scholarly engagements of the book of Ruth have focused on many areas such as Davidic ancestry, levirate, land redemption, hesed-kindness, polemics, widowhood and others. While scholarly works abound on widowhood, not much has been done in relating widow empowerment schema of the book of Ruth to pastoral counseling. Using descriptive method and narrative criticism, this article analyses the text of Ruth to expound different modes of widow empowerment as tool for effective pastoral care and counseling on widowhood. It does so based on findings which reveal that widow challenges vary from different cultures and social settings but the book of Ruth provides a veritable and inclusive empowerment pattern.

Keywords: Widow's empowerment, Pastoral care/counseling, Book of Ruth, Widowhood in Christendom

Introduction

Widowhood, a phenomenon where a married person loses the spouse, is something that transcends culture, ethnicity, religion, educational background and socio-economic state, thus, it is a global phenomenon. It is an ageless and almost unavoidable reality for a married person that usually comes with its attendant challenges of agony and pains. It is a phenomenon that can happen at any stage in the life of a married person. But due to culture and traditions in some places (especially in Africa and Asia), the agony of widowhood is abysmally enormous especially for a widow. A widow is described as a silent victim in terms of socio-economic, psychological and human right violation in many African countries. They face economic hardship and emotional imbalances coupled with social victimisations of all sort (Oluwatunbi, 2009,149). Widowhood can result due to many causes such as poverty, sickness, road traffic accident and violence. As a nation, Nigeria has witnessed so many security issues in recent years the result of which has also increased the cases of widowhood. While widowhood readily attracts sympathy, some of their peculiar needs such as psycho-emotional needs, sexual needs, security needs and others are not met by the various humanitarian gestures from the society. Brian Croft and Austin Walker reinforce this, when they state that few circumstances in life can be as devastating as the loss of a husband. They

further aver that though a husband also goes through grief and intensely feels the sense of desolation arising from the demise of a wife; the Bible has comparatively little to say about living as a widower, while it has so much to say about being a widow. One inferable reason for this distinction, perhaps, is the fact that a widower is not in the same vulnerable and precarious position as a widow (Croft, & Walker, 2015, 15).

Further to this, many widows are exposed to degrading experiences such as sexual harassment, food and financial insecurity, accusations or maltreatment from the late husband's family, sexual immorality and so on. Ordinarily, the situation of a widow elicits sympathy even if the said widow is financially stable. Beatrice Schwartz, A widowed healthcare professional, asserts that no one can prepare a widow for what she faces. Unfortunately, still, her agony seems not to be felt by the world around her (Stockton, 2015). The book of Ruth is a short Biblical narrative. Though small in volume, the book addresses critical social and economic issues. In the pages of this unique text are issues such as migration, inter-communal relationship, famine, harvest, widows' welfare as well as divine providence. Ruth reveals that even in situations of spiritual apostasy and gross moral decadence, God looks for devout individuals upon whom He can bestow His blessing. The book projects the sovereign acts of God in the lives of self-effacing and unassuming individuals at the time of the Judges, the charismatic leaders of pre-monarchical Israel. The amazing story narrates how a family from Bethlehem, in the horrible days of judges receives God's blessing in an unexpected way when gross moral disorder and spiritual decline held sway.

While scholars have ascribed different themes to the book, Ruth narrative implicitly discusses widows' challenges and provides helpful tips that offer framework for widow counseling and empowerment. Since Pastoral Counseling is a kind relationship or activity in which a pastor or minister assists individuals, couples and families resolve their emotional, relational and psychosocial issues with the use of the Bible as primary manual (Odeleye, 2017), application of the book of Ruth, especially its widow empowerment scheme, is therefore appropriate in pastoral counseling and widowhood. Thus, this article explores widow empowerment in the book of Ruth as pastoral counseling tool.

Pastoral Theology and Counseling

It is said that pastoral theology is difficult to define with precision owing to the ambiguity of its boundaries with related disciplines such as practical theology and applied theology (Tidball, 1998, 493). But it concerns the theory and the practice of Christian ministry as right practice proceeds from right belief. Pastoral theology has to do with the relationship between theology and pastoral task; providing theological foundation for pastoral ministry and stimulating reflections on pastoral experience, and at the same time, reflecting on theology from a pastoral perspective (Tidball, 1998). Primarily, Pastoral Theology is concerned with three major areas of local church ministry which are: leadership, pastoral care, and public ministry (Hill, n.d). Thus pastoral counselling fittingly subsumes under pastoral care which is an arm of pastoral theology.

Pastoral counselling is about care for the total man- body, soul/spirit. "Pastor" is a Latin word for 'shepherd' (Hill, n.d) and it literally means nurturer, watchman or care giver (Odeleye, 2022). The role of a pastor as primarily parental is better indicated in Roman Catholic tradition by the priestly title 'Father'. While biblical warrant for such a parental emphasis exists, the Protestant preference is that of regarding the pastor as an under-shepherd of Jesus Christ.

Thus, N. Pam's description of Pastoral Counselling as a type of counselling or psychotherapy in which knowledge and standards from theology and behavioural sciences are employed in working with people... and cultural systems to attain healing and development; and Odeleye's submission that, it is a helping relationship wherein a pastor assists individuals, couples and families to resolve their emotional, relational and psychosocial issues, using the Bible as fundamental manual, are apt about care giving (Pam, 2013; Odeleye, 2022). Widows, undoubtedly, are a group needing pastoral counseling.

The Book of Ruth

The book of Ruth is a narrative of how a family from Bethlehem migrates from Bethlehem to Moab during the anarchistic period of the Judges. The story is built around three main characters: Naomi, Ruth and Boaz. Elimelech, his wife Naomi and two sons: Mahlon and Chilion leave their homeland to seek food security and succor in Moab. The migration is as a result of famine. The irony of the matter, however, is that they migrate from Bethlehem- *house of food* on account of famine to settle in the land of Moab. Mahlon and Chilion marry Moabite women: Ruth and Orpah. But soon afterwards, the man Elimelech dies, leaving his wife, Naomi, widowed. Naomi loses not only her husband but also her two sons who die leaving her and two widowed daughters-in-law. Three widows are left in the family. In fact, Naomi, the wife of the Elimelech cries that she has become empty (1:21). Following the tragedy, Naomi decides to return back to Bethlehem her homeland. Ruth, one of her widowed daughters-in-law, returns with her to Bethlehem to begin a new life.

However, unless an intervention comes from someone to support these distressed women, their only expectation is a life of destitution and solitude. God actually intervenes through the agency of empowerment. Although the book is placed in the historical period of the judges- a time characterised by apostasies, irresponsibility, cruelty and anarchy, Reed finds that the place of God is very prominent in the book. According to him, different names of God are used profusely in the book and on two occasions, the author speaks of God's sovereign, superintending grace on behalf of the main characters: Naomi, Ruth and Boaz (2000, 415-429). Mathew Micahel also substantiates this when he states that one of three theologies that can be highlighted from Ruth is that of divine providence. According to him, the book emphasises the act of providence in Naomi and Ruth's return to Bethlehem and ultimately in the meeting of Ruth and Boaz (2015, 170). As such, by divine providence and twist of events the desolate widows receive God's blessing in an unexpected way in the age of gross moral disorder and spiritual decline. The wealthy man, Boaz, recognises Ruth's dedication, genuine love and commitment. He shows her compassion and in the course of time, marries her. The union produces the grandparents of the great king David.

The book of Ruth is a simple story. In it are no battles or military conquests. There is just a poignant, powerful story about a pair of widowed women struggling to survive during a difficult time. From the story emerges the fact that God is at work and He quietly directs things behind the scene to bring about deliverance to clean the mess created in the book of Judges; and prefiguring David as man for the job (Hayes, & Duvall, 2011, 157-158).

While in the Jewish Bible-*Tanakh*, Ruth is after Proverbs (at the head of a sub-group of books called *Megillot* or 'scrolls') and before Song of Songs, it is placed in between Judges and 1 Samuel in the Christian cannon. Insertion of the story of Ruth between the books of Judges and Samuel in the Christian scripture derives from the Septuagint and Vulgate, which is more or less a chronological order. This location somewhat connects Ruth with the poem of the

virtuous woman in proverb 31 and the Song of Songs wherein the woman takes leading role in the relationship (Longman III, & Dillard, 2013, 144). This probably gives hint about the role of woman in the book.

As regards it literature, the book is a literary masterpiece arranged into four chapters carved almost like a four-act drama. It has a clear opening and a concluding paragraph in each chapter (or scene), and each one centres on important discourse (Arnold & Beyer, 2015, 162). Unlike Characters in other historical books, the book of Ruth is not about great political or religious figures like kings, judges, prophets or priests. Naomi's husband, Elimelech, and his family, are average Israelites negotiating their way through the day-to-day affairs of life (Arnold & Beyer, 2015). Ruth describes simple and rustic life. While it has moral teachings about God, it apparently teaches about women's resilience especially when they work in harmony. Though it is a book in patriarchal epoch, it describes womenfolk as taking advantage of patriarchal structures in pursuit of survival (Phiri, 2006, 319). Not only this, it as well pictures how women, particularly widows can be empowered, and how the empowered women can transform their social outlook.

Different purposes have been associated with the book. Matthew Michael notes as follows: Some have seen the purpose of the book to be romance or propaganda aimed at justifying marriage to gentile women. In this wise, the book is believed by those sharing this view to be a polemic against the pious Ezra's reformation which objects to marriage of Israelite men to foreign women (Ezra 9). Evangelical Christians, on the other hand, understand the book to be dealing with divine providence in the inclusion of gentiles in the family line of David and ultimately, Christ. In this connect, the book of Ruth serves as prototype of the inclusion of the gentile world in the divine plan of human salvation which is expounded in the New Testament (2015). Others also note that the book is written to stir faith in the hearts of the returning exile; while some others hold the opinion that the book is a *midrash* on a Bethlehem fertility cult myth. Still further, reversal of fortune (emptiness-fullness), demonstration of levirate, *hesed*-kindness and *go'el*-redemption are various purposes advanced for the book. However, Olawale Peter (2021) argues that widow empowerment is a dominant motif in the book. His widow empowerment scheme in the text provides counselling tool that can be engaged in pastoral counselling.

Widowhood and Widow Challenges

Usually, widows are socially excluded category in many societies. Narayan affirms that data suggest that in many cultures across the globe and among the poor, to become a widow is tantamount to "social death." This is so as widows are seen as omen of death and misfortune, and they are considered a burden, as useless, and as easy prey. She further affirms that combination of social prejudices, traditions, and lack of accountability on the part of state institutions demonstrates why widows face great risk of social exclusion and poverty (1999, 205). Mary Nwogu comments further that for a woman who loses her husband, there abound experiences of serious agony and sadness which get further complicated by both secluded and communal mistreatment she faces. Widows are abused physically, economically, sexually and psychologically (2015). This makes pastoral counseling based on integrated or holistic widow empowerment to be of urgent and immense imperativeness to address different spheres of widows' lives.

Problems Associated with Widowhood

The trauma that comes on women when she gets news of her husband's demise is just the beginning of many challenges to come. Blessed A. Enekeme says when a woman cries profusely on hearing of the husband's death, she does that not only for the death, but also for fear of the type of trauma she is soon to face from the society, especially from her in-laws (2015, 2). Thus, shock, fears, stigmatization, depression, aloofness, poor health, difficulty in finance are some of the immediate and remote effects of widowhood. Some of these are further itemized and briefly discussed.

Poverty

Poverty goes beyond finance only. For a normal person, well-being or good life is multidimensional and has both material and psychological dimensions. Well-being involves peaceful mind, good health, sense of belonging in a community, safety, freedom to choose and act, reliable and steady source of income as well as food. As Deepa Narayan puts it; being poor involves painful and humiliating stigma and this perpetually leads to segregation (1999, 199). It predisposes the poor to insolence, disgrace, and callous treatment by both individual and communal agents within the society from whom they seek help. Many widows in traditional societies have this to. They have next- to-no rights of inheritance in their father's holdings, and in instances where they can inherit, it is not on an equal basis with male siblings. Since there are no inheritance rights for the widows, they normally depend mostly on the charity of their husband's families who are mostly hostile. "Property-grabbing" and "chasing off" are things that widows usually experience. The combination of illiteracy and absence of training in any trade further worsen situation and further aggravate the poverty level of widows in many climes. Therefore, widowhood reduces a widow to a beggarly status especially where the husband is the sole breadwinner.

Difficulty in Remarriage

Another serious and yet often overlooked problem of the widows is remarriage. On many occasions, a widower is left with other wives (in the event of a polygamy), or may remarry. The situation is not the same for widows. In the event of a polygyny, they are left in competition with co-wives for property. Also in a monogamous marriage, most widows find it difficult to remarry due to certain constraints of male-dominated society. Whereas a widower is usually encouraged to remarry as soon as possible, widows in many societies are ostracized for attempting the same. Sometimes also, widowers may find a willing marital partner but if she has children, difficulty ensues because the man may not want added financial and social burden of providing for the new wife and her Children.

Health Effects

Ill health is not far from a place where poverty abound. Due to shock, inadequate diet, poor housing, impediment to decent health care, susceptibility to attack and dehumanizing widowhood rites experienced by many widows, they become victims of serious health issues such as chronic depression and infections. Also in some places, compelling the widows into sexual acts with nominated personages in the bid to expel malevolent spirits and cutting her hair with unsterile object predispose them to sexually transmitted infections and other scary diseases like HIV/AIDS. Unfortunately, when such happens, the widow is said to be getting consequences of some secret sin, when in actual fact, she is just a victim of circumstance.

Akinbi (2015) also notes that many of them are diagnosed more with hypertension in consequence of burdens they bear unassisted.

Psychological Effect

One other unpleasant consequence of widowhood is emotional derangement and psychological instability that many widows experience and which predispose them to shock, momentary or long-lasting memory loss (amnesia). This happens as Gbile Akanni appropriately remarks that "because of certain societal customs and beliefs that are contrary to the welfare of widows, they are often looked down upon, shamefully-treated and denied their rights" (2001, 20). Many widows lose sense of worth and see themselves as inferior. Apart from this, loneliness and fears are other psychological problems a widow encounters. When the husband dies, a woman misses many things like companionship, responsibility of the children's welfare, consultation on crucial matters and decision making. Thus, some develop Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and some consider option of suicidal attempt. Summing it up, Okorafor Nkemdilim posits that the greatest problem of all that a widow goes through is emotional (2011). A widow also says unless one has another widow to talk to, there is no one out there who really understands a widow's crippling feeling...There is no one to express feelings to either good or bad (Stockton, 2015).

Social Disconnection

Married women are respected and held in esteem in the society. But once a woman loses her husband, she becomes a sexualised being. Writing about a socialite woman who woke from sleep and found her husband next to her dead, Stockton says she remarks that she is now a citizen and member of WOW (World of Widows) (2015). This typifies the first feeling of many widows. A widow becomes single woman again and experiences life like single ladies (never married) do. She may not be able to freely talk with a man again so that she is not perceived to be luring and seducing him. Inadvertently, her interactions are truncated in the society because she is being watched by everyone around. Other social challenges include discrimination, ostracism, oppression, dissociation from social groups and restriction from speaking publicly.

Impact on children

Many widows face double trauma-personal trauma and that of the children especially if they are young. The responsibility of assisting them cope with current situation both physically and psychologically rests on her. In this case, she needs to assist them handle the emotional hurt, pains of separation and get the grip of the reality at hand. She will also need to answer tough questions even though some of those questions might be questions she herself is asking and getting no answers to. Aside this, withdrawal from school is the problems widows face with children. In most cases girl children are usually affected first as they are required to care for other siblings while their mother engages in menial jobs or begs for money. Such girls who are denied education are in all likelihood going to become child-brides and child-mothers, a situation that readily predisposes them to reproductive health challenges and limits their opportunities for economic independence. Lack of fatherly contribution to child rising and discipline may also result in some children becoming juvenile delinquent.

Apart from poverty, all the aforementioned challenges can confront a widow regardless of her socio-economic status. Across many cultural and political settings, 'voicelessness' and

powerlessness are some shared elements underlining widows' marginalisation. As such, every widow in every society needs counseling, especially pastoral counseling. But as proposed in this article, using the widow empowerment scheme expounded from the book of Ruth is a handy tool in pastoral counseling and widow Challenges.

Widow Empowerment in the Book of Ruth

The book of Ruth has attracted attention as a result of which different themes have been associated with it. But certain things make it clear that the book is about widows and how they are empowered to live a meaningful and productive life. For instance, two among the three main character of the narrative are widows (Naomi and Ruth). Secondly, four of all six women mentioned by name in the book are widows. Finally, the book focuses on how destitute and hapless widows' situations changed for better through the agency of the third main character-Boaz thus, ultimately showing that the book is about widow empowerment. When empowerment is mentioned, especially widow empowerment, the first thing that comes to the mind of many is giving of financial aid. But quite frankly, empowerment is about the factor of motivation which is constantly needed in order to help stimulate a course of action in an attempt to change and make a perpetual condition better for the purpose of achieving the desired objectives (Aluko, 2007). Empowerment gives people room not only to define themselves but also to create their own personalities and be the product of a deliberate plan which may be externally initiated by agents of empowerment or lobbied by people who are disempowered (Hamelink, 1994). The book of Ruth demonstrates different modes or forms of widow empowerment as examined below.

Self-empowerment

Ruth 1:6 *Then she arose with her daughters-in-law, in order to return from the field of Moab: because she heard in the field of Moab that the LORD had visited his people in giving them food.*

Ruth 2:7 *She said, 'Please let me glean and gather among the sheaves behind the harvesters.' She went into the field and has worked steadily from morning till now, except for a short rest in the shelter."*

Self-empowerment begins from self-discovery. Scally and Hopson describe self-empowerment as situation whereby someone progressively assumes better responsibility over his or her life generally (1981, 57). This has to do with understanding one's present condition: limitation and challenges, then possible options or way out. It concerns knowing one's ability and opportunity, and then the propensity to spur the ability in pursuit of the opportunity.

Widows usually feel down cast with labile emotion as a result of shock, loneliness, fears, other factors. Some recede to seclusion, aloofness and despair. Ruth 1:6 reports that Naomi rises to return to Bethlehem after she hears that Yahweh has sent help to His people. Earlier, Naomi has lost everyone except her daughters-in-law she intends to send them away too. Thus, as a stranger in Moab, she is completely vulnerable and as an old widow, she is destitute. But on hearing the news of God's provision in Bethlehem, and being aware of legal provision of support system for the widows in Israel.

Elimelch leaves his homeland ^{בֵּית לֶחֶם} *Bethlehem* (house of bread) to go to ^{שְׂדֵי מוֹאָב} (field or open country) of Moab (1:1). While a house provides protection and warmth, *an open field* exposes one to danger and predation. But Naomi,

^{כִּי שָׁמְעָה בְּשִׂדְהָ מוֹאָב כִּי־פָקַד יְהוָה אֶת־עַמּוֹ לָתֵת לָהֶם לֶחֶם:}

because she heard ...that the LORD had visited His people in giving them food, rises ^(קום) to return to her once forsaken homeland where she has a redeemable family property. This shows Naomi as not giving-in to despair. She innovatively thinks of a way out. Whatever help she later gets is because she first of all empowers herself by choosing life rather than death, hope rather than despair and relief (in Bethlehem) rather than suffering (in Moab). The same is true of Ruth, another self-empowered widow in the book.

Ruth decides to return with Naomi against all persuasion to do otherwise. Providentially, their return happens to be during barley harvest. Ruth wastes no time waiting for some manna to fall from heaven. She swings into action of self-support. The verbs ^{לָקַט} *glean* is used in the book of Ruth more than any other book (cf 2:2, 3, 7,6 15, 17, 23). In each case gleaning is associated with either Ruth or Naomi or both of them. She goes to the field which would later better their fortune. It is unlikely that Boaz would come looking for Ruth if she does not take the initial step of doing something to help her situation. This is what self-empowerment entails. The tenor of the book of Ruth clearly reveals that Naomi's decision to return to Bethlehem and Ruth's decision to go with her and her subsequent decision to glean from farms determines the narrative trajectory of the book. Their decisions are self-motivated and this becomes their sources of livelihood and future joy. This, in this writer's view, indicates self-empowerment

In pastoral counseling, widows should be brought to the awareness of the fact of self-empowerment. Each widow should know her major problem or biggest challenge. Her attempt to address this may beckon on others for help. Therefore, counselor should help every widow to look inward to see what she is capable of; and outward to see what is available in order to effect a positive change in her situation. Aloofness and self-pity will do no good and will only make the widow suffer to no end while she lives.

Economic empowerment

In patriarchal society, the husband is usually the breadwinner of the family. Provision of basic needs and financing the home all rest squarely on him. So, his demise spells doom on the family economy. This is very true of many African families even up till now. Many lose not only the source of finance but also the family properties to unkind in-laws. This explains why financial support is the first thing that comes to the mind of many people when widow's care is mentioned.

Ruth by providence comes to a wealthy man's farm. The man, Boaz, speaks kindly to Ruth, gives her lot of grain (for her and Naomi) and makes provision for her protection. But whatever the quantity of gift, it would only for a while. The two widows will soon go back to penury. From their conversation and from his observation, Boaz recognizes ability to work. Knowing this, he instituted a lasting means of livelihood for the two widows by letting Ruth glean continually in his field till the end of harvest. This is a gainful employment rather than

momentary gift of money. By that offer, Ruth's chance of great return is high. First the problem of moving from one field to another and the problem of competition with other gleaners are removed. Secondly, great return is guaranteed since Boaz expressly tells his worker to deliberately leave grains for her; and thirdly she has good working environment with accommodating 'co-workers'

This is clear depiction of economic empowerment for young and agile person, where they are not just given some money or materials that would be exhausted within a short period of time. Bearing in mind that the qualification for certain opportunities in the ancient times was usually a matter of status: whether one is male or female, slave or free person, indigene or stranger and son. So as a widow, Ruth is mainly qualified for gleaning and Boaz makes that easy.

While concerned individuals, group or religious bodies may offer financial or materials gifts to widows, the pastor or counsellor should adequately prepare the mind of the widows to take charge of herself and expand her financial capability rather than living on people's charity. What we see is not just giving of material gifts to the widows, but giving of opportunity for the widows to explore and expend ability. The pastor can enhance this not only through counselling but also by facilitating her connection to job opportunities as some widows possess skills, ability or certificate which can afford them decent jobs and earn them a living.

Social empowerment

Emerging from the text of Ruth is another empowerment framework known as social empowerment. It is very possible for a person to be empowered or 'disempowered from social factors such as culture, religion, law, custom/practices, social roles, social stratification and interpersonal relationship. When people are culturally or religiously considered as a social misfit, their social status naturally depreciates and this will affect their interpersonal relationship with other members of the society and ultimately their productivity.

In many African cultural settings, widows do not enjoy equal status as other women in the society. They usually get treated either with pity or disdain. Sometimes, they are even considered as evil omen and bad company. So, many widows internalize this stereotypic view of their person, take it as norm, and suppress their feeling, ambitions and interest. Therefore, any action or an attempt to correct social phenomena that prevent widows from maximally enjoying their potential and their good wishes is social empowerment.

In Ruth (1:8-9), Naomi gives her daughters-in-law the chance to go and remarry. Culturally, Ruth and Orpah could not have remarried as they remain members of Elimelech's family. As the only consenting family member available, Naomi reserves the right to allow or prevent their remarriage, but she chooses instead, to free them and grant them the choice of choosing their marriage partners. While Ruth, out of uncommon loyalty, commitment and perhaps sympathy does not take this offer, Orpah does. This contrasts negatively with the practices in many societies where the woman would be held 'hostage' by the late husband's family simply because she refuses to marry within the family. One interesting thing about Ruth narrative here is that it shows that in widowhood, there are choices. Both Ruth and Orpah make different choices.

Levirate, and the legal framework providing support and security for the poor and destitute, are other notable social institutions in Israel that feature to empower widows in the book of Ruth. The law of Redemption is one of the institutions in the book of Ruth and does not have

much to do with widowhood. But in the narrative of Ruth, redemption is closely tied to widows' welfare. The legal provision about land redemption is contained in (Lev. 25:23-24) and that of levirate in (Deut. 25:5-10).

These laws basically function to preserve the name and guard the properties of family in Israel. Due to insolvency, Naomi wants to trade a portion of land belonging to her late husband. It seems that at the death of Elimelech, the property passed to Mahlon so, his widow Ruth is included in the redemption responsibility (Reed, 2000, 415-429). Boaz buys the land and takes Ruth as his wife. These social institutions of redemption and levirate marriage are graphically demonstrated in Ruth, restoring the lost hope of remarriage to Ruth and hope of economic sustenance to Naomi.

The legal framework providing support for the widows and other poor members of Israelite society is noteworthy too. It is legal because the instruction is contained in the legal document of Leviticus and Deuteronomy (Lev. 29: Deut. 25:5-10). Israelites were not to harvest to the edge of the field. This is seen in practical term in the book of Ruth with the farm owner going beyond the stipulation of law. It is no coincidence that three important social institutions are brought to bear in a single narrative and all directly effecting the welfare of widows. This lays bare the widow empowerment motif of the book of Ruth.

Another evidence of social widow empowerment motif in Ruth is in "care for the elderly" parents. Naomi loses her two sons who should have provided succour for her in old age. But one of the two daughters-in-law takes up the care of Naomi at old age. This, no doubt, is great refreshment as the grand children who should have been her crown at old age are presently lacking (Pro 17:6). As an elderly widow, the support of the children and the pleasure of having grand children around strengthen and help remove boredom. Ruth adequately fills this vacuum in Naomi's life. Not only is Ruth present with Naomi, she also gives her a son who become a hope of sustenance in old age. The words of the women of Bethlehem perfectly elucidate this fact:

The women said to Naomi: "Praise be to the LORD, who this day has not left you without a kinsman-redeemer. May he become famous throughout Israel! He will renew your life and sustain you in your old age. For your daughter-in-law, who loves you and who is better to you than seven sons, has given him birth." (Ruth 4:14-15)

Psycho-emotional empowerment

Arguably, Psycho-emotional challenge is the most disturbing difficulty that widows face. Financial and social support issues are no problem for some widows based on their race, level of education, type of job, the society they live in; or their social class. However, emotional problem is almost universally shared by all widows regardless of class or financial status. Especially in places like Nigeria where many become widow before the age of fifty, the shock, loneliness and fears of all sort result in serious emotional breakdown. This is further compounded by obnoxious and dehumanizing widowhood rites that emotionally paralyse some widows irrevocably. In addition, some widows become objects of sexual harassment. In their vulnerability, they give in to 'cheap' sex which leaves them feeling used up and further dejected. In frustration, some lose sense of dignity. Thus, the psycho-emotional challenges that widows go through is hard to fathom, and this makes psycho-emotional empowerment one of the most important forms of widow empowerment.

Two passages prominently elucidate Psycho-emotional empowerment in Ruth. The first is

Ruth's classical statement in (Ruth1:16-17) where Ruth cleaves ^{דָּבָקָה} in 1:14 to her elderly mother-in-law with a solemn oath of loyalty and allegiance. Quite frequently in the Old

Testament, ^{דָּבָק} is used in relation to physical objects getting stuck to each other, or affectionate and loyal clinging to somebody. It is expected that Man cleaves to his wife (Gen 2:24). This action which verse 14 demonstrates later gets expression in 16-17. Naomi who earlier blames her woes on God (1:13, 20-21), later has her fortune changed for better because of Ruth presence (4:15b). She sees no hope of remarriage for her young widowed daughters-in-law in Israel (1:11-13), but when psychologically empowered, she becomes aware of the possibility of Boaz marrying Ruth (3:1). Ruth's decision to follow Naomi back to Bethlehem was not basically to provide economic support but emotional one by her presence. The book shows that life becomes worth living and future worth facing for Naomi because Ruth is there. Here we see Ruth empowering Naomi psycho-emotionally. Some widows really do not have financial difficulty nor do they suffer cultural dehumanisation. They simply need someone to share their feelings with, someone to talk to, or just companions in the time when their emotions run high.

Another notable psycho-emotional empowering phenomenon in Ruth is in Boaz and Ruth's meeting. Ruth is not only a young widow but also a foreigner in Israel thus, she is of lower status than that of hired servants of Boaz (2:13). But when Boaz comes to the farm, noticing

Ruth, he speaks kindly to her calling her ^{בָּתִּי} "my daughter" (2:8). This appellation means so much to Ruth. This is the first and only place (apart from figurative expressions) in Hebrew Bible where this appellation is used for someone without biological relationship. More than any other person in the Hebrew Bible, she is called by that phrase (1:11-13; 2:2, 8, 22; 3:1, 10-

11, 16, 18). More so, the person addressing Ruth is ^{אִישׁ גְּבוּרַת חַיִל} a man of wealth and

influence (2:1). Meanwhile Ruth calls herself ^{שִׁפְחָה} *maidservant* (2:13), a more menial term

than ^{אֲמָה} another Hebrew word for *maidservant*. Thus, when Boaz calls her that, it feels elating and affectionate. Naturally, widows need psycho-emotional empowerment from people around them like family members, co-workers, church members, employers and so on. Some just want reassurance of the dignity of their personhood. A pastoral counselor is adequately equipped to do this

Sexual Empowerment

One area usually overlooked in widowhood phenomenon is that of their sexual need. Rebecca Chalker laments that despite groundbreaking research revealing that orgasm in both sexes is triggered by the same mechanism, many people almost universally, still perceive sexuality of women not as powerful, not as fascinating, not as profound as that of men. She notes that from the ancient times, the sexual organs together with sexual response of men have been idealised, while the women's own have been regarded as the less-perfect equivalents. Consequently today, we are in the age where sexual relationships are under what is basically a male model of human sexuality (Chalker, 1994). Many judge a widow's need of remarriage on the basis of whether she has child(ren) or not. But the book of Ruth

The narrative evokes some sexual nuances. For example, the clause *וַתִּגְלֹתָוּ ; מִרְגְּלֶיהָ* and *uncover his feet* in 3:7, describes where Ruth uncovers and sleeps. The term “feet” is sometimes employed as euphemism to denote sexual organs. Edward Campbell (1975, 121) explains that this noun relates to the common noun *regel* “foot” in etymology, and it can serve euphemistically to designate the penis or the vulva, either as the urinary opening or as sexual organs (Judg 3:24; I Sam 24:3; II Kings 18:27, Isa 36: 12; Isa 7:20; Ezek 16:25). Thus, the provocative sexual overtures, and later marriage that ensued (3:1–18) justifies a widow’s need of sexual relationship which should not be denied or suppressed. The text however, demonstrates that sexual activities should be properly situated in the context of marriage only. A widow is not to be sexually empowered in the sense of satisfying her sexual need outside marriage but should be encouraged to remarry if young enough to marry.

As a spiritual therapist, a pastor counselor has the mandate of helping people through and out of their trauma. Widowhood is a traumatic experience and as such, widows need pastoral counseling. However, a counselor must understand that all widows should not be treated homogenously. By this, it means that the need of different categories of widow varies. These variations depend on the age, cultural settings, financial and social status of the widows. Therefore, engaging widow pastoral counseling using the widow empowerment framework expounded from the book of Ruth will help counselor to individualise widows in counseling and help to provide focused and effective therapy.

Further, the book of Ruth which has not been much read into widow support system can now be actively engaged in counseling widows. The narrative is clear and evidence based. Apart from assurances and promises from other passages of the Holy Bible, counselor can focus the attention of widows on the graphical fact of God’s help for widows (both young and hold) in the book of Ruth.

Conclusion

This article examines the book of Ruth. It observes that though different themes such as levirate, Davidic lineage history, polemic against prohibition of foreign marriage, and so on have been associated with the book; a major and dominant motif of the book is widow empowerment. Different factors affect the experiences of some widows. One of such is culture. In some cultures, widows face harsh and dehumanising treatments, victimisation and even accusation as one responsible for husband’s death. Furthermore, among cultures where harsh treatments are meted out to widows, the degree of harshness varies. Apart from culture, social status such as level of education, type of job, level of finance etc. also affect widows.

About five empowerment frameworks emerge from the book of Ruth which are: economic, social, psycho-emotional, sexual and self-empowerments. Since Christians are from different race, cultures and social backgrounds, one or more of these widow empowerment frameworks will apply to an individual widow in any culture or social setting. The paper argues therefore, that knowledge of these widow empowerment schemes provides a veritable tool for pastoral counseling in providing spiritual therapy and succour to Christian (and possibly non-Christian) widows of all categories be they rich, destitute, young or old.

Recommendations

To this end, based on the findings in this research, the following recommendations are made. It is recommended that:

- i. Widow empowerment scheme of the book of Ruth be noted and understood.
- ii. Counseling should be clearly understood as an empowerment.
- iii. Widows should be understood to be of different categories (younger, older, destitute, plebeian etc.) and should not be treated homogenously in counselling.
- iv. Counselor should understand cultural variations about widowhood and use this knowledge in addressing widows of different cultures.
- v. Counselor should understand variation of widows' need, and individualise widows in provision of counseling services.
- vi. Unless, they are not interested for some genuine reason(s), younger widows should be encouraged to remarry and the pastor counselor should help the families concerned to understand the need for this.
- vii. There should be more public sensitisation on younger widows' remarriage.
- viii. Pastoral counselor should embrace and utilise widow empowerment schema of the book of Ruth for effective and focused widow counseling.

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Pastoral Counselling: Panacea for the Divorce in the 21st Century Nigeria

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Abstract

One of the major institutions traceable to the early age of man and based on the Biblical narrative is the institution of marriage. It is not disputable that God instituted marriage from the inception of Adam and Eve which is seen in their union in the Garden of Eden. As such, Marriage in this context is based on the divinely ordained format of one man and one woman coming together in union to build a home. But as against the Biblical position and injunction on marriage which is to stand the test of time and to last "till death do us part", many homes in the 21st century have experienced serious hitches in the 'adventure' of marriage which have led to the threat of divorce in actual fact or in its potential form, divorce is almost the order of the day among many young couples in which there is a call for concern to remedy the situation. An examination of this status quo in Nigeria calls for immediate response and rescue mission. A chronicling of some practical instances and assessment of the response of the personalities involved in various situations which led to complications is the focal point in the course of this research work. Therefore, using the investigative method, this paper studies the major factors responsible for divorce in the 21st century among young and matured couples in Nigeria and the paper presents pastoral counselling in its true form as a panacea to rescue the situation of rampaging divorce in the contemporary age.

Keywords: Pastoral Counselling, Divorce, Marriage, Nigeria

Introduction

Marriage is God-ordained and the original intention and plan for marriage is that it serves "till death do the couple apart". But it appears that the contemporary time and situation of life have led to various complications in matters concerning marriage. Marriage is seen to be literally a contract without essential commitment to such contract, in recent times, marriage has loosed its sanctity because of the response of the people towards the practice among young and adult couples.

The modern days have seen various kind of unnatural marriages which ranges from getting married to the same sex, and marriage to animals among other kinds of marriages that are not part of the programming by God from the initials. The rampaging loss of the sanctity of marriage calls for intentional action and attention by the society as a whole, because the adverse effect tells on the society as a whole. The neglect of the rampaging catastrophe in modern-day marriages which could be due to lack of cultural understanding and not being religiously inclined in a right way, has caused a lot of imbalances in the 21st century world.

To this existing marital malady, there is a need to seek escape route which this paper seeks to review the existing malady and with the discovery that there are a lot of gaps to be breached religiously in some of these situations, the pastoral counseling is seen as a means of calming the situation and to be seen as a remedy to the existing malady in the society

Concept of Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral counselling is a field that focuses on counsel for various issues of life. It is a special type of psychotherapy which promotes healing and growth with the use of both spiritual and psychological resources. The task is to be carried out by pastoral counsellors who are licensed and who have gone through a deep understanding in their Christian teachings and theologies, which will be also corroborated by their certification as mental health practitioners. Pastoral counselling utilises both spiritual resources and psychological analysis and approach to aid the healing process or growth of an individual. Their focus is basically to regulate extreme situations and to stabilise situations from escalating.

In order to promote therapeutic form and progress, pastoral counseling employs both psychological knowledge and spiritual resources. This is seen to be specifically a service or activities rendered by pastors, licensed to have received extensive religious and/or theological studies in addition to being mental health specialist. Challenging situations are bound to occur in lives and involvement of individuals; like mental disorder, overwhelming situations, family issues, child bearing challenges among others. In such season, they are advised to seek help and counsel in a way or the other. While some people will opt for psychologists, some will opt for social workers or psychiatrists, others will rather like to seek spiritual solutions in the context of their situation

Pastoral counselors are to be responsible for providing pastoral assistance, encouragement and the admonition to people who are bewildered or discouraged about various situations of life around them. They provide counsel for adults, children, adolescents, youths and even families. Their tasks also extend to providing assistance for people who are addicted to substances, or some involvements. Their task is encompassing and the goal is simply to bring sanctity into the society that they find themselves using religious, specifically biblical thoughts to encourage stability and progress for an individual or individuals.

The church is one of the most significant places where people seeking assistance visit, both when it deals with material things or when it has to do with the mental state of the individual either due to personal issues or issues from another party. People with depression, grief, sorrow, health challenges, societal imbalance, violence, especially in the African context believes that there is solution in the church and as such, pastoral counselling tend to be necessary to be applied to each situation which an individual encounters. It only becomes a challenge when most religious leaders, who people run to are not really trained in psychotherapy in order to aid extensive dealing with the challenge an individual must have brought to them to address. It therefore hinges that, pastors and church leaders are to be well trained in psychotherapy in order to meet the actual need of some of this member especially when it comes to pastoral counselling.

The crux of pastoral counselling is to restore human back into the right relationship with God and to fellow humans which is not done without Christ in the course of the discourse. The pastoral counselling is an emerging academic discipline which creates a platform of operation for apologists from diverse faiths and religions to express their perspectives, with Jesus as a

good model for pastoral counselling, the field is an emphatic delivery of biblical psychotherapy (Odeleye, 2022)

Techniques and Principles of Pastoral Counselling

As a discipline and as an upcoming field of emphasis, there are some major underlying principles, which guide the proper running of a pastoral counsellor. These principles present pastoral counselling to stand out from other genre of counselling in existence. These principles are discussed below;

First is the in-depth knowledge of the scriptures which is essential for the foundational basis of pastoral counselling. Having in mind that pastoral counselling as a field is spiritually inclined and based on the biblical positions in encouraging or counselling individuals in one challenge or the other. Odeleye (2022) reminded that the Scripture, which contains sixty-six books is the word of God and revelation from him, which is available to guide every aspect of Christian counselling. He further established that the Bible is sine-qua-non and applicable to any case or situation a man can find himself. It serves the purpose of guiding men and revealing the mind of God in various situations. Therefore, as pastoral counsellors, it is essential to have the knowledge of biblical injunctions as this will go a long way in aiding the rightful situating of the challenges of people and addressing it from the biblical perception.

Furthermore, in the techniques and principles of pastoral counselling is the lifestyle of prayer and medication which ought to be possessed by pastoral counsellors. A pastoral counsellor is to be very sound in inculcating a life of prayer and meditation as this are fundamental to the sustainability of their roles as counsellors. Odeleye (2022) expressed that the hallmark through which a pastoral counsellor can operate is through communion and meditation with the Holy Spirit. Through a constant life of prayer and meditation, the counsellor comes up with revelation and insight, they pray for the clients and be spiritually guided concerning the issue brought to them.

Also, a pastoral counsellor must be able to maintain confidentiality just like any counsellor ought to inculcate as etiquette. Craig (2011) opined that it is the role of a pastoral counsellor to provide a sense of hope and trust to the patient or client, this makes people to have trust in the capability and strength of the counsellor in carrying out his duty as a counsellor. A counsellor who does not have a sense of confidentiality is not a trustworthy counsellor and can complicate matters for the patient rather than solving the situation on ground.

More also, empathy on the part of the counsellor is essential to rightly dispose the duties towards a client. As expressed by Odeleye (2022), in this case, empathy is not literally putting one's self in the shoes of the fellow in a complicated situation (this is because not all situation could be properly assumed or imagined) but it is the ability of a counsellor to be able to bear with the counsellee. The counsellee could be complicated in relating with, and for the counsellor to have the best of him and to maximally manage the situation, there is a need to actually be patient with the fellow regardless of the means of the weakness in expression which could most likely be as a result of the complicated situation such person is entangled.

Finally on this note, a personal life of purity is an essential value that a pastoral counsellor should possess. A pastoral counsellor without a good report in the home and society will less likely have people, whose marriage is in disarray, come to him for counselling or admonition. Such counsellor must possess attributes that are enviable to life and that are related to the Christian virtues which he portrays himself to be a proponent towards. This boils down to the

moral conduct and presentation of the lifestyle of a pastoral counsellor which must be sanctimonious and enviable in the society.

Biblical Position on Marriage

The Bible is not silent about the matters about marriage as an institution and this is seen both in the Old Testament and the New Testament owing to the fact that, marriage is a great determinant for the sustainability of the race of man on earth and the progressive existence of humanity. Marriage is an institution that is as old as the times in the Garden of Eden. From the time of creation, there was the plan for God to create for man, a woman who will be his companion and help meet. This was eventually made a reality in Genesis 2:18-22. As such, the initial establishment of marriage is that man and woman live in harmony and to serve complementary roles for each other.

Marriage according to Tolorunleke (2008), should be an atmosphere of excitement and a beautiful adventure which should exist between husband and wife. Marriage and the beauty therein as expressed by Toloruleke (2008) do not imply that there will not be tough times, but marriage in the real sense gives room for offences, which appears to be inevitable in life and there should also be room for forgiveness by the couples in such a way that the offences are forgiven and made to be a stepping stone to higher joy and happiness leading to fulfillment for the couples. According to the definition of Ampitan (2012), God is the source of marriage and it was not originated from neither culture nor tradition as such, marriage is an institution which have the union of a man and a woman. Marriage is an ordination made available by God for mankind to cohabit together in love and in unity of existence.

The biblical perception to marriage is therefore to create room for companionship, abstaining from sexual immorality and for procreation. The biblical perception as obviously taught by Odhiambo, Onyango and Maito (2013) establish that, marriage is ordained by God to be union of one man and one woman. The purposes of marriage is further confirmed from the content of Genesis 2:15-25 and Genesis 1:28 which talks about a one man, husband and one woman, wife with further directive of being fruitful through procreation. The three clearly opined further that a godly and biblical marriage shows the kind of relationship between Christ and the church as contained in Ephesians 5:15-25.

Man and woman in marriage are to serve the purpose of companionship for one another (Stott, 1999). They both are intended from the biblical stance to play complementary roles for each other. This is simply because, the loneliness for man in the first place implies incompleteness and bringing in a woman to live with him in sanctified matrimony is a practice that is meant to last their lifetime as far as both parties are alive. This position is highly held because, the human nature is a jealous type that finds it difficult to give room for multiple "sharing" of a spouse. And such could create complications in the relationship and thereby lead to either party moving the motion for divorce, a motion that is clearly stated by the Bible that God hates (Malachi 2:16).

The contemporary times have seen many forms of marriages which are against the heterosexual form of marriage ordained by the scriptures. Some of these ungodly marriages are gay marriage (homosexuals), lesbianism, bestialism, among others which ranges from getting marriage to same sex to the extent of getting married to animals. Any form of marriage outside a heterogeneous marriage between a man and a woman is not biblically approved.

Marital Conflicts and Divorce in the 21st century Nigeria

Marriage in the 21st century is almost a shadow of its intended purpose of creation. Tolorunleke (2014) strongly posits that there are multiple factors that stand to affect the sustainability of marriage as it starts from simple challenges and arises to complications in the home. This challenges boomerangs because, both parties who have agreed to live together as husband and wife tend to have forgotten or trivialised the fact that there will be differences and continuous adjustments to suit each other and to carry out their roles as couples. Below are some of the major factors leading to divorce in contemporary marriages;

Divorce in the 21st century could be caused by marital infidelity by either of the couple or both. Marital vows made covers fidelity in marriage and this can help the health safety of both parties involved in a marriage. But indulging in marital infidelity poses serious threat to the sustainability of such marriage as mistrust will be built and fear of contracting sexually transmitted diseases will automatically be built. These actions could be caused by the inability of one party to satisfy the other party sexually and it could be as a result of covetousness of the part of the guilty side. Tolorunleke (2014) opine strongly that conflict could evolve when either party fails to satisfy the other party sexually.

Tolorunleke (2014) discovered that marital conflict which can by extension lead to divorce in marriage could be caused by social, economic and physical factors. She also opined that, when the family head is unable to economically and socially meet the needs of the family, conflict can evolve as a result. It implies that, the family is sensitive to meeting individual needs both physically and emotionally.

Some marriages in contemporary times could be shattered by educational imbalance or social imbalance of either party and inability of both to adjust their extremes to relate with one another in the home and in the society. The well-educated party tends to always feel embarrassed by the conduct of the other party who is less educated and it appears as if such fellow cannot be presented in the society. Therefore, rather than to keep up with such imbalance they chose to divorce and go separate ways.

As it had been clearly opined from the biblical point of view, Odhiambo, Onyango and Maito (2013) indicated that a true biblical marriage signifies the relationship between Christ and the church, a kind of affiliation that cannot be broken by challenges. As such, divorce is not an option in the relationship of Christ with the church as it holds the idea of oneness which should also be the similar situation in man and woman marital affinity.

Pastoral Counseling as Panacea For Divorce

The situation of divorce in the society in contemporary times call for immediate action and rescue in order to preserve the sanctimony of marriages and as such, the various counselling methods are adopted and will be discussed in light of rescuing marriage from divorce in the 21st century Nigeria setting;

The first means to be applied is to listen and pay attention to the client when the counselling session resumes. Young, Griffith and Williams (2003) had rightly expressed that paying attention to the actual situation by mainly listening, showing support and care, then counsel and hearing them out, will go a long way to help the situation brought about by the clients. This implies that, if pastoral counsellors pay attention, it will aid in how to show care to couples and that will aid in how to counsel them too. This position presents that there is no complex situation that is beyond fixing and if a listening ear is given to the couples whose

marriage is a dwindling state, divorce can be avoided in order to rescue the marriage from crashing.

Another mode to be applied is the building of trust and confidence in the mind of the concerned persons. People need to feel loved sincerely and not to be judgmental about them, they feel safe sharing their secrets and life with people who would encourage them, instead of condemning them out rightly (Young, Griffith and Williams, 2003). When couples that are facing tough time or couples that are almost at the verge of entering into complicated situations in their families see someone that could be trusted, they tend to open up and be sincere with them. At this point, there is a level of trust and confidence which the pastoral counsellor has built between the couple and himself. This will aid in meddling and rescuing a marriage. As a matter of emphasis, pastoral counsellors should be close to couples ahead of time, this is because, some people find it difficult to open up to people when they are already in a tough situation, but they rather open to someone who have won their trust before such tough time and situation arises.

Furthermore, pastoral counselling should be centered on a discussion to please God rather than only gratifying human's immediate desires. The pastoral counsellor should establish to the couples having challenges in their marriage on a mutual cohabitation to please God. Young, Griffith and Williams (2003) expressed that, the discussion should lead to a more authentic relationship with God. Couples are therefore to substitute and replace wrong thoughts with a positive mental attitude and expression in order to sustain their home. Often times, couples feel other people will be better than their spouse and that is the need and push for aiming towards divorce in order to get a better alternative, but the truth is that there is no perfect being as everyone has one deficiency or the other. This implies that, counsellors are to lay emphasis on the complications of human nature and the need for the couples to adjust and amend their excesses in order to have a proper relationship and a progressive family.

In addition, pastoral counsellors are to get involved from the basis of the relationships of young ones which has a prospect of leading to marriage. They are to win their heart and confidence in a way that the young ones feel safe to share their situations with such counsellor through premarital counselling. Many marriages which were shattered within a short time are marriages which had foundational problem like logical incompatibility or imbalance based on financial situation of the intended couples or families, educational imbalance of either party, religious affiliations, or tribal identity which is not well dealt with before hopping into marriage. As such, a pastoral counsellor will have been able to address some of the issues which will enlighten the individuals on making the decision to proceed with such marriage or to disembark for that marriage to be instituted.

Lastly on this note, pastoral counsellors are to proffer therapeutic solutions in situations where it becomes necessary to do so. This paper posits that, indeed some situations that are threatening the marriage of individuals could be as a result of mental shortcomings and complications. Some misbehaviours are due failure on the part of the husband to provide economically for the family or for either couple to meet the sexual need of each other (Tolorunleke, 2014). Odeleye (2022) expressed that the strength of a pastoral counsellor is the ability to realise boundaries of his discipline and profession as such, the counsellor is to have in mind that counselling could succeed or be a step to success which could be achieved by referring a client to other quarters (discipline) as the case could be in each specific case. In such cases which are not based on spiritual inclinations, a pastoral counsellor should refer the couple to those who major in such field. For example, a sexually inactive person could be

referred to a health nutritionist who could advice on types of food and treatment to be used, while those with mental situation could be referred to the psychiatrist for proper attention before it goes out of hand (Young, Griffith and Williams, 2003). This referral method will further help in establishing a relationship between people of other professions and careers. This can lead to achieving the expected goal in a right way and this should be the joy of any counsellor.

Conclusion

Divorce is never in the plan of God in the marital affairs of men, his plan for man is simply to run a family till a natural death serve the purpose of separation. But considering the current tide and trend in the modern age, there is a call for serious attention from various quarters who are seen to have agitated for divorce or temporary separation as discussed in the course of this paper.

The need therefore arises for a rescue mission to be embarked upon by the church and this could simply be achieved intentionally by the pastoral counsellors who are saddled with the role of both spiritual and psychotherapy tasks to assist in family and marital stability. The pastoral counsellors are simply to be well trained and well groomed to meet marital needs of the society which is one of the most pressing is the malady of divorce. This paper has therefore proffered means and method by which pastoral counsellors can curb or drastically reduced the rampant nature of divorce in the 21st century which will in return rescue and establish the biblical position towards stability in marriage.

Recommendations

In direct establishment of some of the positions discussed about pastoral counselling, this paper recommends that:

- i. Pastoral counsellors should be well trained in both spiritual and psychotherapeutic knowledge in order to have an holistic conduct
- ii. Intended couples should be encouraged to pass through premarital counselling before they settle down for marriage
- iii. Couples are to seek assistance of pastoral counsellors when the going gets tough in their marriage
- iv. Referral in case of complicated factors should be intentionally adopted by pastoral counsellors as procedure to rescuing marital complications

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Pastoral Counselling and Family Stability

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Abstract

Pastoral counseling simply means a kind of therapy that integrates psychological principles with spiritual guidance and pastoral care, which is often provided by clergy members or trained professionals within a religious context. This is very vital in every facet of human endeavour in the society, especially at the family level. The complexity of the composition of humanity emanates from the family units and the world view of any society is built upon the acceptable and approved norms which are foremost preserved and practiced at the family level which automatically permeate every nook and cranny of the society. However, problem ensued in the family with various forms of instabilities as a result of the demonical forces which have infiltrated and disrupted the ranks and files of the world order, a reflection of which was recorded in Genesis 6: 1-6, hence, this necessitated the Divine, the Supreme Being, who created a secured world to be raising his servants, the prophets, pastors, etc, to offer counsel to humanity, and the strategy that God maps out at times is to offer counsel to the family because once stability is enhanced in the family, it will permeate other aspect of human endeavours. Using sociological and historical methods to gather relevant information, sociologically, interview was conducted with fifty families who are well advanced in marriage and the data collated and analysed using simple percentage method, and from the result, it is unequivocally evident that pastors are undaunted to offer the right counsels that will enhance family stability in the face of heinous crimes bedeviling our family, causing instability, confusion and insecurity.

Key Words: Pastoral, Counselling, Family,

Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral Counseling: "Pastoral counseling is the practice of talking with individuals, couples, and families to increase their understanding of emotional and religious conflicts and to help resolve problems using religious and other resources" (Moruf, 2023). Also, "Pastoral counseling is a form of counseling that integrates psychological principles with spiritual guidance, often provided by clergy or individuals with a strong religious background" (Moruf, 2023), or "Pastoral counseling is a form of counseling that integrates psychological insights with spiritual guidance, often provided by religious leaders or trained professionals within a faith community" (Moruf, 2023) and this counseling is usually provided by clergy or trained individuals in order to address spiritual, emotional or psychological issues of life that relate to individuals, families or the society at large.

Each family is a composite part of the larger society and seeks to exist and survive in a pluralistic society of which many people, irrespective of their arrogant and uncompassionate social relationships among humanity still claim to have a worthwhile religious way of life, what a paradox! Donald Bloesch rightly said that they are "arrogant and uncompassionate in a world of pluralism, a world in which there are many worthwhile religious ways" (Donald, 1991) and when a family lives in a society full of such personalities, pastoral guidance will be

required so as not to fall victim of their intricacies, because when a member of any family is in a dilemma among such people, the kind of therapy such people will proffer, most often will not achieve the desired result, beside, there is a limit and extent to which any therapy can take care of, Richard has this to say: "However intricately a clinical theory can help us analyze a client's dilemma, it cannot tell us why any of the various dramas in anyone's life is worth caring about or what meaning our lives have --- We can do therapy, come up with clever interventions, but we're going to die anyway, just like everybody else" (1991)

Hence, the need for the involvement of pastoral counselling of which mature spirituality often times comes into play or use, whereby various potentialities and factors are applied so as to proffer lasting solution to any unsatisfactory situation or circumstance. Scott Peck, in explaining mature spirituality, as a yardstick of proffering solution to a deplorable situation and a state of dilemma in a family and the society at large, through unity with one another and with the universe, has this to say, "a mystical communal stage of spiritual development, a stage of unity, of an underlying connectedness between things: between men and women, between us and the other creatures and even inanimate matter as well, fitting together according to an ordinarily invisible fabric underlying the cosmos" (Scott, 1987).

Family, according to Advanced English Dictionary, "is a social group or unit that live together, consisting of parents and their children" (Advanced English Dictionary, 2023), is not isolated from the troubles of the world, a nuclear family which consists of the father and mother and their children ought to be a place of consistent happiness and joy together with everything that makes life merry, but alas, it has not always been so. The kind of challenge some families pass through often presents to the world that there are unseen forces wagging war against the family. Andrian Rogers rightly said that, "but today all of the artillery of hell seems to be aimed at the nuclear family- humanism, relativism, materialism, hedonism" (Adrian, 2005). When pondering on the various ills that bedevil families, Garry Collins, in his book, *Family Shock: Keeping Families Strong in the Midst of Earthshaking change* has this to say;

"--- many people today are scared, fearful about their safety, worried about their families, and lacking in hope for the future. Almost every day the newspapers and television reporters tell us about crime, abuse, uncontrolled sexuality, militant groups that push their perverted values, teenage pregnancies, poverty – stricken families, single – parent frustrations, poor schools, neglected children, and kids that kill other kids. In our homes – including the homes of Christians –there is conflict, tension, insensitivity, communication breakdown, and probably more abuse than we dare admit. We face endless demands that rob us of our time, pull us apart, and disrupt our hopes for family unity and stability. A host of forces shake our homes and cause our families to crumble, but three are of major impact: catastrophic change, persistent pressure, and pervasive pessimism" (1995).

However, of all the predicaments that befall the family, there is a potent weapon with which they could be addressed or taken care of, and as regard this, Rogers says, "The chief weapon in our arsenal is truth that brings a fixed standard for right and wrong, and that truth is encapsulated in the ten commandments" (2005). This emphatically shows that pastoral counseling is required in each family so as to curtail, curb, and check the various menaces therein. God is interested in the well-being of the family, even from the record about the first family that God created in the Bible, in Genesis chapter 3, the cordial relationship of visiting the couple in the cool of the day which God established between himself and the first family indicates that God is concerned for their wellness. Rogers added that, "God has a plan to give us successful homes. It is given to us in his Word and is communicated in divine shorthand

in the Ten Commandments. His perfect law. If we want to have homes that win, we can rediscover God's will as revealed in His Ten Commandments" (2005). According to Plato, "The life of the nation is the life of the family written large", and if there will not be solid cohesion and national security in a nation, it is from the family such foundation is easily laid, just as Adrian opined, "There is a war going on ---, a battle for the soul of our nation. The battleground is the home, and *the issue is truth*, Satan has aimed all of the artillery of hell at our homes, and every shell in that artillery is a lie" (2005). Hence pastoral counselling is of necessity so as to help evade these intricacies and to manoeuvre all the manipulations of Satan against the family. Various aspects of the family that possibly require the counselling of a pastor are discussed below:

Marital Problems

The many challenges or conflicts witnessed in a marriage are symptoms of attitudes such as lack of love, anger, selfishness, unwillingness to forgive, bitterness, anxiety, communication gap or problems, sexual mistreatment, substance abuse, sin, feeling of inferiority, deliberate rejection of God's will, etc, and according to Collins, "each of these can cause tension in the home, each can be influenced by husband or wife" (Gary, 2007). Scripturally, Gary asserts that, marital problems, per se, are not analysed, but affirms that, the Scriptures deal with marital conflict only indirectly and in passing, the issues underlying many marriage problems are considered in detail (Gary, 2007). The major three categories of marital problems are unfulfilled expectations, disappointing sex, and faulty communication. Pastors need to come in to offer useful counsel of the probable way forward or out of such situations based on the Scriptural directives, Holy Spirit, experiences, etc.

As regard unfulfilled expectations, some couples experience variations in their marital expectations which could be complex or simple. These expectations, for instance, range from how to spend their weekends, how best to celebrate their birthdays, how they intend spending their money and how they would have wanted the various duties at home to be discharged, and amazingly, problem of frustrations from time to time sets in, when variations such as the above are ignored, and such problems might be difficult to handle.

Concerning disappointing sex, couples are shaped on the background of their cultural worldview, especially from the knowledge acquired from experienced old couples on teachings about their sex lives. This orientation shaped their mentality which culminates into what individual spouse would expect in their marital sexual lives, some might have hope of exciting and consistently satisfying sex lives, while some might be nursing fears and uncertainties in marital sex.

Also, about faulty communication, whenever communication, either verbal or non-verbal, which is expected to involve sending and receiving of message, results in contradiction, it can lead to confusion and communication breakdown. A person facial outlook or countenance ought to tally with the verbal expression, a person's action should agree with his verbal expressions.

Other issues that can cause marital problems are;

Unhealthy relationships, whereby a partner in a marriage gets close and builds intimacy with another person, such might be suspicious, and might betray trust, which can make the husband and wife to drift apart and as such, stops sharing confidence, stop developing life goals together which might make any of them to be vulnerable.

Unwise choice, the choice a spouse makes in a marriage that might make or mar the marriage, wrong choices can crumble a marriage. Keeping secrets is also an important issue that can cause marital problems. Likewise, a weakening emotional bond can cause marital problems, the emotional bond between a husband and wife has been called the “golden thread that holds partner together” (Frank, 1987). Boredom can also cause marital problems, a situation when a marriage is dull and routine, which might make couples to look somewhere else for variety. Personal differences, etc can cause family problems.

Pastoral Counseling in Marital Problems

Involving in pastoral counseling is highly tasky, Gary wrote, “This is the kind of work that demands a lot of prayers and reliance on the Holy Spirit. Before starting, (and frequently thereafter) counselors should look at themselves to clarify some of their own attitudes, possible prejudices, motivations and vulnerabilities” (Gary, 2007). The following should be considered in pastoral counseling;

The counselor, firstly, should take a close look at himself, together with his attitudes and biases. Also, the counselor should be alert to special issues that relate to couples counseling. Likewise, the counselor should try to determine the reason the couple has come for counseling. More so, the counselor should not lord it over the couple, rather, he should partner with them in setting of goals.

Furthermore, the counselor should focus on the person, not himself, he should also focus on the problems, he should also focus on the process, and he should be conscious of common mistakes and try to avoid making them. When a couple is well guided pastorally, a good marriage is built up that give birth a healthy family, hence a coherent and secured society at large.

Family Problems

“No family is perfect and without problems and periodic crises” (Collins, 1995) and the problems that bedevil families range from misunderstanding that culminates into crisis, conflicts, there are communication breakdown, insensitivity, tension, unmet desire and demand, unrest among kids, poverty, abuse of various kinds, etc, as opined earlier, “--- A host of forces shake our homes and cause our families to crumble, but three are of major impact: catastrophic change, persistent pressure, and pervasive pessimism” (Gary, 1995), and in the face of all these challenges and difficulties, how each family responds differs, because “Every family is unique. This impacts how they cope with problems and how they can be helped. For example, there are several influences that mold every family and create family distinctive” (Gary, 1995). Also, the factors that cause these problems in families range from one family to another, such as; issue of personal history, of which secrets are kept without revealing it to other members of the family, like divorce or previous marriage, illegitimate pregnancy, past affair with other people, etc and all these can hinder people from coping honestly during crisis in a family when eventually known. Also, issue of stress whereby a member of the family is stressed up and finds it difficult to relate with others well at a given point in time, likewise, issue of resources, where some families can cope well due to strength and skills acquired by members of the family while on the other hand, there might be breakdown of peace due to certain weakness in some members of the family. Other issues are also critical such as communication style to be adopted in the family, worldview, rules to be observed, values that are cherished, intimacy, role clarity, commitment to agreement, (Gary, 2007) etc.

Pastoral Counseling and the Family

The various family problems which are discussed above will necessitate the involvement of pastoral counseling so as to offer counsel or guidance of the probable way forward. However, when pastoral guidance are to be proffered or given in a family, the cognizance of the following should be taken; immediate practical guidance should be given, focus should be concentrated on the family and not individual, attempt in analyzing the present should be the priority and not the past, psychological approach should be adopted so as to reduce family tension, referring the family to where more help or solution could be accessed, and when families are helped to resolve crisis will definitely and eventually give the family the wherewithal to handle their problems from time to time (Gary, 2007).

Conclusion

Pastors are strategically positioned to offer or proffer guidance and advice leading to probable solution to various problems, challenges, crisis, and most often, the pastors are spiritually inclined and influenced to give illumination to the dark situation by using the Scripture, experience and the leading of the Holy Spirit. Since each family is a composite unit of the larger society that causes varying degree of problems to the family, then, each family should avail herself of the availability of Pastors who will offer spiritual guidance.

Recommendations

The following are the probable recommendations:

1. Each family should have a spiritual father who serves as the family pastor so as to offer useful counsel during troubles and challenges
2. Family altar where they worship together, study the word of God and teach the word of God to their subjects should be encouraged.
3. Pastors should not relent in heralding how marriages and homes should conduct themselves in noble practices.
4. Pastors should encourage NGOs and other governmental agencies to sensitize the public about right and wrong values of life, and they should desist from all forms of assaults.
5. Churches and communities should have welfare units and centers that are composed of pastors where families with difficulties can be directed to for guidance

Appendix

Some of the questions during the interview:

1. What has been the cause of instability in the family?
2. Which role does the father or mother or children play during instability in the family?
3. Is God needed during instability in the family?
4. Mention some of the challenges encountered during instability in the family
5. Can peace be sustained in the family?
6. What should the father, mother and the children do so as to check instability in the family?

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Inculcating the Value of Integrity in Young Persons in Ibadan Local Government Areas, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Integrity, the quality of being honest, upright and of good character has always been an essential ingredient for societal and national development. The observed lack of integrity among young persons in Ibadan Local Government Areas, (consisting of Ona Ara, Lagelu, Egbeda, Akinyele, Oluyole, Iddo), and at an increasing rate, is worrisome. This observed loss of integrity in individuals, families, communities, and Nigeria at large has been entrenched deep as a cultural worldview, militating against the general progress of the younger generation. To restore the value of integrity therefore, change must also occur at the deep level of their cultural perceptions, as efforts to change patterns of behaviour will at best be temporary. This paper suggests that intense efforts be made, by governmental and non-governmental agencies, to re-orientate both the elderly who naturally should teach values and beliefs, and the upcoming generation whose decay needs to be salvaged, as a strategy for holistic transformation of society. The curriculum to be utilized has already been put together by Nigeria's National Orientation Programme. Lack of integrity by those who should teach by precept and lifestyle has not permitted the programme to bring desired change in young Nigerians. Leaders, elders and parents who do what they say they will do, and who passionately pursue intentional re-orientation at the core of culture, are the solution to restoring integrity in the young in Ibadan Local Government Areas and Nigeria at large. To achieve this feat, not only should all hands be on deck, funding it must be prioritized by all.

1. Introduction

The nation, Nigeria as it stands currently is fraught with multiple anomalies in the socio-economic, political, educational and other spheres of life. The corruption ranking of Nigeria is 150 out of 180 countries, and she has 24 points out of 100 on the Corruption Perceptions index, reported by Transparency International for 2023 (Trading Economics, 2023) Middle aged Nigerians have tales of woes to talk about the dropping standards of living and the increase in corruption. Lacking in accurate census data, Nigeria is estimated to have a population of 217 million, 70% of these being youths. In this estimate, 42% are under the age of 15 (Worldometer, 2023). Another survey puts the age bracket of these large percentage of youths in Nigeria at 18-29 years, making Nigeria the youngest country in Africa (Akinyemi and Jacob, 2022). With the median age of Nigerians at 18.1 years, Nigeria indeed has a teeming population of young people.

The situation on ground in Ibadan, its environs and the whole of Oyo State in Nigeria, is a generation of young people in a precarious condition. Large numbers of school leavers who are not suitable for tertiary education, occasioned by lowered standards of education and the institutionalization of examination malpractices at both the primary and secondary schools. Increase in crime rates among the young, especially as it pertains to criminal acquisition of wealth is the order of the day. This phenomenon plays out among the males in efforts at swindling, robberies, cybercrimes, kidnappings and ritual killings for money, among others. Among young females, the loose life has become popular for acquiring material gains. Of

course, we have a fair portion of young persons who are enterprising and taking laudable strides in the right direction, but the vast majority fall under the previous description.

The decrease in levels and standards of living due to the economic woes of the nation seems to have compounded the dilemma of the young. Everyone seems to want to make money by the fastest possible ways and with the least efforts. Yet, no nation has ever developed on falsehood and crime (Proverbs 14:34). This paper addresses what it takes for the next generation of adult Nigerians to have the essential ingredient for holistic national development and visionary leadership.

1. **Integrity – A Core Value for Development**

Integrity simply defined is the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles. To describe integrity as it plays out in lives of persons, institutions or communities, it encapsulates these qualities – rectitude, honourableness, good character, principles, ethics, morality, virtue, trustworthiness among others (Mirriam-Webster Dictionary, 2023). Derived from the Latin word *integritas*, integrity connotes wholesomeness and the state of being undivided, indicating that a person of integrity is the same within and without. He can be relied upon, does what he says he will do and acts ethically correct no matter the pressures.

A people of integrity will by the definition proffered above, have value for what is true, will abhor and refuse to honour untruthfulness and ill-gotten wealth. They will value hard work and diligence as channels for successful enterprise. Top among their expectation from those who lead them will be integrity of character and credibility (Kouzes and Posner, 2011).

Where integrity is embedded as a societal value, parents and guardians will teach and model these traits; leaders will lead with integrity and policies of government will make it difficult for deviants to have a field day. Transparency in governance and in financial dealings have been the standard for development in many countries. In his paper, “Integrity – Foundation of Good Government”, Dr Emsley D Tromp, the president of the Bank of the Netherlands, proffered conditions necessary for economic efficiency and the eradication of corruption, which their country had practiced earlier on (Tromp, 2010). Among these are:

- Transparent government financial operations.
- Strong management of public resources and establishment of stable regulatory environment.
- Transparent budgetary procedures.
- More effective and accountable economic and financial institutions.

The bottom line in Emsley Tromp’s submission is that accountability and transparency of government institutions and officials have helped the Netherlands in its journey in developing as a nation. Integrity helped Netherlands and is still helping her development.

Countries we applaud as developed today all had their times in history when they were in chaos, and had to decide that doing the right things and doing them the right way, was the way to go. Great Britain’s history is fraught with periods when the people needed to have paradigm shifts to allow ethics and truth to rule their nation. It took British slavery abolitionists over 50 years (1770s - 1834) of struggle with the government and parliament of their days before they finally succeeded in effecting the Act (Henry, 2023). At the height of the British Industrial Revolution, when children were used in factories for long hours in hazardous conditions, for a few to get rich, right thinking British people pushed for the

enactment of the Factory Act (1833), and the Mines Act (1842) (The British Library, 2023). Today they have a nation that works, where Nigerians have targeted for migration.

Fruits of integrity in personal lives and families include wholesome behaviour, good mental health, committed workforce, forward looking and credible leaders at local, state and national levels.

Adelaja posits in his paper, "How to transform a nation through truth and honesty", that there is a strong relationship between truth, honesty and national development and that any country that we see progressing and forward looking, is fundamentally based on the principles of integrity (Adelaja, 2022). He further opined that national transformation will continue to be a mirage in Nigeria as long as the citizens are as corrupt as the politicians from whom they collect largesse in exchange for votes.

As long the ordinary citizens pay bribes to corrupt officials, to help them get waivers from doing the right things, in the right ways and at the right times, it means lack of integrity has become systemic. Albert Einstein rightly said, "Whoever is careless with the truth in small matters, cannot be trusted with important matters" (Adelaja, 2022). Such is the Nigerian situation because, it is the citizenry that produce their leaders; hence the nation's progress remains hampered because of the systemic lack of integrity. The undoing of the land presently is that those who should model integrity, as elders and leaders have only the opposite character to present as models for the teens and youths.

"Currently, we live in society that celebrates the rich without questioning what people did to acquire wealth, and this scenario has slowly but surely defined a new normal for the younger generation who aim to be rich by any means possible" (Chukwuka, 2021).

As it is obvious that lack of integrity is the root cause of corruption and its resultant effects on Nigeria's development, it is of utmost necessity that we pursue its return into our societal culture.

Evidence of Lack of Integrity in Ibadan Society Personal Lives

The society in question in this paper covers Ibadan city and its environs. Ibadan, the capital of Oyo State comprises eleven Local Government Areas (LGAs); five of these are Urban (Ibadan North, North East, North West, South East and South West), while six of them are suburban (Egbeda, Lagelu, Ona-Ara, Akinyele, Oluyole and Iddo). The estimated population of Ibadan is 3.6 million in the metropolis and about 6 million with the suburbs combined (Oyo State Nigeria -Population Statistics, 2021).

The population is made up of people of all age groups. Even though the target population in this paper are the young within the suburban LGAs mostly, it takes the older to teach or impact the younger. Since no one can give to another what he does not have, the older people are also targeted, so that they can be instruments of the desired change for a better Nigeria in the near future.

Integrity says, you are who you are when you think that no one is watching. Your true character is that which you really are on the inside, irrespective of what you portray when eyes are on you. A person of integrity maintains that quality all the time, irrespective of the pressures around.

The paramount evidence of lack of integrity starts with the individuals. Society is full of

- Persons who cheat others in the market place, either by exorbitant pricing or direct shortchanging of customers.

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- Persons who tell lies to escape doing what is right; give false evidence on oath in the law courts; alter prices on receipts to defraud institutions; are involved in bribery and similar evils.
 - Individuals who commit atrocities as rape, murders, kidnaps, ritual killings to get rich, among others.

3.2 Family Life

These are evidenced in the news every day in the target areas and the whole nation at large. The individuals living with the core values of lack of integrity cannot produce families that are different. Moses when instructing the nation of Israel before they entered the land of Cannan, asked the parents and guardians to first put the law of God for righteous living in their own hearts. He said that was when they would be able to teach it accurately to the younger generations. (Deuteronomy 6:4-9).

Evidence of lack of integrity abound at the family levels.

- Parents who ask their children to lie when creditors are around, abound. By these and similar acts, family heads entrench lack of truthfulness as family norms.
- What do you think happens to a child whose parent/guardian pays depraved school teachers to "help" his ward pass examinations? This parent has demonstrated to him that he does not need to follow due process to succeed in life. The foundation for fraud, bribery and corruption is well laid within the family. When under pressure for funds that child would commit crimes as serious as kidnapping or ritual killing to get those funds. These and worse occurrences are the order of the day.
- Within many families, different forms of assault are perpetrated from fathers on mothers and the children. Verbal, physical, even sexual abuse is on the increase. The children of these homes have simply been taught to be violent and cover up when interrogated.

Society

As the family is the bedrock of any society, it is obvious why the evidences of lack of integrity abound everywhere.

3.3. SOCIETY

As a result of lack of personal/family integrity, the communities are dysfunctional. The parents have eaten sour grapes, but it is the children whose teeth are on edge (Ezekiel 18:2). The prevailing situation in many of the communities covered within Ibadan is that of an increase in vices which include but are not limited to these:

- Unstable families where fathers are either absent or uncommitted to providing for the children.
- Young mothers (often times teenagers) who have not completed secondary education, impregnated by young men who have no stable jobs or skills to provide for themselves and their families.
- Many disillusioned youths without prospects for a better future hooked on drugs and alcohol, setting the stage for many mental health casualties.
- Robberies, gangsterism/cultism, internet fraud and selling off lands previously sold, and similar crimes.
- Those who suddenly become affluent are admired without questioning how that happened in the absence any tangible enterprise linked to them.

- In rural and suburban communities, the youths have abandoned the farms and shun career in Agriculture, preferring to be commercial motorcycle riders, and to do similar daily paid jobs.
- Due to ignorance of what is right in the society, many in the communities have already begun to view cybercrimes among youths as a skill to be acquired thereby despising enterprise, perseverance and diligent efforts.
- In response to peer pressure and the 'need' to be acclaimed as 'rich', the youths captured in the situations above, resort to all kinds of vices that are offshoots of thought patterns void of integrity.

When this generation of young people become the elders, will they have better values to teach their children than what they themselves are? As it stands, the above is the present pattern of life evolving in this society.

Where did things go wrong?

Where should right values begin to be put in place?

1. How Can Culture Change or Be Transformed

Culture simply defined is the totality of the way of life of a people. Culture comprises the learned patterns of behaviour of a people and their underlining assumptions. The patterns of behaviour are what we see, which include their dress patterns, their food, their artifacts, ceremonies/rights of passage and how they generally behave. For every behaviour seen on the outside, underlining assumptions are influencing such behaviours (Kwast, 2009). As Kwast explains that underneath what we observe as people's visible cultural patterns, lies layers of factors that influence what people do.

BEHAVIOUR: These are the customs, products, and language. This comprises what people do or what they consider as appropriate behaviour.

VALUES: These are standards of conduct and determinants of judging what ought to be done, what is good or best. Values answers for people, the question, 'What is normal in order to conform to the pattern of life of that community'? So, we see that values people hold influence their behaviours.

Figure 1

BELIEFS: Here, what the true belief of people is, determines their values. Theoretical beliefs do not influence values; rather it is what they believe in their hearts that determine what they value.

WORLDVIEW is at the core of every culture. It is the lens as it were, with which the people see things and interpret reality. Worldview assumptions may not have been proven and may be myths, but they are accepted as reality. They directly influence the beliefs and values, which ultimately define the behaviour of the people.

If any aspect of culture is going to change, it must begin at the worldview level, and work its way to their patterns of behaviour. Worldview is so powerful that it still controls people even after they receive a new belief system. As long as their worldview is not changed, they still behave as they did before they received their new beliefs (Kraft, 2009). This phenomenon explains the syncretic behaviours of some variants of Christianity.

The core of any culture is often guarded by elders whose duty it is, to impart such to the younger generations. We have observed that integrity has become a lost aspect of Nigeria's culture, and is now a needed ingredient for national development, societal health and prosperity. We therefore need to explore ways to restore this virtue back into our national worldview. But, how does culture change? Using the onion analogy, the core (centre) of the onion is the only part that can reproduce an onion. The outer layers of the onion are not reproducible. If we keep trying to change behaviours, values and beliefs without addressing the people's worldview, there cannot be any enduring result. People will still manifest their old patterns of values and behaviour.

5. Areas Where Integrity Must Be Inculcated in the Society and Nation

- a) Individuals should come to the realization that they need to be persons with their own personal integrity. When people have been taught to have a sense of worth over their own persons, they begin to see it is demeaning for them to be liars, cheats or to have bad reputation before others.
- b) Families should pride themselves based on the integrity of their members, the truthfulness and transparency of their children's sources of wealth, and sharply oppose sudden wealth that cannot be accounted for. Traditional cultural values that frown on promiscuity and loose life of ladies should be upheld. The home and the parents in the home should decide on what they wish to be known by, and teach such to their children and wards.
- c) Community and political leadership should be above board. People with integrity should be those who become our leaders.
- d) Government and its officials should be credible. Without integrity at this level, there cannot be national orientation that will successfully eradicate corruption.

6. Who Does What?

All hands will have to be on deck to tackle a systemic lack of truth, honesty and uprightness. When a good seed is sown in the soil, you expect to be able to re-propagate it and still get that seed with all its original features.

Stakeholders for the return of the vital ingredient of Integrity will have to include:

- The teachers of Religion who will teach the fear of God to the people. This cannot be achieved by those who practice or teach religion as a duty. Only the passionate can persevere in efforts to change the warped worldview assumptions of the young Nigerians of today.

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- The community and opinion leaders who are not part of the ‘bandwagon’ of corrupt elders will need to arise to speak for and live out the values that will give birth to the return of integrity in their domains.
 - Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) will need to come up with innovative ways to teach Integrity to government and call government officials to become accountable to the society. Example of an area that can be very fruitful is the school system, where NGOs can mount up pressure and insist that all teachers who ‘help’ pupils writing the common entrance examinations, or students sitting for their secondary school certificate examinations, should be permanently sent out of the teaching profession. Since we have enrollment of pupils and students in very high percentage in schools (public and private) in Ibadan, next to the home, the school system should be targeted.
 - Government parastatals and ministries saddled with various responsibilities are in very good position to effect a new orientation. These would be able to present a covering for all other efforts by nongovernmental agencies, if they work in synergy.

What To Do

The curriculum for this proposed worldview change is not far-fetched. On paper, Nigeria has a National Orientation Policy (National Orientation Agency, 2021). Strategic Plan for 2021-2026. We do not need to reinvent the wheel. In this plan, the goal for Strategic Pillar 3 is, to “Positively change attitudes, values and behaviours that promote peace, harmony and national development”. Its priority areas are

- a. Citizen engagement
- b. Public enlightenment
- c. Civic responsibility

The plans if followed, should have turned Nigerian youth into people of great integrity and great hope for the nation’s development. Of relevance to the discourse in this paper is the fact the plans include hopes that the nation will be rid of corruption. What laudable plans! The problem this paper sees and presents for solution, is that those who will make an impact with their teachings, should first be people who practice what they teach. The leadership has to show that they mean what they say. Worldview changes precede changes in values and behaviours, hence the need for parents, guardians, teachers, community leaders and elders to be first, people who teach by life before teaching by precepts.

Conclusions

In exploring avenues for inculcating the value of integrity into young Nigerians, particularly in Ibadan and its environs, this paper concludes that

1. The status quo must change. It is unacceptable for the young people on whom the future of our country lies, to be allowed to continue living lives that lack integrity and truth when we know that it does not augur well for future progress and prosperity for the nation.
2. Since the lack of integrity has been deeply embedded in the present culture of both the elderly and the young, it will require a deep level culture change aimed at bringing about a worldview that agrees that integrity, uprightness should be the norm.

3. To achieve this feat, everyone is a stakeholder. The individuals in families, the families in the communities, the leaders and elders in communities, the teachers both secular and religious, government and non-governmental agencies.
4. The fear of God should be taught from the home front and the religious groups should take up the challenge to be the change agents of these times.

Recommendations

Concerned persons and groups who have the understanding that things are wrong, should arise to put in their own part in the inculcating integrity into young persons in Ibadan Area and nationally. This paper recommends that there be a proliferation of efforts in these areas:

1. Orientation for parents and guardians based on written ethics, code of conduct and responsible parenting. Aspects of the National Orientation policy programme book could be adapted.
2. Organize and run intentional neighbourhood clubs for children and teens. These could be sports based, faith based, or intellect based. Here the activities should include Story-telling sessions where integrity, uprightness, diligence and the likes are portrayed and taught.
3. School teachers' re-orientation to return to ethics of the profession. The ministry of education and the Teachers' Commission should spearhead this aspect. Non-governmental agencies should help to spur these government agencies, and hold them accountable to enforce teachers' compliance to ethics.
4. Use of all media avenues (regular and social) to air jingles and playlets that resonate with integrity as key for personal, community and national progress.
5. NGOs and Faith bodies to coin appropriate ways to amplify the government's national orientation agency plans for the young in Nigeria.
6. Funding by government and philanthropic organizations should be made available to societies and groups who are committed to doing any of the recommendations above.

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Pastoral Counselling and National Development

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Abstract

Nigeria is besieged by many ills such as social disintegration, political intolerance, tribal discrimination, violation of human rights, and insecurity. Such problems threaten the survival of the nation. It is a common experience that majority of Nigerians today are wallowing in abject poverty, penury and backwardness, while a few people live in luxury and affluence. The situation is attributed to "bad" governance among other factors. Leadership creates record of reckless plundering of the Nation's resources for personal gains. Therefore, Nigeria is at the mercy of corrupt, tyrannical and power drunk minority. The situation has adversely affected the citizen morally, emotionally and psychologically. Scholars have discussed guidance and counseling and Pastoral counseling and psychotherapy as possible ways of solving this national menace, however, not much have been done on how Pastoral counseling can influence good governance and national development. So, there is still need to interrogate the Biblical principles of counseling and apply it to governance in Nigeria. Therefore, this paper seeks to examine the significance of Pastoral counseling in national development. The research employs the descriptive method, interviews were conducted and data collected were qualitatively analysed. Findings from the study reveal that psychotherapy contribute greatly to human development, and that pastoral counseling is a tool that enhances good governance, and therefore recommends that Christian leaders and public office holders should rise to the occasion to save the tragic situation by employing the biblical and counseling principles to condemn the causes of hardship and poverty in the society.

Keywords: Pastoral counseling, Therapy, Psychotherapy, Governance, Servant-leadership

1. Introduction

The nation building is one which involves effort of the patriotic people of a country, and its joint responsibility of every individual. The degree of involvement, however, depends on the different age-stages of the citizens of the country. For instance, people who are old cannot perform any effective role as the youth and adolescents would. Also, youth and adolescents irrespective of the agility and pro-activeness cannot occupy the place the adults and the elderly. Development is highly needed among the citizens, such as; the youth, adolescents, adults and elderly, since they are major stakeholders in the project of nation-building (Adegoke, 2003: 56). Due to this singular and crucial point, all efforts must be put in place for their physical, social, moral, mental, spiritual, educational, psychological, vocational, and personality development. In reality, it is impossible to separate one facet of development or growth from another; so interrelated and interdependent are they within the complexity of human development. Counselling is therefore required as mechanism to foster a sense of nationhood and promote national development, to ensure adaptability to promote social equality and remove divisions of race, tribe and religion; to respect the cultural traditions of the nation, both as expressed in social institutions and relationships etc. (Adekola, 2000: 43-46).

2. Meaning of Counselling

Counselling is a process of helping people with their problems. Other synonymous names with counselling include; therapy, helping rehabilitation and others. Effective Counselling should result in desirable changes in the lives of the people with problems. Counselling thus describes processes by which a professionally trained person (a counsellor) attempts to help an individual (a client) resolve some problems. Guidance and Counselling thus describe the organized efforts of individuals or institutions to help a client achieve his potentials and the processes initiated to help him solve his or her problems so that he or she could be more effective and satisfied (Ademola, 1999: 62-64). Generally, in a guidance and counselling relationship, the Counsellor may be able to effect desirable changes in the client's perceptions, thinking, feelings, emotions and actions so that the client is, in the end, more effective and satisfied. Guidance is a family name for all the helping services within the general educational and community systems. This is why Ipaye (1983) posited that guidance on the one hand is a general label, an umbrella term that covers all the means whereby an institution identifies and responds to the individual needs of people and thereby helping the individual to develop his or her maximum potential. Counselling, on the other hand, is a subset of the general term that are called guidance.

Furthermore, Olayinka (2019) defined counselling as the process in which one person assist another in a person-to-person or face-to-face encounter. This assistance, he stressed, may take many forms: it may be educational, vocational, social, recreational, emotional and or moral. Makinde (2015) opined that counselling as "an enlightened process whereby people help each other by facilitating growth, development and positive change through an exercise of self-understanding and self-actualisation." According to Blocher (2014), it involves helping an individual become more fully aware of himself and the ways in which he's responding to the influences in his environment. It further assists him to establish some personal meaning for this behaviour and to develop and clarify a set of goals and values for future behaviour.

3. Pastoral Counselling

The pastoral counselor, through a spiritual leader should utilize a number of psychological experiential and academic strategies to rehabilitate the church member with a problem. The pastoral counsellor may begin by observing certain behaviour such as: (1) how the church youth members behave, (2) why they behave that way; (3) how to handle them; (4) how to counsel them. The implication of the above approach is that the pastoral counsellor should conduct psychological assessment of the behaviour he is observing. This means that the pastoral counsellor should know much more than the Bible. He needs adequate knowledge of psychology and other subjects such as Biology, Sociology, medicine, while he may not necessarily be an expert in these areas. Since the solution of the problem pre supposes that it has been clearly defined, adequate assessment should precede any programme of pastoral counselling.

The works of Thornburg, Walsh and Akinboye (2008) essentially outlined the basic principles of counselling, ranging from the strictly psychodynamic to the terribly behavioural:

- i. Concerns about self (including physical appearance, peoples' perceptions, health etc).
- ii. Morality: Drinking alcohol. Smoking and other drugs, breaking societal rules.
- iii. Peers and friends- Concerned about being popular, utopian perfectionist beliefs, fault-finding.

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- iv. God-how to know what he wants them to do, does he listen to me, how to talk to him. What is he likes.
 - v. National and world issues- hunger, money, war.
 - vi. My future- what to do living, having enough money, how to make decision, can I get a job.
 - vii. The church- Is satisfying, should be involved in social issues, not planned for youth, need better leaders.
 - viii. Religion- Wishing to relate more personally with God, is it alright to doubt, hard to explained faith and convictions, having not enough faith etc.

Useful pastoral counselling may include programmes directed towards:

- (a) Solving personal- social problems- preaching teaching sermon- modelling talking etc. Any form of communication with the church member that leads to trust and consequently relieve his problem. At every stage, the guiding questions include how and why he behaves, how to handle him and how to help him out.
- (b) Prevention of the development of maladaptive behaviours such as drug abuse, alcoholism, smoking, conflicts, frustrations, depressions, low self- concept and anxieties
- (c) Establishing adequate vocational adjustment decision- making skills maturity, employment seeking and occupational adaptation competence.
- (d) Developing adequate work habits and creativity.
- (e) Evolving pre- marital and marital counselling programmes.
- (f) Establishment of adequate community and national awareness (Idowu, 1974: 55-59).

4. Pastoral Counselling and National Development

National development presupposes that either there has been no nation, and therefore one is envisaged and is being planned; or that one that exists has to be reconstructed in order to be worthy of the name. National development, therefore, needs a chief Architect or developer- someone who has not only a theoretical conception of what a nation should be, but is also equipped with the practical knowledge of the facts and rule that will make the building a worthy work of art as well as an abiding reality- a triumph of skillful planning and execution (Lovell, 2016: 70). He should also be a person who has regard for genuine talents and is ready to afford himself of the best of such talents in persons of suitable caliber without any prejudice with regard to places of origin or relational connections. What the developer needs in his co-workers or builders and general workers should be capacity for work, ability to understand and carry out well laid out plans, honesty and integrity (Akinboye, 2005: 57). He himself should be a dedicated person, leading dedicated co- workers- all of them together with one central aim of making the best job of their assignment; he should have appropriated the wisdom of ages that the best art of commanding is to take a fair share of work. If the master planner and those who work with him to translate his plan into reality should become self-centered or selfish, or if they should deviate from the noble principle dictated by their goal of architecture, the result will be inevitable futility; their planned "city, a tower with its top in the heavens" will only attain the confusion of Babel (Adeyemi, 2018:60-65).

Furthermore, what are the basic materials for developing a nation? These are people, persons created and endowed with inherent freedom, which may be latent (to assert itself in due course) or is being expressed in various ways; persons with the faculties of intelligent will and

purpose which develop and come into some forms of fruition in accordance with opportunities, education and development (Kalish, 2001:95). At the domestic or a single ethnic level, such personal autonomy as outlined above is prevented from excesses by what may be described as a natural community of interest. With a nation, peoples at various levels of cultures and development are brought together, or flung together, as in the case of Nigeria or other countries of Africa where it was the hand of foreign imperialism that determined which peoples should come together to form a country which they hoped would become a nation (Akinyode, 2016: 78).

This is a situation which needs very careful handling, especially when the heavy, compelling-restraining hand of imperialism is removed and the peoples of various backgrounds and levels of culture are faced with the task of settling down together, accepting leadership, developing a community of interest, and thinking of themselves, not exclusively and selfishly as belonging to this or that ethnic group (e.g. as Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba), but as belonging together as one people, all together and with sincerity seeking "the good of their Jerusalem". A national consciousness has to be born, but not without the process of becoming – birth throes, growth and development, and conformity to the immanent norm of being. This is the inevitable rule for a nation to develop her own authentic corporate personality (Baumrind, 2019:58-61).

Paul the apostle wrote in a metaphorical language about building. This metaphor is quite relevant to the Christian, in developing the nation, Nigeria. He wrote in part,

... As a wise master-builder, I have laid the foundation and another builds thereon. But let every man take heed how he builds thereupon. For other foundation can no man lay than that which is laid, which is Jesus Christ. Now if any man build upon this foundation, gold, silver, precious stones, wood, hay, and stubble; every man's work shall be made manifest... and the fire shall try every man's work of what sort it is (Bryne, 2005: 87).

When fire tries materials like gold, silver, precious stones, they shall come out fire, shining than ever before. On the contrary, if fire has to try the other three materials, that is, wood, hay and stubble no doubt, nothing but may be ashes would be left. So, as Christians build on Jesus Christ who is the foundation, they are called upon to build on the entity called Nigeria as well. There is a very clear warning for the Christian. He is called upon to build with materials that endure, that is, the first three rather than the last three materials. Otherwise, he shall "suffer loss". In developing the nation, such materials as prayers, patriotism, promotion of righteousness, discipline etc. will represent good and enduring materials (Crutchfield, .and Ballachey, 2012: 77-81). On the contrary, things like unrighteousness, lawlessness, apathy, compromises, etc. will represent materials that cannot endure or stand the test of fire. For using that former, there is a reward, but for using the latter, there is no reward. The Christian is then enjoined to make use of the 'building materials,' that endure through time and eternity (Elegbeleye, 2021: 43-47).

Obligation of the Christian to Earnest Prayer: One great responsibility of the Nigerian Christian to the building of his nation, is fervency in prayer. Paul underscores this point when he wrote:

I exhort therefore, that, first of all, supplications, prayers intercessions, and giving of thanks, be made for all men; For kings, and for all that are in authority; that we may lead a quiet and peaceable life in all godliness and honesty (1 Tim.2;1-2).

No matter how despotic the ruler may be, the Christian has no choice but to pray for him. It does not even matter if such a ruler persecutes Christians (Elwell, 2018: 91-93).

The injunction of Jesus Christ Himself is very clear. "Love your enemies, bless them that curse you, ... and pray for them which despitefully use you and persecute" (Mat. 5:44). So, any lack in this area, for the Christian, is simply, disobedience

God does not expect the ungodly or the unbeliever to pray. He expects His own people to come to Him penitently in prayer. Abogunrin (2014) puts it thus:

The healing of the sick nation is not committed to the politicians nor to the freedom fighters, but God says, it is the responsibility of His people, those who are called by His name.

The failure of Christians to engage in fervent prayers may not be unconnected with many evils being perpetrated, seemingly unrestrained in the Nigerian society. There is no limit to what the Christian can achieve, if he will take the issue of praying to God, for the nation, with all the seriousness it deserves. Rather than analyse the national problem and apportion blames alone, the Christian should pray more. One enduring material that will help Nigeria to be developed up is prayer.

In addition, Promotion of Righteous is another factor: 'Righteous exalts a nation but sin is a reproach to any people' (Prov. 14:34). True righteous involves being really obedient to the law of the land and the recognition that all men irrespective of color or race, are of one blood having been created in the image of God. It is obvious that, there is no society in which all men are on the same level. However, the Christian should be actively involved in causes that support and promote equal opportunities (Feldman & Elliot, 2014: 66-68).

In obeying the laws of the land, there is a problem that nags. What if government promulgates an unrighteous law, or a law that is not in consonance with the will of God, is the Christian obliged to obey? The apostles were confronted with a similar situation on a number of occasions. On one such occasion, they were forbidden from preaching the gospel of Jesus Christ. Peter and John had to respond bluntly, 'Whether it be right in the sight of God to hearken unto you more than unto God, judge ye. For one cannot but speak the things which we have seen and heard' (Acts 4:19-20). The Christian should not find any ambiguity, if the interest of the state clashes with that of God (Gaddis, & Brooks-Gunn, 2015: 23-25).

Patriotism and performance of civil responsibilities: quite a number of Christians are ignorant of political issues. Perhaps that explains why few committed Christians are actively involved in influencing the political process. The Christian cannot afford to be ambivalent about governments. Like it was pointed out earlier, God established government and because of this divine origin, he cannot be apathetic towards politics. Governments are parts of God's plan (Hart, Gulbranson, & Smith, 2018: 80).

Many things are done by legislation and that underscores the reason why the Christian must be interested in the governmental processes. Somebody like Wilberforce brought an end to slave trade by making use of political power. Many others have worked tirelessly in government to see a new order emerge. Christian should take keen interest in the people that would be elected to rule him. He should familiarize himself with the candidates vying for one post or another. Then, he should exercise his voting privilege. This will go a long way in making sure that the right person who will promote the will of God being done in the country, would be chosen (Hein, 2010: 54-56).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, national development is a task for every individual and responsibility of patriotic citizen. The counselor is in a good position to create counselling techniques about implementing life skills programs that will help people to grow and develop in their full potential. Counselors have the training to apply cognitive behavioural approaches, group processes, and other developmental strategies in the effort to improve Nigerians ability to adjust properly to crisis situation. The pastoral counsellors were therefore challenged to play their God-given role in taking part in national development, using their professional experience, technical competence and their right standing with God. Counsellors' positive contributions will help in behavior modification, adjustment mechanism and upholding the social and moral values in bring sanity into the system.

Based on the conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- a. Counsellors should play well their part in national development, using their professional experience and training
- b. Counsellors should be recognized by Government and given an enabling environment and necessary encouragement as they discharge their duties in nation-building
- c. Government should give adequate orientation to citizens on the need to seek counselling regularly.

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Redemptive Excommunication in Matthew 18:15-20 and Its Implications for Pastoral Counselling in the Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria

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Abstract

Redemptive excommunication is a component of church discipline through which the church corrects sinful behaviour in the congregation or removes a sinful person from the membership. Through the centuries the church has shown vital concern about how to discipline and restore its erring members. Jesus in Mathew 18:15-20 instructed the church to treat an erring member who refuses correction as they would a pagan or a tax collector. Keeping heretic and immoral members within the fold posed serious danger to its existence. This researcher is goaded by this scenario to write this paper. Past and recent works on settling church dispute is replete but none has brought in the expulsion of unrepentant erring member as measure of preservation of the remaining faithful members of the church. The methodology adopted is historical and exegetical. The study discovered that Church discipline is neither the exclusive responsibility nor the prerogative of church leaders. Also, discipline does not first push the contamination out of the church but rather draws the erring back to church. The researcher recommends that the first task of the church leaders is to develop churches in which people really know and care for one another. The first disciplinary approach should be made in private. That a member is excommunicated does not mean that the church should abandon him. Excommunication should be redemptive both to the erring and the members of the church. The full restoration of excommunicated member should be an expression of pastoral care in its motive and effect.

Keywords: Counselling, Discipline, Excommunication, Pastoral, Redemptive

Introduction

Within the realm of Christian ministry and pastoral care, one of the most challenging and theologically significant matters that confront the Church is the issue of discipline and restoration within the body of believers. The Gospel of Matthew, in particular, provides us with a profound and redemptive framework for addressing this sensitive topic. In Matthew 18:15-20, we find the words of Jesus, our Lord, and Savior, who presents a divine blueprint for reconciling and restoring those who have strayed from the fold. This passage is not merely a set of instructions; it is a sacred mandate, a scriptural revelation of divine wisdom aimed at preserving the sanctity of the Christian community while exemplifying the mercy and grace of the Triune God.

The heart of this research lies in "redemptive excommunication," a term that may appear paradoxical at first glance. Yet, in exploring the depths of Matthew 18:15-20, we discover a divine paradox-the simultaneous need for discipline and grace, correction and compassion. In its essence, redemptive excommunication signifies the act of removing an unrepentant

believer from the fellowship of the Church for the purpose of reconciliation and restoration. It is a process bathed in love, designed to draw the erring one back to the path of righteousness, safeguarding not only the purity of the Church but also the soul of the wandering sheep. The burden of this is that despite the fact works has been done on the subject of excommunication in the church, none has addressed the removal of erring member as a measure of preservation of the remaining faithful members who may be prone to contamination from the unrepentant erring member if not removed. This study delves into the profound theological implications of redemptive excommunication as outlined in Matthew 18:15-20, seeking to unearth the treasures of divine wisdom that guide the Church in its role as a community of grace, love, and transformation. Furthermore, this research aims to examine how this divine directive interfaces with the realm of pastoral counseling, a sacred discipline within Christian ministry among the Pentecostal churches in Nigeria.

I. Definition of Terms

A. Redemptive Excommunication

Excommunication is the disciplinary action of a local church to remove one of its members from the membership on the basis of his or her stubborn disobedience to the commands of Christ, or divisive distortions of the doctrines of Christ. It is the end of the disciplinary process. It declares that although the person may profess Christ with his or her mouth, they have denied him by their way of life. Excommunication, therefore, puts to an end all of the benefits of Christian fellowship for the one excommunicated. It also puts an end to the obligations of the Church as it pertains to the care of the person's soul (Anady, 2012). Excommunication is the word that we use to describe what Christ stated in Matthew 18:17, saying, "If he refuses to listen to them, tell it to the church. And if he refuses to listen even to the church, let him be to you as a Gentile and a tax collector" (Matthew 18:17, ESV). To excommunicate is to put a person out of the church and into the world, for his or her unrepentant way of life has made it plain that that is where he or she belongs – in the world and not in the church, according to Anady (2012).

The term redemptive Excommunication is a term used in certain Christian contexts to describe a process by which an individual who is a member of a church community, and who is in unrepentant sin, is temporarily or permanently removed from the fellowship of the church. The primary purpose of redemptive excommunication is to bring about repentance and restoration in the individual's life.

B. Pastoral Counselling

Counselling could be said to refer to a number of procedures used in assisting an individual in solving problems which arise in various aspects of his life or in assisting him to maximize his overall personal development so that he could be more effective, satisfied and more useful to the society in which he lives. The nature of counselling, according to Patterson, is to be found in the following characteristics:

1. Counselling is concerned with influencing voluntary behavioural change on the part of the client or counsellee.
2. The purpose of counselling is to provide condition that facilitates voluntary in behaviour.
3. As in all relationship, limits are imposed on the counsellee by counselling goals that are influenced by the counsellor's values and philosophy.

4. Conditions facilitating behavioural change are provided through interview (not all counselling is interviewing, but interview is always involved).
5. Listening is present in counselling but not all counselling is listening.
6. The counsellor understands clients.
7. Counselling is conducted in privacy and the discussion is confidential (Abidogun, 2022).

According to Abidogun (2022), Pastoral counselling is also known as ministerial or religious counselling. In Banner's (1992, pp. 56-57) opinion, pastoral counselling involves the establishment of a time-limited relationship that is structured to provide comfort for troubled persons by enhancing their awareness of God's grace and faithful presence and thereby increasing their ability to live their lives more fully in the light of these realizations.

C. The Nexus

Pastoral counselling and redemptive excommunication can complement each other. Pastoral counselling is often the first step in addressing issues of sin or spiritual waywardness. If counselling does not lead to repentance and restoration, the church may proceed with redemptive excommunication. These approaches can be sequential. A person who initially receives pastoral counselling may face excommunication if they continue in unrepentant sin. Redemptive excommunication is a more severe step and is typically considered after other attempts at reconciliation have been exhausted. The key to the relationship between pastoral counselling and redemptive excommunication is that both are motivated by love, grace, and a desire for the individual's spiritual well-being. The hope is that through counselling and, if necessary, excommunication, the person may ultimately come to a place of repentance and restoration (Tomlinson, 2020).

II. Goal of Redemptive Excommunication

Redemptive excommunication also refers to "corrective church discipline", with a primary purpose of discipling, has five goals; reconciliation, purity, restoration, freedom and communal value. Below, each goal will be articulated theologically to provide a more precise understanding of the construct of corrective church discipline:

Reconciliation: The primary objective is to achieve reconciliation, which can be defined as the transformation of hostility into friendship. This concept of reconciliation is deeply rooted in the nature of the Trinity, which is characterized by love. The Triune God, being loving, eternally exists in a state of perfect community (Grenz, 1998, p. 47). The church is called to partner with Christ in this ministry of reconciliation, one aspect of which includes corrective church discipline. Spirit-filled love conditions the attitudes and actions in which the reconciliation processes are to be exercised. These attitudes include gentleness, humility, sorrow, forgiveness, and brotherliness. The posture of reconciling corrective discipline is sorrow for a brother or sister who is trapped, and not condemnation for an enemy who is to be injured (Hull, 1993, p. 147).

Purity: The second goal of the corrective discipling process is purity. Purity is anchored in the holy character of God. The church is called to the moral responsibility of purity on the basis of God's holiness. One aspect of this participation is through corrective discipline in which the believer caught in sin is called back to the life of personal purity (Grenz, 1998, p. 49).

Restoration: The third goal of corrective church discipling is restoration. Restoration, through discipline, is the gracious action of God. Restorative action issues from God's character of love

and more precisely His particular love for the church. God's restorative discipline is neither punishment nor judgement. The church is called to partner with God in the ministry of restoration. In fact, restoration within the church is the ministry of Christ working by the Holy Spirit through the church in perfecting the church. The believer who is "caught" (*prolambano*) in sin is "trapped," "bound by," or "in bondage to" to sin. Those that are spiritual are commanded to-restore that individual. The idea of restoring is renewing someone to usefulness. The verb - restore (*katarizo*) in Galatians 6:1 is a medical term that was used in secular Greek for setting a fractured bone (Grenz, 1998, p. 49).

Freedom: The fourth goal of corrective discipline is freedom. Sin always causes enslavement. Alternatively, living in righteousness brings Christian freedom. This freedom is not the right to do as one pleases as advocated by the individualism of Western culture. Rather, freedom is the power and capacity both to will and to do as one ought. The freedom of Christian liberty is freedom from sin in order to be like Jesus Christ. Christian liberty is never freedom from responsibility. Rather, it is responsibility for choice and empowerment for right choice. Thus, through restoration of members who have been caught in sin there is a new liberty that is realized within the church (Sider, 2005, 45).

Communal Value: In addition to the aforementioned, the writer believes that another goal of corrective discipline is establishment of communal values where the place and the roles of the elders within the community are highly celebrated and the community is seen as more important collectively than an individual. Adamo listed that a sense of the community, a sense of good human relations, a sense of sacredness of life, a sense of hospitality, a sense of sacredness of everything and religion, and a sense of respect for authority and elders who are in possession of wisdom by virtue of their experience should be celebrated. (Adamo, 2015, p. 11).

III. An Exegetical Study of Matthew 18:15-20

A. Background of Study

The anonymity of the four Gospel writers is a serious issue in scholarship since the Gospels are unlike the epistles which follow certain writing styles that easily identify the writers. According to France (1989, pp. 50-1), there are scholars who argue that the names of the authors of the Gospel books were a later addition by the Church about 215 CE. The authorship of Matthew received the most criticism because it was not only nameless but both the internal and external evidences seem to go against the traditional view of Matthean authorship. Hence, so many notable scholars have decided to disagree with the traditional authorship of Matthew, one of the 12 apostles. In response to Green's arguments, the following ensues: (a) —The structure and composition of the Gospel show that the evangelist is influenced by Jewish literature. Green (2000, pp. 19-27) argues that the Gospel of Matthew has almost no link to Hebrew and/or Aramaic even though Papias had reported it was written in Hebrew instead of Greek which he said is misleading. Kurzinger suggests Papias's statement means: Matthew arranged the traditions in a Jewish manner (Luz, 2001, 46). Therefore, this implies that Matthew used and arranged other materials like Mark, Q (and other early Christian traditions) in the above manner. This may also explain the existing literary relationship of Gospel books and their different arrangements. (b) Probably —[t]he Matthean sources, Mark and Q, [may] have been arrayed and circulated in Jewish Christian community before the writing of Matthew. (c) The author's familiarity with Jewish concepts and environment, the Law and the Old Testament suggests a Jewish author.

Hengel refutes claims that titles were later added to the first century gospels by the Church and presented a thought-provoking thesis contrary to that assumption. He based his research on—the nature of references to the gospels in the second-century Christian literature, and the general practice of book-distribution in the Greek world, where titles were necessary for identification of a work to which reference might be made. Therefore, Hengel's argument is that it would be very unlikely to have such sacred documents in circulation among the Christian communities in the late first century without proper reference to their authorship (France, 1989, p. 50).

Therefore, it is reasonable to argue with the Church tradition on the authorship of Matthew as one of the twelve apostles of Jesus. Moreover, Keener (1999, p. 41) rightly observes that:—some scholars who reject Matthean authorship are troubled by the antiquity of the Gospel titles and the tradition of authorship ... [even though] too many scholars simply ignore these difficulties. The place of writing has been argued mostly for Egypt, Palestine and Syria among Bible scholars. For example: Brandon singled out Alexandria as the place of writing due to the significant presence of a good number of Jews in the city; for they were the next leading practicing Jewish community after the destruction of the Temple and the disorganization of the Jewish community in Jerusalem (France, 1989, p. 51). France (1989, p. 51) appears more inclined to the Palestinian origin of the gospel. The option of Syria is divided between either Antioch or Tyre (or one of the neighbouring Phoenician cities) The preceding discussion suggests that the author's place of writing may also be the same locality of his immediate recipients. The date of writing may be (a) either before or after AD 70; (b) the early second century.

B. Textual Consideration of Matthew 18:15-20

15 "Ἐὰν δὲ ἀμάρτη εἰς σὲ ὁ ἀδελφός σου, ὕπαγε ἔλεγξον αὐτὸν μεταξὺ σοῦ καὶ αὐτοῦ μόνου. ἐὰν σοῦ ἀκούσῃ, ἐκέρδησας τὸν ἀδελφόν σου.

16 ἐὰν δὲ μὴ ἀκούσῃ, παράλαβε μετὰ σοῦ ἓτι ἓνα ἢ δύο, ἵνα ἐπὶ στόματος δύο μαρτύρων ἢ τριῶν σταθῇ πᾶν ῥῆμα.

17 ἐὰν δὲ παρακούσῃ αὐτῶν, εἰπέ τῇ ἐκκλησίᾳ. ἐὰν δὲ καὶ τῆς ἐκκλησίας παρακούσῃ, ἔστω σοι ὡσπερ ὁ ἐθνικὸς καὶ ὁ τελώνης.

18 Ἀμὴν λέγω ὑμῖν, ὅσα ἐὰν δήσητε ἐπὶ τῆς γῆς, ἔσται δεδεμένα ἐν οὐρανῶ, καὶ ὅσα ἐὰν λύσητε ἐπὶ τῆς γῆς, ἔσται λελυμένα ἐν οὐρανῶ.

19 Πάλιν [Ἀμὴν] λέγω ὑμῖν ὅτι ἐὰν δύο ἢ ἕξ ὑμῶν συμφωνήσωσιν ἐπὶ τῆς γῆς περὶ παντὸς πράγματος οὗ ἐὰν αἰτήσωνται, γενήσεται αὐτοῖς παρὰ τοῦ πατρὸς μου τοῦ ἐν οὐρανοῖς.

20 "Ὅπου γάρ εἰσιν δύο ἢ τρεῖς συνηγμένοι εἰς τὸ ἕμὸν ὄνομα, ἐκεῖ εἰμι ἐν μέσῳ αὐτῶν."

NIV English Version

"If your brother or sister sins, go and point out their fault, just between the two of you. If they listen to you, you have won them over.

But if they will not listen, take one or two others along, so that 'every matter may be established by the testimony of two or three witnesses.'

If they still refuse to listen, tell it to the church; and if they refuse to listen even to the church, treat them as you would a pagan or a tax collector.

Truly I tell you, whatever you bind on earth will be bound in heaven, and whatever you loose on earth will be loosed in heaven.

Again, truly I tell you that if two of you on earth agree about anything they ask for, it will be done for them by my Father in heaven.

For where two or three gather in my name, there am I with them."

C. Structural Flow of Matthew 18:15-20

Title: Restoring Fractured Fellowship: The Redemptive Process of Matthew 18:15-20

- I. Private Confrontation (Matthew 18:15)
- II. Involving Witnesses (Matthew 18:16)
- III. Church Involvement (Matthew 18:17)
- IV. Redemptive Excommunication as a Last Resort
- V. Divine Authority (Matthew 18:18)
- VI. Power of Agreement (Matthew 18:19)
- VII. Christ's Presence (Matthew 18:20)

D. Literary Context of Matthew 18:15-20

In Matthew 18:15-20, we find a passage that addresses the early Christian community's transition from the old covenant to the new covenant. This shift calls for new ethical guidelines and a deeper understanding of faith and how it translates into daily life. The passage centers on the term "ἐκκλησία" (*ekklēsia*), meaning "church," which is mentioned only twice in the Gospels. The first instance occurs in Matthew 16:18, where Jesus declares the foundation of His church upon Peter's confession of His messiahship. This declaration marks the beginning of the new community. The passage also reflects the disciples' struggles in comprehending the sacrificial aspect of Christ's mission, as seen in Peter's rebuke of Jesus and their general misunderstanding. Matthew 18:15-20 deals with conflict resolution and confronting sin within the faith community. It stresses reconciliation, mutual accountability, and the presence of Christ throughout the process. The teachings in this passage connect to earlier discussions on causing others to sin, the parable of the lost sheep, and the concept of perishing, emphasizing the need for mutual correction and care within the community. This passage provides guidance to the new faith community as they navigate their journey in this new covenant (Hare, 1993, p. 2).

E. Textual Analysis of Matthew 18:15-20

The use of the Greek conditional construct "Ἐὰν" (if) is notable in this passage, appearing nine times from verses 15 to 20. The use of the Greek conditional construct "Ἐὰν" (if) is notable in this passage, appearing nine times from verses 15 to 20. This suggests that the pursuit of acceptable and ethical standards, as instructed by Jesus, may not always yield the desired outcomes. The effectiveness of these standards is contingent upon the choices made by individuals within the faith community (Wallace, 1996, p. 696):

The presence of the Ἐὰν clause serves as a bridge between verse 19 and the preceding verses 15 to 17. Furthermore, the contrast between actions "on earth" and "in heaven" creates a connection to verse 18. Consequently, verses 19 and 20 maintain a strong connection with the previous verses, forming a distinct unit. It's worth noting that the use of the word "everything" (πάντα) to connect verses 18 and 19 raises questions regarding the logical relationship between these two verses (Wallace, 1996, p. 696).

Verse 18 in the first half addresses a specific conflict situation which if it has not yet happened probably will in the near future; consequently, it conveys steps to respond to it. Verse 19 in

the second half addresses a general condition because of the Greek words *πεξὶ παληὸο* concerning anything. However, it appears that the specific condition mentioned in verse 18 is a subset to the general condition mentioned in verse 19 because of *πεξὶ παληὸο*. There is a movement from a singular offender to plural which has also affected number in Greek (Luz, 2007, p. 448). The NIV rightly follows the rhythm of the movement while the NRSV does not. The clause "Ἐὰν δὲ ἁμαρτήσῃ ὁ ἀδελφός σου" or "But if your brother sins [against you]" is closely linked to the context of avoiding actions that lead others into sin. When someone within the faith community wrongs another believer, the response of the offended party is crucial. They can either respond in a way that avoids sin or succumb to temptation. While the offender is clearly at fault for causing another to sin, the individual being influenced has the power to choose their response, which ultimately determines whether they, too, commit a sin. This highlights the importance of individual choices when faced with wrongdoing (Gundry, 1994, p. 376). The second mention of the *ἔθθειζία* appears in v. 17 where there is need for healing a hurting relationship within the faith community. The first mention of *ἔθθειζία* in chapter 16 calls attention to its foundation and what needs be done for its firmness; while the second mention in chapter 18 calls attention to a part of its missional. The *ἔθθειζία* in verse 18 has been saddled with the responsibility to *δήζεθε θαὶ ἰχζεθε* bind and loose which summons the entire community of faith to respond in unity. This may connect between the responsibility in verse 18 and the preceding verses 15–17: people in the community whose faith and ethics are persistently incongruent (vv. 15–17) should be *δήζεθε* but only if they repent would they be *ἰχζεθε*.

Matthew somewhat differs with the Lukan account even though they seem to point to the same event. According to Gundry (1994, p. 376), the Lukan account was not concerned about the steps outlined by Matthew or the place of the Church of the faith community in resolving conflict among believers. The Greek terms "*ἀδειθο*" (brother) and "*ἀδειθή*" (sister), as indicated in the word study, encompass both physical and spiritual relationships. In a spiritual context, these terms unite all individuals who are justified by their faith in Jesus into one family of God. However, this spiritual connection also necessitates that Jesus' disciples exhibit godly character. Consequently, the significance of these words goes beyond merely being a disciple who listens to Jesus' teachings. It encompasses both listening and obeying the divine revelation provided by God through Jesus Christ (as seen in passages like Mark 3:31–35, Matthew 25:40, Matthew 28:10, and John 20:17). Failing to live in accordance with this teaching results in a disconnect between our professed beliefs and our actions, highlighting the importance of aligning our confession of faith with our conduct (Hare, 1993, p. 213).

F. Conclusion of the interpretation of Matthew 18:15-20

The message is crystal clear, emphasizing that the integrity of any faith community hinges significantly on how it responds to a brother or sister within its midst who sins and continues in that sin. The handling of such situations is a critical factor. It's essential to look to Scripture for guidance, especially in challenging circumstances where the individual causing offense is unrepentant and holds influence within the faith community, to the extent that they might leave if disciplined. So, how should the community navigate these complex and controversial situations? Matthew provides a response: First, the faith community should recall its foundational principles and the source of its existence. Second, they must remember their responsibilities to all members within the faith community. Third, they should also consider

their responsibilities to those outside the faith community. Additionally, Matthew may want the faith community to keep these things in mind:

- a) While engaging in reconciliation and restoration, they should not be disheartened by the fact that there may be exceptions, with certain members persisting in their wrongdoing.
- b) Leaders of the faith community should exercise their privilege responsibly and not misuse it.
- c) The members of the community should be supportive of the decision to excommunicate a member who continues in their wrongdoing.
- d) Lastly, it's important to remember that Jesus Christ has promised to assist the community in their efforts to instill deep faith and ethics within the faith community.

IV. Application of Redemptive Ex-Communication in Matthew 18:15-20 for Pastoral Counselling

Redemptive excommunication, as highlighted in this passage, involves a process of addressing sin within the community with the ultimate goal of restoring the erring member. It emphasizes the need for personal responsibility and mutual care. In the context of pastoral counselling, this passage offers valuable insights:

Conflict Resolution: Pastoral counsellors can draw from the principles of addressing conflicts laid out in this passage. It emphasizes the importance of addressing issues one-on-one and in a spirit of gentleness and love, which can be applied in counselling sessions to encourage constructive communication and reconciliation.

Accountability: The concept of accountability is central in both redemptive excommunication and pastoral counselling. In counselling, individuals can be encouraged to take responsibility for their actions and seek forgiveness or make amends when necessary.

Community Involvement: The involvement of the faith community in the process of addressing sin and facilitating restoration highlights the significance of a supportive and caring community. Pastoral counselling can encourage individuals to seek support from their faith community and involve their spiritual leaders when facing challenges.

Restoration: The ultimate goal of redemptive excommunication is restoration. Similarly, pastoral counselling should focus on the restoration of individuals to a place of spiritual and emotional well-being. Counsellors can use the process outlined in Matthew 18:15-20 as a model for facilitating healing and growth.

Prayer and Guidance: Pastoral counselling often involves prayer and seeking divine guidance. The passage emphasizes the power of agreement in prayer and the presence of Jesus in the midst of the faith community. This can inspire pastoral counsellors to incorporate prayer and spiritual guidance into their sessions.

In conclusion, Matthew 18:15-20 offers valuable insights for pastoral counselling within the context of redemptive excommunication. It underscores the importance of addressing conflicts, accountability, community support, restoration, and spiritual guidance, which are all vital components of effective pastoral counselling.

Conclusion

In summary, the study of redemptive excommunication in Matthew 18:15-20 and its implications for pastoral counselling in the Pentecostal churches in Nigeria, reveals a compassionate and structured approach to addressing conflicts and promoting restoration in

the faith community. If the Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria applied the process and procedure for redemptive excommunication, most of the problems of heretical teachings, immoral acts, embezzlement and misappropriation of funds, and the likes would have been curbed and curtailed to a very large extent. This process emphasizes reconciliation, accountability, and ultimately seeks to guide individuals back to a path of righteousness. Lastly, it can be stated that redemptive excommunication, as outlined in Matthew 18:15-20, offers a pathway to resolve conflicts with the ultimate goal of bringing individuals back into the fold, ensuring the well-being and unity of the faith community. This process holds significant implications for pastoral counselling, promoting accountability and healing within the faith community of the Pentecostals.

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Pastoral Counseling and Its Impacts on Selected Rehabilitation Centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State Nigeria

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Abstract

Pastoral counselling is a form of counselling that integrates spiritual and religious beliefs into the therapeutic process. The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) being a religious organisation, incorporates pastoral counselling into its rehabilitation centres to support the recovery process of individuals struggling with addiction or other issues of life. Previous studies on Pastoral counselling have been without a critical examination of its impacts on the rehabilitation of individuals to determine its social influence or otherwise. Hence this paper explores pastoral counseling and its impacts on selected rehabilitation centers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State Nigeria. This research utilizes a qualitative approach including interviews and observations, to gather data and analyse the impacts of pastoral counseling. The study aims to assess the effectiveness of pastoral counselling in facilitating the rehabilitation process and improving the overall well-being of individuals seeking help in the centres. It was discovered from the findings that pastoral counselling had a significant impact on people in rehabilitation, as it addresses not only the individual's mental and emotional well-being but also the dynamics and relationships within the rehabilitation unit. These findings contribute to the understanding of the significance of pastoral counselling in rehabilitation centres and provide insights for further improvement in the field.

Keywords: Pastoral Counseling, Rehabilitation Centres, The Redeemed Christian Church of God, Ogun State, Nigeria

Introduction

Pastoral counselling is a form of counselling that integrates spiritual resources and beliefs into the counselling process (Ayegba, 2015). It aims to provide emotional and psychological support to individuals who are facing various challenges in life (Adeniran, 2017). In recent years, pastoral counselling has gained popularity as an effective approach to addressing mental health issues and supporting personal growth and development.

This research paper focuses on the impacts of pastoral counselling on selected rehabilitation centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State, Nigeria. The Redeemed Christian Church of God is one of the largest and fastest-growing churches in Nigeria, with a strong focus on the well-being and spiritual growth of its members (Oyewumi, 2019). The church operates several rehabilitation centres across the country, providing support and care for individuals struggling with substance abuse, mental health issues, and other challenges.

The purpose of this research is to explore the efficacy of pastoral counselling in the rehabilitation centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State. This study investigates the experiences of individuals who have received pastoral counselling in these centres, as well as the perceptions of the counsellors and staff members involved in the

counselling process. By examining the impacts of pastoral counselling on the rehabilitation centre, this research aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on the effectiveness of this approach in addressing mental health issues and promoting well-being.

To support this research, a comprehensive review of relevant literature on pastoral counselling, mental health, and rehabilitation will be conducted. The theoretical framework for the study will be grounded in the principles of pastoral counselling and the unique context of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Nigeria. Data will be collected through interviews, surveys, and observational methods, and analyzed using qualitative research techniques.

Overall, this research paper seeks to shed light on the role of pastoral counselling in promoting mental health and well-being in rehabilitation centres, particularly within the context of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State, Nigeria. The findings of this study will have implications for the development of effective counselling programmes and interventions in similar settings, as well as for the broader field of pastoral counselling and mental health care.

Overview of Pastoral Counseling

Generally, counselling means discussion, advice, exchange of ideas, consultation, or decision-making process. Counselling is a service designed to help individuals analyze themselves by relating their abilities, achievements, interests, and ways of adapting to new decisions they have made or need to make (Neukrug, 2018). This service is central to a rehabilitation counsellor's work. While other aspects of rehabilitation may concern the provision and interpretation of information, counselling is concerned with a person's feelings, attitudes, and emotional dispositions about themselves and the situations they face. In other words, advising is when an advisor develops a dialogic relationship to help people better understand themselves concerning current and future decisions and issues. Makinde in the words of Roger describes counselling as a series of direct contacts with individuals aimed at assisting in changing attitudes and behaviours. Makinde, further writes that "effective counselling" consists of a structured and tolerant relationship in which the client gains self-understanding to the extent that he or she can consider changing direction and taking positive steps. Masu Arbuckle states that the general purpose of counselling is to help the person free himself from the entanglement and disempowerment of tentacles so that he can be his authentic self and contribute more to himself and those around him (Gladding, 2018).

In the same sense, pastoral counselling is a form of psychotherapy that combines both psychology and spirituality. It is provided by certified pastoral counsellors, who are not only mental health professionals but who have also had in-depth religious and/or theological training. The goal of pastoral counselling is to help individuals overcome emotional, psychological and spiritual challenges by integrating their faith into the therapeutic process. Pastoral counsellors use a variety of techniques to help their clients, including prayer, meditation, and other spiritual practices.

Pastoral counselling can be beneficial for individuals who are struggling with a wide range of issues, including depression, anxiety, grief, addiction, and relationship problems. It can also be helpful for individuals who are seeking guidance on how to live a more fulfilling life or who are looking for support during a difficult time.

Selected Rehabilitation Centers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State Nigeria

Rehabilitation Centers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State selected for this study are two out of 5 because of easy accessibility to the researcher including:

1) The Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre

The Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre is a faith-based organisation run by the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) that provides rehabilitation and support services for individuals struggling with addiction and other behavioural issues. The RCCG recognized the growing problem of addiction and substance abuse in society and the need for a comprehensive rehabilitation programme. In response to this, the church established the Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre as a solution to the prevailing societal challenges (Olowe & Olusanya, (2014). It was founded in 2006 to take care of juvenile drug addicts and street children between the ages of 7 to 17years old. The rehabilitation centre has over 180 boys, 40% of which are in private secondary schools. There is also a primary school within the rehabilitation centre for the younger ones. Others who are not academically inclined are into various vocational activities like tailoring, shoe making, carpentry, and computer training.

The centre aims to offer a supportive and structured environment to help individuals recover and rebuild their lives. It employs a holistic approach that combines spiritual guidance, counselling, medical care, vocational training, and life skills development. The Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre of RCCG believes in the power of faith and prayer in the recovery process. It offers daily devotions, Bible studies, and church services to help individuals strengthen their spiritual well-being. The centre was founded on the principles of the Christian faith, with the belief that true freedom from addiction can only be achieved through a personal relationship with Jesus Christ. Overall, the Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre of RCCG aims to provide a safe and nurturing environment for individuals to heal and transform their lives.

2) Wholistic Outreach Rehabilitation Centre

The Wholistic Outreach Rehabilitation Centre of the Redeemed Christian Church of God, (RCCG) was founded in April 2002 as a result of the moral decadence in society, reflected in the horde of commercial sex workers, increase in numbers of pregnant and stranded teenagers, neglected young girls and ladies in various stages of destitution who are all suffering from the effect of drug addiction. The organization offers social services for female youth and women who are between the ages of 16 to 50, both within and outside the Church (RCCG) in various communities.

It is a faith-based non-profit organization founded upon Christian values and principles, committed to reducing harms associated with prostitution and other accompanying activities. It is located in Mowe, Ogun State, in Southwestern Nigeria. The centre models God's love and purity to a generation of youths and brings hope, love, and succour to them. Rehabilitation strategies at the centre include the use of capacity-building, income-generating activities, the scriptures and pastoral counselling as a means to behavioural change to checkmate problems like HIV/AIDS/STIs/STDs and unwanted pregnancy in society. The organization offers social services and promotes women's development both within and outside the Church and in various communities to prove the sacredness of life, especially that of females and in developing the country.

Major Types of Pastoral Counselling in RCCG Rehabilitation Centres

The three major types of Pastoral counselling that were identified in the rehabilitation centres include individual, group and family counselling:

1) **Individual Counselling:** This counselling is scheduled to take place a minimum of once a week but some of them may have daily individual sessions when special needs arise. During individual counselling, the clients meet in one-on-one sessions with the counsellor. These sessions are private and generally last about an hour. During individual counselling, the counsellor explores the client's background to find the root causes for the drug addiction and other behavioural issues. Then, the counsellor and the beneficiaries work together to ensure that the beneficiaries receive all the tools and coping skills needed for a life of recovery and enable each of them to deal with issues that they prefer not to deal with in a group setting (Interview:13/10/2023).

2) **Group Counselling:** This is done three times per week at the various centres. Here, the recovering person also meets with fellow clients in a group counselling session. These sessions are all about sharing experiences and providing support for one another. This process can be intimidating at first, however, the sheer release of talking to other people who have been through the same experiences provides an amazing relief. This group counselling focused on a particular issue, for example, obsessive-compulsive disorder or anger management. While the counsellor usually harmonises the contributions from each member of the group that are considered valuable because, most of them in the group share similar issues, feelings, defences and differences are addressed. Each person learns how to express emotion openly and to trust others. Here, everyone feels comfortable, safe and relaxed knowing that they are with people who are going through similar experiences (Interview: 13/10/2023).

3) Family Counselling

This is done at the beginning and the end of the rehabilitation programmes. Here, the addicts are allowed to have an open and honest discussion with their family members, parents and siblings. It is believed that when an individual develops a drug addiction with its accompanied behavioural problems, they are not the only one who suffers. Often, the addict's family suffers right along with them, and in many ways can even have a more difficult time than the addicts themselves. Therefore, counsellors provide family members with strategies that will help the recovering addict stay on the right path when they leave the rehabilitation centres. Parish ministers with skills in counselling and theological education are called upon to counsel individual addicts as part of their shepherding mandate (Interview: 13/10/2023)

Impacts of Pastoral Counseling on Rehabilitation Centers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State, Nigeria

1. **Emotional and Spiritual Healing:** Pastoral counselling within the RCCG Rehabilitation Centre offers emotional and spiritual support to individuals undergoing rehabilitation. Their counselling sessions for example in Wholistic Outreach Rehabilitation Centre, aim to address the underlying issues and traumas that may have contributed to addiction or other challenges, thereby helping individuals gain emotional and support healing. Pastoral counselling provides a safe and non-judgmental space for individuals to express their emotions, fears, and struggles. The counselling process provides an enabling environment for them to address underlying issues contributing to their addiction or mental health challenges.

2. Integration of Faith: RCCG's pastoral counselling incorporates the principles of the Christian faith, including prayer, scripture-based guidance, and support from pastors or trained counsellors (Interview: 14/10/2023) This integration helps individuals in the two rehabilitation centres to find strength, hope, and a sense of purpose through their faith, which is a powerful motivator for recovery.

3. A sense of Community and peer support: The RCCG Rehabilitation Centre aims to provide a supportive community for individuals seeking rehabilitation, and pastoral counselling plays a significant role in fostering this sense of community and peer support (Observation:16/10/2023). Group counselling sessions and activities in the Habitation of Hope and Wholistic Outreach Rehabilitation Centre led by pastors or trained counsellors promote a supportive environment where individual clients share their experiences, learn from one another, and build meaningful relationships.

4. Personal Transformation: Pastoral counselling in the RCCG Rehabilitation centres empowers individual clients/rehabilitators to undergo a journey of personal transformation (Interview:16/10/2023). By addressing issues such as guilt, shame, self-worth and forgiveness, counselling sessions equip individual clients with the tools necessary to make positive changes in their lives and develop healthier habits.

The integration of spiritual principles in pastoral counselling in these centres allows individuals to explore their faith and find meaning in their lives. This spiritual guidance fosters a sense of purpose and helps individuals develop a stronger connection with their God as written in 1 Corinthians 5:17, thereby leading to transformation and personal growth.

5. Aftercare Support: Pastoral counselling extends beyond the duration of the rehabilitation programmes, as the RCCG rehabilitation centre is dedicated to providing comprehensive aftercare support (Interview:16/10/2023). This support often includes continued counselling, spiritual guidance, and access to resources that can enhance long-term recovery and prevent relapse (Adeyemi, 2015).

Conclusion

Pastoral counselling plays a significant role in the rehabilitation process in the two centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State, Nigeria selected for this study. The impacts of pastoral counselling include Emotional and Spiritual Healing, Integration of Faith, A sense of Community and peer support, personal transformation, and Aftercare Support. This paper highlights the importance of integrating pastoral counselling in rehabilitation centres and provides insights for further improvement in the field.

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Mentoring in Leadership: Appraising Samuel-Saul's Relationship

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Abstract

Pastoral office is inherently a leadership office as it involves guiding and shepherding a congregation, community or an individual towards spiritual and moral wellbeing. Pastors as leader have a crucial role to play in fostering sense of unity, provision of support, and nurturing growth in the body of Christ. This leadership extends beyond traditional organisational structure but focuses on the total development of an individual in the community of faith. In the pastoral context, leadership is not solely limited to administrative duty but also involves guidance and care for individuals. By the very nature of their task, pastors are meant to be mentors who offer counsel and provide source of inspiration to their mentees. Their leadership style analysis empathy, compassion and deep understanding of the need of their protégé. In this wise, the effectiveness of a pastor as a leader is measured by their ability to connect with people on a personal level by helping them navigate the challenges of life. Samuel, by circumstances, becomes the spiritual leader to Saul. In a hitherto-new office of monarchy, Saul needs a mentor. This study uses Textual, and descriptive methods of analysis, in examining Samuel and Saul's relationship in the Biblical text. It finds that Samuel fails in mentorship due, perhaps, to personal grudges. It concludes that every spiritual leader is, after all, a fallible being. Therefore, it recommends among other things that spiritual leaders should be weary of personal sentiment in discharging their roles.

Introduction

For most Bible believing individuals (Christians or Jews), King Saul's failure is as a result of divine displeasure and rejection (1 Sam 16:1). But be that as it may, Saul's tragedy reveals a mentorship flaw on the part of Samuel, Israel's first king maker. But the towering figure of Samuel in the scripture shields this weakness of Samuel from view. It is worth noting from here that the intent of this study is neither to cast aspersion on Samuel nor to diminish his positive roles in Saul's' career. In point of fact, Samuel gives Saul dignified reception at Zuph (1 Sam. 9:22-24), announces divine choice of Saul (1 Sam. 9:27-10:1), and even has a discussion with him (1 Sam. 9:25). However, certain flaws are evident in his dealings with Saul and much can be learnt from it about mentorship. By divine providence, Samuel was in position to guide King Saul. But for certain reasons this was not always the case. Maxwell says leaders usually fail to develop other leaders either on account of their lack of training or because they have wrong attitudes about allowing and encouraging others to come alongside them (Maxwell, 1995). The latter seems to be the case of Samuel as would be discussed.

The often-overlooked mortal error of Samuel may be due in part to the 'Touch not my anointed' syndrome which makes some people believe that spiritual leaders are to be absolved of any error whatsoever; or as a result of the misconstrued intent of Jesus in saying "Do not judge..." (Matt. 7:1). This paper briefly reviews Samuel's mentorship inadequacy in early monarchical narratives with a view to correcting the belief that spirituality forecloses mistakes.

What is Mentorship?

A wide variety of definitions to capture the meaning of mentorship may be available with each reflecting different roles and intents behind mentoring. However, some things that are common to most of these definitions are an acknowledgement of the reciprocity, and one-to-one nature of the relationship between a more experienced and a less experienced individual for the purpose of personal and professional development. Canadian Coalition for Global Health Research reports some definitions two of which are offered here for consideration: Mentoring is a “dynamic and non-competitive nurturing ‘process’...that promotes independence, autonomy, and self-actualization in the protégé while fostering a sense of pride and fulfillment, support and continuity in the mentor.” “Mentoring occurs when a senior person (the mentor) in terms of age and experience undertakes to provide information, advice, and emotional support for a junior person (the protégé) in a relationship lasting over an extended period of time and marked by substantial emotional commitment by both parties” (Canadian Coalition, 2007, pp.6-7) World Education Services puts it thus; “A mentorship is a relationship between two people where the individual with more experience, knowledge, and connections is able to pass along what they have learnt to a more junior individual within a certain field. The more senior individual is the mentor, and the more junior individual is the mentee (Center for Health, 2003).

A United Nation handbook on mentoring says important traits like empathy, curiosity, authenticity and the ability to connect and impart trust are among those things a mentor should have. It says further that “Research shows that these are more important than the professional skills a mentor may have” (Together, p.5).

Mentoring is crucial for leadership development as it provides opportunity for prospective future leaders to see transformational behaviours in action. Wofford reports Gary Yukl’s guidelines for mentoring. He says mentors are expected to have interest in the development of their mentees, serve as role models to them, help them identify skill deficiencies and guide them to overcome the deficiencies by giving career advice among other points (Wofford, 2004).

The Core of Mentorship is Mentorship

Mentorship is a phenomenon that has similarity with some other transformational relationship. As such, mentorship, discipleship, and modeling may have been used interchangeably sometimes. While some believe that they can be used interchangeably, others are of the opinion that they are different and should not be so used. Though it is out of the scope of this article, to give delineating marks of each of the terms, they seem vastly different and may not be used *substitutably*.

A number of features distinguish mentorship from other interactions between more experienced and less experienced individuals in organisational or institutional settings. Consequently, mentorship can, but does not always, exist in relationships between teacher and student or between professionals at varying levels of a bureaucratic or academic hierarchy. The relationship grows over time and is deliberate, purposeful and interpersonal. Just as there are different definitions, so are types of mentorship. Mentorship can be spontaneous or formal, direct or indirect, and short or long-term (Canadian Coalition, 2007). Perhaps the most closely aligned with our definitions of mentorship is direct mentorship. Here, direct relationship results between two individuals, often a more experienced member

in an organisation or group (the 'mentor') and a less experienced one in the same organisation or group (the 'mentee' or 'protégé'). It can also result from supervisor-student relationship. Collegial mentorship integrates the characteristic of friendship into the traditional definition of the relationship of mentorship. This type of mentoring acknowledges and promotes the development of a personal, supportive relationship between mentor and protégé. The starting point may be through friendship or professional contact and not due to professional needs. For instance, a junior faculty member may develop collegial mentoring relationships with more senior faculty. Student-supervisor relationship is another example of collegial relationship, which creates opportunities for collaboration in research beyond the thesis or dissertation. Indirect mentoring does not involve mentor-mentee direct contact. It is the result of intentional efforts from a mentor to be available to junior members of an organization intending mentees.

Formal and informal mentorship differ in the way the relationship is initiated, how mentor and mentee are identified, and the focus, length, and structure of the relationship. Formal mentoring evolves from structured, organised programmes or assigned roles within an organisation. On the other hand, informal mentoring develops through mutual identification—the mentor believes in the mentee's potential and the mentee selects mentors they consider role models.

Linda Phillips-Jones mentoring expert and author describes four basic mentoring skills which are: Active listening, Building trust, Determining goals/Capacity building and Encouraging/Inspiring (Center for Health, 2003). According to her, not only does active listening establish rapport it also creates a positive, accepting environment which gives room for open communication. By listening actively, a mentor comes to ascertain the protégé's interests and needs. As regards trust building, one will increase trust by keeping conversations and other communications with a protégé confidential, honoring scheduled meetings and calls, consistently showing interest and support, and by being honest with him/her. Capacity building will involve various assistance and knowledge impartation. But she wraps it up by maintaining that "giving encouragement is the mentoring skill most valued by protégés" (Mentoring Guide, 2003, p.4). This can be achieved by commenting favorably on their accomplishments; assuring them of belief in their capacity to grow; responding to their frustrations and challenges with words of support, understanding, encouragement and possibly praise. Mentors may even describe their own experiences, mistakes, and successes all in a bit to provide proper mentorship.

From the foregoing, a mentor helps protégés advance within their chosen career and connects them with opportunities that they might not have otherwise had access to. They do this by sharing their knowledge, helping their protégé identify prospects and opportunities in their path. Potentially, mentors can open doors for their mentee when the time comes. Thus, mentorship is a prized instrument for turning one's vision into reality.

It is expected of mentors to give guidance and counsel to their mentees, helping them build a successful career or gain a strong foothold within a certain organisation. Because it is a relational affair, a mentor typically (but not in every instance) has one mentee at a time and focuses on shaping the trajectory of their career life. The experience affects the amount of psychosocial support, career guidance, role modeling and communication that occurs in the mentoring relationships in which the protégés and mentors engaged.

Mentorship is a mutually beneficial relationship. The mentors gain because they are able to lead the future generation in an area they care about and ensure that best practices are passed

along; in the same vein, the mentees benefit because they prove that they are ready to take the next step in their career and can receive the extra help needed to make that advancement. Across different disciplines, mentorship is recognised both in academic and practice settings as an important contributor to capacity building within organisations and among individuals. In secular mentoring, attention is given to professional development, improvement of leadership skills, or guiding people into skills they want to grow in. Not only are these valid reasons to seek mentorship, they are also important. But in biblical mentorship (especially the Old Testament), mentoring entails more than self-improvement, personal development or merely passing on knowledge about God. It involves showing people how to love and serve God. It is about helping an individual grow in obedience to the requirement of the law. The concept finds poignant expression, at least, as old as the book of Deuteronomy:

Hear, O Israel: The Lord our God, the Lord is one. Love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your strength. These commandments that I give you today are to be on your hearts. Impress them on your children. Talk about them when you sit at home and when you walk along the road, when you lie down and when you get up. Tie them as symbols on your hands and bind them on your foreheads. Write them on the doorframes of your houses and on your gates. (Deut. 6:4-9)

God provides a biblical format of mentoring within the family to ensure that faith in the one true and living God would be passed from generation to generation.

It can be generally assumed that a good mentee is a product of good a good mentor in keeping with popular saying that “like begets like.” It should be noted that some mentors may have character flaws and weak leadership but nonetheless provide good mentoring. Instances abound where a not-too-good mentor produces a good mentee (Jacob-Joseph, Eli-Samuel) and where acclaimed good leader produces a flawed protégé (e.g. Elisha-Gheazi). But one clear fact from biblical examples is that many great biblical leaders were mentored.

Leaders in Old Testament and Influence of Mentorship

Though arguably, there are no better known leaders in the Old Testament than Moses and David. Other notable ones include Joshua, Joseph, Samuel, Elisha and Esther. All these aforementioned individuals have remarkable achievements in their leadership. But also notable about them, is the fact that each of them enjoys some sort of mentorship under certain individuals: Joseph under his father Jacob (Gen. 37:2), Moses under Jethro (Exo.2:16-22; 18:1-27), Joshua under Moses (Exo.32:17-18, Num.27:18-23, Deut. 34:9), Samuel under Eli (1 Sam. 3:1-9), David under Samuel (ISam. 16:13; 19:18), Elisha under Elijah (II Kings 3:11) and Esther under Mordecai (Esther 2:7,10).

This reveals a fact that every great leader has frailty and human failings which are helped by some mentorship. Ted Engstrom notes that a close scrutiny of leaders mentioned in the Bible, indicates that majority of them at one time or another experienced failure. Many of them, according to him, have their failure in marked ways but they later succeed because they never grovel in the dust (Engstrom, 1976). For dearth of space, three of these leaders are briefly examined: Moses, Samuel and Elisha.

Moses

Moses, the great leader and lawgiver of Israel, is born an Israelite into slavery in Egypt. As indicated earlier, someone says apart from Jesus, in Moses we have the greatest and best

example of leadership found in the Bible (Amanzee, nd, p. 75). By divine providence, he is raised in the palace of Pharaoh King of Egypt (Exo. 2:10). But Moses, aware of his origin, decides to help his people. Undoubtedly destined to be a leader of his people, Moses starts out by an attempt to settle dispute between two Israelites (Exo. 2:13-14). Of course, at the outset, his people do not understand his role in their midst (cf. Act 7:23-25). They ask “who made you a ruler and judge over us?” Although, Moses receives much direction and encouragement for the herculean task ahead of him, and on countless occasions demonstrates fabulous leadership qualities, he nonetheless, begins his career as a statesman when he attains the age of eighty (Engstrom, 1976). That is pretty well after having been mentored by his father-in-law. Philomena Amanzee states that at this time, which she prefers to describe as God’s tutorship of Moses, he comes out of the training being kind, considerate, and compassionate. He also acquires abilities for organization, administration, law, and sound judgment (Amanzee, p. 7).

Obviously, Moses is an ambitious and zealous leader who desires the emancipation of his people from the clutch of Egyptian enslavement. Having been raised in the palace, the leadership (or perhaps *rulership*) tendency in him is well formed. His drive and zeal make him break the tablets (Exo.32:19), earn him jealous rebukes from siblings (Num. 12:1-2), and other detractors (Num. 16:1-3). But despite his zeal and drive, he is said to be extremely meek (Num. 12:3). This is in sharp contrast to the Moses in Exodus 2:11-12 killing an Egyptian. What makes the difference is mentorship.

Moses departs Egypt at age 40 and returns at 80. He lives with a Midianite priest whose daughter he marries. One clear indication of his mentorship is the visit of Jethro (Exo 18) where he comes to see his mentee demonstrate his skill of leadership. Observing yet another impropriety in Moses’ administration of his leadership, Jethro offers some instructions which Moses follows. Thus, it is reasonable to conclude that moderation that comes to Moses’ leadership is a result of mentorship.

Elisha

Elisha is described as one who used to pour water into the hand of Elijah (II Kings 3:11). He becomes Elijah’s protégé towards the end of Ahab’s reign (I Kings 19:19-21). Elijah is still active until after the death of Ahaziah. Thus, Elisha’s ministry spans the reigns of Kings Joram, Jehu and Jehoahaz. He dies during the reign of king Jehoash after about fifty years of public ministry which certainly involves leadership. He dies a revered national figure whose exploits are proudly rehearsed (Martin, 1986).

Elisha is renowned for his great miraculous acts, leadership and interpersonal relations. But his great success does not just come about. He is a man of sharp focus, unrelenting determination and staunch commitment to his mentor. Apart from Moses, hardly is there anyone in the Old Testament that performed more miraculous acts than the duo of Elijah and Elisha. Judging by this common denominator, one can rightly conclude that Elisha is well groomed by Elijah in the ‘art’ of waiting on God. Warren W. Wiersbe (2003) notes that from the outset of Elisha’s ministry, he demonstrates himself to be a worker of miracles like Elijah his master and predecessor. He opens the Jordan River, crosses on dry land, and then he purifies the water at Jericho. Apart from this, one feels that Elisha’s ‘harsh’ dealing with the young men of Bethel (II Kgs 2:23-25) as well as Gheazi (II Kgs 5:25-27) reflects the nature of his mentor who deals with reprobate prophets I Kgs 18:40 and calls down fire on unruly soldiers II Kgs 1:10, 12.

Samuel

More than any other mentor-mentee relationship in the Old Testament, Eli-Samuel mentorship differs significantly in that Samuel starts from a young age. Samuel serves before the Lord under the Eli's guidance a time when God speak less often to His people. The spiritual leaders are corrupt, and God's voice is scares. But with Samuel in place, God changes the situation and speaks His prized word to a young boy who would be about twelve years old then (Wiersbe, 2003). While spiritual laxity is prevalent and the cherished law of God is dishonoured especially by the sons of Eli, the Biblical text still reveals Eli's close relationship with Samuel in a manner that demonstrates mentor-mentee rapport: the boy ministers before the Lord under Eli (3:1); he runs to Eli when a voice calls, thinking it is Eli's. This shows he is closer to the place Eli is sleeping than Eli's sons.

The most instructive demonstration of mentorship is when The Lord calls Samuel. The Lord calls him four times (1 Sam 3:4,6,8,10), and the first three times, Samuel thinks it is Eli calling him. He has never heard God's voice, so he does not know how to answer. Eli is discerning enough to recognize that it is God speaking to the boy, so he tells him how to respond. The young Samuel is helped by his elderly mentor who, at the time, is a dying light but bright enough to light Samuel's candle. Another notable thing is that Eli tells Samuel to say "Speak, Lord, for your servant is listening" (1 Sam 3:9, NIV) but Samuel instead says "Speak, for your servant is listening" (1 Sam 3:10, NIV), and leaves out the word, "Lord". This may be because he does not yet have a personal knowledge of the Lord he could not know whose voice it is. By the time Samuel later reports to Eli, Eli reiterated the fact that it is the Lord speaking: *He is the Lord...* (1 Sam 3:18, NIV).

Eli's choice of sleeping in the tabernacle precinct may be in keeping with The Ancient Near Eastern practice for incubation dream (Walton, et'al, 2000). It was a belief in the ancient world that a person sleeping in the temple or its precincts may become privy to divine plans. Some would in fact perform certain rituals and spend the night in the temple so as to receive such revelation. This process is known as incubation. 'In early literature kings such as Naram-Sin and Gudea sought information through incubation' (Walton, et'al, 2000) Samuel may simply be performing his regular duties and clearly has no expectation of revelation of any sort, his experience however, would be understood in light of the common association between temple and revelation. This is a practice he most certainly imbibes from Eli his mentor.

Can Leaders be Mentored?

The above pertinent question, if reframed, would be "are leaders born or made?" for decades, this throbbing question has been asked both in religious and secular organisations. Scholars have over the years offered arguments stating that effective leaders emerge both from nurture of parents and from random choices of genetics. It is maintained by this position that leadership is largely formed before one graduate from high (secondary) school. A group of other scholars hold that effective leadership can be modeled in the years of adulthood (Wofford, 2004).

While hereditary and life experience play key roles in forming leadership ability an individual because leaders are expected to have some minimum level of intelligence, energy and personal appeal; effective leadership can be developed. Wofford reports the finding of a research done by Barling, Weber and Kelloway (Barling et al., 1996). They trained about twenty branch managers of one of Canada's largest banks on 'an effective and transforming

leadership behaviours.’ In the research, they found out that training resulting in leadership change, brought about positive effects which produced better financial income of the banks (Wofford, 2004). Two other studies by Kilpatrick, Locke, Howell and Frost (Kilpatrick et al., 1996) further buttress the point. They found out that training increases the use of transforming leadership behaviours as well as leader’s effectiveness. Engstrom also says that for centuries, it has been assumed that leadership is inherited or passed from generation to generation, meaning “leaders were born-not made.” But following the overthrow of feudal system by a new burst of freedom in Europe due to the Renaissance, concept of leadership took a new shape. It is now seen that leaders can be trained and developed. Focus shifts to a person’s personality and skill which can be latent, waiting to be developed (Engstrom, 1976).

In biblical accounts, a number of individuals are trained for places of leadership even though they have a sure call from God. Best of these examples, perhaps, would be the disciples of Jesus Christ who receive training from Him (Jesus). During the Old Testament in the days of Samuel, a ‘school of prophets’ was set up to train the prophets (I Sam 18:19-20). Apparently, David no doubt seeks refuge here when fleeing from King Saul. Similarly, during Elijah and his protégé Elisha, such schools are located at Gilgal, Bethel and elsewhere (II Kings 2:1; 4:38; 6:1).

Jewish tradition has it that these schools trained persons to the office of prophets during Israel’s long history. The schools also served as forerunner to the Jewish Later Rabbinic centres in the postexilic era (Engstrom, 1976). Engstrom further maintains that these schools are meant to develop, train and educate people in leadership. Therefore, it is right to say that from biblical witnesses, leaders are made. Other Bible narratives and events demonstrate the need and justification for development of an individual’s gift in order to place them in positions of leadership which is what mentorship is all about. Moses, for instance, mentored Joshua. Seeing his potential, Moses groomed him to become an undisputed and enviable leader.

Samuel and Saul

When appraising the life of any man of God, it should be born in mind that they are human beings who are only privileged to have the divine mandate and calling to the nobler task of intermediary between the divine and human interfaces (Heb. 5:1). As such, the human failings and frailties are just as much to be expected of them. Denying this fact or attempting to shield it is a rude attempt to exchange humanity for divinity.

The summation above is very apt in appraising Samuel’s action or inactions against Saul in Early monarchy in Israel. But briefly on Samuel, he occupies a very honourable position among the ancient Jews as revealed by many historical portrayal of his person. The only leader in Israel who occupied the three notable positions of prophet, priest and judge is Samuel. Provan, Long, and Longman describe him as transitional figure; being the last of the judges, successor of Eli the priest, and the prophet of the Lord (Provan et al, 2003). Among the ancient Israelite leaders, starting from Moses through Samuel and to the end of Biblical history, there is no one who held all these three positions. Not even Moses the lawgiver of Israel and greatest of their prophets was a high priest. He was only a judge and prophet. He is regarded as national leader second in rank to Moses as he revitalises the lost political and spiritual hopes of the people of Israel like Moses (Jensen, 1980). Even his role in military involvement is somewhat attested. While some contest this, Joseph Blenkinsopp (1983) sees no reason to deny him diversity of prophetic, political and military roles.

With this towering credential of Samuel, he was one that leaders expected to leave behind great leaders properly mentored. King Saul, being the immediate next in national leadership to Samuel, should be someone to enjoy this mentorship the most. But this is not the case. Samuel is an experienced leader and one who enjoyed mentorship. Saul, on the other hand, seems not only to be ignorant but also uninterested in leadership (1 Sam 9: 1ff; 10:21). So, when providence thrusts leadership on Saul, he doubtlessly needs a shoulder to rest on. The mark of true leadership is that someone is following. Saul has Samuel to look up to but Samuel provides him the needed training in leadership.

Saul has every reason to look up to Samuel for guidance. First, Samuel is a leader of great esteem and vast experience. Having led Israel from his youth to old age (12:2), and gaining national reputation for being a transformational leader; such a person would naturally attract mentees. Secondly, Samuel is the one that declares the divine choice of Saul to him (Saul). If then God chooses him through Samuel, it is reasonable that Saul would need his guidance in matter of administration of his office. As such, mentor-mentee relationship should ensue. Thirdly, Saul's office is political and that of Samuel is spiritual. Because of the theocratic state of ancient Israel, a synergy between the two office holders is of necessity. Samuel, being older, would therefore need to provide guidance or better still mentoring to the younger fellow. But the narrative shows a mentoring flaw on the part of Samuel as indicated below.

Samuel's criticism of Saul: The Bible records few meetings between Samuel and Saul: His anointing (9:26-10:1), public presentation (10:17-25; 14-15), after Philistine battle at Michmash (13:5-15) and after destroying the Amalekites (15:1-29). After the anointing and public presentation, the scripture tells that Samuel and Saul meet again during the battle at Michmash; and after the battle against the Amalekites. In each of the instances, Saul is heavily criticised and tongue-lashed by Samuel. Saul is only a new king given instruction by his superior. Bruce Birch (1998) states that Chapter 13 of 1 Samuel is a narrative of Saul's external conflict with the Philistines, and internal conflicts with Samuel. He declares that Saul does not succeed in overcoming either of these conflicts and is eventually brought to a tragic end by these conflicts. In fact, the text of 1 Samuel 13 presents with challenges. It is unlikely that the instruction given in (10:8) is what Samuel charged Saul of not obeying. Laurent Porter (1979) comments that the event in this chapter must have taken place considerably later, just as many scholars too. One fact is that Samuel does not retreat into privacy after making Saul the king. He continues to act publicly and watching how kingship is executed. He issues a command which Saul is said to have disobeyed.

Many have misconstrued this episode to blame Saul for the whole problem. Samuel earlier makes arrangement to meet Saul at a certain time most likely to offer sacrifices and ask the Lord's blessing on the military venture. But as he does not show up, the few soldiers with Saul tremble and some start departing the war zone. Saul waits for seven days but Samuel does not arrive as promised. Was Samuel watching Saul to fail in the battles or seeking occasion against him to condemn monarchy? Is his arrival intentional or a coincidence? Has Saul done something wrong in offering the sacrifice? These are difficult questions to answer. But in sincerity, they implicate Samuel. Samuel is too angered as his brief question: 'What have you done?' indicates. Saul's explanation sounds as deprecates the situation and perhaps as intimidating as Samuel's gesture is? Saul may have disobeyed some unknown divine instruction but Samuel's overreaction can only be read from the context of his hatred for monarchy and perceived persona rejection. Whatever the case, a mentor would have corrected a frustrated protégé in love and admitted his own wrong which Samuel does not do.

In the case of the destruction of the Amalekite, Saul's disobedience is obvious. But the befuddling things start from Samuel's introduction of the divine message (15:1). Ever since Samuel kissed Saul at the beginning of chapter 10, they never again share happy moments. As a matter of fact, Samuel's general disposition to Saul has not been especially joyful. At the beginning of Chapter 15, the situation is not poised to change, in fact it would be worse. Samuel's first words indicate a stern mood. It begins with; 'I am the one the Lord sent to anoint you king over His people Israel; now listen' (15:1). This is a very odd introduction given that God disowned Saul's dynasty according to Samuel in Chapter 13. What then is the implication of Samuel's statement? By frontloading the pronoun "me" (rendered as 'I am the one' in NIV), the prophet sends a message to the king. He seems to be saying; 'I am the one in charge here even if you are the king and you must always take my word!' Samuel then announces divine judgment on Saul's action. But the tone raises questions about Samuel again. He said the king has refused the voice of the Lord, the Lord has also rejected him as king, but the king begs for forgiveness. It should be emphasised that Saul asks for forgiveness not for restoration as king but for the prophet to accompany him to worship God. Samuel refuses with a harsh negative response. In fact, he repeats essentially, his earlier lines: 'I will not return with you because you have rejected the word of the Lord and the Lord has rejected you from being king over Israel.' Peter (2015) opines that Samuel should have been more pastoral, and as a mentor of the first Israelite king, he should have offered counseling (p.89). Someone notes about the sternness of Samuel's reaction: 'is this the stern true prophet of the Lord declaring the Lord's word versus a sinner or is this a stern unrelenting prophet denouncing a rival?' (Miscall, 1986, p. 111). With this, it is hard to deny that Samuel has a lingering animosity towards Saul ever since his emergence on the scene. Here we see the poor ignorant and perhaps innocent king who is expecting succor and mentoring from a 'father' getting nothing but rebukes upon rebuke. No wonder he later becomes tarumatized and lapses into paranoia, and eventual suicide.

Samuel's desire to perpetuate a dynasty: Another point that demonstrates Samuel's failure in mentorship of Saul is his desire to perpetuate a dynasty. One of the reasons for the people's request to have monarchy is the failure of Samuel's children to live uprightly like their father (8:1-5). When age caught up with Samuel, he could no longer perform his duties especially the political cum judicial duties. So, he appoints his sons to take up the responsibilities. They however, lack the integrity and uprightness of their father. Apparently, his sons were appreciated no better than Eli's sons, and the people do not want them to take over. The elders of Israel lobby for a fundamental change. They demand for monarchy like other nations. When his sons fail as leaders, the elders see the system of discontinuity of the era of the judges returning. Their wish is to solve the problems of continuity, unifying the tribes, creation and maintenance of a professional army. Samuel may have thought of putting forward his sons for this position so that in future, his family line would enjoy the preeminence of producing the first king and perhaps maintain a dynasty. It is ironic that while the elders notify Samuel about the spiritual and moral flaws of his sons as one of the bases for their request for a king (8:1-5), he still bring up their case in Saul's coronation more as an undying protest that even if monarchy is to be considered his family should have been given priority (12:1-2). If Samuel wants his family in monarchy, then, it won't be difficult to know why mentoring Saul would be hard to consider.

Aversion for monarchy: Through the years, the elders and the people of Israel have followed the political and spiritual leadership of Samuel without questioning in spite of the

international political and military pressures. At this time, Samuel has grown old to the point that he cannot adequately lead the pole any longer. So, he appoints his sons. The once strenuous efforts of Samuel which youthful spirit, animated by piety and patriotism, had enabled him to make are perhaps no longer there. Thus, he sinks to phlegmatic indifference. Disabled by the infirmity of age from performing his duties, he delegates some to his son, but they by no means follow the step of the father.

The elders take advantage of this, coupled with desire to resolve their internal squabbles, and forge a national military apparatus, and approach Samuel to ask for monarchy. Samuel is immediately displeased by this (1 Sam. 8:6). While we may agree with Provan and other (2003) in their assertion: "that Israel's elders should so quickly in narrative time at least-demand 'a king to govern us like other nations' strike the attentive readers as a foreboding development" (p. 207). It is noticed that Samuel's reason for displeasure is not the same as that of Yhwh. The people want to be like other nations (something that they have been repeatedly warned against by God), but Samuel's concern is his own position!

The point is not that Israel was never to have a human monarch. Their traditions replete with anticipations for this (Gen. 17:6, 16; 35:11; Num. 24:7; 17-19; Deut 17:14-20). Also, given the fact that kingship was commonly practiced among their neighbours, it is perhaps less surprising that Israel should seek a king than that they have resisted doing so for so long. This event paints a different Samuel from what is popularly known him. He is seen here not displaying patriotism but self-seeking. He experiences demand for a king as a personal rejection. He prays to God perhaps to reject the people's request. God then tells him to heed the people's request (8:7). God has to repeat this to him to heed their demand, but that they should avoid idolatry. But in spite of God's explanation of the situation to Samuel; "it is not you they have rejected, but they have rejected me as their king" (8:7), God has to convince him over and over again to 'Listen to all that the people are saying to you...and give them a king' (8:7, 10, 22).

As can be seen, all the above show why Samuel felt no need to mentor Saul. Saul is trapped in the mist of battle of ambitious men. Men of Israel want a king Samuel wants a dynasty and Saul become the sacrificial lamb on the altar of their ambitions in the narrative sub-plot where he is presented as passive and yet blamed for whole scenario in the long run. More also, the fact that Samuel has corrupt sons is probably one of the signs of a more complex character, with all the strengths and shortcomings common to well-developed personages in biblical literature. Since the narrator chooses to filter the narrative of the monarchy through the eye of Samuel, it behooves the readers to pay attention to such matter of Characterisation. Therefore, despite the overwhelming positive characterization of Samuel in the Monarchical narratives, his mentorship failure is evident not only in the case of Sal but also his sons.

Conclusion and Recommendation

From the foregoing, it is clear that Samuel is no doubt a great leader in Israel. Life application Study Bible notes that as a spiritual leader, he enjoys the uniqueness of filling different spiritual offices of judge, priest, prophet and counselor (NLT, 2007). He is so greatly used of God because of willing obedience to his parent's pledge to God, and desire to lean on God and to learn from Him. He champions great spiritual revolution, making word of God that was hitherto scarce, to be in abundance (cf. 1 Sam. 3:1; 19-21). He chooses a godly life despite growing among the ungodly children of Eli (1 Sam.2:1-8); orchestrate national spiritual

cleansing and revival (1 Sam.7:3-6), and calls people to godliness (1 Sam. 12:14-23). Even the rise of prophetic institution in Israel has so much to do with him.

As regards his civil roles, Samuel is the first kingmaker, anointing the first two kings of Israel. He serves as a judge, and mediates in military venture (1 Sam. 7:7-12). Samuel may have had opportunity of mentoring many people. But from biblical text, the chance to mentor Saul and failure to do same is obviously a flaw in his intimidating good credential. While this does not make Samuel less spiritually and morally high personality, it does show that however spiritually great an individual is, the human part of them poses a great challenge and often faults their good nature. To this end; this recommends the followings:

- i. Leaders should try as much as possible to shun sentiment in the discharge of their leadership/mentorship roles
- ii. It should be recognised that every man of God is a human being prone to human failings. As such, they should not be overrated as superhuman in overall assessment of them.
- iii. Mentors should be conscious of the far-reaching influence of their actions/ inactions on themselves and their protégé (Samuel weeps later, perhaps for his own mistake. Also, Saul internalises his constant criticism, develops negative self-image and later commits suicide).

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Impacts and Benefits of Pastoral Counselling on Human Wellness in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examines the impacts and benefits of pastoral counselling on human beings, the definition of pastoral counselling, the history of pastoral counselling, the qualifications of a pastoral counsellor, and the uses and benefits of a pastoral counsellor for the wellness of clients. It also looked at the dimensions of health, which are physical, emotional, social, spiritual and intellectual aspects of human beings and factors of the 5F-WELL, which are illustrated in the Indivisible Self as in creative self, coping self, social self, essential self and physical self. The study's participants were 150 from different religious groups and community organisations. A descriptive survey research design was employed, and data was collected and analysed using the mean, standard deviation, and t-test; findings show a positive correlation between the duration of pastoral counselling and spiritual well-being, indicating that more extended engagement in pastoral counselling contributes to a more profound sense of spiritual fulfilment and connection. Pastoral counselling is not for everyone, but it can be a good option for those seeking psychological counselling informed by religious or spiritual ideology and teachings. Recommendations include integrating pastoral counselling with mental health services, implementing specialised training for pastoral counsellors, increasing access to pastoral counselling services, raising public awareness of pastoral counselling and upholding ethical standards.

Keywords: Pastoral Counselling, pastoral counsellor, wellness, 5F-Well factors, Coping Strategies, Ibadan North Local Government Area

Introduction

Religious communities have traditionally sought to provide spiritually-based solutions for those in trouble. For centuries, clergy have listened intently to personal problems and cultivated a spiritual counselling response to those suffering from mental and emotional illness. Traditional spiritual counselling continues to help many of those people. However, it was recognised long ago that conventional spiritual counselling is only sufficient with classical pastoral counselling experience in many areas such as in the Northern part of Nigeria, Sokoto to be precise and in the South-West of Nigeria during the time of the Colonial Masters.

What is Pastoral Counselling?

Pastoral counselling is a branch of counselling in which psychologically trained ministers, rabbis, priests, imams, and other persons provide therapy services. Pastoral counsellors often integrate modern psychological thought and methods with traditional religious training to address psychospiritual issues in addition to the traditional spectrum of counselling services. (Benner, 2003). Pastoral counselling is a form of psychotherapy that combines both psychology and spirituality. Chinebell (1984) opined that pastoral counselling seeks healing for people suffering from crisis-induced dysfunction and brokenness. The author stated that pastoral counselling is a structured, informed, caring dialogue with people with problems. Unlike religious counsellors, which can be clergy, dull counsellors are trained mental healthcare professionals with in-depth training in religion and theology. Pastoral counselling uses existing psychological and therapeutic models and incorporates faith-based ideas. While individual pastoral counsellors may represent specific religions, the concept and framework of pastoral counselling are not tied to any one religion or faith. Pastoral counselling is a unique form of psychotherapy that uses spiritual resources and psychological understanding for healing and growth (Chinebell, 1984). These ideas were supported by Egan (1994), who strongly opined that people sought help when they could not handle problematic situations properly. These problems show up in various ways, that is, in relationships, in marriage, amongst siblings, in the workplace, through a traumatic experience, for example, being raped, robbed, hijacked and nowadays divorced. Summarily, pastoral counselling:

- i. Focuses on people with problems;
- ii. The field requires expert knowledge, which sanitised training;
- iii. Involves redemptive and therapeutic dialogue (Egan, 1994).

Statement of the Problem

Despite the widespread availability of various forms of psychological and therapeutic support, there needs to be more understanding and recognition of the specific impacts that pastoral counselling has on human well-being. This form of counselling, which integrates spiritual guidance with psychological care, offers a unique approach to addressing emotional, mental, and spiritual challenges. However, the extent of its effectiveness and the way it contributes to overall well-being need to be well-documented and studied. This study seeks to bridge this gap by exploring the impacts and benefits of pastoral counselling on individuals' holistic health.

Research Hypotheses

- **Hypothesis 1** Individuals who receive pastoral counselling will exhibit significantly more significant improvements in emotional and psychological well-being than those who do not accept any form of counselling.
- **Hypothesis 2** Participants who undergo pastoral counselling will report higher levels of spiritual well-being than those who do not.
- **Hypothesis 3** The duration and frequency of pastoral counselling sessions positively correlate with overall life satisfaction and perceived quality of life.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research methods to comprehensively understand the impacts and benefits on human well-being in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria.

Participants

- **Sample Size:** The study involved 150 participants for a robust analysis
- **Selection Criteria:** Participants include 80 individuals (40 Christians and 40 Muslims) who had undergone pastoral counselling within the last year. A control group of 40 individuals (20 Christians and 20 Muslims) who had not received any form of counselling during the same period were also involved for comparison.
- **Recruitment:** Participants were recruited from Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) Oke Agbara, Ashi-Basorun, and NASFAT Society at Samonda, beside the University of Ibadan, in the Ibadan North Local Government of Oyo State, Nigeria.

Surveys and Questionnaires: Structured instruments such as the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-21), the Spiritual Wellbeing Scale (SWBS), and the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) were administered to assess psychological, emotional, and spiritual well-being.

In-Depth Interview: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of 30 participants (15 Christians and 15 Muslims) to gain deeper insights into their pastoral experiences with pastoral counselling.

Focus Groups: Small groups of 6-8 participants were organised to discuss the perceived benefits and impacts of pastoral counselling, facilitating rich and interactive discussions. Techniques such as t-tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis were used to compare the well-being measures between the counselling and control groups.

The History of Pastoral Counselling

People have long turned to religious leaders for support, guidance and solutions related to mental health issues, and ministers of all denominations traditionally provide counselling to members of their religious communities. Pastoral counselling was born from the idea that, although this kind of support is valuable, some issues may require more professional help. (Griffith & Young, 1987). In the early 1900s, Reverend Anton Boison, one of the founders of the Pastoral Education Movement, pioneered a unique enrichment program in which he connected theology students with hospital patients who were also experiencing concerns of a psychiatric nature. In the early 1930s, Minister Vincent Peale and psychiatrist Smiley Blanton formed the American Foundation of Religion and Psychiatry, known today as the Blanton-Peale Institution. Clinical pastoral education programs like these laid the foundation for the pastoral counselling field, which evolved over the next several decades as more and more clergy members sought formal training in psychology. (American Association of Pastoral Counsellors, 2020).

Required Qualifications for Being a Pastoral Counsellor

Pastoral counsellors are certified mental healthcare professionals with extensive religious education and training. It is common for pastoral counsellors to be licensed Marriage and Family Therapists (LMFTs) or Clinical Professional Counsellors (LCPCs). Below are some qualifications of a pastoral counsellor:

- A bachelor's degree;
- A master's or doctoral degree;
- A master's or doctoral degree in the mental health field

What is Pastoral Counselling Used For?

As with other mental healthcare professionals, pastoral counsellors can help with various issues and often have extraordinary marriage and family therapy, substance use disorders, or mental health conditions. They can also help with spiritual or religious matters. Some areas pastoral counselling may address include;

- Grieving the loss of a loved one
- Coping with illness
- Handling significant insignificant challenges, times of transition or life crisis
- Parenting difficulties
- Preparing for marriage or adjusting to divorce
- Mental health disorder treatment
- Processing difficult or traumatic life events
- Counselling for all ages and couples and family
- Integrating faith with daily life
- Strengthening relationships include, ng with oneself and with God
- Wellness programs
- Spiritual direction
- Outreach preventive services such as in prison, military settings and schools
- Community Education (Michael, 2000).

Wellness in Pastoral counselling

Wellness is a dynamic process of physical, mental, and spiritual optimisation and integration, which is the outcome of that process. Bill Hettler (1984), the father of the modern wellness movement, defined wellness as 'an active process through which people become aware of and make choices toward a more successful existence. Myers, Sweeney, and Witmer (2000) also concluded that wellness is a way of life oriented toward optimal well-being. In that body, mind and spirit are integrated by the individual to live more fully within the human and natural community. Ideally, each individual can achieve the optimum state of health and well-being.

Dimensions of Wellness

There are five aspects of personal well-being: physical, emotional, social, spiritual, and intellectual. All five areas must be addressed to be considered healthy.

Physical Wellness

1. Regular exercise, such as walking 30 minutes daily, will significantly improve one's health.
2. Eat healthy. Avoid fried foods, soft drinks, processed meats, and sweets. Include fruits and vegetables in your diet every day.
3. Make sure to eat all meals, especially breakfast.
4. Avoid heavy episodic drinking and drug use.
5. Get at least 6-8 hours of sleep every night.

Emotional Wellness

- i. Maintain a positive attitude even when problems arise.
- ii. Discovering one's stress reliever and managing time wisely can lower stress.
- iii. Share information with a trusted person
- iv. Smile even when one does not feel like improving emotional wellness.

Social Wellness

- i. Balance social life with academic responsibility.
- ii. Choose a good and resourceful friend.
- iii. Recognize when in an unhealthy relationship.

Spiritual Wellness

- i. Find a quiet place to meditate every day
- ii. Contemplate the meaning of life.
- iii. Appreciate the natural world.

Intellectual Wellness

- i. Keep abreast of current affairs
- ii. Seek academic help always
- iii. Become a lifelong learner (Bill, 1984)

Five-Factor Wellness (5F-WELL)

According to Jane, Myers, and Sweeney (2005), the Five Factor Wellness Inventory (FFWEL) is an evidence-based tool for assessing wellness characteristics and helping individuals make choices for healthier living.

Creative Self

- **Thinking:** Being mentally active, open-minded, creative and experimental, having a sense of curiosity, and applying problem-solving strategies to social conflicts.
- **Emotions:** Being aware of or in touch with one's feelings. Ability to express appropriately positive and negative feelings.
- **Control:** Belief about one's competence, confidence and personal mastery, beliefs that one can usually achieve the goals set for himself.
- **Work:** Satisfaction with one's work, feeling that one's skills are used and appreciated, feeling one can manage one's workload, feeling a sense of job security, and feeling appreciated in the work none does.
- **Cheerful humour:** Being able to laugh at one's mistakes and use humour to accomplish even serious tasks.

Coping Self

- **Leisure:** Satisfaction with leisure time, feeling that one's skills are used appropriately.
- **Stress Management involves ongoing** self-assessment of one's coping resources and the ability to organise/manage resources such as time, energy, and setting limits.
- **Self-worth:** Accepting who and what one is, positive qualities, imperfections, and a sense of being genuine within oneself and others.

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- **Realistic Beliefs:** Ability to process information and perceive reality accurately, absence of persistent, irrational beliefs and thoughts and need for perfection.

Social Self

- **Friendships are social** relationships that involve a connection with others individually or in the community but do not have a marital, sexual, or familiar commitment. Friendship requires empathy for others and feeling understood by others.
- **Love:** The ability to be intimate, trusting, self-disclosing with another, giving as well as expressing affection to significant others, and accepting others without conditions.
- **Spirituality:** Personal beliefs and behaviours practised as part of the recognition that we are more than the material aspects of mind and body, faith in a higher power, hope and optimism, the practice of worship, and prayer. And meditation, purpose in life, compassion for others, moral values and transcendence (a sense of oneness with the universe).
- **Gender Identity:** Satisfaction with and feeling supported in one's gender, ability to be androgynous.
- **Cultural identity:** Satisfaction and feeling supported in one's cultural identity, cultural assimilation.
- **Self-Care:** Taking responsibility for wellness through preventive self-care and safety habits.

Physical Self

- **Nutrition:** Eating a nutritionally balanced diet, maintaining an average weight within 15% of the ideal.
- **Exercise:** Engaging in sufficient physical activity through exercise or work to maintain good physical condition. Jane, et al. (2005).

Procedure

The Participants of this study were randomly drawn from members of the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) Oke Agbara, Ashi-Basorun in Ibadan and from members of Nasfat Society, Samonda beside University of Ibadan in Ibadan North Local Government of Oyo State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1 states that Individuals who receive pastoral counselling will exhibit significantly more improvements in emotional and psychological well-being than those who do not accept any form of counselling.

Table 1 Comparison of receivers of pastoral counselling and those who did not receive it on emotional and psychological wellbeing

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	T-abs	T-Crit	P
Receiver of pastoral counselling	85	48.50	8.389	298	1.18	0.96	****
Did not receive pastoral counselling	65	48.70	9.857				

The above result shows that the differences in emotional and psychological well-being between the counselling and control groups were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) since the computed t-value (1.18) is greater than the t-critical value (0.96). This is an indication that pastoral counselling has an impact on the emotional and psychological well-being of the individuals.

Hypothesis 2 states that Participants who undergo pastoral counselling will report higher levels of spiritual well-being than those who do not.

Table 2 Comparison of participants who undergo pastoral counselling reporting higher levels of spiritual well-being than those who do not.

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	T-obs	T-Crit	P
With pastoral counseling	60	37.005	5.291	298	1.96	1.74	*****
No pastoral counselling	90	38.071	4.785				

The results from Table 2 above show a significant difference in the level of spiritual well-being of participants who underwent pastoral counselling, reflecting enhanced spiritual health compared to those who did not. The observed values (1.96) are more significant than the t-critical (1.74). This indicates that pastoral counselling participants reported higher spiritual and life satisfaction levels than the control Groups.

Hypothesis 3 states that the duration and frequency of pastoral counselling sessions positively correlate with overall life satisfaction and perceived quality of life.

Table 3 compares the duration and frequency of pastoral counselling sessions, which positively correlates with overall life satisfaction and perceived quality of life.

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	Obs -t	Crit-t	P
Long duration and more frequency	55	31.1448	6.000	298	2.93	1.96	*****
Low duration and short frequency	95	38.071	5.900				

The results from Table 3 show a positive correlation between the duration of pastoral counselling and spiritual well-being, suggesting that more extended engagement in pastoral counselling contributes to a more profound sense of spiritual fulfilment and connection.

Discussion of Findings

Qualitative Findings

Common themes emerged from the interviews, including increased hope, emotional relief and a stronger sense of purpose. Participants often described pastoral counselling as a unique source of comfort and guidance that addressed their emotional and spiritual needs. Participants in the focus group highlighted the importance of the spiritual dimension in their healing process, noting that pastoral counselling provided a holistic approach that traditional counselling sometimes needed to improve. Many shared their experiences of overcoming significant life crises with the help of their counsellors. Participants identified several techniques as particularly beneficial, including prayers, scripture reading, and spiritual reflections, combined with traditional therapeutic methods such as cognitive-behavioural strategies. The pastoral counselling environment was also described as compassionate and non-judgmental, fostering a safe space for individuals to express their deepest concerns and explore solutions.

Conclusion

Psychology uses scientific language to discuss human beings and behaviours, whereas pastoral counselling discusses human beings, their relations with fellow beings, and the spiritual aspects of wellness. Pastoral counselling combines psychology and religion. Pastoral counsellors are mental healthcare professionals with associated privileges and responsibilities. They are also educated and trained in religion and theology (Adebayo & Kolawole, 2013).

Counselling provided by religious leaders in Christ Apostolic Church and Nasfat Society differs from pastoral counselling because they lack the appropriate orientation required by mental healthcare professionals. Pastoral counselling is not for everyone, but it can be a good option for those seeking psychological counselling informed by religious or spiritual ideology and teachings. Ensuring one's pastoral counsellor's beliefs align with one's needs is essential.

Ask about the counsellor's views before beginning counselling, and try a different counsellor if they are not a good fit.

Recommendations

1. Foster collaboration between pastoral counsellors and mental health professionals to create a more holistic approach to care.
2. Implement specialised training programs for pastoral counsellors that include psychological principles and therapeutic techniques.
3. Promote the availability of pastoral counselling, especially in underserved and rural areas, through funding initiatives and partnerships with community organisations.
4. Launch public awareness to educate the public about the benefits of pastoral counselling, emphasising how it addresses both spiritual and psychological needs to improve overall well-being.
5. Tailor pastoral counselling to the client's needs by understanding their unique spiritual and psychological context.
6. Ensure pastoral counsellors adhere to strict ethical standards, including confidentiality, informed consent, and professional boundaries. Regular training on moral issues should be mandatory to maintain trust and professionalism.

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Paul's Counsel in 1 Corinthians 7:1 & 8, Preferment of Celibacy: Its Authenticity and Effects among the Catholic Priests

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Abstract

Celibacy simply means not married and not having sex, from a specific time till the rest of your life, especially because of your religious belief. It is a very strong and widely held mandate of service in the Catholic Church. There is no doubt that the Catholic Church and other individuals that uphold celibacy or virginity dwell heavily on 1 Corinthians 7:1 & 8 as their biblical evidence for the doctrine. It is also certain that Paul's counsels on relationships particularly in 1 Corinthians 7 have given rise to serious marital concerns. Many scholars have written so much on 1 Corinthians 7, celibacy, and sexual sins. But more needs to be said about the original intention of Paul in 1 Corinthians 7:1 and 8 and its effects on our society today. And again, the authenticity of the rising number of people that claim to be practising celibacy is doubtful to many people. Can many people be faithful to such a sensitive doctrine? The theoretical frame work of Historical and theological methods is used to retrieve information from various sources. Library was used as a major source of information. Practice of celibacy that distinguished Catholic Church from other Christian Ministries or denominations was identified. The background of Paul was examined. Importance of marital counsel was discussed. The exegesis of 1 Corinthians 7:1 & 8 has been presented. Celibacy and virginity were clearly defined. Advantages and disadvantages of celibacy or virginity were listed. The likely reasons Paul preferred celibacy were suggested. The effects of Paul's counsel on the preferment of celibacy has been stated. And finally, practical and biblical recommendations for the Church and the society were highlighted.

Keywords: Catholic, Celibacy, Counsel, Marriage, Paul, Virginity

Introduction

Catholic priest is without a wife. Indeed, this image has been built-up by the church administration as an essential part of its own *esprit de corps* (Thomas O'Loughlin. 2013). It is now a popular practice for some individuals in our society to abscond marriage for various reasons especially among the Catholic priests. What is the relevance of celibacy in the Church? If the first fourteen Popes were married men, and the priests in our contemporary society are been denied of same privilege, then we need to go back to the Church history to remind one another the original tradition (Kasomo Daniel. 2012). Most times, it sounds very strange to discover that some highly religious sets of people have chosen not to marry or engage in any form of sexual activities for the sake of the gospel. Some people believe that it is possible for very few people to be faithful till the end. Some believe that it is not possible for any healthy person, especially men to stay without having sex for a long period of time except such individuals are having some health challenges or if they have castrated themselves like Origen (Elizabeth Abbott. 2000). It is also alleged that celibacy as recommended by Apostle Paul contradicts the institution of marriage and can be very misleading because God cannot

contradict himself. God said in Genesis 2:18 that, "It is not good for the man to be alone. I will make a helper suitable for him" (NIV). It is therefore necessary to find out the background of Paul very well and verify his state of health and physical fitness as of the time he was counselling the Corinthians on male and female relationship. How practicable is this celibacy? What challenges are those that vowed to stay away from sex are facing? And what are the effects of this strong doctrine in our society, especially in Catholic Church? The purpose of this paper is not to run down the importance of this principal doctrine, rather; it intends to re-examine the validity of celibacy and its significance in the Church.

Importance of Marital Counsel in the Contemporary Society

As we listen to news daily and witness the events within our vicinities, it is no longer news that marriages contracted in the church, court, or traditionally are collapsing every day. For various reasons, some couples will just conclude that they can no longer continue as husband and wives. Marriage, as a social institution, has been around for thousands of years. It is easy to assume that such an institution can only change slowly. But development since the middle of the 20th century show that this assumption is wrong. In many countries marriages are becoming less common, people are marrying later, unmarried people are increasingly living together and, in many countries, we are seeing a lots of divorces and serious conflicts. Within the last two decades the institution of marriage has changed more than in thousands of years before (Esteban Ortiz-Ospina and Max Rose. 2020).

Again, Paul specifies some qualities of bishops and priests: they should have shown skill in running their own families and be monogamous (1 Tim 3:2 and 3:12; and Tit 1:6); and indeed, there is a general caution against those who prohibit marriage on religious grounds (1 Tim 4:3). Yet, by the fourth century something had changed. Then we see the first signs of concern about the compatibility of marriage and priesthood. For example, at a local synod in Spain (c. 306) it was decreed that any cleric who would not undertake absolute continence should be deposed (Thomas O'Loughlin. 2013). Therefore, there is a desperate need for marital counselling if we want to get the best of human relationship in our society. So, the importance of marital counsel cannot be over-emphasised.

Celibacy and Virginity Defined

Celibacy simply means not married and not having sex, from a specific time till the rest of your life, especially because of your religious belief. For instance, Catholic priests are required to be celibate (Longman Advanced Dictionary of Contemporary English. (6th edition) 2014). Celibacy is here understood as the unmarried state chosen in the light of the Christian faith and in particular as one of the duties of the state in life of the clergy of the Latin Church by which they are forbidden to marry and obliged to live in total continence (Karl Rahner. 1975). Virginity is the condition of never having had sex. Both celibacy and virginity signify chastity, maidenhood, virtue, honour, purity, pureness, innocence, decency, modesty, dignity, and self-denial. Celibacy originated in the early church as an ascetic discipline, noted partly in a Neo-Platonic contempt for the physical world that had nothing to do with the Gospel (Daniel Kasomo. 2012). The rejection of sexual enjoyment by men fit nicely with a patriarchal belittling of women. Non virginal women, typified by Eve as the temptress of Adam, were seen as a source of sin. According to Matthew 19:3-12 Jesus campaigns for discretionary celibacy. For nearly 2000 years the Catholic Church has decreed Church laws and doctrines planned to more clearly explain the teachings of Christ. But curiously, while history discloses that Jesus

carefully chosen only married men to serve as His apostles, the Church today prohibits priestly marriage. Also, today the Catholic Church is among Christian denominations experiencing worldwide condemnation from “scandalous” allegations of sex abuse committed against women and children by priests and bishops. Historically, scandals similar to these are known to have appeared only after mandatory celibacy laws were first instituted, centuries after Christ. Why were these changes made? (Daniel Kasomo. 2012).

Paul’s Counsel and the Exegesis of 1 Corinthians 7:1 and 8

1 Corinthians 7:1 - Now for the matters you wrote about: It is good for a man not to marry. **Περὶ δὲ ὧν ἐγραψατέ μοι, καλὸν ἀνθρώπῳ γυναικὸς μὴ ἄπτεσθαι.** The above is 1 Corinthians 7:1 Meaning: Now for the matters you wrote about: It is good for a man not to marry (NIV). “Now for the matter you wrote about ...” It is adequately apparent that the primary part of this epistle was written in answer to some enquiries which had been sent to the apostle in a letter from the Corinthian church; and the first question seems to be this: “Is it appropriate for a man to marry in the present state of affairs of the church? The question concerning the expediency or in expediency of marriage was often debated among the early philosophers; and many, though inclined to decide against it, because of the difficulties and attentions connected with it, tolerated it in their opinions; because, though an evil, it was judged to be a necessary evil. The words of Menander are full to this effect: “If a man consider marriage in a proper point of view, it is an evil; but then it is a necessary evil.” (Matthew Henry’s Commentary on the whole Bible *in six volumes, carefully revised and corrected* - 1706-1721). God demonstrated His interest in and the value placed on the marriage and family, by being practically involved in its institution. He carefully put it together step by step. He put man into sleep, made a woman and presented her to man. Therefore, giving the impression that marriage is divine (Faith Oyedepo. 2019). God’s view about marriage is that it is good and it is to be enjoyed. God’s view is contrary to man’s view on marriage. Some people say, “Marriage is a necessary evil.” Others introduce a state of irony into this holy institution. They contend that the married are looking for a way of escape, while the unmarried are eager to get into it. This assertion is borne out of man’s philosophy and the experience of those who have not found fulfilment in marriage. But neither philosophy nor experience is the truth; God’s Word is. Buttressing the fact that marriage is good, Paul says: Marriage is honourable in all... (Hebrews 13:4). If marriage is evil, it cannot at the same time be honourable. Since it is honourable, it cannot be evil. James also says that: Every good gift and every perfect gift is from above, and cometh down from the Father of lights, with whom is no variableness, neither shadow of turning (James 1:17). Scripturally, marriage is good! It is the use to which some put it that paints a deceptive picture of evil.

1 Corinthians 7:8 **λεγω δε τοις ἀγαμοις και χηραις, καλον αὐτοις ἐαν μεινωσιν ὡς καγω** meaning “Now to the unmarried and the widows I say: It is good for them to stay unmarried, as I am” - NIV

The expression also may carry in it an intimation that Christians must avoid all occasions of this sin, and flee all fleshly lusts, and incentives to them; must neither look on nor touch a woman, so as to provoke lustful inclinations. I say therefore to the unmarried and widows, it is good for them if they abide even as I. The unmarried and widows - It is supposed that the apostle speaks here of men who had been married, in the word ἀγαμοι, but were now widowers; as he does of women who had been married, in the word χήραι, but were now widows. And when he says ὡς καγω, even as I, he means that he himself was a widower;

for several of the ancients rank Paul among the married apostles. This indicates that Paul married but later lost his wife. He chose not to remarry and claimed that it is better for him to concentrate on the preaching of the gospel instead of bordering himself with the burden of marriage.

History of Celibacy

Celibacy can also be traced to Paganism. Among the ancient Greece, premarital chastity was such an essential requirement in brides before they were thrust into marriage. Three ambitious goddesses maintain a lifelong vigilance over the virginity of their children (Abbott Elizabeth. 2000). Origen, the great Christian thinker well-known for castrating himself to make himself a eunuch for the Kingdom of Heaven, as well as for his fascinating teaching and deep writing in Scripture, philosophy, and ethics, had first expressed this idea. Origen maintained that you cannot be holy without punishing the flesh in every ramification. Self-denial and separation from the outside world with its sinful distractions is the only way to true Christianity (Abbott Elizabeth. 2000).

The biblical foundations of celibacy are taken to be the saying of the Lord about not marrying (becoming a eunuch) for the sake of the kingdom of heaven as stated in Matthew 19:10. The disciples suggested celibacy because they did not wish to give up the liberty of divorce. Luke 18:29 also suggests celibacy for the sake of the reign of God. Mark 10:29 talks about leaving one's wife for the sake of Jesus and the gospel. Matthew 22:30 and Mark 12:25 affirm that in the resurrection there will be no marriage. Paul also wished all men to be in the same state as himself as mentioned in 1 Corinthians 7:7. The unmarried is committed to the things of the Lord, while the attention of the married is divided – 1 Corinthians 7:32. The above texts do not link celibacy directly to the priestly ministry.

Celibacy as an obligation of the priestly state was introduced only progressively. It originated from great significance attached to virginity as in Matthew 25:1-13; 2 Corinthians 11:2; Ephesians 5:25-30, 21; 2 & 9. Celibacy also grew from the way of life of ascetics and monks with their recourse to the Old Testament laws of purity. The advancement of the law of celibacy was significantly promoted by the precept laid down in the Pastoral letters that bishops, priests and deacons should be "husband of only one wife" (1 Timothy 3:2, 12; Titus 1:6ff), though the precise meaning of the principle was debated (Karl Rahner. 1975). Rules dealing with celibacy are set up as early as the beginning of the 4th century. It was inspired by the desire for total dedication and also to some extent under the influence of dualistic Gnostic tendencies of a Manichaean type. Many priests felt bound to discontinue marriage relationships after their ordination. In the Eastern Churches celibacy triumphed only for those who were well appointed with the fullness of the priesthood, the bishops, and was given force of law in the 7th century by the Emperor Justinian and the second Trullan Synod (Karl Rahner. 1975).

However, in the West the declarations of the Synod of Elvira were widely imposed by Pope Siricious (DS 118f. 185). An effort to prescribe celibacy as a universal Church law was made at the First Council of Nicaea (325), but did not meet with success. Leo 1 and Gregory 1 extended the law to include sub deacons. Since what was forbidden was not so much marriage as the continuation of married life. Promises of discontinuation of married life were often demanded of candidates for the priesthood (and their wives) between the 5th and 7th centuries (Ruth. A. Tucker. 1987). For over 700 years after Constantine, Roman Emperors and later European royals controlled papal elections and personally appointed bishops and

abbots who served at their discretion, not the Pope's. Monasteries and dioceses brought great wealth to these secular lords through Simony, although little accrued to Rome. During all that time bishops and priests were married and Churches became Sacramental filling stations owned by mercenary clerics who willed them to family heirs, who then often bought and sold these valuable offices. The Church had a strong need to curb priestly heirs' power and corruption, and this problem was solved when Popes submitted to the Emperor's secular authority, with agreement that Cardinals alone would elect future popes. Finally, after a 700-year struggle, and desiring to eliminate future loss of wealth and control over married clerics, mandatory celibacy laws preventing future heirs were finally instituted.

Separation of spouses was also demanded. It is as clear as a bell as from the 6th century a major factor that led to the promotion of celibacy in the Middle Ages was the efforts to prevent the alienation of Church properties, which might otherwise pass into the possession of the priests' family. This gave rise in the 12th century to the marriage of those in major orders. Despite the sharp controversy at the time of the Reformation, the Council of Trent re-affirmed the principle that clerics in major orders were incapable of contracting matrimony (DS 1809). In the form already laid down by the Council of Nicaea "by virtue of ancient tradition" that there should be no marriage after the reception of a major order, the magisterium held fast to this law, as if it were apostolic regulation, even in Vatican 11 and the documents which have appeared since then (Karl Rahner. 1975).

According to the law in force in the Latin Church, as laid down by the CIC, (In 1983 Code of Canon Law (abbreviated 1983 CIC from its Latin title *Codex Iuris Canonici*), also called the *Johanno-Pauline Code*. Is the "fundamental body of ecclesiastical laws for the Latin Church." So, the Catholic Integrated Community (CIC) is an apostolic community within the Roman Catholic according to Decree Apostolicam actuositatem No. 18/19 of the Second Vatican Council). clerics in minor orders lose their clerical status by contracting matrimony (can. 132, 2). Clerics in major orders are forbidden to marry. They are obliged in a special way to preserve chastity. A sin against chastity is a sacrilege (can. 132, § 1). And if it involves an external breach of the law (can. 2195) incurs sanctions (can. 2325). All attempt to contrast matrimony are null and void (can. 1072) and to presume to enter upon a civil form of irregularity (can. 985, § 3), loss of ecclesiastical office (can. 188, 5) and excommunication (Karl Rahner. 1975). It has also been noted that ...there is a mistrust among twentieth century Christians that the female holy ones were not quite as equal as their brothers ... Wives of members of the clergy are rarely mentioned in a treatment of medieval Church minister, except in regulation to keep them separated from their husbands. That is because as a rule, those who committed themselves to "professional" Church ministry during the Middle Ages also committed themselves to celibacy (Eleamor McLanghlin 1979).

Celibacy stems also originated from a competition to be as holy as the pagan priesthood? For instance, Athenagoras advocated that the very thought of sexual pleasure was evil. "Among us are many men and women who have grown to old age without marrying, in the hope of being closer to God." (Sipe, Richard. 1995). Justin Martyr disagreed with all matrimonial sexuality apart from "reproductive intentionality" and identified with pride to some Christians who rejected marriage and survived in perfect continence. Tatian founded the Encratites, who forbidden sexual intercourse, intoxicants, and meat. He proclaimed that woman is entirely a creation of the devil, but man is only halfway so (below the waist). He first claimed that Jesus was a celibate. Tertullian did not denounce sexual intercourse but he questioned why God had conceived the sordid act! Origen thought that celibacy was more

appropriate of Christians, and acknowledged notions that were more pagan than Christian. He contended that since pagans refrained from sexual intercourse in order to worship idols, how much more should worshipers of the supreme God abstain (Hoge, Dean and Jaqueline Wenger. 2003).

However, Clement of Alexandria, Origen's teacher, was bothered by Christians who did not identify that a couple collaborates in the holy work of creation. He regarded celibacy as a timid avoidance of responsibility. "Is it not possible to live in harmony with God? Is it not permitted also for both the married person and his partner to care for things of the Lord?" he asked. By the time the Council of Elvira in Spain (Hoge, Dean and Jaqueline Wenger. 2003)

Other Possible Reasons for Paul's Counsel in 1Corinthians 7:1 & 8

Paul's physical characteristics as listed below could be part of the reasons for his preferment of celibacy: Paul is Short, Bald (ing), Black beard – Jews despised the Roman habit of shaving. He was exuded an aura of confidence (arrogance?) and had bow-legged. He has some kind of physical ailment – "Thorn in the flesh" (2 Corinthians 12:7), both painful and humiliating (Galatians 4:13-15). He probably had malaria, back problems, and epilepsy (see: Galatians 4:14, scorn = "spit out") Men would spit in the presence of an epileptic in a fit to keep themselves from taking on the evil (C. T. Wood, 1932). These physical ailments of Paul are more than enough for him to recommend celibacy. Paul was ready to carry his cross. Yoruba people of Nigeria will say: 'O gba kamu'

Advantages and Disadvantages of Celibacy

Some of the benefits of celibacy include the following: the fact that someone gives himself to God unconditionally. There is little or no concern for family and marital responsibilities. There is an amplified concentrated on goals. There is a fortification from the worries of relationship and sexuality. The tendency that a celibate will be closer to God is undisputable all other things being equal. Celibacy is one way of obeying Christ's invitation: (*Letter of Ignatius to Polycarp*, V, W. R. Shoedel, ed. Koester, *Ignatius of Antioch, A commentary on the Letters of St Ignatius of Antioch*, Philadelphia 1985). Celibacy helps a lot to focus on other important areas of life without unnecessary distractions that usually arise as a result of sexual desire from the opposite sex. A celibate does not need to take any risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases. The celibates are unlikely to notice any negative physical side effects on their health. The detriments are also enumerated below: According to research, only ten percent of all priests and bishops effectively refrain from sex during their priesthood. Ninety percent participate in sex, 50 percent uninterruptedly and 40 percent occasionally. Of those, 30-50 percent are homosexually oriented and their sexual activity is comparable to heterosexual priests and bishops. Similar studies from Spain, Switzerland, South Africa, and the Philippines produced similar numbers. In areas of South America and Africa more than half of all priests have wives/mistresses. A major problem that goes unreported by the media is priestly sex abuse of women and young girls. Female abuse statistics are comparable to male pedophilia abuse. This is the sad state of our priesthood today (Rose, Michael S. 2002). Again, a 2016 study found that men who ejaculate at least 21 times per month had a lower risk of prostate cancer compare with those who ejaculate 4 – 7 times per month (Zawn Villines. October 11, 2023). When sexual abstinence is not voluntary, some individuals may feel negative effects on their mental health. Experts say months without physical touch can have adverse health impacts such as increased anxiety,

depression and trouble sleeping. Lack of physical intimacy can also lead to touch starvation, which can contribute to loneliness, isolation and even compromise your immune system. Lack of sex may lead to sexual frustration (Paul Frysh. February 22, 2023). Sex is another way of exercising one's body, if one abstains from sex, the heart of the person may not work well.

Other Challenges of the Celibates

One of the challenges that arise is when members of consecrated life find in their environments, particularly during their ministry and pastoral undertakings, couples living in harmony in a good marital relation. They happen to unpleasantly deliberate on the priestly life they chose to live. It often happens when they encounter their old friends having settled married life. It causes a sort of regret and anguish regarding their own life. In many cases, people speak of danger in maintaining heterosexual friendships between consecrated people. It is a reality that many clergy and nuns 'entertain relations of husband-wife or lover-beloved under cover of an authentic friendship.' But it is a great problem growing drastically in our times. These examples show that many have not integrated their voluntary celibacy into religious existence. One of the important aspects regarding the diocesan priests must be emphasized. Such people experience a high level of loneliness and boredom. Unlike the religious communities, diocesans seem to be more vulnerable to sexual tendency. Also, they encounter a lot of people in their parish and ministry who are mostly married.

Authenticity of Celibacy and its Effects in the Society

Catholics are taught from childhood that Jesus' apostles ended sexual interaction with their wives in order to "Act in the person of Jesus", by adopting His celibate way of life and dedicating their lives to the spreading the Gospel unencumbered by family duties. But history discloses a different story (Kasomo Daniel. 2012). Jesus made few modifications in existing Jewish law for His supporters. But among the most significant alterations He introduced were those in relation to marriage for Christians. Jewish men of the time were permitted to have more than one wife as well as concubines; Jesus outlawed polygamy. They were allowed to divorce; Jesus banned divorce (Matthew 19:9). And most essentially, Jewish law mandated all Jews, including priests, to marry by age 20 (Genesis 1:28), but Jesus certified Christians to stay unmarried if they freely chose to do so (Matthew 19:12). And, conflicting to current myth, Jesus did not necessitate His apostles to take a pledge of celibacy or to refrain from marital sex in order to duplicate His lifestyle; Christ permitted His apostles to liberally choose either marriage or celibacy. For these reasons the question of Jesus' celibacy is meaningless as defense for contemporary celibacy regulations that entered the Church centuries later. As Jesus left the Church, an individual's free choice to marry and multiply or to remain unmarried was permitted, and no constraint against future marriage by unmarried priests existed. Today many Catholic traditionalists have begun anew to scrutinize these teachings of Jesus and to compare them to the modern law of compulsory celibacy, a law that did not exist in the beginning (Charles A., Frazee. 1972).

Catholics seems to depend heavily on the extra Biblical records such as apocryphal than the New Testament letters. Catholics are not allowed to question Church teaching. Today, Church clarifications of compulsory celibacy pose unlimited problem because it is known by all that apostles and priests during the earliest era were married. In addition, in the New Testament St. Paul explicitly required bishops and deacons be married fathers, "capable of managing their families" (1Timothy 3). Even more detrimental to the notion of a required vow of

celibacy, St. Paul precisely gave a sermon against newly converted Christian-Gnostics who brought with them a belief that all priests must reject cravings of the flesh in order to effectively intercede between God and man. This ascetic and dualistic belief of conflict between flesh and soul was first taught by Plato c.428BC and spread across the western world with Alexander the Great before 300BC. By Christ's time it had made its way into all religions' beliefs other than Orthodox Judaism and Christianity, who were unique among all beliefs (Kasomo Daniel. 2012).

An investigation of early modifications in Church teaching during the second and third centuries exposes comparable alterations in Jesus' original teachings also began to appear in some areas as Christianity rapidly spread throughout the Roman world. Many excellent scholars and philosophers from pagan religions became captivated with the resurrected Christ and converted, becoming prominent Christian teachers who thought priests should not desecrate themselves with sex. These converts are known as Patristic Fathers, and while they were noble and devout men, they also conveyed with them non-Christian philosophies that would forever affect the relationship of men and women, and marriage. Little did they understand that Christianity originally developed via House-churches, with priests reinforced by their wives as teachers (1Corinthians 16:19). Overcoming paganism and winning pagan converts were vital objectives for the developing Christian Church. This is where the story of compulsory celibacy actually originates. It is a story of change masked in the middle of a time before 350AD, when pseudo-Christian literatures were considered to be authentic source of Christian scripture, and popes were incontrovertible when claiming to talk ad hoc for Christ. For this reason, Christianity's first tradition of married priests was quite different from what the Church teaches today.

Gnostic endeavors to encourage the supremacy of celibacy and explain away the apostles' wives that St. Paul spoke of (1Corinthians 9-5), when he complained that he too should marry "just like the other apostles and Jesus' brothers", a myth was created, a myth that had no place in Christianity. This legend was first presented in apocryphal literatures suggesting the apostles had abandoned sex with their wives in order to imitate Jesus.

Practical and Biblical Recommendations

- i. In our contemporary society, many people find it difficult to appreciate the discipline of celibacy. We should be thankful to the clergy and the men and women who have made the total sacrifice of themselves out of love to serve our Lord and the Church (Fr. Saunders. 1996).
- ii. According to Matthew 19:3-12 Jesus campaigns for discretionary celibacy. Therefore, it is not expedient for any denomination to make it mandatory, rather, celibacy should have been optional and without any benefit attached to it.
- iii. Since history discloses that Jesus carefully chosen only married men to serve as His apostles, the Church today should not prohibit priestly marriage any longer.
- iv. There is no outstanding record to affirm that celibacy has reduced sexual sins among the priests rather it brings defilement into the priesthood instead of expected purity. Therefore, it is better to discourage priesthood celibacy.
- v. Sexual relationship is holy as long as it is expressed within the confinement of marriage. And again, holiness and purity go beyond illegal sexual relationship. Man is expected to demonstrate the fruit of the spirit through the power of the Holy Spirit after such a person must have accepted Jesus as His Lord and saviour before he can

become holy. Therefore, celibacy is not and should not be the principal virtue for the priests. Love is the greatest as clearly stated in 1 Corinthians 13:13.

- vi. Though sex is regarded as immoral unless expressed in the matrimonial embrace of husband and wife, it is held as fundamentally healthy, a part of God's creation. To preserve itself, the Roman Catholic Church has to be much more careful not to let men with "deviations in their affections" enter the priesthood. Catholic should also re-affirm the Church's rule on celibacy, saying it should not be seen as a "useless" imposition but a vital part of a tradition in which the priest offers himself unconditionally to God.
- vii. Therefore, celibacy should not be imposed on anybody or recommended as a prerequisite for the clergy in any denomination. Though prophets like Elijah and Jeremiah have remained celibates throughout their life, these examples could not be considered as consecrated celibacy. Generally, singleness and bareness were considered as a matter of shame. The Jewish tradition gave much significance to family life. This is much evident in the Old Testament. Children were considered as favours of God Almighty. 'Sons are indeed a heritage from the lord, the fruit of the womb a reward' (Psalms 127:3). Since the survival of family and the tribe was among the main concerns of the Israelites, virginity was often considered as a misfortune even as a tragedy- and at times, as a curse and punishment. 'A boy or a girl who, for whatever reason, could not marry and have children was pitied and even held in contempt. It was thought that they would never fulfill the reason of their existence, and that they failed in a basic debt they owed to all people.'
- viii. Celibacy is good for anyone that has the sufficient grace to cope with it, but it does not make the person holier than the married person as mentioned by the following reformers. Martin Luther the forerunner of reformation and protestant revolution in the church, at first didn't support married clergy. But later his views changed and in 1522, he rejected celibacy and married a nun. Calvin's opinions were more judicious. He advocated celibacy as an acceptable means of serving God but remarks that it is of no greater value than married life.

Conclusion

In the ecclesiological sense, just as Christ was totally united to the Church, the priest through his celibacy bonds his to the Church. He is better able to be a minister of the Word of God, listening to that Word, pondering its depth, living it and preaching it with whole-hearted conviction. He is the minister of the sacraments, and, especially through the Mass, acts in the person of Christ, offering himself totally to the Lord. Celibacy allows the priest greater freedom and flexibility in fulfilling his pastoral work: "(Celibacy) gives to the priest, even in the practical field, the maximum efficiency and the best disposition of mind, psychologically and affectively, for the continuous exercise of a perfect charity. This charity will permit him to spend wholly for the welfare of all, in a fuller and more concrete way" ("*Sacerdotalis Caelibatus*," No. 32). Finally, for anyone to live a celibacy life, it requires the grace of God. Repeatedly, celibacy is seen as a gift of the Holy Spirit. However, this gift is not just to keep one's physical desires under control or to live as a bachelor; this gift is being able to say "yes" to our Lord each day and live His life. Only Luke says that those who are celibate will be qualified for resurrection as recorded in Luke 20:27-37, a statement which is under serious scrutiny by the New Testament scholars. Matthew and Paul did not take it far, but they all

agree that celibate is superior to marriage and family as in Matthew 19:3-12 and 1 Corinthians 7. What is important to this paper is that, you cannot really create a system of Christian sexual ethics that is "Biblical" because the Bible presents enthusiastically and fundamentally diverse opinions on the topic.

However, since there is no authentic record to show that God cannot use married priests to perform certain miracles which can only be performed by the celibates. We have numerous married priests in other denominations that are much focused, highly committed to God's work, and God has been using them to expand the scope of Christian faith over the years. If Pastor E.O. Adeboye of the Redeemed Christian Church of God is not a celibate, Bishop David Oyedepo of Living Faith Church is not a celibates and God has been using them for missions all over the world, then, what is special about being a celibate? What kind of achievement has any celibate made that married priests in other denominations have not been able accomplish? The church authority should make celibacy optional. According to this paper, Jesus makes celibacy optional in Matthew 19: 11 and 12. Paul in his epistles also make celibacy elective in 1 Corinthians 7:1-9. History also revealed that the primary reason celibacy was enforced was to disallow the priests' families from inheriting the Church properties. Therefore, it is not an attempt to obey the New Testament injunctions that celibacy became an order that must be strictly observed in Catholic, rather for economic and political reasons. Since mandatory celibacy is not biblical, the Catholic Church is advised to make it optional and married priests should not be denied of any privilege nor limited in their duties as priests.

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The Scope and Dynamics of Pastoral Counselling

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Abstract

There is a dearth of scholarly writings on pastoral counselling as a different concept from pastoral care. Most Nigerian theological seminaries and departments of religious studies' curricula are centred on pastoral care. Pastoral counselling, a specialized branch of counselling psychology, is dedicated to assisting individuals in resolving life challenges and emotional issues, ultimately leading to a more fulfilled existence. Rooted in the intersection of biblical theology and psychology, pastoral counselling aims to enhance humanity's comprehension of behavioural and personality dynamics. By integrating spiritual and psychological elements, it provides comprehensive support and guidance to individuals in resolving personal and relational issues, among others. Thus, this study delves into the antecedents, various perspectives, theoretical frameworks, clinical assessment methods, scope, and prospects of pastoral counselling. The author contends that pastoral counselling holds the potential to facilitate humanity's spiritual restoration.

Keywords: Behaviour, pastoral counselling, psychological theories

Introduction

Pastoral Counselling is the specialised aspect of Counselling Psychology that links divinity with humanity. It is the interconnectivity of theology and psychology with the primary aim of helping people cope with issues of life (Worthington 2014). The pastoral counsellor leverages psychological theories, principles and practices to resolve human emotional, social and psychological concerns. They provide support and guidance on many issues, including marital choice, relationships, spiritual confusion and exploration, family cohesion, bereavement, and sibling rivalry, among others. It involves applying knowledge of psychological principles and skills to the ministry of providing clinical pastoral care for people within and outside the faith community.

The pastoral counsellor, in helping people deal with various challenges of life, is concerned with three major aspects: spiritual health, mental health and physical health. Since the spiritual is ahead of the physical, and the unseen precedes the seen, it is taken that mental wellness may be a function of one's spiritual wellness. It is within the soulful realm that cognition and emotions are developed.

Pastoral counselling seeks to integrate spiritual, emotional, and relational dimensions of human life. It recognizes that mental health is related to people's faith, community, and personal well-being. In contemporary times, where fragmentation and disconnection are prevalent, pastoral counselling offers holistic support for wholesome living. Pastoral counselling is interested in gaining knowledge and understanding of the psychological needs and experiences of people within the context of faith, religion, and culture. The pastoral counsellor is committed to the integration of faith into a life of wholeness for people (Odeleye 2022). Religious leaders and pastoral counsellors collaborate in providing people with the

spiritual and psychological education they need to cope better in life. Religious and cultural sensitivity are expedient for the effective pastoral counsellor. The therapist should always be sensitive to the beliefs and faith of their clientele.

Antecedents

Historically, pastoral counselling may be as old as humanity since its thrust is assisting others to make decisions that will lead to more fulfilling life outcomes through the lens of divinity (Odeleye 2017). As a profession and academic discipline, pastoral counselling is reputed to have evolved in the United States of America through the initiative of Rev. Anton Theophilus Boisen, who started clinical pastoral counselling with his theology students. Rev. Anton Theophilus Boisen is indeed considered one of the pioneering figures in pastoral psychology. His contributions have significantly shaped the field, particularly in the context of clinical pastoral education (CPE). Boisen is recognized as the founder of the clinical pastoral education movement. He was the first clergy member to supervise students in what we now know as CPE. He believed in the importance of firsthand study of human experience to challenge seminarians' theological thinking. Rather than relying solely on classroom training, he emphasized engaging with "living human documents.

Boisen's approach shifted theological training from a focus on the past to a present-centered, experiential approach. The parish became the laboratory, and individual needs took precedence. Boisen's personal experiences with mental illness (he had several episodes of schizophrenia) influenced his theological perspective. He sought to bridge the gap between science (medicine) and religion. His work emphasized empirical inquiry into the theology of sin and salvation. For Boisen, salvation meant being incorporated into the "Beloved Community emphasizing community as central to theological thought. Boisen pioneered the establishment of pastoral care in psychiatry. He recognized that spiritual health and caring for a patient's soul were integral components of psychological well-being. His work challenged traditional religious views by proposing connections between religious experiences and certain forms of mental illness. Rev. Anton Boisen's legacy lies in his innovative approach to theological education, his emphasis on experiential learning, and his commitment to understanding the human predicament through the lens of faith and community.

Pastoral counsellors help others to cope better with life and its challenges leveraging the spiritual aspects of their personality. They help their client to become a better version of their present self by exposing them to causative issues in asocial behaviour, the coping techniques needed to mitigate certain behaviours, and the dynamics of maintaining optimal mental health. Areas of concern for pastoral counsellors include (but are not limited to) premarital, marital, and post-marital issues, relationships, intimate partner violence, traumatic life events such as ageing, divorce, bereavement, illness, and job loss. There are several psychosocial theories and therapies pastoral counsellors use to help people. These may include social learning, psychoanalysis, humanistic therapy, and cognitive behaviour therapy, among others.

Perspectives in Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral counselling is an interdisciplinary field that focuses on the understanding of human psyche and spiritual well-being. It combines elements of psychology and spirituality to provide holistic support and guidance to individuals.

The origins of pastoral counselling can be traced back to early religious practices, where spiritual leaders were responsible for providing guidance and support to their communities. Over time, this role evolved to incorporate psychological principles and techniques, leading to the development of pastoral psychology as a distinct field. Today, pastoral counselling draws from various disciplines, including education, psychology, counselling, and theology, to offer a comprehensive approach to understanding and addressing human needs.

Even though pastoral counsellors may be as varied as the religions and persuasions in the world, they typically agree on the place of the supernatural in humanity's creation and sustenance. They seem unequivocal that there is a supreme being overseeing the universe. They also generally posit that central to humanity's challenge is disobedience to God. The question of SIN is a recurring decimal in pastoral counselling. It is this author's perspective that all will be well with humanity if they return to their "manufacturer".

There are two primary perspectives in pastoral psychology: the spiritual perspective and the psychological perspective, and the two have variants, the moderate and the hyper. The spiritual perspective is a continuum that emphasizes the importance of faith, belief systems, and religious practices in promoting mental and emotional well-being. The moderate-spiritual perspective leverages psychological theories, skills, and practices for therapy while the hyper-spiritual perspective rarely utilizes psychology in counselling. On the other hand, the psychological perspective is a continuum that focuses on understanding human thoughts, emotions, and behaviours through psychological theories and concepts. The moderate psychological perspective engages the holy books and other religious rituals for counselling intervention, but the hyper-psychological perspective deemphasizes religious rites in their counselling relationships. However, the holistic integration of both perspectives in pastoral counselling may allow for a comprehensive understanding of individuals' spiritual and psychological needs.

The Effective Pastoral Counsellor

There are two critical things in the effective delivery of pastoral counselling services: the pastoral counsellor and the therapeutic process. Pastoral counselling is not just about offering advice; it is a skilled practice that thrives on a unique blend of personal qualities, professional development, and a deep understanding of the religious context (Hunter 2017). Among other qualities, the pastoral counsellor must demonstrate empathy, active listening, knowledge of God, good communication skills, mastery of the scriptures, interpersonal skills, and the capacity to keep secrets secret.

Empathic Connection

Effective counsellors demonstrate genuine empathy, a cornerstone for building trust and rapport. By stepping into the counsellee's shoes, they create a safe space for vulnerability and open communication, fostering the groundwork for healing.

Active Listening

Beyond simply hearing words, pastoral counsellors actively listen. This involves attentive focus, allowing the counsellee to express themselves freely without interruption. Through active listening, counsellors can identify underlying issues and concerns, building trust and demonstrating genuine care.

Rooted in Faith

A deep love for their faith and a personal relationship with God are essential for pastoral counsellors. Their own spiritual journey equips them to guide and support others, drawing from their faith to provide wisdom, hope, and encouragement.

Bridging the Gap

Effective communication is a two-way street. Pastoral counsellors must express themselves clearly, using language that resonates with the counsellee's background and understanding. This includes translating biblical principles and spiritual truths into relatable concepts that can be applied to everyday life.

Scriptural Expertise

Understanding and explaining God's Word is a unique ability of pastoral counsellors. They utilize Scripture as a source of guidance, comfort, and encouragement during sessions, drawing from its wisdom to address the specific needs of each counsellee.

Synergy is Key

Pastoral counsellors don't work in isolation. Collaboration with other members of the faith community, such as church leaders, support groups, and ministries, is essential. This team approach allows for a holistic care plan, providing multifaceted support for individuals and families.

Confidentiality

Maintaining confidentiality is paramount. Pastoral counsellors must create a safe space where individuals feel comfortable sharing their struggles without fear of judgment or gossip. Upholding confidentiality builds trust and encourages open communication.

Pastoral counselling stands at the intersection of psychological insights and spiritual guidance. It's a unique blend of mental healthcare and faith-based support, offering a holistic approach to address the multifaceted needs of those seeking help. By effectively balancing these aspects, pastoral counsellors can provide transformative care that empowers individuals on their journey towards healing and growth.

Effective Pastoral Counselling Services Delivery

Pastoral counsellors use several methods to help their clients to regain self-mastery and become better versions of themselves. A combination of assessment and diagnosis, prayer, meditation, the sacred scriptures, and fasting may be deployed to help their counsellees, depending on the problems they are dealing with. Specifically, the pastoral counsellor should create a safe and supportive environment for their clientele, undertake a clinical assessment, diagnosis, treatment and referral.

Create a Safe and Supportive Environment

The first line of intervention in pastoral counselling is to create a safe and supportive environment for the client. The counsellor will seek to build rapport with the client, winning their trust and enjoying their confidence. The client should be accorded "unconditional positive regard". The motive of the counsellor is to win the heart of the client so that the

counselling encounter will be successful. This experience may take a few days, depending on the severity of the case at hand. Thus, it will allow the therapist to further blend with the client.

Clinical Assessment

While it is expected that more counselling interviews should be client-centred, with the counsellee taking the lead in expressing themselves, the therapist should guide the client with questions and rapt attention. The clinical interview is an in-depth conversation to elicit information on the client's faith, background, and life concerns, among others. The client discusses freely about their beliefs, faith, and concerns.

Clinical assessment in pastoral counselling involves the use of various techniques and tools to evaluate an individual's spiritual and psychological well-being. These may include interviews, psychological tests, and assessments of religious and spiritual practices. Holistic assessment is crucial in pastoral counselling, as it considers both the spiritual and psychological aspects of an individual's life, providing a comprehensive understanding of their needs and challenges. The assessment should lead to a diagnosis of the challenge the client is dealing with.

Diagnosis

The counsellor explores the client's strengths, coping mechanisms, and existing support systems such as family, faith, and community. After gathering as much information on the client, the therapist should be able to identify the main needs of the counsellee and thereafter prepare an intervention plan.

Treatment

The counsellor and client work together to establish goals for therapy, considering both spiritual and psychological well-being of the client. The plan should incorporate spiritual strategies, including prayer, scripture study, memorization of scriptures, or participation in religious activities to promote growth. Depending on the counselor's training and the client's needs, techniques like active listening, cognitive-behavioural therapy, mindfulness, or breathing exercises might be used. In all, pastoral counselling offers a unique approach to mental and emotional well-being, acknowledging the importance of faith and spirituality in people's lives.

Referral

If necessary, the counsellor may refer the client to another mental health professional for further assessment and/or treatment.

Some Theories in Pastoral Counselling

Pastoral Counsellors draw from various theoretical frameworks to guide the counselling process. They engage different psychological orientations as they delve into the study of human personality and mental health over different parameters (Augsburger 1989, Odeleye 2008). Specifically, we shall be looking at some personality theories, mental health theories, and interpersonal relationship theories.

Personality Theories

These are frameworks that explain why individuals behave the way they do. These theories elucidate why some traits are dominant in particular persons and not in others.

- **Psychoanalytic Theory:** This classic theory propounded by Sigmund Freud, proposes a three-part personality structure: id (primitive desires), ego (mediates id and superego), and superego (internalized moral compass). It emphasizes childhood experiences and unconscious motivations (Friedman 2017).
- **Trait Theory:** This approach (which is also called The Big 5 Theory) focuses on identifying core personality traits like extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience. These traits are seen as relatively stable across situations (McCrae & Costa 1999).

Mental Health Theories:

- **Biological Theories:** These theories explain mental health issues through the lens of brain chemistry, genetics, and neurophysiology. For example, imbalances in neurotransmitters like serotonin are linked to depression (American Psychiatric Association 2013).
- **Psychological Theories:** These theories focus on how our thoughts, emotions, and behaviours contribute to mental health. Cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) is a prominent example, aiming to change negative thought patterns that contribute to emotional distress (Beck 1976).
- **Social Learning Theories:** These theories propose that mental health can be impacted by social factors like stress, trauma, and social support. For instance, it is suggested that social isolation can exacerbate depression (Turner 2003).

Interpersonal Relationship Theories

- **Attachment Theory:** John Bowlby's theory suggests that early childhood attachment to caregivers shapes how people form relationships later in life. Secure attachments lead to healthier and more trusting relationships, while insecure attachments can contribute to difficulties in intimacy and emotional regulation (Bowlby 1982).
- **Social Exchange Theory:** This theory proposes that relationships are formed and maintained based on a cost-benefit analysis. People seek relationships that offer rewards and satisfaction while minimizing costs (Kelly & Thibaut (1978).
- **Social Penetration Theory:** This theory describes how relationships develop through layers of self-disclosure. As people share more personal information and experiences, intimacy deepens (Altman & Taylor 1973).

Some Areas of Intervention

Pastoral counsellors work with people from diverse backgrounds and virtually all works of life (Clinebell 2011). They also provide spiritual and emotional support to people dealing with a variety of challenges. Some of the areas of pastoral counselling intervention are as follows:

- **Grief and loss:** For people who have lost loved ones, or jobs, the pastoral counsellor is handy to help them cope with their emotions and find meaning in their loss.
- **Marital and family problems:** Pastoral counsellors can help couples and families communicate more effectively, resolve conflicts, and strengthen their relationships.

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- **Mental health issues:** Depending on the extent of training, pastoral counsellors may be able to provide support and guidance to people struggling with anxiety, depression, and other mental health challenges.
 - **Life transitions:** Pastoral counsellors can help people adjust to major life changes, such as serious illness, accident, retirement, or a new baby.
 - **Spiritual concerns:** Pastoral counsellors can help to explore their faith, deal with doubt, or find comfort in difficult times.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Pastoral counsellors and therapists work with individuals, couples, and families to address spiritual and psychological concerns, providing support and guidance based on their unique needs. Additionally, pastoral counselling plays a vital role in community support and advocacy, offering outreach programmes, crisis intervention, and support groups to promote overall well-being within communities.

Looking toward the future, pastoral counselling faces emerging trends and challenges. The increasing diversity in religious and spiritual practices calls for a greater understanding and respect for different belief systems. Additionally, the integration of technology in therapy and counselling presents both opportunities and challenges in maintaining the personal and spiritual connection between counsellor and client. Despite these challenges, there is immense potential for the growth and development of pastoral counselling, as society continues to recognize the importance of addressing spiritual and psychological needs holistically. It is expected that pastoral counsellors should work more with a network of other helping professionals such as social workers, nurses, doctors, psychiatrists, and clinical psychologists, among others. This will help them maximise their impact on the community they are called to serve. In all, pastoral counselling can restore humanity to Edenic purity as it helps people to find peace and tranquillity in God.

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